

**RETAILING STRATEGY OF PRODUCTS & CUSTOMER
SERVICES IN ORGANISED RETAIL SECTOR**

A
THESIS
SUBMITTED TO THE

**SHRI JAGDISHPRASAD JHABARMAL TIBREWALA
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OF

**DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY
IN
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Year 2015

DECLARATION BY THE CANDIDATE

I, Atul Kumar, declare that thesis entitled “RETAILING STRATEGY OF PRODUCTS & CUSTOMER SERVICES IN ORGANISED RETAIL SECTOR” is my own work conducted under the supervision of **Dr. V. K. Soni** and co-supervision of **Dr. Pradeep Kumar Sinha** of Department of Management, Shri Jagdishprasad Jhabarmal Tibrewala University, Jhunjhunu, Rajasthan, India approved by the research Degree Committee. I have put in more than 200 days of attendance with the supervisor/co-supervisor at the centre.

I further declare that to the best of my knowledge the thesis does not contain any part of any work which has been submitted for the award of any degree either in this University or any other University/deemed University without proper citation.

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This is to certify that work entitled “**RETAILING STRATEGY OF PRODUCTS & CUSTOMER SERVICES IN ORGANISED RETAIL SECTOR**” is a piece of research work done by **Mr. Atul Kumar** under my supervision for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy in Management of Shri Jagdishprasad Jhabarmal Tibrewala University, Jhunjhunu, Rajasthan, India. That the candidate has put attendance of more than 200 days with me.

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ABBREVIATIONS

Sr. No.	Abbreviation	Full-form
1	GDP	Gross Domestic Product
2	FICCI	Federation of Indian Chambers of Commerce and Industry
3	GRDI	Global Retail Development Index
4	NDA	National Democratic Alliance
5	BJP	Bharatiya Janata Party
6	FDI	Foreign Direct Investment
7	USD	United States Dollar
8	IBEF	India Brand Equity Foundation
9	M&A	Merger & Acquisition
10	IKEA	Ingvar Kamprad Elmtaryd Agunnaryd
11	USA	United States of America
12	D&B	Dun & Bradstreet
13	RBI	Reserve Bank of India
14	CRM	Customer Relationship Management
15	SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats
16	MBO	Multi Brand Outlets
17	SKU	Stock Keeping Units
18	ATM	Automated Teller Machine
19	CDIT	Consumer Durable IT and Telecom
20	FMCG	Fast-Moving Consumer Goods
21	RRL	Reliance Retail Limited
22	PDS	Public Distribution System
23	DMPL	Del Monte Pacific Ltd.
24	B2B	Business To Business
25	CD	Compact Disc
26	DVD	Digital Versatile Disc
27	VCD	Video Compact Disc
28	CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
29	NYOP	Name Your Own Price
30	UK	United Kingdom
31	SERVQUAL	Service Quality
32	DIY	Do It Yourself
33	PEST	Political, Economic, Social and Technological

34	ETOP	Environmental, Threat and Opportunity Profile
5	BCG	Boston Consulting Group
36	USP	Unique Selling Proposition
37	SBU	Strategic Business Units
38	EDLP	Everyday Low Pricing
39	CLV	Customer Lifetime Value
40	OTC	Over The Counter
41	CFL	Compact Fluorescent Lamp
42	LCD	Liquid-Crystal-Display
43	USB	Universal Serial Bus
44	OTG	Oven Toaster and Griller
45	HCL	Hindustan Computer Limited
46	DTH	Direct To Home
47	HUL	Hindustan Unilever Limited
48	UPS	Uninterruptible Power Supply
50	DSLR	Digital Single-Lens Reflex
51	HDMI	High-Definition Multimedia Interface
52	CCTV	Closed-Circuit Television
53	EMI	Equated Monthly Instalment
54	ROI	Return On Investment
55	RMM	Retail Marketing Mix
56	PRM	Partner Relationship Management
57	MRP	Maximum Retail Price
58	RCP	ResQ Care Plan
59	SMS	Short Message Services
60	NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
61	LPA	Lacs Per Annum
62	WAS	Weighted Average Score

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this research work is to furnish a conclusive picture of retailing strategies of products and customer services in the organised retail sector. Therefore, the research work is multifarious and comprises the analysis of the various products & customer services and retailing strategies introduced by organised retail industry to comprehend the viewpoint of organised retailers. And to perceive the viewpoint of customers, an analysis of their buying behaviour, factors influencing their buying behaviour and satisfaction level with various products & customer services have also been incorporated in this work.

Both descriptive and exploratory research approaches were employed in compiling this study. The study was endeavoured in the Maharashtra state of India and the organised retail stores from various segments were selected from various parts of the state. Efforts were made to cover the entire state geographically and regionally, at least 2 well-known cities were selected from each region. The whole Maharashtra state was divided into 5 regions, i.e. northern, southern, eastern, western and central. From each region, two well-known cities were selected. Further, from each city, one retail store was selected for the study. Out of total 10 retail stores, 5 were hyper stores and remaining 5 were super stores. These hyper and super stores have also been selected by a planning that from each region one hyper and one super store must be selected for the study.

A non-probability convenience sampling technique was resorted for institutional (store personnel) and individual (customers) respondents. From each retail store, an institutional questionnaire got filled up by store personnel to receive accurate data about various products, services and retailing strategies introduced by the respective retail store. In total 2000 customers of retail stores (i.e. 10 retail stores * 200 customers) were contacted. From the area of each selected retail stores 200 respondents contacted at a convenient basis for obtaining data about their buying behaviour, factors influencing their buying behaviour, and satisfaction level pertained to products and services offered by retail stores.

The research work is based on both secondary and primary data. Two instruments, one for personnel of retail stores (institutional questionnaire) and another for customers of retail stores (individual questionnaire), were constructed to accomplish the objectives of the study. Both questionnaires were tested by conducting a pilot study of the few respondents selected on a random basis. Taking the insight from this pre-testing of the questionnaires, certain items were included and even excluded to modify the questionnaire for the final study. Survey method and printed questionnaires were exercised in accumulating the primary data. The questionnaires were supervised individually practising the face to face approach.

The research work yields vivid research results. Most noteworthy, results depicted that retailing strategies introduced by organised retailers are significant to sustain in the hyper-competitive retail market. Results also flaunted that customers are significantly satisfied with various products & services introduced by organised retailers except a few.

The research work would be rationalised for its multiple utilities. The study contributes knowledge & facts about the merchandise (products) & customer services penetrated by organised retailers. The study aspires to reveal the retailing strategies determined by organised retailers. This study also delivers evidence about the dilemmas of customers along with some potential solutions to them. The study ascribes details for the betterment needed in the merchandise (products) & services that clients want. The study also determines diverse components and customer services mandatory to persist the retailing industry. The study additionally functions to deliver the factors that serve towards the superior level of customer satisfaction in the organised retail industry. The study also offers the suggestion to the management of organised retail stores to appraise upon the retailing strategy. The study assists in comprehending the retailing environment, retailing culture and the retail decision process.

Section 1

Descriptive Analysis

CHAPTER 1: Introduction

CHAPTER 2: Review of literature

CHAPTER 3: Conceptual framework

CHAPTER 4: Research methodology

Chapter 1 Introduction

- An overview of Indian retail industry
- An evolution of retail in India
- Reforms in Indian retail
- Investments in the retail sector
- Government initiatives for growth of the sector
- Key drivers to the exponential growth of the Indian retail industry
- Key challenges in Indian retail industry
- SWOT analysis of organised retail industry in India
- The classification of retail industry
- Retailing formats in India
- Major retailers in India

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 An overview of Indian retail industry

The Indian retail industry is one among the most contributing sectors to Indian GDP at the rate of 14 to 15% (Dikshit, 2011) and 8% in the employment of the country (FICCI, 2011). The Indian retail industry is considered as one among the most vibrant industries in India and one of the pillars of Indian economy. A bright future of the Indian retail sector can be glanced with the growth estimation of this sector, as India is estimated as the fastest growing retail market and will become one of the top five retail markets in the worlds in terms of economic value (Majumder, 2011). In 2011, from the perspective of investment in the retail sector, India has been ranked in Global Retail Development Index as 4th most attractive country among the 30 flourishing market around the globe (FICCI, 2011).

Global Retail Development Index (GRDI) 2014 of the US Based global management consulting firm A T Kearney ranked the Indian retail industry at 20th position among the top 30 developing countries. *Figure 1.1* explains the competitive position of India in comparison to other 30 promising countries of the world. Moriarty *et al.* (2014) explain that in GRDI 2014, India has been dropped in 20th place from its 14th place in 2013 due to slow economic growth (4.7% only), currency fluctuations, high rate of consumer price inflation, government debt, high current account deficits and strict FDI policies. But, Moriarty *et al.* (2014) mention further that India is still an eye-catching long-term retail destination due to several reasons, which are the population of 1.2 billion, younger population (50% of the total population is under 30 years), one-third of the total population is cities resident, increasing disposable income and pro-business policies attitude of the current National Democratic Alliance (NDA) government headed by the Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP) and prime minister Mr. Narendra Modi. Many industry experts have positive feelings for long-term GDP outlook and industrial growth of India. According to Global Retail Development Index (GRDI) 2014, despite the several slumps, Indian retailing sector has a potential to grow in the future and the market is attractive for investment. *Figure 1.2* explains the attractiveness in terms of investment in Indian Retail Sector as to consider.

On the radar To consider Lower priority

2014 rank	Country	Market attractiveness (25%)	Country risk (25%)	Market saturation (25%)	Time pressure (25%)	GRDI score	Change in rank compared to 2013
1	Chile	100.0	100.0	13.2	47.3	65.1	+1
2	China	60.9	52.5	44.5	100.0	64.4	+2
3	Uruguay	93.4	57.5	70.3	32.4	63.4	—
4	United Arab Emirates	98.5	82.3	17.5	43.8	60.5	+1
5	Brazil	99.4	59.8	48.7	33.2	60.3	-4
6	Armenia	26.4	35.3	81.5	86.7	57.5	+4
7	Georgia	32.4	32.8	79.6	78.8	55.9	+1
8	Kuwait	78.8	72.6	32.9	31.7	54.0	+1
9	Malaysia	66.7	68.7	32.2	43.5	52.8	+4
10	Kazakhstan	45.4	38.5	72.7	54.3	52.7	+1
11	Turkey	83.6	50.2	46.5	30.2	52.6	-5
12	Russia	94.0	38.4	30.7	46.4	52.4	+11
13	Peru	46.0	43.0	61.9	51.3	50.6	-1
14	Panama	56.2	46.9	52.7	41.3	49.3	+8
15	Indonesia	46.2	33.4	57.7	59.6	49.2	+4
16	Saudi Arabia	72.3	67.3	29.5	27.4	49.1	—
17	Oman	75.1	79.1	27.0	11.1	48.1	—
18	Sri Lanka	6.3	36.7	78.8	67.3	47.3	-3
19	Nigeria	39.6	6.6	92.3	48.0	46.6	N/A
20	India	26.4	39.0	72.3	43.4	45.3	-6
21	Colombia	50.6	43.0	53.5	29.4	44.2	-3
22	Jordan	49.8	43.7	65.6	15.2	43.6	-2
23	Philippines	33.0	33.2	55.8	50.5	43.1	N/A
24	Costa Rica	62.1	45.9	40.4	21.5	42.5	N/A
25	Mexico	80.0	54.4	2.9	31.8	42.3	-4
26	Botswana	26.1	60.7	34.8	44.1	41.4	-1
27	Morocco	24.1	35.5	69.5	35.7	41.2	—
28	Vietnam	3.8	21.9	75.0	55.7	39.1	N/A
29	Namibia	8.6	57.9	27.2	58.8	38.1	-3
30	Azerbaijan	22.0	29.5	82.3	18.6	38.1	-1

0 = low attractiveness 100 = high attractiveness 0 = high risk 100 = low risk 0 = saturated 100 = not saturated 0 = no time pressure 100 = urgency to enter

Figure 1.1: Global Retail Development Index (GRDI) 2014
 Source: Adopted from Moriarty *et al.* (2014)

Figure 1.2: Global Retail Development Index 2014: Market attractiveness
Source: Adopted from Moriarty *et al.* (2014)

The retail sector of India, especially organised retailing is passing through the transformation from last one decade and despite the several slump, the organised retail market is growing exponentially. The organised retail segment is shifting towards the adoption of modern retailing concepts. In 2007, the Indian retail market size was approximated at USD 339.7 billion; in which USD 13.9 billion was organised retail market size. In 2010, the Indian retail market size was approximated at USD 435 billion, in which 95% market (USD 414) was of an unorganised traditional retail market and only 5% i.e. USD 21 billion was organised retail market size (FICCI, 2011). In 2011-12, the Indian retail market was taped at USD 500 billion in which the organised retail market has been just 7%. The Indian retail market is anticipated to reach USD 738.71 billion by 2016-17 with a compounded growth rate of 15% per annum. While, the organised retail is anticipated to attain the 10.2% share of the total retail market with a growth rate of 24% (The Hindu, 2014). In 2014, the Indian retail market was estimated at USD 490 billion and was projected to reach USD 865 billion by 2023 with a compounded annual growth rate of 6% (The Hindu Business Line, 2014). The *figure 1.3* indicates that in 2013, the organised retail market was 8% and expected to grow 24% by 2020.

Figure 1.3: Significant scope for expansion in organised retail
Source: Adopted from (IBEF, 2015)

Table 1.1 depicts the comparative situation of organised and unorganised retailing sector of India and other countries of the world.

Table 1.1: India in comparison to the world in retailing		
Country	Organised	Unorganised
USA	85	15
Taiwan	81	19
Malaysia	55	45
Indonesia	30	70
China	20	80
India	08	92
Source: Adopted from (Madann, 2012)		

The growth of the organised retail sector in India can also be glanced in terms of sheer space. In 2012, the total organised retail space supply was 2.5 million square feet, which was increased by 4.7 million square feet with a growth rate of 78% (Chakraborty, 2013).

The Secretary General of Assocham, India D. S. Rawat, also glanced a phenomenal growth of the Indian retail sector and said that “favourable demographics, increasing urbanisation, an increase in the number of nuclear families, increasing affluence amid buyers, increasing attraction and preference for branded products and greater aspirations are the factors that will enhance the Indian retail consumption” (The Economic Times, 2014).

The consumer market in India is getting a robust growth and the consumption level in India is assumed to be double in the next five years from 750 billion USD to 1.5 trillion USD. According to panel members of 7th Food and Grocery Forum of India, the food and grocery retail market of India has ample growth opportunities and that segment of the retail market constitutes about 60% of the total retail market (Phulia and Sharma, 2014; Moriarty *et al.*, 2013). *Figure 1.4* explains the breakup of USD 500 billion retail sector of India.

Figure 1.4: India’s retail market
Source: Adopted from Moriarty *et al.* (2013)

The growing number of middle-class households is also a contributing factor to the growth of the Indian retail sector. It has been estimated that 91 million households will be in the category of the middle-class from its 21 million by 2030. It has also been estimated that 570 million people will prefer to live in the cities in 2030 (Chakraborty, 2013; FICCI, 2011). The growing middle class is redefining the luxury market with their changing buying habits. The growth of retailing sector can also be glanced from the fact that about 40% of the luxury goods sales in India occur from the non-metros customers (Rai and Gopal, 2014). The huge population, especially the young population, higher domestic consumption and the favourable macro trends are other contributing factors to the exponential growth of the Indian retail sector.

1.2 An evolution of retail in India

Figure 1.5: An evolution of retail in India over the years

Source: Adopted from (IBEF, 2015)

Retailing is a revolutionary and one among biggest sector in India. The new entrant in Indian retailing signifies the beginning of the retail revolution. Retail market of India is growing with a great pace and it will have great growth opportunities in the future. The origin of retailing in India can be identified with the emergence of Kirana stores and mom-and-pop stores, such kind of stores used to cater to the people of local communities. By the time, government supported rural retail and, many franchise stores enter into India with the assistance of Khadi & Village Industries Commission of India. The economy opened up in 1980s results in a change of retailing. The first few companies who came up in India as retail chains were in the textile sector, for instance, S Kumar's, Bombay Dyeing, Raymond's, etc. Later Titan opened their retail showrooms in the organised retail sector of India. With the time passing new entrants started shifting from manufacturing to pure retailing.

Retailing in India was considered in an opening stage in the 90s, when some manufacturers opened their own outlets. Many players realised the potential of this market and entered into the apparel segment in the period of 1990-2005. A great expansion can be seen in the period of 2005-10, when large corporate entered into this market with substantial investment in food and general merchandise segment. From 2010 onwards, the period is considered as the consolidation phase. During this period,

players are moving towards smaller cities and even rural areas. *Figure 1.5* explains the growth of the Indian Retail Sector over the years since its inception. The players have introduced the international brands for their customers. During this period, the FDI in retail is 100% in the case of a single brand and 51% in multi-brand retailers. Private label brands have also emerged in this period. Moreover, the emergence of e-retailing is also the gift of this period.

Figure 1.6: Evolution of retailing in India
Source: Adopted from (Sikri and Wadhwa, 2012)

Retail stores like as Planet M and Music world in music, Crossword in books, Food world in FMCG entered the market before 1995. Shopping Malls started opening in urban areas, giving the world class experience to the customers. Later supermarkets and hypermarkets emerged. The evolution of retail sector in India includes continuous improvement in distribution channels, supply chain management, technology, back-end operations, etc. this will lead to more and more mergers, acquisitions, consolidation and huge investments. Indian retail sector, which has a huge potential for growth in a modern retailing world is just a beginning. In Indian retail sector, the most of the market is unorganised. The key challenge for the organised retail sector is the closest competition from the unorganised sector of the Industry. Unorganised retailing in India is prevalent for centuries. The advantage in unorganised retailing in India is consumer familiarity which runs from one generation to another. Unorganised retailing is a low-cost structure; mostly run by self-owned

peoples with a very low retail space as well as labour costs and ultimately lower taxes to pay. The organised retail sector in India is very small but with a great scope for growth.

1.3 Reforms in Indian retail

The central government of India was reluctant to allow the FDI in multi-brand retail business till 2011 that resulted in no trade and FDI in any kind of retail outlets by foreign investors to offer multiple products with diversified brands to consumers in India. However, on 24 November 2011, the central government of India announced that India will allow up to 51 percent FDI in “multi-brand retail”; single brand retailers can own 100 percent of their Indian stores, which has been increased from the previous cap of 51 percent; both single brand and multi-brand stores in India have to source nearly a third of their merchandise from small and medium sized Indian suppliers; moreover, all these single or multi-brand stores are obliged to restrict their business in only 53 cities having a population of over one million in India. It is expected that the stores will have full access to over 200 million urban customers in India; multi-brand retailers are obliged to have a minimum investment of USD 100 million, with at least half of the amount invested in cold chains, transportation, back-end infrastructure, packing, refrigeration, sorting and processing to reduce the post-harvest losses; and bring remunerative prices to farmers; and opening of retail competition will be within the India’s federal structure of government. It means the policy is operational to the legal framework of India. The states of India have right to accept it and implement it, or they can reject. Which means actual implementation of the policy will be within the parameters of state laws and regulations. The opening of the doors of the retail industry will lead to global competition and the retail rush to India. Indian retail is equipped with the capabilities of transforming not only the retailing landscape, but also the nation's existing infrastructure. It is expected to help high inflation, but is likely to be opposed by millions of small-scale retailers, who consider these large foreign chains as the biggest threat. Analyst’s claim- the need to control food price inflation, which doubles in previous years, forced the government to open the sector. India’s food supplies have been controlled by tens of millions of middlemen. Traders offer little technical support to help farmers to boost their packaging technology, productivity, but traders add huge markups to farm prices.

According to analysts, big foreign retailers will provide a force to set up modern supply chains along with refrigerated vans, cold storage and more efficient logistics.

On September 20, 2012, the government of India has notified two significant regulations that would go a long way in the development of the Indian retail sector (Nath and Gupt, 2012). First, permitting FDI in multi-brand retail trading and second is, simplifying the rules for single-brand retail trading to make it more business friendly. On January 11, 2012, India government has approved innovation and increased competition in single-brand retail. The reform attempts to attract investments in marketing & production, encourage increased sourcing of goods from India, and increase the competitiveness of Indian enterprises with the access to technologies, management practices and global designs. According to the announcement, India requires single-brand retailers who have more than 51% foreign ownership to source at least 30% of the value of products from Indian village & cottage industries, artisans & craftsmen and small industries.

1.4 Investments in the retail sector

In the recent time, Merger & Acquisition (M&A) in the Indian retail sector are also indicating the growth potential of this sector. In 2013, there were a total number of 26 M&A deals of worth UDS 3.5 billion, refer the *figure 1.7 & 1.8*, which depict the recent M&A in the sector.

Acquirer name	Target name	Year	Deal type
Kalyan Jewellers India Pvt Ltd	Warburg Pincus	Oct 2014	Private Equity
Celio	Future Lifestyle Fashions Limited	Oct 2014	Private Equity
Warburg Pincus	Biba Apparels	Dec 2013	Private Equity
Hassan Food Co	Bush Foods Overseas Pvt Ltd	Apr 2013	Acquisition
Trent Ltd	Landmark Ltd	Feb 2013	Acquisition
Future Venture India Ltd	Big Apple (convenience store)	Sep 2012	Acquisition
Peter England Ltd	Pantaloons Retail India Ltd	Sep 2012	Acquisition
Pantaloons Retail India Ltd	R&R salons	May 2012	Private Equity
Phoenix Mills Ltd	Classic Housing Projects Pvt Ltd	Mar 2012	Acquisition
Flipkart online services Pvt Ltd	eTree Marketing Pvt Ltd	Feb 2012	Acquisition
Gitanjali Gems Ltd	Crown Aim, China	Dec 2011	Acquisition
Shoppers Stop Ltd	Gateway Multichannel Retail India Ltd	Jun 2011	Acquisition
TTK Prestige Ltd	Triveni Bialetti Pvt Ltd	Sep 2011	Acquisition

Figure 1.7: Merger & acquisition in the Indian retails sector in 2013

Source: Adopted from (IBEF, 2015)

Analysing the strong growth potential, many corporations are attracting for high foreign investment in the sector.

Figure 1.8: Strong growth potential attracting high foreign investment

Source: Adopted from (IBEF, 2015)

According to the Department of Industrial Policies and Promotion, the retail industry in India has received FDI equity inflows USD 275.38 million in the single brand segment from April 2000- January 2015 (IBEF, 2015). Due to the rising need of Indian consumers in different sectors including home appliances and consumer electronics, many companies have invested in India in the past few months (IBEF, 2015). Some of them are as follows:

Amazon and Future Group have made an agreement for selling goods online and both the companies will introduce new lines of products that will be offered only at Future Group retail stores as well as Amazon. Initially, Future Group will introduce for selling more than 45 private labels of apparel, the electronics, home, and food category products, while Amazon will be responsible for order fulfilment as well as customer service for the merchandise on its portal. The Japanese firm Soft Bank has invested approximate US \$ 627 million in Snapdeal, which made them largest shareholder in the e-commerce. Snapdeal has planned to utilise this investment for

expansion and growth of its chain of fulfilment centres. Myntra.com is planning to expand their business by launching a wedding store by November, 2014. This wedding store will cater the needs of wedding wear and accessories of a bride and groom.

Free charge plans to launch a service that will promote online shopping through its mobile platforms and Website by giving cash back offers to shoppers who use the service to buy products on eCommerce sites. Burger King a well-known American fast food chain store plans to start 12 outlets in India within next three months. At present, Burger King is looking for a company-operated and company-owned model for its store operations in India and its store will be located in the high street as well as food court locations.

A logistic service provider, i.e. Gojavas has introduced a 'try-before-you-buy' experience in the eCommerce space. In this model, the delivery person waits at the place of the customers until the customer uses the product before accepting or returning it. Paytm is planning to set up 30,000 to 50,000 retail outlets where the customers can load the cash in their digital wallets. It's searching retailers mostly Kirana stores to enrol them as merchants for accepting digital payments (IBEF, 2015). Mobikwik a mobile wallet company has made a partnership with Jabong.com to give mobile payment services to Jabong.com customers. FashionAndYou has opened three distribution hubs for faster deliveries.

Amazon Inc and Flipkart India will invest approximately ₹ 2,300 crores in the near future in order to acquire more customers in the fast-growing online retail market. Abu Dhabi based Lulu Group is planning to invest ₹ 25,00 crore in an integrated meat processing unit, a fruit and vegetable processing unit and a modern shopping mall in Hyderabad, Telangana. Datawind has made a partnership with Homeshop18 to jointly launch special sales programmes for broadcast, mobile and internet media to provide greater access.

1.5 Government initiatives for growth of the sector

The Union Minister of Commerce and Industry, Government of India, Ms Nirmala Sitharaman stated that the ministry is stressing to build a branding and

marketing culture of the Indian products to the world. She has stated further that the ministry is willing to start a Free Trade Agreement with the European Union. The Indian Government has taken various initiatives to improve the retail industry in the country. Some of the initiatives are as follows: IKEA has entered into a Memorandum of Understanding with the government of Telangana state to set up its first store in Hyderabad (India). IKEA retail outlets adopt a set of standard design and their each location requires an investment around ₹ 500-600 crore (US\$ 80.38 - 96.46 million). The Foreign Investment Promotion Board has approved five different proposals of worth ₹ 420 crores (USD 67.53 million) from Puma SA, Flemingo and Bestseller for retailing in India (IBEF, 2015). Furthermore, the board cleared three 100 percent single-brand retail proposals worth ₹ 222.5 crores (USD 35.77 million). The Indian Government is also in the final phase of to implement Goods & Services Tax Bill. This Bill is seen as a key in improving the business climate of our country and to facilitate industrial growth. The strong efforts of the Indian government lead to the investors' confidence for FDI in India. *Figure 1.9* depicts the competitive position of India in the FDI Confidence Index 2014 in comparison to other countries of the world.

Figure 1.9: FDI Confidence Index 2014
 Source: Adopted from (IBEF, 2015)

Earlier, to protect the 15 million small retailers or Kirana stores government of India has mainly closed the organised retailing for other countries and solely permitted 51 % FDI in single-brand retail with prior Government permission (Corporate Catalyst India, 2012). FDI is also allowed in the wholesale business. Policymakers were trying their best to find out new ways by which FDI is possible without hurting the small retailers or unorganised retailing. The government of India was also planning for retail trading in sports goods, stationery, electronics goods and building equipment. The policy of allowing 51 % FDI in single-brand product retailing had led to the entry of solely a few global brands like as Louis Vuitton (shoes, travel accessories, watches, ties, textile ready-to-wear), Nike (footwear), Fendi (luxury products), Toyota (retail trading of cars), Argenterie Greggio (silverware, cutlery, traditional home accessories and gift items), Lladro (porcelain goods) and Damro (Knock-down furniture), into retail trading. French luxury industry of 12 billion Euro is keeping an eye on India to enter into retail business in the domestic luxury segment.

Now, the Indian government has approved the 100% FDI in single brand product retailing and 51% FDI in Multi-brand and front-end retailing. The wholesale cash-&-carry sector has already been allowed 100% FDI. This will provide several benefits to the country as depicted in *figure 1.10*.

Figure 1.10: Benefits of FDI and its limit in the different segment

Source: Adopted from (IBEF, 2015)

1.5.1 Business models for entry into Indian markets prior to the recent initiative of the Government

There were three different routes as stated in *figure 1.11* for foreign players to enter into India's retail sector prior to the approval by the Indian government for the 100 FDI in single brand product retailing and 51% FDI in Multi-brand and front-end retailing (Corporate Catalyst India, 2012).

Earlier entry option for foreign players	
Franchise agreement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Most widely used entry route by multinational retailers • Domino's entered in India through master franchise route and Pizza Hut entered through regional franchise
Cash and Carry Wholesale Trading	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 100% FDI is allowed in wholesale trading which involves building of a large distribution infrastructure to assist local manufacturers • The wholesaler deals only with smaller retailers and not consumers • Metro AG of Germany was the first significant global player to enter in India through this route
Strategic licensing agreement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Foreign company enters into a licensing agreement with a domestic retailers • Mango, the Spanish Apparel brand has entered in India through this route with an agreement with Piramyd, Mumbai • SPAR entered into a similar agreement with Radhakrishna Foodlands Pvt. Ltd.

Figure 1.11: Business models for entry in Indian retail markets prior to September 20, 2012

1.6 Key drivers to the exponential growth of the Indian retail industry

- **The huge population, especially the younger population:** India is considered as one among the largest emerging markets of the world due to its population, which is over 1.2 billion (Rahman, 2012). India is also considered as one of the largest economies in terms of purchasing power of the population. The 50% of the total Indian population is below the age of 30

years and about 1/3 of the Indian population resides in cities (Rai and Gopal, 2014). Table 1.2 presents the percentage of population below the age of 25 years in different countries.

Country	Percentage of Population
India	53
China	42
Indonesia	30
USA	30
Japan	27
Germany	26
Source: Adopted from (Madann, 2012)	

- **Changing lifestyle and consumer behaviour:** Due to increasing working population, comfortable life style, more travel and leisure are the preferences of Indian customers. These factors are the drivers for the growth of retailing in India; whether it is Appliances, Cosmetics & Toiletries, Electronics etc. (Handa and Grover, 2012).
- **Rising affluence amid consumers:** It is estimated that 91 million households will be in the category of the middle-class from its 21 million by 2030 (Chakraborty, 2013; FICCI, 2011). This increase in the middle-class households is a contributing factor towards the growth of the retail sector.
- **Demographic changes and improvements in the standard of living:** The growing middle class is redefining the luxury market with their changing buying habits. The growth of retailing sector can also be glanced from the fact that about 40% of the luxury goods sales in India occur from the non-metros customers (Rai and Gopal, 2014).
- **Favourable demographics:** The Demography Dynamics are also favourable for the Indian organised retail sector as approximately 60% of Indian population is young and below the age of 30 years (Rahman, 2012).
- **Changing consumer preferences and shopping habits:** Shopping behaviour of consumers has been totally changed due to the change in taste and preferences of consumers. Due to the online retailing consumers are well aware of new brands and stores and they buy according to their needs and occasions. Consumers are driving the growth of organised retail. Therefore, the organised retailing is not only growing its market, but also compelling the retailers to offer a wider range of brands as well as a variety (D&B, 2014).

- **The increase in a working population:** India is the second largest country in the world in terms of population after China. And, it is the largest consumer market in the world due to its favourable demographics (D&B, 2014). An increase in the number of working women has increased the growth of discretionary items. There has been a 20% increase in the number of working women population in the last decade.
- **The emergence of nuclear families:** With the passage of time there is a shift from joint families to nuclear families. The income level of nuclear families has been increased because both the members have started to earn; which results in an increase in purchasing power and lack of time. Thereby nuclear families are expecting everything under one roof. This led to the development of organised retailing.
- **Increasing urbanisation:** The preference shift of population towards the urban livings is also a good sign of the growth of the Indian organised retail sector. It is estimated that 570 million people will prefer to live in the cities in 2030 (Chakraborty, 2013; FICCI, 2011).
- **The increase in disposable income and customer aspiration:** Booming Indian economy is a consequential source of opportunity for the retailing sector. India is the third largest country of the world in terms of purchasing power of consumers (Rahman, 2012). Due to large working population and an increase in double-income households, the disposable income, as well as the purchasing power of consumers, especially in urban India, has been growing. The growing preference for branded products and services, higher aspirations, demand and increase in the expenditure for luxury items are the major cause of the growth of this sector in India. The branded products, especially in the categories of Cosmetics, Apparels, Shoes, Watches, Beverages, Food and even Jewellery are being preferred as the lifestyle products by the urban consumers of India.
- **Increase in per capita income:** The per capita income of Indian consumers is ₹ 44,345 (Rahman, 2012), which is growing and can be referred from *figure 1.12*. Due to an increase in per capita income, the household consumption is increasing, which is a good sign for organised retailers. As the earnings are increasing, a proportionate increase in spending can also be glanced. Moreover, the Indian economy is expected to grow by a rate of 8% and

salaries are also expected to hike with a rate of 15% (Rahman, 2012). This in turn will increase the household consumption, which is a healthy sign for manufacturers and retailers of consumer goods and services.

Figure 1.12: Rising per capita income in India

Source: Adopted from (IBEF, 2015)

- Increasing use of plastic money:** Among the Indian consumers, the use of plastic money has been increased and due to this the consumers prefer to buy the merchandise in the category of Apparel, Consumer Durable Goods, Food and Grocery etc.
- Improvements in infrastructure and enhanced availability of retail space:** Due to the overall betterment of transportation infrastructure and services in India, now the consumers are able to cover a distance to reach a particular retail outlet. *Figure 1.13* depicts the enhanced availability of retail space and mall space breakup in India.

Figure 1.13: Mall space breakup in India

Source: Adopted from (IBEF, 2015)

- **Easy credit availability:** Ease in getting credit cards and ease of use of credit cards for shopping has also boosted the growth of the organised retail sector. Due to the issuance of credit cards at a larger piece by Foreign and Indian banks has increased the retail growth. According to the RBI, as of the financial year 2009, the total number of outstanding credit and debit cards in India was 24.7 million and 137.4 million respectively (D&B, 2014).
- **Growing liberalisation of the FDI policy in the past decade:** *Figure 1.14* states the Growing liberalisation of the FDI policy in India. The main benefit of FDI is that it is both supplementary and complimentary with regards to local investment. Due to FDI companies has gained access to world class technology and supplementary funds. Companies have also access to new management practices around the world and get the chance to become the part of a global market system (Prasad and Harikumar, 2013). With the help of FDI, companies will get new technologies and skills from other countries; which results in infrastructure development of the nation. It will also lead to help in creating more value for money for the customers.

Figure 1.14: Favourable FDI policy encouraging investment

Source: Adopted from (IBEF, 2015)

- **Organised retail concentration in tier II and III cities:** Retail revolution started with the tier I cities in India, which thereby has been saturated (D&B, 2014). Now retailers are focusing on tier II and tier III cities as depicted in

figure 1.15. Due to the changing landscape of Indian retail segment and the increase in competition has forced the retailers to find out the growth opportunities in tier II and III cities.

Figure 1.15: Organised retail in India

Source: Adopted from (IBEF, 2015)

- **The internet drives awareness and online purchases:** There has been a huge increase in the number of internet users and online buyers in India (D&B, 2014). Online retailing has been increased due to increase in awareness of the internet and online buying; which has opened a whole new channel of retailing in the Indian retail scenario. Online retailing is prevalent due to ease in buying and ease in getting the goods on the doorstep.
- **Experimentation with formats:** Due to huge competition in retailing market of India the retailers are experimenting with the new formats (Handa and Grover, 2012).
- **Store design:** Shopping malls and supermarkets are growing day by day, which leads to improvements in infrastructure. Large availability of retail space & competition has also encouraged the retailers to adopt attractive store designs and make the ambience eye-catching (Handa and Grover, 2012). This results in more visits to the shopping malls which ultimately lead to more sales & higher growth of organised retail in India.
- **Brief about growth value propositions:** *Figure 1.16* summarises the major growth value propositions in this Indian retail sector. Which can be described as higher brand consciousness, growing aspiration levels of consumers and appetite to excrement, growing young population and working women, rising incomes and purchasing power, credit availability, changing consumer preference and growing urbanisation, rapid real estate and infrastructure development, emergence of new categories, development of supply chains and

improving their efficiency, easy availability of credit to suppliers, expansion of existing players, R&D, innovation and new product development etc.

Figure 1.16: Growth value proposition in organised retail industry

Source: Adopted from (IBEF, 2015)

1.7 Key challenges in Indian retail industry

- **Porter’s Five Forces analysis of the organised retail sector:** *Figure 1.17* explains the five forces of competition in the retail industry of India.

Figure 1.17: Porter’s Five Forces analysis of organised retail sector

Source: Adopted from (IBEF, 2015)

- **Shortage of skilled/trained manpower:** 75 to 80% of the total manpower is required for store operations in the organised retail industry and front/end line assistant profiles are major positions for employment opportunities in the sector (FICCI, 2011). Unfortunately, in India, very few retail operations specific courses are offered at graduate and post graduate level. Moreover, there is also a shortage of niche retail operations specific courses in the area of store merchandising, supply chain management in retailing, CRM in retailing, stock management, customer service management etc.
- **Lack of industry status:** The retail industry in India is still fighting for the industry status from the government. In the absence of this industry status, the organised retailing is facing issues in procuring the required finance and fiscal benefits.
- **Policy-induced barriers:** There a time's need that Indian government should establish an apex body for governing all the retail operation In India, as the organised retail sector is administrated by two different ministries of the government of India. The Ministries of Commerce formulates policies pertained to retail operations in India, while the Ministry of Consumer Affairs takes care of licensing and other legislation related to retailing. A single apex body can govern retail operations and address the grievances of retailers more effectively.
- **Real estate market:** The real estate market is offering the retail space with high prices and low availability. A brief comparison of rent as %age of sales to Indian retailers and international retailers has been presented in *table 1.3*. It is very difficult to find appropriate space in a central location of the cities due to an absence of retail space planning in India. Moreover, space which is available for use can easily be interchanged for commercial utilisation. Other reasons for retail space issues are infrequent auctioning of government owned lands, litigation disputes of land owners and fragmented private holdings.

Table 1.3: A comparison of rent as %age of sales		
Format	Indian Retailers	International Retailers
Hyper market	5-10%	1-5%
Speciality retailers	15-30%	10-12%
Source: Adopted from (Madann, 2012)		

- **Government regulations:** Government regulations, especially the Urban Land Ceiling Act) for the development of real estate is hindering the growth of the retail sector. The existing labour laws are restricting the retailers for offering a 24/7 shopping experience to their customers. Moreover, the multi-stage taxation system and other taxation laws are hindering the growth of this sector.
- **Technology:** Technology is a major challenge faced by organised retailers for effective management of retail operations. First of all, the technology available in India in this sector is out-dated. A strong need of latest technology (digital merchandising, online inventory monitoring system, mobile payment, etc.) is there to cope up with the customer aspirations.
- **Lack of efficient supply-chain management and distribution channel:** Distribution channels are an integral part of the retail industry. The main role of the distribution channels is to deliver the right kind of goods at the right place at the right time. The improper infrastructure and distribution channels are the reasons for inefficient distribution processes in India. Moreover, supply chains are expensive in India. Therefore, the stakeholders in the retail industry are required to improvise distribution channels as well as supply chain systems, so that they can meet the desired quality and service level by their customers.
- **Understanding customers:** Understanding customer behaviour is not an easy business. However, converting your customers into loyal customers is a more critical task in the retail industry. Retailers are required to have the implementation of effective CRM as well as a loyalty programme.
- **Inefficient power supply:** Organised retail outlets utilise the electricity for various store management orations like billing systems, cold storing, lighting, lifts, escalators, air conditioning etc. and need large volumes of electricity for the same. Due to inefficient and insufficient power supply, retailers have to invest for ensuring power backups.
- **Competition from unorganised sector:** Competition from the unorganised sector is also a challenge confronted by organised retailers in India as unorganised retailers caters niche and more personalised service to their customers.

- **The slow growth of organised retail market:** The people are shifting continuously to modern stores from their preferred traditional stores. But this organised (modern) retail format could account only for 8% of the total retail market (Moriarty *et al.* (2014), which is a challenge for stakeholders.
- **Online retailing:** Moriarty *et al.* (2014) estimated that e-commerce market in India will grow more than 50% in the coming five years. This may be a big challenge to store based organised retailers. *Figure 1.18* presents a comparison of total retail sales and e-commerce sales. The applications of internet among the young population of India are increasing day by day and speed of the internet as well. Cash on the delivery option by online retailers is a key factor for the growth. However, the inventory management, resource availability and logistic planning are important challenges for the growth of online retailing in India.

Figure 1.18: Comparison of total retail & retail e-commerce sale in India
Source: Adopted from (Mahajan, 2015)

- **Other bottlenecks:** Few other bottlenecks of Indian Retail are as follows: there is a long way to meet international standards by Indian organised retailers. There is a lack of required retail space for organised retailing and there is no fixed consumption pattern. Other bottlenecks are inadequate utilities, IT infrastructure hurdles, policy-related hurdles, limited consumer insights, taxation challenges.

1.8 SWOT analysis of organised retail industry in India

SWOT Analysis	Positive Factors	Negative Factors
Internal Factors	Strengths (See point 1.8.1)	Weaknesses (See point 1.8.2)
External Factors	Opportunities (See point 1.8.3)	Threats (See point 1.8.4)

Figure 1.19: SWOT analysis of organised retail industry

Source: By author

1.8.1 Strengths

- The Indian retail market was estimated at USD 490 billion in 2014 and was projected to reach USD 865 billion by 2023 with a compounded annual growth rate of 6% (The Hindu Business Line, 2014).
- Organised retail was at USD 3.31 billion and growing with a rate of 8% (Rahman, 2012).
- The retailing sector is the second largest contributor to the Indian GDP at the rate of 14 to 15% after the agriculture (Dikshit, 2011).
- The Indian retail industry is contributing 8% to the employment of the country (FICCI, 2011), which is largest after agriculture.
- Entry to various sources of financing in the organised retail industry.
- Improvements in infrastructure and enhanced availability of retail space, almost 25 million sq. ft. retail space available (Rahman, 2012).

1.8.2 Weaknesses

- The retail industry in India is still fighting for the industry status from the government.
- There is a lack of preferred retail spaces at affordable rates in India.
- Indian retailers have to travel a long distance to meet international standards.

- There is a lack of effective supply chains in India; moreover, these supply chains are expensive.
- The improper infrastructure and distribution channels are the reasons for inefficient distribution processes in India.
- In India, the variations in consumption pattern can be seen on a large scale.
- Retailers in India also face the shortage of trained manpower.
- Need to provide Value for Money is squeezing the profit margins of retailers.
- Retailers in India also feel shortage of investments for expansion of their operations

1.8.3 Opportunities

- The huge population, especially the young population
- The lifestyles of consumers, as well as their behaviour, are changing.
- Rising affluence amid consumers
- Changing demography and improving the living standards
- Favourable demographics
- The preferences, as well as the shopping habits of consumers, are changing.
- Increase in a working population
- Social factors, like dual household income of consumers
- Emergence of nuclear families
- Increasing urbanisation
- The aspirations of customers are also increasing as an increase the disposable income
- Increase in per capita income
- Increasing use of plastic money
- Easy credit availability
- The basic infrastructure is improving and availability of retail space is also enhanced
- Growing liberalisation for the FDI in the sector by the government
- High domestic consumption
- Favourable macro trends
- Increasing spending grocery

1.8.4 Threats

- Government regulations (especially the Urban Land Ceiling Act) for the development of real estate.
- Increasing rental and lease costs are affecting project viability.
- Existing labour laws are restricting the retailers for offering a 24/7 shopping experience.
- Multi-stage taxation system and other taxation laws are hindering the growth of this sector.
- Retailers in India face a shortage of trained, qualified and professional personnel for supporting the growth of this sector.
- Niche and more personalised service catered by Mom & Pop stores.
- E-retailing

1.9 The classification of retail industry

The Retail industry can be classified into 2 major categories i.e. organised retailing and unorganised retailing. A comparison of key characteristics of organised and unorganised retails in India has been presented in *table 1.4*.

- **Organised retail:** Organised retailers or traders are those, who have a license for trading activities and registered themselves to pay taxes are called as organised retailers.
- **Unorganised retail:** Unauthorised small shops like Kirana stores, general stores, corner shops, etc. are called as unorganised retail.

Table 1.4: A comparison of key characteristics of organised and unorganised retails in India		
Basis	Organised Retailers	Unorganised Retailers
Average size (sq. ft.)	4000	300
Average Number of SKUs	5000	1200
Service format	Self-service	Over the counter
Customer Expectations	Predominantly experience based	Predominantly need based
Stocks turn	High	Low
Profit Margin	High	Low
Source: Adopted from (Madaan, 2012)		

1.10 Retailing formats in India

The Indian retailing sector is witnessing the drastic changes not only in the terms of growth, but also in the introduction of the different formats of retailing. In India, starting from Flea Markets to shopping malls can be seen. In between, there are various formats like Wholesale Clubs, Factory Outlets, Value Retailers, Off-Price Retailers, Vending, Mom-and-pop stores, E-trailer, MBO's or Category Killers, Convenience Store, Discount Stores, Specialty Stores, Department Stores, Supermarkets and Hypermarkets. *Figure 1.20* explicates the retailing formats in India and their basic facility.

Figure 1.20: Retailing formats in India and their basic facility

Source: Adopted from Dhillon *et al.* (2012)

- **Shopping malls:** Today, shopping malls are largest form of organised retailing in India, which caters a conducive and ideal shopping experience with a wide range of products and services under the one roof. The malls are usually located in metros or near to urban outskirts. These shopping malls exist in the space ranging from 60,000 sq. ft. to 7,00,000 sq. ft. and above (Rahman, 2012). They cater not only products and services, but also provide entertainment, refreshment, spa, beauty salon, etc. The examples of this category are Pune Central, Shoppers Stop, Pantaloon, Inorbit (Levy *et al.*, 2012) etc.
- **Hypermarkets:** It ranges from 50000 to 100000 sq. ft. (Madaan, 2011). Hyper markets are also known as multi-department stores. It is one kind of superstore that combines supermarket as well as a department store (Hyper One Center, 2011). It is a very large retail facility that carries a numerous range of products at one place, including full lines of general merchandise and food & groceries; it may sell some services. When hypermarkets are planned, constructed, and executed correctly, a consumer can satisfy all of their routine weekly shopping needs at one time. Hypermarkets have an extensive width, medium depth and may offer private labels. They have stand-alone locations, malls (as anchor store also). Their pricing policy is lower than market prices and they provide self-service. Their promotional mix includes mass media and loyalty programmes. (Madaan, 2011). Examples are Big Bazaar, Shoppers Stop, Vishal Megamart, Hyper City, Star India Bazaar, Spencer's Hyper, Reliance Mart etc. (Pradhan, 2009)
- **Supermarkets:** The supermarkets contribute 30% to the total sale of food and grocery retail in India (Rahman, 2012). There are located near to the residential streets, self-service outlets which focus on food, grocery & household items and personal sales by offering the products and services to the varied needs of the shoppers. These supermarkets are categorised as mini supermarkets which typically exist in the space of 1,000 sq. ft. to 2,000 sq. ft. and large supermarkets, which range from of 3,500 sq. ft. to 5,000 sq. ft. Supermarkets have an extensive width, shallow depth and may offer private labels. They have a competitive pricing policy. Their level of service is average and offer self-service. A promotional mix of supermarkets includes mass media and loyalty programmes. (Madaan, 2011). The example of this

category includes Reliance fresh, D'mart, More, Food bazaar, Trumart, Spencer's Daily, Spencer's Super (Pradhan, 2009), Reliance Super (Levy *et al.*, 2012), etc.

- **Speciality stores:** Speciality stores are the retail chains, which deals and focus on specific market segments (category) and recognised in their sector. The speciality stores offer general merchandise, single line and multiple lines. They have a narrow width, deep depth and offer usually high quality. They are located in business districts, strip shopping centres and malls. Their pricing policy is average to above average and also premium pricing. Discount stores provide personalised full services. The promotional mix of these stores is suggestive selling, catalogues and visual displays (Madaan, 2011). The example of this category includes Crossword (a book retailer), Kids Kemp (retailer of kids' products), RPG's Music World, Planet M music chain of the Times Group, Fashion Station, aLL, Depot, Blue Sky, Home Stop, Mothercare, Desi café, Brio, Books & Beyond, RPG Cellucom, (Pradhan, 2009) Reliance Digital, Toy shop Hamleys (Levy *et al.*, 2012), Reebok, etc.
- **Discount stores:** Discount stores or factory outlets offer the products at discounted rates for selling in bulk to achieve economies of scale and to get rid of overstock. Their product categories comprise the variety of perishable as well as non-perishable goods. They have an extensive width, medium depth and offer medium quality. They are located in business districts, stand-alone and strip shopping centres. Discount stores have average services. Their promotional mix includes mass media and price-oriented promotions (Madaan, 2011). Examples of discount stores are Discount Circuit, Brand Factory, (Pradhan, 2009) Fashion Yatra, (Levy *et al.*, 2012) Walmart, Kmart etc.
- **Department stores:** Large stores ranging from 20000-50000 sq. ft and caters to a variety of needs of the targeted customers. Further, they have been classified into localised departments such as clothing, toys, home, groceries, general merchandise, apparel, accessories, gift items, sports, etc. They have an extensive width, deep depth and offer good to high quality (Madaan, 2011). Their location is mainly business districts, stand-alone, strip shopping centres. Pricing policy of department stores is above average. They offer assorted to full services. Their promotional mix includes suggestive selling, catalogues

and mass media. Examples of department stores are Pantaloons, Westside, Piramyd, Shopper's Stop, (Pradhan, 2009) Sears, Bloomingdale's etc.

- **Convenience store:** Convenience stores are located near residential areas and considered as smaller stores of 400-2,000 sq. feet. These stores offer a limited range of convenience products with high-turnover and open 7 days a week as well as extend hours during the day. Slightly higher prices are charged due to the convenience premium. They offer food, grocery and household items (Madaan, 2011). These stores have a medium width of merchandise, shallow depth and average quality. Convenience stores have average and above average pricing policy. They offer highly personalised, average services and they also provide home delivery. A promotional mix of convenience stores includes personal rapport and average promotion. Examples are Spencer's Express, (Pradhan, 2009) 7-Eleven, Circle K.
- **MBO's or category killers:** Multi Brand outlets, also known as Category Killers. They offer Specialty products. These stores have a narrow width, deep depth and offer average to high quality. They are located in stand-alone and strip shopping centres. These usually do well in busy market places and Metros. Category killers offer discounts and competitive pricing. Their level of service is assorted and promotional mix includes mass media. Examples of category killers are Toys R Us, PetSmart, etc.
- **E-trailer (E-tailers):** Retailers are offering online products and services for buying and selling (Sikri and Wadhwa, 2012). E-Tailing is popular as the retail E-Commerce that comprises sales as well as purchases of products done through electronic mode between retailers and their customers. The spread of the internet and falling prices of desktops, had enabled many people to turn to E-Tailing. Advances in telecommunications like reliable broadband and the advent of smartphones have made mobile commerce called by the acronym M-Commerce, a fast growing segment. It offers several advantages to the customers in the form of product choice, 24X7 shopping experience, saving time and cost of travelling. Customers feel as a savvy consumer for making a more intelligent purchase by accessing their online catalogues. Customers may purchase goods with a single click of a mouse without travelling. Customers also benefited enormously by getting the products at a lower price in comparison to the conventional stores. (Prasad, 2013). Examples of E-tailers

are Yebhi.com, Flipkart.com, Myntra.com, Ebay.com, Jabong.com, Snapdeal.com, Amazon.com etc.

Channel/Format	Type of merchandise	Pricing	Size (sq ft)	Average stock-keeping units (SKUs)	Location	Example
Store						
Supercenter	All types of merchandise	Discount pricing	200,000-300,000	200,000	Outskirts	Wal-Mart supercenter
Hypermarket	Mostly food & grocery and apparels with focus on value products	Discount pricing	60,000-120,000	80,000	Malls	Hypercity, Big Bazaar
Supermarket	Food & grocery	Discount pricing	10,000-30,000	20,000	Malls	Food Bazaar
Neighbourhood/co-nvenience store	Daily use items		500-3,000	4,000	all localities within a city	Subhiksha
Cash and carry	Mostly food and grocery	Bulk buying, heavy discounts	100,000-300,000	150,000	outskirts	Metro cash and carry
Discount store	Food & grocery and fashion & accessories	Heavy discount	NA	NA	NA	Subhiksha
Department store	Apparel and accessories	Competitive	20,000-100,000	50,000	Malls	Shoppers Stop
Speciality store	Any one type of merchandise	Competitive	500-5,000	1,000	Main markets, Malls	Mobile Store
Category killer	Any one type of merchandise	Discount pricing	30,000-100,000	10,000	Malls, high streets	Vijay Sales
Non-store						
Kiosks/stalls	Small food items and accessories	Normal	20-100	50	Malls, multiplexes, cinema halls	Popcorn
Vending machines	small items	Normal	-	10	Stations, commercial and office complexes	Chocolate and newspaper vending machines
Order retailing (Catalogue/TV/Website)	Any type of merchandise	Competitive	-	-	-	Argos
Door-to-door	Mostly low-value items	Normal	-	-	-	Amway

Figure 1.21: Brief summary of the formats in organised retailing

Source: Adopted from D&B (2014)

- **Mom-and-pop stores:** These are family owned businesses which cater to small sections and are individually handled retail stores which provide a personal touch (Sikri and Wadhwa, 2012). Mom and pop stores are businesses

that are owned and operated in a single location. Rather than being part of a national chain, these stores offer a distinct shopping experience to the consumers, who want to deal with businesses that are local to a particular city or town and at those places where business owners have created the community. While the proliferations of huge retail chains have considerably decreased the market for independent retail stores. Still, numerous locally owned businesses are continuing and thriving in the competitive economy. An example of this type of store is local general stores. A small, usually family-owned, independently controlled, and operated the store, which has fewer numbers of employees as well as smaller sales volume turnover, and is typically not franchised and open in a single location for business operations.

- **Vending:** Vending is a new entry, in the retail sector, where snacks, beverages and other small items can be purchased via vending machine (Sikri and Wadhwa, 2012). A vending machine is a machine that dispenses items after the customer inserts currency or credit into the machine. E.g. the ATM.
- **Off-price retailers:** The off-price retailer provides general merchandise, inconsistent, out of fashion, odd sizes, etc. These stores have a medium width and shallow depth. They are located in stand-alone, shopping strip and at any low rent location. Their pricing policy is very low and offers minimal services & self-service. They focus on mass media as a promotional mix (Madaan, 2011) Examples of off-price retailers are TJ Maxx, Marshalls, Ross stores, Big Lots, Stein mart etc.
- **Value retailers:** Value retailers provide general merchandise and Multi-brands. And these stores have a medium width and shallow depth. They are located in stand-alone, shopping strips and at any low rent location. Their pricing policy is highly discounted prices. The level of services of such stores is average and the promotional mix is mass media (Madaan, 2011). Indian example of value retailers is a Pantaloon Brand Factory and U.S.A. examples of value retailers are Dollar Tree and Dollar General.
- **Factory outlets:** Factory outlets offer general merchandise, Self-Manufactured items, and are inconsistent. These stores have a moderate width and shallow depth. Such stores are located in a stand-alone location, Factory premises and any low rent location. They provide highly discounted prices and offer self-service. A promotional mix of such stores is low promotions

(Madaan, 2011). Examples of these include Pantaloon Factory Outlets, Lei's factory Outlets, etc.

- **Wholesale clubs:** Nature of merchandise of wholesale clubs is general merchandise, food items and is inconsistent. These stores have a moderate width and shallow depth. Such stores are located in stand-alone, out of town and industrial areas. They offer very low prices and level of services is low. The promotional mix of these stores is low promotions and direct mail (Madaan, 2011). Examples of wholesale clubs are Costco Wholesale Club and Sam Club.
- **Flea markets:** Flea market offers some general merchandise items and has extensive width but very shallow depth. These are located in open surroundings, low rent, and semi-urban locations. Pricing policy includes bargaining and low prices. Their level of service is low. A promotional mix of flea markets is limited and point of sales promotion (Madaan, 2011). Examples of flea markets are Janpath in Delhi, Crawford and Zaveri Bazaar in Mumbai etc.

1.11 Major retailers in India

The Indian retail industry witnessed a great expansion in the period of 2005-10. And a large number of corporate houses entered into this market with substantial investment in food and general merchandise segment. *Figure 1.22* presents the brief summary of Indian Retail Groups and Area of their Business. The industry is being flourished by the presence of the following players.

1.11.1 Aditya Birla Retail Limited

Aditya Birla Retail Limited is US\$ 28 billion Corporation. In 2007, the company entered into food and grocery retail sector by acquiring a south India-based supermarket chain 'Trinethra'. By the time Company expanded its business with the brand named '**More**' with 2 formats Supermarket and Hypermarket. Supermarket 'More' conveniently located in neighbourhoods and it's catering to the daily, weekly and monthly needs of consumers. Their product includes a wide range of fresh fruits & vegetables, home care, personal care, general merchandise & a basic range of apparels. Presently Aditya Birla Retail Ltd have 640 'More' supermarkets across the country. The Hypermarket '**More**' **Megastore** is the complete shopping experience

for its customers. Hypermarket 'More' Megastore not only offers fruits & vegetables, groceries and FMCG products, but also it offers general merchandise, apparels and CDIT. At present 8 Hypermarket 'More' Megastores are operating in New Delhi, Mumbai, Bengaluru, Hyderabad, Indore, Aurangabad & Vadodara. Aditya Birla Retail Ltd has more than 11,000 employees. 'More' stores have over 1.6 million members of its loyalty programmes.

Aditya Birla retail Ltd has private label brands such as Kitchen's Promise, Germex, Feasters, Enriche and Best of India. The objective of private label brands is to offer quality products with attractive prices to its customers. Aditya Birla Retail was awarded with 'Retail Best Employer of the Year' at Reid & Taylor awards for Retail Excellence by the global jury of the Asia retail Congress 2009. The company was also recognised for impactful Retail & Visual Merchandising at the same forum. The Company was awarded with the 'Most Admired Retailer of the Year' in the Smart Strategy category at the Images Retail Awards 2009 at the India Retail Forum, Mumbai.

1.11.2 Bharti Retail Ltd.

Bharti Retail Ltd. is a wholly owned subsidiary of Bharti Enterprises. It operates a chain of multiple format stores in India. The neighbourhood formats of the company's stores are named as '**Easyday**' and the compact Hypermarket named as '**Easyday Market**'. At present Company is more focusing on food economic sectors with a joint partnership with agriculture company Field Fresh. Field Fresh Foods Private Ltd is a joint venture of DMPL India Ltd (a subsidiary of Del Monte Pacific Ltd.) and Bharti Enterprises. The Company offers processed foods & beverages and fruits & vegetables in the domestic as well as international markets. Presently neighbourhood 'Easyday' has 70 stores and hypermarket 'Easyday Market' has 6 mid-size compact stores.

In order to serve farmers, small scale manufacturers and retailers, Bharti Enterprises and Walmart Stores Inc signed a deal for wholesale, B2B, cash & carry business and back-end supply chain management. They ventured their first B2B Best Price Modern Wholesale cash-and-carry store in May 2009 in Amritsar, Punjab, as of now they have their stores in Jalandhar, Kota, Zirakpur. Their cash & carry stores are about 50,000 and 10,000 square feet and offer a wider variety of products, i.e. fruits &

vegetables, fresh, frozen and chilled foods, dry groceries, hotel & restaurant supplies, personal & home care, office supplies, clothing and other general merchandise items. These stores offer a competitive wholesale price and allow retailers to lower the cost of business. This venture of Bharti Enterprises and Walmart Stores Inc is planning to launch their 10 to 15 wholesale cash-and-carry points and will recruit 6,000 to 7,000 people in next 3 coming years.

1.11.3 Reliance Retail Limited

Reliance Retail Limited (RRL) is a subsidiary of RIL. Since 2006, Reliance Retail Limited is catering to millions of customers and thousands of farmers & vendors. Its core strategy is backwards integration; it has made huge progress towards building entire value chain starting from farmers to the end customers. Over 3 years of operation, the company has now expanded its presence in more than 85 cities across 14 states in India. It has more than 1,000 stores in the country.

The company operates with several 'Value' and 'Speciality' formats. The 'value' formats that Reliance Retail Ltd operates are- **Reliance Fresh** - a neighbourhood concept, **Reliance Mart** - supermarket concept, **Reliance Super** - a mini-mart concept. The 'value' formats offer a wide range and assortment of products required for daily household needs. Whereas, the 'specialty' formats are: **Reliance Trends** - an apparel & accessories concept, **Reliance Digital** - a consumer durables & information technology concept, **iStore by Reliance Digital** - an exclusive Apple products concept, **Reliance Wellness** - a health, wellness & beauty concept, **Reliance Footprint** - a footwear concept, **Reliance TimeOut** - a books, music & entertainment concept, **Reliance Jewels** - a jewellery concept, **Reliance Living** - a furniture, homeware, furnishings, and modular kitchens concept and **Reliance AutoZone** - an automotive products & services concept.

Reliance Retail Ltd expanded the stores network and operating through strategic partnerships with World-Class companies like as Pearl Europe and Marks & Spencer. The company has signed a deal with the Asics Corporation of Japan for distribution arrangement to market Asics brands of shoes & accessories in India. Reliance Retail Ltd. has also launched its flagship store with a franchise arrangement with Hamleys and also planning to enhance their network in a succeeding year. The

company has also expanded its presence in B2B office supplies through its joint venture with Office Depot.

1.11.4 Pantaloon Retail

Pantaloon Retail is the company of Future Group. Pantaloon Retail (India) Ltd is the India's leading retailer, which operates multiple retail formats both in the value & lifestyle segment. It was established in the year 1993 and Company headquarter is in Mumbai. It is operating over 16 million square feet of retail space and has over 1,000 stores across 73 cities and 65 rural locations in India, and employs over 30,000 people. The leading formats of the Company are as follows:

- Entertainment: Bowling Co.
- Shoes: Shoe Factory
- Health & Beauty Care: Star, Sitara
- Food & Grocery: Big Bazaar, Food Bazaar
- E-tailing: Futurebazaar.com
- Home Solutions: Furniture Bazaar, Hometown, Collection-i
- Books, Music & Gifts: Depot
- Rural Retail chain: Aadhaar
- Consumer Electronics: e-zone

Future Value Retail Limited is a fully owned subsidiary of Pantaloon Retail (India) Limited. This company was established by considering the size and growth of the value of the company, which further led by **Big Bazaar** and **Food Bazaar**. The company is running its business with more than 120 Big Bazaar stores and 120 Food Bazaar stores in 70 different cities of the country and occupies over 6 million square foot retail space.

A subsidiary company, Home Solutions Retail (India) Limited is operating **Home Town**, a large-format home solutions, store, collection, selling home furniture products and **eZone** focused on catering to the consumer electronics segment.

1.11.5 Vishal Retail Ltd.

Vishal retail Ltd is the company of Vishal Group, which operates its Hypermarkets with an average area of 25,000 to 30,000 square feet with a chain of

172 fully integrated stores which spreads over the area of more than 24,00,000 square feet in around 110 cities across India in 24 states. It is the fastest growing retail group in India. Its stores cater to almost all price ranges. The stores have more than 7000 product range which caters to all household needs and offered at one place. The group is maintaining the highest standards in quality and design, these stores have introduced to offer the finest fashion garments at down-to-earth price structure. The store is named as Vishal Megamart, the stores are the best place for bargainers and fashion conscious people. The turnover of the company for the year 2009-10 was 1105 crore.

1.11.6 Tata Group

The Tata group is also a leading player of Indian retail industry and business with its subsidiary Trent that has **Westside** and **Star Bazaar** for the business. It was launched in 1998. In 2005, it has acquired 'Landmark' which is the largest book and music retailer in the country. Trent owns over 4 lakh square foot retail space across the country. It has main categories like apparel, speciality books and music. Its formats include supermarkets and hypermarkets.

1.11.7 Spencer's Retail Limited

Spencer's Retail Limited is the company of RPG Enterprises. It is the largest & growing fastest multi-format retailer in India and it was established in 1988. Its footage is 1 million square feet approximately and has 220 stores, including 30 large format stores across 35 cities in India. It offers the product range in the following categories: fruit and vegetables, food and grocery, personal care, home and office essentials, garments, fashion accessories and electrical & electronics. It was established in 1996 and now become a popular destination for shoppers in India. It is operating with two formats, i.e. hypermarkets and a convenient store for catering the shopping needs consumers.

Spencer hyper stores are of more than 15,000 square feet in size and offer everything under the same roof. Their product range comprises the categories like fruits & vegetables, meat, chicken, fish, groceries, bakery, processed foods, chilled and frozen foods, garments and fashion accessories, office stationery, home decor and

needs, soft toys and electronics & electrical products. On an average a Spencer's hyper store stocks 70,000 Stock Keeping Units (SKU's) across the 35,000 items.

Spencer's stores are neighbourhood stores ranging from 1500 square feet to 15000 square feet. The stores offer the widest range and assortment in fruit and vegetables, non-food, staples, FMCG food and frozen foods and cater to the daily and weekly top-up shopping needs of the consumer.

Music World is India's largest chain of music store retailing and it offers the widest range of music & home video products (International and Indian). The Music World's product portfolio includes audio CDs, DVDs and VCDs, CD-ROMs, gaming consoles & software of all the leading brands and other music accessories. The company is a key player in the home video market. Music World has successfully formed into high end 'personal audio' gadgets of several top brands. The company also offers home theatre systems, speakers, headphones and DVD players.

1.11.8 Piramal Group

Piramyd Retail belongs to Piramal Group. In 1999, it launched its apparel business under the brand name, i.e. Piramyd Retail and Merchandising Pvt. Ltd. (PRMPL). While its food; home and personal care businesses were grouped under Crossroads Shoppertainment Pvt. Ltd. (CSPL). When the apparel and food businesses reached a critical mass, the management merged these 2 into a Piramyd Retail Ltd. Pyramid also offers merchandise with its smaller format of stores called TruMart. It caters to food & personal care products. Piramyd Retail at present is operating with 5 **Megastores** as well as 8 **TruMart stores** in the Maharashtra state of India.

1.11.9 Madura Garments- part of AB Nuvo

It was established in 1988 and deals with apparels. It offers Louis Philippe, Van Heusen, Allen Solly, SF Jeans and Peter England. It operates with Specialty and Lifestyle formats. **Planet Fashion** has more than 50 stores and **Trouser Town** has more than 9 stores.

1.11.10 K Raheja Group

Shoppers' Stop, promoted by the real estate group K Raheja, was one of the first retailers to have set up a large retail outlet in New Delhi with international ambience and it was established in the year 1991. Shopper's Stop Ltd has made its a presence in the country and occupies retail space over 7 lakh square feet and stocks over 200 brands of garments and accessories. The stores are located all over India in the cities like Delhi, Bangalore, Jaipur, Pune, Mumbai, Chennai, Kolkata, Gurgaon, Ghaziabad & Hyderabad. Shopper's Stop Ltd. has Home Stop, Mothercare, Crosswords, Desicaffe, Brio etc. and its formats include Lifestyle, Department stores and Specialty.

1.11.11 Vivek Group

It was established in 1965 and has main categories like Food, Beauty, Specialty-Electronics. It has stores like **Vivek, Jaisons** and **Premier**. Vivek has more than 23 stores, Jaisons has more than 26 stores and Premier has more than 3 stores.

1.11.12 Globus

It was established in 1998 and deals in apparel. It has stand-alone formats named as **Globus** and **F21**.

1.11.13 Nilgiri's Ltd.

It was established in 1904 which has main categories like Food, Specialty-Bakery Products. It has a supermarket format which has more than 21 stores.

1.11.14 Trinthera Super Retail Ltd.

It was established in 1986 and has categories like Food and Beauty products. It has stores named as **Trinthera Quick Shop** and **Trinthera Super Retail Ltd**. Its formats include Convenience, Super & Hypermarkets. It has more than 150 stores.

Indian Retail Groups	Formats / Area of their Business
Future Group	Big Bazaar, Food Bazaar, Pantaloons, Central, Fashion Station, Brand Factory, Depot, aLL, E-Zone
Reliance ADAG Retail	Reliance World
Lifestyle International	Lifestyle, Home Centre, Max, Fun City and International Franchise Brand Stores.
Aditya Birla Group	"More" Outlets, More Hyper
Vishal Retail Group	Vishal Mega Mart
Fabindia	Textiles, Home Furnishings, Handloom Apparel, Jewelry
The Tata Group	Westside, Star Bazaar, Steel Junction, Landmark, Titan Industries with World of Titans Showrooms, Tanishq Outlets, Croma
Next Retail India Ltd.	Consumer Electronics
Trinethra	Fabmall Super Market Chain and Fabcity Hyper Market Chain
Rei Agro Ltd. Retail	6TEN and 6TEN Kirana Stores
Reliance Retail	Reliance MART, Reliance SUPER, Reliance FRESH, Reliance Footprint, Reliance Living, Reliance Digital, Reliance Jewelry, Reliance Trends, Reliance AutoZone, iStore
K Raheja Corp Group	Shoppers Stop, Crossword, Hyper City, Inorbit Mall
Pyramid Retail	Pyramid Megastore, TruMart
BPCL	In & Out
Raymond Ltd.	Textiles, The Raymond Shop, Park Avenue, Park Avenue Woman, Parx, Colourplus, Neck Ties & More, Shirts & More
German Metro Cash & Carry	Metro Cash & Carry
PGC Retail	T-Mart India, Switcher, Respect India, Grand India Bazaar
Nilgiri's	Nilgiris' Supermarket Chain
Marks & Spencer	Clothing, Lifestyle Products
Shoprite Holdings	Shoprite Hyper
Kapas	Cotton Garment Outlets
RP - Sanjiv Goenka Group Retail	Spencer's Hyper, Spencer's Daily, Music World, Au Bon Pain (International Bakery Cafeteria), Beverly Hills Polo Club
Vivek Limited Retail Formats	Viveks, Jainsons, Viveks Service Centre, Viveks Safe Deposit Lockers
Paritala Stores Bazar	Honey Shine Stores

Figure 1.22: Indian retail groups and area of their business

1.11.15 Provogue Ltd.

It was established in 1997 and deals with Apparel and Footwear. It has standalone stores named as **Provogue** and **Prozone**. It has more than 139 stores.

1.11.16 Bata India Ltd.

It was established in 1931 and has categories named as Footwear and Accessories. It has stand-alone stores named as **Bata**. It has more than 1,100 stores.

1.11.17 Archies Ltd.

It was established in 1979 and it deals in Specialty- Cards and Gifts. It has stand-alone stores named as **Archies and Stupid Cupid**. It has more than 73 stores.

Chapter 2

Review of Literature

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- Introduction
 - Retailing strategies
 - Customer behaviour
 - Customer service
 - Customer satisfaction

CHAPTER 2

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Introduction

This chapter comprises the relevant literature review pertained to the research topic. This chapter consists the review of literature pertained to retailing strategies, customer behaviour, customer services and customer satisfaction. The review of relevant literature available assisted to understand the studies, which have been completed in the field. Further, review of relevant literature played a vital role to understand the problems, research gaps, forming the hypothesis, and preparation of the questionnaire.

2.1 Retailing strategies

Muzondo and Mutandwa (2011) assessed the significance of seven Ps of marketing in influencing consumer choice of store for main grocery shopping in a hyperinflationary economy. The results of factor analysis confirmed the significance of six viz. product, process, price, place, physical evidence, and promotion of the 7Ps of marketing.

Tyagi (2008) expressed that retailers looking to adopt a customer-centric strategy to succeed in the hyper-competitive environment, it is important to understand the impact of such a strategy on retailer's business functions, on merchandising in terms of sharper assortment and improved presentation and on supply chain needs. This would ensure the alignment of customer-centricity with the organisation's overall direction and growth of revenues and profitability while increasing customer satisfaction levels.

Mai *et al.* (2011) vocalised that product managers need to better understand the relationships between primary product network size and the complementary product sales. Further, retail marketing strategies should be adjusted accordingly with the different purchase frequency segments of customers.

Asikhia (2010) found that customer orientation moderated by the marketing information system and managerial attitude is an efficient strategy of providing and sustaining customer advantage for small and medium scale businesses in an ever changing business environment and suggest that managers of small and medium scale businesses should allow their businesses to emerge out of a customers' need.

Omholt (2002) argued that the right horizontal strategy is the one of the critical ways to achieve the superior competitive position in retail organisations. With increased competition from neighbouring and out-of-town centers, increased consumer mobility, and a more diverse population with regard to household structures and lifestyle, sharing a specified location may not be enough for a group of outlets or centers to sustain a competitive advantage.

Standop and Grunwald (2009) in an empirical research stated that the compensation, communication and logistics are the elements of product crises response strategies in the retail industry. These elements can influence the evaluations of customers positively; either directly or indirectly which are affected by product problems thus enhances the brand equity.

Evans *et al.* (2008) in the light of recent changes in the international environment, consider whether the drivers of, and impediments to, retail internationalisation and the business strategy adopted has changed. Results suggested that meanwhile a variety of factors drive retail internationalisation, however, the profit growth is the most dominant factor.

Sun and Ma (2009) unpacked that the foreign capital Retail business constructs the trade integration management system in the Chinese retail industry, implements the global trade strategy. In China, the majorities of successful foreign retail businessmen choose the latest information technology, implements customer loyalty strategy, retail sales business strategy, implements a localisation strategy in the investment management processes, enhances the competitive advantage and expands the market share.

Medina and Rufin (2009) focused on the effects of three different strategic orientations have on firm performance in the specific domain of retailing. Their results show that market driving proved to be a strong predictor of performance in addition to innovation acting as a mediator between strategic orientations in retailers and business performance. Among the strategic orientations developed by retail firms, market driving proved to be better both in its direct influence on performance.

Rani (2012) examined the present retail strategies of store services and store choice and the effect of store services and store choice on Customer satisfaction at MORE and FOODWORLD. Results of study shown that the MORE retail store should concentrate more on improving the store services and store choice Retail strategies for better customer satisfaction and FOOD WORLD should concentrate on some more retail strategies on store choice.

Padilla and Eastlick (2009) conducted the exploratory examination of management strategies and urban retail marketing in 6 US cities having the reputation of central business districts that are either flourishing or developing. They classified strategies into three urban retailing and five economic revival themes. The specified strategies vary and are dependent on flourished cities or developing central business districts.

Vetrivel (2011) advised that retailers should create a good rapport with their customers for increasing further strength of CRM system among Retailers and the Customers. To enhance profitability and customers' satisfaction in Marketing sector, the retailers must focus on implementing Customer Relationship Management strategies like a customer database, customer retention, data mining and tracking system that aim to seek, gather and store right information.

Coca-Stefaniak *et al.* (2010) found the key pillars of the "localization" strategic marketing approaches chase by small retailers. They are- meaningful interpersonal relationships between customers and shopkeepers, place attractiveness, community embeddedness, word-of-mouth customer-to-customer marketing and ultimately service beyond simple advice.

Cacho-Elizondo and Loussaïef (2010) argued that if retailers want to be identified as socially responsible, they must create the “right” associations to reshape their new brand image. By keeping this in mind, creating an awareness of CSR efforts by the firm is an essential attribute for the assessment of their brand image. Developing a CSR facet in their image-building programs, retailers will meet the expectations of an increasing number of socially-conscious consumers in a better way.

Altintas *et al.* (2010) found that the strategic objective factors have a great effect on the competitive advantage of private label manufacturers in Turkey. They also found that three strategic objective factors have an effect on competitive advantage. These factors are product selling control, production efficiency, and market embeddedness.

Datta *et al.* (2006) examined the shopper behaviour regarding the impact of Iceland Foods Plc store design refit strategy. The findings pointed to the relative importance of the stages of the consumer decision-making process, and also to the relative importance of the factors which influences the consumer decision-making process. Overall, service quality was found to be important to all and the refit strategy, according to the customers was indeed a success.

Ilonen *et al.* (2011) explained the different roles and implications of manufacturer’s branded retail operations of its international strategy. They have examined the roles through two dimensions, the role of branded retail as a sales channel and brand strength. They have also examined the two approaches to implementing branded retail strategy internationally, which can be and frequently overlapping. Their emphasis on branding appears to be very important in both the approaches.

Ranganath *et al.* (2011) said that the technology enables all the managers of the retail company to access important information almost up to the minute and consequently to take timely and quick decisions. Modern technologies are transforming the retail environment and it has also helped a lot many companies to expand their operations. Retail organisations are introducing online retailing at a rapid

rate by realising its growing importance of the sales of merchandise through these new distribution channels.

Chen and Huddleston (2009) studied the effect of 4 promotional strategies on the purchase intentions of the students. A significant and positive relationship was found between attractiveness and trustworthiness of the sports celebrities and customers' purchase intention in a campus convenience store. To gain purchase intention of customers less expensive promotional strategies are equally effective than celebrity endorsements.

Joo *et al.* (2012) found that how bidding strategies of successful bidders have influenced the savings which they derive from 'Name Your Own Price' (NYOP) retailer in relation to buying the same merchandise from a retailer who post prices. They explained in the case of utilising bidding data for hotel room purchases the consumer savings rate depends positively on consumer decision to bargain and on the shape of bid function. Bargainers who employ a constant bid increment strategy and a decreasing bid increment strategy save more in relation to non-bargainers, while those who employ an increasing bid increment strategy fare are desirable.

Diona and Arnould (2011) expressed that luxury retail strategy differs from other retail strategies not merely in distinctive formulations of the 4 Ps to customer distinction. Alternatively, it increasingly stands or falls on the justification of a charismatic, creative director, the director offers aesthetic brand ideology. Luxury retail relies on the principles of magic to assemble the charismatic persona of the creative director, it is an art and to diffuse his aesthetic ideology to the brand. Further, they explain that this strategy appears to be to some extent a response to justification crises stimulate by recent strategic extensions of luxury brands into mass marketing.

Shankar *et al.* (2011) written that shopper marketing is the key to managerial practice among manufacturers and retailers, which are desperately accepting innovations in the different aspects of shopper market. Shopper marketing mentions as the planning & execution of all marketing activities which influence a shopper from purchase to post purchase, from the time when a shopper gets the first

motivation to purchase, consumption, repurchase and suggestions. The aim of shopper marketing is to enable a win-win-win solution for the manufacturer-retailer-shopper.

Barone *et al.* (2007) examined how retailer-cause fit affects consumer evaluations of retailer's cause-related marketing strategies. The results suggested that the effects of retailer-cause fit are monitored by consumer perceptions of the retailer's motive for engaging in cause-related marketing, by the influencing effects associated with the two moderators, as well as by the affinity that consumers hold for the social cause component of the campaign.

Gauri *et al.* (2008) said that two powerful and highly strategic tools that retailers possess are store format decisions and pricing. By using a unique data set which covers all grocery retailers in three states and applying a multinomial logit model to study the determinants of format, price and combination strategies of retailers; it was found out that a consideration of the format or pricing strategy in isolation fails to depict a complete picture, the strategic implications change in important ways when they study format and price strategies in combination; although, some combinations are more similar than others.

Dharni and Chawla (2012) made an attempt to explore the impact of IT-related benefits as well as problems in the performance of IT in the retail sector. Results indicated that IT related problems were having a significant impact on the performance of IT in retail. Results also indicate that IT in retail is moving towards the commoditisation phase.

Baskaran (2011) identified that customer experience management is an important strategy in retailing and suggests the several ways (e.g., brand, price, promotion, location, advertising, supply chain management, packaging & labeling, atmosphere, and service mix) to provide superior customer experience which must result in higher customer satisfaction, larger wallet shares, more frequent shopping visits and higher profits.

Burt *et al.* (2011) assessed the degree of standardisation within three countries (The UK, China and Sweden) for distinguishable marketing mix activities: location &

merchandise, service environment and selling, market communication and store format. These three countries (Sweden, the UK and China) represent different cultural settings and are markets in which IKEA has been operating for a long time. They recommend that while IKEA operates a standardised concept, therefore, degrees of adaptation can be observed in customer facing elements, and in the supporting 'back office' processes which support these elements.

Etgarand Rachman-Moore (2011) examined the links between the national cultural values that characterise an origin country of retailers and the adoption of their strategy between generalist versus specialist format. Their results indicate that the probability of being a generalist retailer is higher for retailers originating from countries characterised by collectivism, a low power distance, a present orientation and high uncertainty avoidance. Whereas, the chance of occurrence of being a specialist is higher for retailers having a future orientation, low uncertainty avoidance, a greater power distance and originating from countries characterised by individualism.

Sheng and Pan (2009) examined how a new brand can take an advantage for bundling with a strong brand. The results of their two studies indicate that consumers' quality perception of a new brand will be affected by the bundle partner brand image, and the effect is retarded by the bundle forms and the complementarity of bundle components. Therefore, retailers can bundle an unknown brand with a strong brand as a new product introduction strategy.

Yan and Pei (2009) developed a model which focuses on the strategic role played by the retail services in a dual-channel competitive market. In their research, results suggest that the improved retail services effectively alleviate the channel competition and conflict and improve the supply chain performance in a competitive market.

Campo and Gijsbrechts (2004) examined the conditions for such micro-marketing to be beneficial, and in particular - how these benefits depend on store format. Their results suggest that micro-marketing is beneficial in both types of formats. Still, the appropriate way of localising space allocation patterns is dependent

on specific format. Whereas supermarkets should mainly adjust the space shares of food (core) categories and hypermarkets should primarily adapt the space shares of non-food (non-core) categories of local market conditions.

Tanabe *et al.* (2004) considered the relative impact of management's strategic planning practices and economic changes in company performance. The results derived suggested that variables representing changes in economic conditions and strategic planning were both statistically significant when they were used to explain performance differences. Differences in company management practices were found to play a more important role than changes in the environment.

2.2 Customer behaviour

Smith (2006) talked about the large and growing role of vertically integrated supermarket chains, which has raised a buyer power concern. The reason behind it is the potential to harm other suppliers or consumers and retailers. The exercise of buyer power by the chains in relation to their suppliers may indirectly impact adversely on retail competition, to a great extent as barriers to entry into grocery retailing are relatively high.

Watchravesringkan and Punyapiroje (2011) contributed towards the understanding of consumer attitude and marketing efforts of hypermarket retailers regarding marketing practices of retailers: Big C, Tesco-Lotus, and Carrefour in Thailand. The findings have depicted that consumer attitude is different towards fair price, retail services and positive advertising; Thai consumers have a similar attitude towards product quality across samples and business provisions.

Ruiz and Descals (2008) assessed the impact of sales on temporary retail price discounts on all brands within a merchandise subcategory and other subcategories that are slightly different in terms of tests as well as the composition. The results indicate that the temporary reduction in prices increases the sales of promoting brands, especially in weekends.

Omar and Abisoye (2008) examined the role price as a determining factor in consumer patronage of grocery retail stores in the United Kingdom. They suggest that

price cuts affect consumer store choice. Price awareness has a positive impact on retail stores which implement low-cost strategies. Whereas, price/quality plan and status sensitivity plans tend to have a positive impact on retail stores that implement high price strategies. They recommend it is good to communicate store pricing policy to the target consumers.

Thiruvankadam and Panchanatham (2011) explored the demographic factors that influence the decisions of the consumers on retail store selection in Chennai. In their opinion the demographic factors like gender, education, income and age have a major role in retail store selection. Shopper groups differ in the selection of a store based on their importance for factors of a store.

Lonarkar and Gore (2012) concluded that there is a significant change in the shopping behaviour of the people of the II tier city. This change is more in income group, specific age group, and service group some variations are found when we compare the small and mega retail outlets in case of a distance of outlets and residence of customers. The reason behind the change is the time-saving shopping with satisfactory services.

Rajagopal (2011) examined the impact of radio ads on urban customers in relation to buying behaviour in retail. His result revealed that shopping behaviour of the urban consumer is highly influenced by the physical, cognitive and economic variables at retail stores in reaction towards radio advertisements. Radio advertisement listeners get attracted towards promotional messages regarding sales of products and entertaining advertisements which have a quick reaction to the department stores and supermarkets.

Shaikh *et al.* (2012) noticed that brand has a specific impact on consumer psychology. Most of the consumers purchase from supermarket due to its brand name. The rating of a brand name of the supermarket is a compelling force in buying decision and it has co-occurrence with marital status, qualification, gender and occupation of respondents. Quality is a fundamental point to justify the purchase of a particular product. It has also been noticed that the respondents had a price sensitive approach while purchasing products from supermarkets.

Prasad and Aryasri (2011) made a detailed study and unpack that shoppers' age, gender, monthly household income, distance travelled to store, occupation, family size and education have a significant relation with retail format choice decisions. The findings from shoppers' psychographic dimensions such as shopping orientations, lifestyle factors and values results in the segmentation of grocery and food retail consumers into autonomous, hedonic, conventional, socialisation and utilitarian type.

Rao and Manikyam (2012) gave the customers' perceptions of the experience related to four areas which are: shopping experience, buying experience, service experience and relationship experience and established the fact that the small scale retailers are providing valued experiences to the customers. The customer experience management requires the efforts of the management for improvements qualitatively and organised efforts of retailers.

Khraim *et al.* (2011) pointed out that retail store attributes are influenced by consumer's religiosity. Consumer religiosity is an important indicator of retail store attribute selection. Results indicate that there was a difference between low, moderate and high consumers' religiosity in evaluating the importance for all retail store factors except for the service factor, while there was no difference between moderate and high levels; however there was a difference between them and low level.

Richards *et al.* (2012) expressed that price promotions are becoming an increasingly important method of managing consumer demand for fresh produce items. They applied a multiple discrete/continuous model of fresh produce demand to study the impact of price promotion on retail apple sales. Their findings showed that the brand switching/category incidence effect of promotion is closer to 65/35 than the more usual 80/20 rule when the nature of the decision is appropriately taken into consideration.

González-Benito and Martos-Partal (2012) analysed that recent information acquired by experimentation towards the relationship between store loyalty and store brand purchase recommends a non-monotonic relationship: positive up to a certain

store brand level of consumption, later it becomes negative. To investigate this idea further, they analyse the role of the retailer's competitive positioning, and specifically it's the product category, and price positioning. The more prices oriented retailer's positioning leads to the more favourable relationship between store brand consumption and store loyalty. The relationship between store loyalty and store brand consumption seems to differ across product categories as a result of several factors including perceived risk.

White *et al.* (2012) examined the effects of fairness perceptions of these self-service technology “push” policies on relationships between established antecedents of self-service technology adoption and customer behavioural intentions toward the provider in a retail context. Their results suggested fairness perceptions exert a significant influence on the relationships between these antecedents and customer patronage, negative word of mouth intentions and future spending.

Murthi and Rao (2012) discovered that between 40 to 50% of the purchases are made by consumers having expectations of prices rather than posted prices. Consumers who have price expectations may be thought of as being not aware of the prices. Additionally, they found promotions cause few consumers to focus only on promoted brands, and this effect is higher on the price-aware consumers than on the price unaware consumers.

Kukar-Kinney *et al.* (2012) examined the relationship between consumers' tendencies to buy compulsively and their response to price based on a survey of customers of an internet clothing retailer and found that compulsive buyers are more brand conscious, are prestige sensitive and have greater knowledge of store prices in comparison with non-compulsive buyers. Moreover, compulsive buyers obtain greater transaction value from price promotions; are sale prone and are more price conscious than non-compulsive buyers.

Suwelack *et al.* (2011) resulted from two experimental studies in addition to cognitive effects are: Money-back guarantees evoke a positive response which results in an increase in readiness to pay price premium and consumer purchase intention. Moreover, money-back guarantees have a positive effect on consumer response to

experience and search goods. While Money-back guarantees for experience goods should be designed with stricter return conditions in comparison to money-back guarantees for search goods.

Demoulin and Zidda (2009) studied consumers' process of adoption of a new loyalty card in a grocery retail context. Simultaneously, they investigated the impact of behavioural, socio-demographic and attitudinal variables on the likelihood of adoption and the time of adoption. The results of the study have shown that these variables differently affect the adoption likelihood and timing and demonstrate the importance of attitudinal measures of customer loyalty such as commitment to the retail store. The study extended to the attitudinal dimension of loyalty and confirms the so-called self-selection bias.

In a series of experiments, Manning and Sprott (2007) found positive effects of multiple unit price promotions on quantity purchase intentions is dependent on the rate of product consumption and the extent of the quantity specified in the offer. Contradictory, offer effectiveness is not influenced by drawing special attention to single unit prices, and it is not limited to the nature of these promotions or aggregate savings.

Kukar-Kinney *et al.* (2007) examined the antecedents and consequences of perceived price-matching policy fairness. The three experiments of them demonstrated that consumer perceptions about the fairness of store pricing policy have an influence on price fairness perception as a result, influence the retail shopping intentions.

Meyer-Waarden (2007) inspected the influence of loyalty programs on customer lifetime duration in grocery stores by using behaviour to scan single source panel data. He suggested that loyalty schemes have a positive effect on the share of consumer expenditures and customer lifetimes. Multiple loyalty card holders of geographically close retailers reduce lifetime duration.

Mohan *et al.* (2012) explored the effect of store environment on variety seeking behaviour, with a model which incorporates various components of store

environment (music, light, assortment, employee, and layout) and personality variables, optimum stimulation level and deal proneness. They suggested that retailers need to invest in the components of store environment to enhance the variety seeking.

Diallo (2012) investigated jointly the effect of store image perceptions, store brand price-image and perceived risk toward store brands on store brand purchase intention in the context of an emerging market (Brazil). The results of the investigation have shown that store image perceptions and store brand price-image influence significantly store brand purchase intention directly or indirectly via the effect of perceived risk toward store brands.

Ngobo (2011) analysed that when retailers increase the share of private labels in their product assortments then how does it affect customer store loyalty? The results indicated that the effects of the private label share on the store loyalty depend on - the store private label branding strategy, how the private label share is measured (e.g. private label share vs. relative private label share) and the household's private label usage.

Koistinen and Järvinen (2009) studied consumer observations on their choices between various grocery retailing channels. The results indicated that the consumers have one primary store, which is mostly a supermarket or hypermarket. In addition, consumers like to buy in several supplementary stores that are located close to their residence.

2.3 Customer service

Dhume (2012) found two dimensions: problem-solving and personal attention had high gap scores which indicate a disparity between what specialty store consumers expected and their perceived service quality and identified the sub-components of 'Personal Attention' Dimension which are: Enthusiasm, Polite and courteous salesperson, Sales person behaviour instills confidence, Service delivered when promised, Prompt service, Individual attention, Customised service, interest at heart, and never too busy to respond. For Problem Solving Dimension: Interest in solving problems, Willingness to help customers, knowledgeable salesperson and expected to deal with customer queries,

Jayawardhena and Farrell (2011) found that service and customer orientation behaviours are positively related to service encounter quality and service quality; service encounter quality is positively related to service quality and customer satisfaction; service quality is also positively related to customer satisfaction as well as value perception; and customer satisfaction is positively related to retail customers' buying intention. However, the value is not related to customer satisfaction.

Lu and Seock (2008) examined the relationships between perceived service qualities their satisfaction to the stores. The findings showed that all three service quality dimensions in the research were positively and significantly in relation to their satisfaction at preferred department stores and overall loyalty behaviour to the stores.

Walker (1995) gave the model which has a better understanding of the service satisfaction process. By identifying and separating the core and peripheral dimensions of services, by implementing the concept of passive and active expectations within service encounter, by considering the evaluation process over time, and by including the consumer's zone of difference, a much more realistic decision process for consumer evaluations of services comes onwards.

Grewal *et al.* (2008) identified the effect of compensation on repurchase intentions of consumers after a service failure. They utilised an experimental process and analysed the impact of compensation instability and locus of responsibility conditions. Findings from their three studies using scenarios from different service industries indicated that compensation is necessary only when the company is responsible for the failure and the failure occurs frequently. If the failure occurs rarely or the company is not responsible for it then, compensation does not affect repurchase intentions.

Wiles (2007) studied the announcements of 48 retailers regarding customer service strategies. He found that customer service increases the retailer market values. Further, study suggests that the shareholder value created by the retailer's customer service is affected by the heuristics and cues used to judge the likelihood of service delivery. The result of the study shows that the retailer's reputation can also prevent the customer services shareholder wealth creation.

Kleijnen *et al.* (2007) focused on the perceived utilitarian value of a new service delivery model, the mobile channel and develop a framework that includes three mode specific benefits: service compatibility, time convenience and user control. And, two costs: cognitive effort and perceived risk as antecedents of perceived value. Findings revealed that the identified antecedents exclude service compatibility which has an effect on mobile channel value perceptions which ultimately affects behavioural intentions.

Schau *et al.* (2007) analysed more than 2,000 service encounters of service retailers and find evidence of two types of code switching suggested by sociolinguists: language and dialect. Further, the idiosyncratic terminologies, the concept of brand codes are introduced in the service provider's script. Language code switching has a positive outcome at little cost to organisational efficiency, whereas on-script encounters are preferred.

Thakor *et al.* (2008) found the response of young adults towards fellow consumers who are old or middle-aged. The research suggested that stereotypes of older adults vary depending on the person attributes considered and stereotypes are context dependent according to testing predictions based on recent research. Varying the age of the other consumers and service settings they found that the presence of older consumers affected the young adult's attitude to their patronage intentions as well as the service.

Netemeyer and Maxham III (2007) suggested that the ratings assigned by the supervisor for customer service employee performances can be the preferred base for predicting customer outcomes. Maximising in-role performance inputs may have decreasing returns for customer evaluations in the service recovery context; but maximising extra-role performance inputs may actually "delights" customers, which means higher returns for customer evaluations.

Singh *et al.* (2010) expressed that to measure the service quality of retail stores requires an instrument due to the unique attributes of the retail business. Retail Service Quality Scale has been preferred in their research over SERVQUAL. In this study Service quality is measured for a hypermarket in Delhi.

Torres-Moraga *et al.* (2008) expressed that the success of supermarkets and the retail industry is ascertained by the services they offer. The results showed that Supermarket service quality is a multidimensional construct made up of personal attention, hygiene, accessibility, assurance, reliability and tangibility which are different from the standard constructs.

Watson (2012) examined the effects of service type, previous service experience, service criticality and service recovery on the loyalty of customer, customer satisfaction and complaint behaviour. The results of a 2 (service criticality: high or low) x2 (service type: personal or non-personal) x2 (previous service experience: failure or non-failure) x3 (service recovery: assistance only, compensation only, or assistance with compensation) between-subjects experimental design indicated significant main effects for each independent variable on the combined dependent measures.

Goodrich and Ramsey (2012) with attribution theory they studied service quality theory as well as a disability orientation theory for focusing on perceived quality of the service for people with disabilities, which provides a connecting framework. The research revealed that there is much space for improvement. In a survey with disabilities, people reveal that retailers are rated lower on accessibility than on traditional service quality dimensions. In addition, feelings of disability pride and social activism significantly affect ratings of accessibility.

Auh *et al.* (2011) drawn a self-determination theory and the job characteristics model to develop a multi-level model that examined the relationship between perceived autonomy and perceived service climate and how these relationships alters at varying levels of store-level tenure diversity and suggested that perceived autonomy is positively associated with the employee's perception of service climate. Perceived autonomy had a greater impact on perceived service climate at low and high levels compared to moderate levels of tenure diversity.

Kohijoki, Anna-Maija (2011) by analysing the finish household panel data in their longitudinal study look attentively at the accessibility of grocery retail services among the elderly. The results indicated that most of the elderly have not experienced

significant difficulties in accessibility. With the increase in consumer's age, they demand high-quality services and products and they are willing to make an effort to satisfy their needs.

Söderlund and Julander (2009) involved two different service settings which were used to manipulate the level of the service worker's physical attractiveness in an experimental approach. The researchers, for both experiments, have demonstrated that a high level of physical attractiveness in comparison to a low level, the service employee generates a greater level of customer satisfaction. Results also indicated that exposure to an attractive service employee set in motion a process in which an attractiveness appraisal affected the attitude toward the service employee, which in turn had a significant as well as positive impact on the satisfaction of customers.

Zolfagharian and Paswan (2009) examined consumer perception of service innovativeness and its effect on patronage intention. Using survey data, the empirical analysis suggests: (a) consumer perception of service innovativeness is associated with patronage intention; (b) different consumer perception of service innovativeness dimensions emerges as significant in different service industries, and (c) consumer trait innovativeness modifies the effect of consumer perception of service innovativeness on patronage intention.

Cassab (2009) examined the dynamics of multi-channel service attributes and their effect on customer's intention to renew a service agreement, by using the response surface model based on conjoint analysis of service profiles. The results provided insights for the design of a service that may not be what customers have experienced in the past and demonstrate the qualities of a set of multi-channel service attributes that have not been included in previous studies.

Fullerton (2005) found that affective commitment and continuance commitment are mainly partial mediators of the loyalty relationship and service quality. Results revealed that affective commitment to the retailer had a positive impact on customer loyalty while continuance commitment in marketing relationship had a deleterious effect on customer loyalty.

Avlonitis and Indounas (2007) analysed the data from 170 companies operating in six different sectors to explore the pricing information that service companies collect in order to price their services and the pricing objectives they follow. The research concluded that the companies frequently follow a hierarchy of pricing objectives with the special importance being placed on the company's customers.

Barber and Tietje C (2004) compared the distribution services offered by the smaller retailers versus Home Depot, using both in-store measures & consumer perception data and look attentively in relation to the importance of distribution services as determinants of store choice. They said the primary economic function of retailers is to deliver products with distribution services. The results have shown that the Home Depot's superiority in pricing and assortment attracts a noteworthy market, but small retailers can secure niche markets by delivering higher levels of ambiance and information.

Swinyard (2003) proposed that store type, salesperson mood and shopper behaviour have an effect on the level of customer service provided by the stores. Salespeople in a good mood are more uniformed in their delivery of customer service, whereas salespeople in a bad mood are more probable to make available the poor service to pleasant than to unhappy customers. The research also revealed that department-store salespeople provide a more uniform level of customer service than a discount-store salespeople.

2.4 Customer satisfaction

Martínez-Ruiz *et al.* (2011) proposed a classification of factors and attributes as stated with their importance for customers' evaluations in different countries for higher levels of customer satisfaction includes three main factors. The first-order factor comprises most valued attributes by all customers which are not depending on the country of residence. The second-order factors include attributes with lesser importance; the importance relies on country of residence. The third-order factor attributes are valued less in comparison to others.

Haemoon (1999) suggested a model which possesses the explanatory ability and possess practical validity for customer satisfaction. He used this model in the hotel industry, and results are supporting a holistic approach to the hospitality of customers post-purchase decision-making process.

Torben *et al.* (2011) argued that consumer satisfaction is considered as the degree to which consumer preferences or/and expectations are met. Further, they found that when patronising discount stores and upscale stores – consumers who attach high weight to quality and price are likely to become more satisfied than consumers who attach only medium weight to both the parameters. For long-established supermarkets, satisfaction occurs equally in both groups of consumers.

It is resulted out in the study of Fornell (1992) that customer satisfaction increases customer loyalty and prevents customer churn, reduces the costs of failed marketing, lowers the customer's price sensitivity, and new customer creation, improve the effectiveness of the advertising, reduces operating costs due to the increase in the number of customers, and further improve business reputation.

Hansen *et al.* (2011) found whether consumer supermarket satisfaction has an influence by the mere composition of consumer's preference structure, in contrast to widespread approaches where consumer satisfaction is concerned with the degree to which consumer expectations and/or preferences are met. And expressed their opinion that Consumers' level of satisfaction with various retailers may not solely be determined by matching preferences with retail products & services, but can also be based on considerations of possibilities for mental justification within a certain preference structure.

Hamburg and Koschate (2004) explored the role of perceived fairness and customer satisfaction on the repurchase intention after a price increase. Their findings of two experimental studies reveal that perceived fairness has a positive impact on the repurchase intention and that satisfaction moderates this relationship.

Yi (1991) in a critical review of customer satisfaction argued that customer satisfaction operates in two different ways: transaction-specific and generally overall.

Where, transaction-specific concept relates to customer satisfaction as the assessment done after a specific purchase.

Martenson (2007) analysed the impact of the corporate store image on customer satisfaction and store loyalty in grocery retailing, found that store as a brand is the most important for customer satisfaction. Retailers need to be good at retailing. Consumers become a satisfied consumer if they think that their needs are understood and addressed by the store as well as the store environment is pleasant and clean.

Brown and Lam (2008) reported a meta-analysis of relationships linking customer satisfaction to employee job satisfaction and perceived service quality makes an effort to achieve correlate employee data with customer data. Overall, both relationships are found positive and statistically and substantively significant. Utilising the aggregated data, estimation of a path analytic model demonstrated that customer-perceived service quality completely mediates the relationship between employee job satisfaction and customer satisfaction.

Esbjerg *et al.* (2012) developed a conceptual framework for analysing customer satisfaction with individual grocery purchasing experiences within an overall 'disconfirmation of expectations model' of customer satisfaction. The contribution of the conceptual framework is twofold. One, framework synthesise and integrates the multiple central concepts from different research groups into a common framework to analyse shopping trip satisfaction and two, by having a focus on satisfaction with individual grocery shopping trips.

Kantabutra (2011) in retail stores of Thailand examined the relationships between perceived vision-based leadership, and consumer and staff satisfaction. Store visions characterised by clarity, challenge, stability, future orientation, brevity, ability to inspire, abstractness and containing a reference to employee, sales, consumer & store leadership directly predict and further improve the store manager leadership as perceived by staff. Such visions also indirectly predict improves staff satisfaction, whereas, staff's perceived leadership enhances staff satisfaction directly. There is no direct impact of staff satisfaction on consumer satisfaction as normally expected elsewhere.

Mazaheri *et al.* (2011) with the help of a lens of a conflict management framework studied service recovery with customer satisfaction; by specifically evaluate the role of pre-existing attitude in determining customer response to service failures. The research of two scenarios based experiments recommended that conflict management style affects service recovery efforts with customer satisfaction. A cooperative recovery style is necessary to satisfy customers and to exceed expectations.

Söderlund and Rosengren (2010) assessed the impact of the service worker's display of emotions (unhappiness vs. happiness) on customer satisfaction under the conditions of different levels of technical service quality (poor vs. good). The research has shown that the impact of the service worker's emotional display behaviour on customer satisfaction is dependent on the level of technical service quality, which means that customer satisfaction is affected only when technical service quality is better rather than poor.

Sánchez-Fernández and Iniesta-Bonillo (2009) analysed the relationship between consumer satisfaction and economic value. Their results provided an operational tool to measure economic value which will allow retailers to design suitable strategies for creating and delivering value to consumers and the usefulness of economic value in the consumer satisfaction.

Veseland Zabkar (2009) suggested that the quality of personal interactions bears no direct influences on members' loyalty; however, it influences the satisfaction of the members strongly than the loyalty program's perceived quality. However, influence on members' loyalty is stronger from the mediating variable of customer satisfaction than from perceived quality of the loyalty program. The results have shown that the role of customer satisfaction is the most important determinant of customer loyalty in the DIY setting.

Fonseca (2009) applied a new technique and a new conceptual model of customer's satisfaction as an approach to modelling and to develop an overall satisfaction index and argues that in order to estimate the global customer satisfaction

measure we must appeal to methodologies recognising that satisfaction must be understood as a latent variable, quantified through multiple indicators.

Orth and Green (2009) indicated in their study that there is higher consumer trust in family business management practices and policies, satisfaction and frontline employee trust but no variations in loyalty. Their research demonstrates differential effects of how image elements affect customer loyalty directly as well as indirectly through trust and satisfaction by examining an integrative loyalty framework.

Darley *et al.* (2008) examined the relationship of perceived salesperson attributes and customer satisfaction behaviour in the purchase experience leading to the patronage of a service department. Their results indicated that gender is a strong moderator of the relationship among the customer satisfaction, future intentions towards service department patronage and perceived salesperson attributes.

Demoulin and Zidda (2008) found up to what extent the satisfaction of loyalty card rewards affects the effectiveness of loyalty card programs in the food retail industry. With the analysis of survey data within the framework of the store, choice models show that the loyalty card owners are more stores most loyal. More precisely, they have indicated that if the reward schemes of the loyalty card program are satisfying the card owners, they are lesser price sensitive and more loyal in comparison to unsatisfied card holders.

Zielke (2008) discussed retail stores asymmetric effects in the formation of satisfaction related to price. The research indicated that value for money, price level, and special offers are both satisfiers and dissatisfiers (one-dimensional); price perceptibility, price processability and price fairness tend to be dissatisfiers only (must be requirements); and price advertising and products in the upper price range are indifferent requirements.

Bodet (2008) according to a double view of concepts found the satisfaction-loyalty relationships. The empirical analysis highlighted the role of overall satisfaction on attitudinal loyalty and reduces the role of transaction-specific

satisfaction. And therefore, found that neither attitudinal loyalty nor customer satisfaction predicts customer repurchase behaviour.

Söderlund and Rosengren (2007) inspected how receiving positive and negative word-of-mouth from dissatisfied and satisfied customers influence the potential customer. The results are consonant with not directly expressed assumptions in the existing literature that word-of-mouth of existing customers has a possibility of a significant effect on potential customers, and this examination shows that in the influence process emotional variables play an important role.

Vázquez-Carrasco and Foxall (2006) investigated the relationship between aspects of consumers' personalities and their perception of active or passive loyalty, satisfaction with, and relational benefits toward the provision of a service. The results have shown that the perception of relational benefits leads to passive loyalty and a higher satisfaction. The results are derived by using partial least square analysis.

Huddleston *et al.* (2009) demonstrated that price, employee service, product assortment, and quality, effect store satisfaction despite store type i.e. conventional or specialty stores. The degree of influence of these attributes varied according to store type. The results indicated that specialty store shopper satisfaction characteristics are clearly described whereas conventional store shopper characteristics are more difficult to pinpoint.

Chapter 3

Conceptual Framework

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- Retailing
 - Retailing strategy
 - Segmentation strategy
 - Targeting strategies
 - Positioning strategy
 - Retail marketing strategy
 - Defensive strategy
 - SWOT analysis
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 - Customer service strategies
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CHAPTER 3

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Introduction

This chapter contributes the brief description of diverse conceptions pertained to the present study. The following important conceptions have been incorporated in this chapter: retailing, retail marketing strategies, retail marketing mix, segmentation strategies, targeting strategies, positioning strategies, defensive strategies, SWOT analysis, PEST analysis, Five forces analysis, ETOP analysis, BCG matrix, Generic strategies, brand, types of brands, merchandise planning, retail assortment strategies, stock (inventory) planning, objective of pricing, price-adjustment strategies, customer service, customer service strategies, store design and its elements planning, customer behaviour and customer satisfaction, etc.

3.1 Retailing

The word 'Retail' originated from an Old French word i.e. 'tailler' that intends "to divide" in terms of tailoring (1365). In 1443, it was first time envisioned with the connotation of a "sale in small quantities" (Harper, 2015).

Retailing is comprehended as an approach of trading / selling merchandise (products) and/or services directly to the customers at a profit. Waters (2015) defines the term retailing as "the sale of goods or commodities in small quantities directly to consumers".

3.2 Retailing strategy

Retailing strategy is a comprehensive marketing plan, which summarises how a merchant (retailer) has the intention of offering the merchandise and / or services to customers and inciting their buying decisions, which comprises the target market of merchant, the retail format planned to exercise to serve the target market and bases for having sustainable competitive advantages. The target market is the segment of the market, which will be the focal point of the merchant's resources and offering a mix. The format explicates the elements of its offering mix [i.e. merchandise assortment,

service assortment, pricing, promotion and communication, premises (i.e. location, store design, etc.), presentation (i.e. layout and visual merchandise), personnel and other physical evidence], decided to serve the target market. A sustainable competitive advantage is an edge to the merchants over its competitors (Levy *et al.*, 2012).

3.3 Segmentation strategy

Market segmentation is a strategy, which segregates broad target market into subsets of consumers, businesses, or countries based on common needs, interests and priorities. Segmentation strategies are exercised to identify and later define the target customers and contribute supporting data for marketing plan elements to triumph specific objectives of the marketing plan. The following are the types of the segmentation strategies:

- Single segment concentration strategy
- Selective specialisation strategy
- Product specialisation strategy
- Market specialisation strategy
- Full market coverage strategy

The below mentioned are the most common variables for segmentation:

- **Geographic variables:** Population density, size and climate factors, location or region, etc.
- **Demographic variables:** Gender, marital status, age, race, education, income, occupation, etc.
- **Psychographic variables:** Opinions, shared interests, values of customers and attitudes, etc.
- **Behavioural variables:** Usage, benefits, customer status or prospect, loyalty, etc.

3.4 Targeting strategies

- **Undifferentiating targeting strategy or mass retailing (no specific mix):**
The firms prefer this strategy do not target any particular segment and select a

single marketing strategy with the conviction that their product & appeal will entice numerous individuals.

Figure 3.1: Undifferentiating targeting strategy

- **Differentiated targeting strategy or selective retailing (specific mix):** The firms determine this strategy, decide to target many segments of the market and develop different offering mix strategies for each of the segments.

Figure 3.2: Differentiating targeting strategy

- **Concentrated targeting strategy or niche retailing (small but profitable):** The firms adopt this strategy concentrate all marketing efforts towards a single segment of the market and develop an offering mix, which caters the needs of the segment.

Figure 3.3: Concentrated targeting strategy

- **Micro (local or individual) targeting strategy or customised retailing:** The firms elect this strategy to design their offering mix to suit the tastes of certain locations and individuals.

3.5 Positioning strategy

Positioning is a systematic process of constructing a unique position in the customer's mind compared to competitors. Firms construct a unique position either by intensifying the USP or by blueprinting the different brand identity through advertising. The following are the types of positioning strategies:

		Price		
		More	The same	More of less
Benefits	More	More for more	More for same	More for Less
	The same			The same for less
	More of less			Less for much less

Figure 3.4: Positioning strategies

Source: Adopted from (Ripley, 2015)

3.6 Retail marketing strategy

- **Market penetration:** This opportunity comprises achievement of growth by directing efforts towards existing customers with the present retailing format of the merchant. Retailers using this strategy, open more stores in the target market, allow existing stores for longer hours, training salesperson for cross-selling and displaying merchandise to increase impulse purchases.
- **Market expansion:** Retailers adopting this strategy, use the existing retail format in new market segments to serve them.
- **Retail format development:** Retailers adopting this strategy, develop a new format of retailing with a different retail mix for the same target market.
- **Diversification:** Retailers adopting this strategy come with a new retail format to serve a new market segment. The diversification may be related

diversification or unrelated. In a related one, present target market or retail format of the retailer has something similar with its new opportunity; however, unrelated diversification has nothing common between the present and the venture.

Growth Opportunities		Target Market	
		Existing	New
Retail Format	Existing	Market Penetration	Market Expansion
	New	Format Development	Diversification

Figure 3.5: Retail marketing strategy
 Source: Adopted from (Levy *et al.*, 2012)

3.7 Defensive strategy

Mostly, the market leaders employ defensive strategies in strategic decisions (Arbuckle, 2015). However, a small-scale firm may use this strategy if achieved a market leader position. The prime objective of such strategies is to protect position, market share, profitability, remain a market leader and fighting off with the present as well as potential competitors, discouraging competitors, making attacks unattractive. It is not any easy task, but, fortunately, firms have multiple choices of strategies. These strategies assist in maintaining a high level of confidence among customers.

- **Preemptive defense** (more aggressive launch an attack on the enemy): Firms adopting this strategy attack a competitor before they are attacked.
- **Counteroffensive defense** (provides an opportunity to an attacker to attack frontally): Firms adopting this strategy attack a competitor when a competitor attacks the firm.
- **Flanking defense** (serve as a defensive corner for weak front): Firms adopt this strategy to protect their market share by diversifying their operations into new segments or niche segments.

- **Position defense** (strategy to retain position): Firms adopting this strategy, try to hold the current market position of them.
- **Mobile defense** (stretches its domain to new territories): Firms adopting this strategy make regular changes in their business operations to discourage the competitors to compete.
- **Contraction defense** (giving up weaker territories or activities): It is the least desirable defense strategy and firms adopting this strategy retreat from the markets.

3.8 SWOT analysis

The SWOT is an acronym for strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats. A SWOT analysis, also known as SWOT matrix is a comprehensive and systematic planning tool utilised to evaluate strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats in any project or any business venture to take prior actions.

It is a very common tool and analysis with this tool could be done to any person, place, product, company or industry. It assists in specifying the goals and objectives of the firms or project based on the internal and external factors, which may be favourable or unfavourable to accomplish those goals and objectives.

	<u>Strengths</u>	<u>Weaknesses</u>
Internal	Internal capabilities, which assists a firm to accomplish its objectives.	Internal limitations, which influence the objectives achieving ability of the firm.
	<u>Opportunities</u>	<u>Threats</u>
External	External factors, which could be exploited by a firm to gain an advantage.	Current & emerging external factors, which may challenge the performance of the firm.
	Positive	Negative

Figure 3.6: The SWOT Analysis
 Source: Adopted from (Humphrey, 2005)

3.9 PEST analysis

The PEST is an acronym for Political, Economic, Social and Technological analysis, which includes the macro-environmental factors important to scanning of the environment for better strategic decisions.

Some analysts include the Legal environment factors and rearrange the mnemonic to SLEPT and after adding environmental factors the same becomes PESTEL or PESTLE.

Figure 3.7: The PEST analysis
Source: Adopted from (Admin, 2011)

3.10 Five force analysis

The initiator of five-force analysis is Prof. Michael E. Porter of Harvard University. Therefore, it is also known as the Porter five forces analysis, which basically offers a framework to understand the level of competition in the industry for developing business strategies. It describes that industrial organisation economics should consider the five forces to understand the intensity of competition and attractiveness of an Industry. Here, attractiveness means the overall profitability of the industry.

Figure 3.8: Five force analysis
Source: Adopted from (Kazmi, 2007)

3.11 ETOP analysis

ETOP is an acronym for Environmental, Threat and Opportunity Profile and utilised as a tool to structure environmental concerns. This tool divides the environment into different sectors and the individual sector is further divided into different sub-sectors. Hence, this tool is also used to analyse the impact of each individual sector and sub-sector on the firm. This tool also offers an explanation about the impact in the form of a statement.

Sr. No.	Environmental Sector	Nature of Impact	Impact of Each Sector
1.	Market		
2.	Technological		
3.	Suppliers		
4.	Economic		
5.	Regulatory		
6.	Political		
7.	Socio-cultural		
8.	International		

Figure 3.9: ETOP analysis
Source: Adopted from (Glueck and Lauch, 1984)

3.12 BCG matrix

BCG Matrix is a portfolio planning mechanism, which analyse the different SBUs / Products / Businesses of the firm, according to the market growth rate and relative market share. SBUs / Products / Businesses are categorised as stars, cash cows, question marks or dogs based on their market growth rate and relative market share.

Figure 3.10: BCG Matrix
Source: Adopted from (Kazmi, 2007)

3.13 Generic strategies

The concept of generic strategies was initiated by Michael E. Porter in 1980. Therefore, also known as Porter's generic strategies and explicate that how a firm can pursue competitive advantage in the selected market. There are 4 generic strategies:

Figure 3.11: Generic strategies
Source: Adopted from (Porter, 1985)

- **Cost Leadership** (i.e. broadly target with lower cost): Firms adopting this strategy, target the customers in most of the segments of an industry with the lowest price.
- **Differentiation** (i.e. broadly target with differentiation): Firms adopting this strategy, target the customers in most or all segments on the basis of attributes rather than price. Firms adopting this strategy attempt to differentiate themselves from their competitors. The firms look to minimise costs in all the areas, which do not differentiate.
- **Cost Focus** (i.e. narrowly target with lower cost): Firms adopting this strategy, focus on one or few segments. The firm adopts to offer a lower cost in that scope.
- **Differentiation Focus** (i.e. narrowly target with differentiation): Firms adopting this strategy focus on one or a few segments and differentiate them in that scope.

3.14 Retail marketing mix

The retail marketing mix is a set of tools, which work together for catering the customer needs and building a long-term relationship with them. The set of tools comprises merchandise (product), price, promotion, place or premises, presentation, personnel and other physical evidence.

- **Product:** It is the most important element of the retail marketing mix that comprises the classification and brands. With this element, the retailers may satisfy the needs and desires as per the expectations of the customers.
- **Price:** It is considered as an important element of the mix, as brings profits to the firm. Methods of pricing usually based on the target market, competition, margins and brands.
- **Promotion:** This element is designed for promotion and communication pertained to various products and services that include the advertising (in-store or out-store), sales promotion, public relations, personal retailing, direct retailing, internet retailing.
- **Premises / Place:** This element is designed to choose the right channels for reaching to the customers and comprises the locations, sites, space, etc.

- **Presentation:** This element portrays the image of the retailers and comprises the presentation of the merchandise, stores, premises, offices, delivery vans, warehouses, websites, etc.
- **Personnel:** It is an important element of the mix and directly associated with the satisfaction of the customers pertained to services. It comprises the sales personnel, contact personnel and factors pertained to personnel.

Figure 3.12: Retail marketing mix
Source: Adopted from (Jhureley, 2011)

3.15 Brand

The brand is a registered name, term, design, symbol, or any other features that differentiate merchandise of one producer or merchant from the others. The legal term of the brand is a trademark (Cohen, 2011). There are different types of brands as follows:

- **Generic brands:** Generic brands are those, which do not have a brand name, logo and promotion.
- **Local brands:** The merchandise distributed and sold in a few specific areas of the country.

- **Manufacturer brands:** Manufacturer brands are developed by the manufacturer himself and carry the manufacturer's name or any other name of the manufacturer's choice.
- **National brands:** The brands that are distributed nationally, but owned by the manufacturer or distributor.
- **International brands:** The brands that are distributed across the borders (world) but owned by the manufacturer or distributor
- **Private (store) brands:** Products which are distributed in the brand name of the retailer, not the manufacturer.

3.16 Merchandise planning

It is a strategic choice pertained to planning sales and inventory for maximising ROI and profitability. This is accomplished through increasing sales potential and decreasing the losses from overstock or out of stock conditions (The planning Factory Limited, 2014).

Figure 3.13: Merchandise planning
Source: Adopted from (Sayed, 2015)

Following are the important factors in merchandise planning:

- Target market
- Goods & service growth potential
- Fashion trends
- Image of retailer
- Competition
- Customer segments
- Responsiveness to customers
- Amount of investment
- Profitability
- Risk

Following are the important factors for planning quality of merchandise:

- Target market
- Competition
- Image of retailer
- Store location
- Stock turnover
- Profitability
- The customer service offered
- Personnel
- Perceived goods/service benefits
- Manufactures vs. private brands

3.17 Retail assortment strategy (product assortment):

Retail assortment strategy is a strategic decision pertained to the number and type of merchandise, the merchant (retailer) decides to display in the store for customers. The retailers have few choices to decide about assortment:

- **A narrow variety & a shallow assortment:** Retailers adopting his strategy offer few goods/service categories and a limited assortment in each category.
- **A wide variety & a shallow assortment:** Retailers adopting his strategy offer many goods/service categories and a limited assortment in each category.
- **A narrow variety & a deep assortment:** Retailers adopting his strategy offer few goods/service categories and a large assortment in each category.

- **A wide variety & a deep assortment:** Retailers adopting his strategy offer many goods/service categories and a large assortment in each category.

3.18 Stock (inventory) planning

Stock (inventory) planning has a consequential impact on the cash flows as well as the profit of the firm. It assists in understanding the optimal time and quantity of inventory. It is the decision pertained to the alignment of sales and production capacity. Retailers inventory planning includes the:

- Weekly planning.
- Monthly planning.
- Yearly planning.
- Long term planning.

3.19 Objectives of pricing

Pricing objectives are the guiding principles in the overall pricing process. When, firms decide their pricing objectives need to consider the overall marketing, strategic, and financial objectives of the firm; objectives of brand or product offered, consumer price and price elasticity in the market and the resources. The firms have a different pricing objective, approaches, and strategies to choose:

3.19.1 Pricing objectives

- Survival.
- Maximising current profit.
- Maximising market share.
- Maximising market skimming.
- Product quality leadership.

3.19.2 Pricing approaches

- Demand-oriented pricing.
- Cost-oriented pricing.
- Competition-oriented pricing.
- Leadership-oriented pricing.

3.19.3 Pricing strategies

- Market-skimming pricing.
- Market-penetration pricing.
- Variable (zone) pricing.
- Markup pricing.
- Target return pricing.
- Perceived value pricing.
- Going rate pricing.
- Value pricing.
 - Everyday low pricing (EDLP).
 - High-low pricing.

3.19.4 Price-adjustment strategies

- **Discount & allowance pricing:** Reduction in prices to reward customer responses like as promoting the product or paying early.
- **Segmented pricing:** Adjusting the price to allow for differences in customers, locations or merchandise.
- **Psychological pricing:** Adjustment in prices for psychological effect.
- **Promotional pricing:** temporarily reducing prices to increase short-run sales.
- **Geographical pricing:** Adjusting prices to account for the geographic location of the customer.
- **Dynamic pricing:** Adjustment in prices continues to meet the features and needs of individual customers and various situations.
- **International pricing:** Adjustment in prices for the international market.

3.20 Customer service

Customer service is catering the needs of customers with the delivery of high quality and professional assistance before, during and after the customers' needs are satisfied. The customer services assist in maintaining the long-term relationship with customers and continuing the revenue to the company. Customer service is one among the many key factors for building rapport and brand name of the company. The basic characteristics of good customer service are:

- Promptness.

- Politeness.
- Professionalism.
- Personalisation.

3.20.1 The Customer Service skills that matter

Ciotti, (2013) identified some skills that every support employee should develop to delight the customers are:

- Patience.
- Attentiveness.
- Clear communication skills.
- Knowledge of the product.
- Ability to use "positive language".
- Acting skills.
- Time management skills.
- Ability to "read" customers.
- A calming presence.
- Goal oriented focus.
- Ability to handle surprises.
- Persuasion skills.
- Tenacity.
- Closing ability.
- Willingness to learn.

3.20.2 Basic rules for good customer service

- Be ready to serve your customers at any point of time at any place.
- Do not keep your customers waiting.
- Have answer of all the questions and answer those questions, which have not been asked.
- Decide what to promise or not to promise to your customers.
- Always cater more than the promise of firm and expectations of customers.

3.20.3 Customer service strategies

The service providers may have one approach among the mentioned below:

- **Patronage builders:** Firms adopting his strategy involve in high-cost activities that which are basic reasons behind the customer loyalty).

- **Patronage solidifiers:** Firms adopting his strategy involve in the low-cost little things that increase loyalty.
- **Disappointers:** Firms adopting his strategy involve in expansive activities that do no real good.
- **Basics:** Firms adopting his strategy involve in low-cost activities, which are naturally expected.

3.21 Store design elements

- **Layouts:** It is an important element of store design. The retailers use following layouts:
 - **Grid (straight) layout:** In this layout, the parallel aisles are used and the products (merchandise) are kept on the shelves on both sides of the aisles. The Cash counter can be located at the exits or entrances of the stores.

Figure 3.14: Grid layout

Source: Adopted from (Stanton, 2015)

- **Curving or loop (race track) layout:** In this layout, the major aisle is used to loop around the store for guiding the customer traffic in the several departments of the store.

Figure 3.15: Curving or loop layout

(Source: Stanton, 2015)

- **Free flow layout:** Popularly known as a boutique layout, in which the fixtures and aisles are arranged in a symmetric pattern.

Figure 3.16: Free flow layout

Source: Adopted from (Stanton, 2015)

- **Spine layout:** In this layout, the main aisle is used as the movements between the several cells established on both sides of the aisles.

Figure 3.17: Spine layout

Source: Adopted from (Stanton, 2015)

- **Signage:** Signage is used to assist the customers in locating the merchandise, categories, different departments and promotional offers. Three kinds of signage are used:
 - **Category signage:** Used to assist in locating the information within a particular department of the store.
 - **Promotional signage:** Used to assist in locating the information pertained to special offers.
 - **Point-of-sale signage:** Used to assist in locating the information pertained to price and other details of products.

3.22 Visual merchandising

It is the decision pertained to the presentation of the merchandise and stores to entice the customer visiting the store. The retailers utilise the straight sacks, rounders, four-way fixtures, gondolas to present the merchandise in the stores and also create an appealing store atmosphere (exterior and interior).

- **Exterior atmospherics:** Exterior atmospherics comprises the elements like a storefront, entrances, display window, visibility, adjoining store, etc. These elements assist in creating eye-catching and attractive store exterior
- **Interior atmospherics-** Interior atmospherics comprises the elements like flooring, lighting, colour, personnel, cleanliness, walls, aisles, temperature, sitting areas, music, etc. These elements assist building up the physical shopping environment of a store.

3.23 Consumer behaviour

It is all about the psychological processes, through which a consumer travel for need identification, alternatives to satisfy the needs, making purchase decisions, collecting & interpreting information, taking the decision of purchase, consumption and disposal.

Figure 3.18: Consumer behaviour

3.23.1 Consumer choice and decision-making

Figure 3.19: Consumer choice and decision-making

Source: Adopted from (Perner, 2008)

3.24 Customer satisfaction

Customer satisfaction measures the degree how well the expectations of customers pertained to products or services have been met. According to Beard (2014), top reasons, why customer satisfaction is important are:

- A tool for evaluating the consumer repurchase intentions as well as loyalty
- A point of differentiation.
- Helps in decreasing customer churn.
- Assist in increasing Customer Lifetime Value.
- Assist in creating positive word of mouth.
- Assist in retaining customers.

Chapter 4

Research Methodolog y

-
- Objectives of the study
 - Significance of the study
 - Delimitation of the study
 - Research hypotheses
 - Research design
 - Locale of the study
 - Universe of the study
 - Sampling design and selection of samples
 - Collection of data
 - Tools for data collection
 - Pilot study
 - Scales used for accumulating the responses
 - The validity of scales
 - The reliability of scales & internal consistency of reliability
 - The method used for collecting the data
 - Methods of reporting
 - Statistical analysis of data

CHAPTER 4

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Introduction

This chapter on methodology provides the description of the objectives, scope, limitations and research procedure followed to carry out the present study. The individual response and institutional responses have been studied independently in this study and the relationship between the two has not been studied so far. The detailed research methodology of the present study is being presented under the following heads:

4.1 Objectives of the study

After a thorough review of existing literature, it is understood that around the globe, researchers carried out very less research work pertained to retailing strategies of products and customer services in the organised retail industry. The maximum work carried out is presenting either the view of retailers or the customers and the existing work is not able to provide a comprehensive picture of retailing strategies of products and customer services in the organised retail industry. Therefore, to full-fill the gap, the current study has been taken to provide a comprehensive picture of retailing strategies of products and customer services in the organised retail industry from the retailers' point of view as well as from customers' point of view. The current research has been carried with the following objectives:

- To study the various products and customer services introduced by organised retail industry.
- To appraise the various retailing strategies introduced by organised retail industry.
- To unpack the changing buying behaviour of customers in the organised retail industry.
- To get at the factors that influence the buying behaviour of customers in the organised retail industry.
- To assess the customer satisfaction level with regards to various merchandise (products) and services introduced by organised retail industry.

4.2 Significance of the study

The study could be rationalised for its multiple utilities and implements in the consequent significancies: the study contributes knowledge & facts about the variegated merchandise (products) & customer services penetrated by organised retailers in the industry. The study aspires to discover the retailing strategies determined by organised retailers together with finding the dimensional gap to comprehend in the domain of retailing strategies in the line of the hyper-competitive environment. The study observes and reveals appropriate indices for employing modern / high-tech retailing approaches to terminate the gaps.

This study also delivers evidence about the dilemmas of customers along with some potential revelations to them. The study ascribes details for the betterment essential in the merchandise (products) & services that clients want. The study also determines diverse components and customer services mandatory to persist the retailing industry in a highly competitive retail environment. The study additionally functions to deliver the factors that serve towards the superior level of customer satisfaction in the organised retail industry.

The study assists the management of organised retail stores to appraise upon the retailing strategy. The study benefits in comprehending the retailing environment, retailing culture and the retail decision process. Through this study, the researcher appropriated the opportunity to exercise the theoretical knowledge in the appropriate practical arena. The researcher not only fulfils the requisite of Ph.D. curriculum, additionally comprehended lots about the industry. The study will additionally ascertain to be of comprehensive assistance to the researchers, who yearn to do uniform or accompanied studies in the forthcoming time.

4.3 Delimitation of the study

- The study focuses only on the organised retail sector.
- The study is limited to 3-5 years data.
- The study was delimited to the selected cities of Maharashtra state, namely Nagpur, Amravati, Navi Mumbai, Thane, Nashik, Jalgaon, Kolhapur, Sangli, Pune and Aurangabad.

- The study was delimited with 10 retail stores, namely Big Bazaar, NEXT, HyperCITY, Max, more.MEGASStore, D⁺Mart, Star Bazaar, Reliance Digital, Big Megamart and **West Side**.
- The study is limited to 3 formats, i.e. multi-format retail stores, specialised fashion retail stores and specialised electronics retail store. It cannot be implemented in other formats of retailing.
- The study is also delimited to the 2000 respondents from selected cities.

4.4. Research hypotheses

Based on gaps in the literature review and objectives of the study, the following two null hypotheses have been formulated:

- H₀₁:** Retailing strategies introduced by organised retailers are not significant to sustain in the hyper-competitive retail market.
- H₀₂:** Customers are not significantly satisfied with various products & services introduced by organised retailers.

4.5 Research Design

Philips (1966) defined a good research design as “....The blueprint of the collection, measurement and analysis of data. It aids the scientists in the allocation of his limited resources by posing a crucial choice- is the blueprint to include experiments, interviews, observation, the analysis of records, simulation, or some combination of these? Are the methods of data collection and the research situation to be highly structured? Is an intensive study of a small sample more effective than a less intensive study of a larger sample? Should the analysis be primarily quantitative or qualitative?” Taking the inspirations from this definition, the research design for the present study has been defined as follows:

Both descriptive and exploratory research methods were used for compiling this study. An exploratory research focus to develop initial hunches or insights and to provide direction for any further research needed and descriptive research aims to describe something (Parasuraman *et al.*, 2007). In the present study, the exploratory research helped in developing the hypotheses and framing the objectives of the study through the analysis of secondary data, while descriptive research was used to pursue the objectives and the hypothesis of this study.

4.6 Locale of the study

The study was conducted in the Maharashtra state of India and the organised retail stores from various segments were selected from various parts of the state while choosing the sample unit. Efforts were made to cover the entire state geographically and regionally, at least 2 well-known cities were selected from each region.

Figure 4.1: Locale and universe of the study

4.7 Universe of the Study

For conducting the present study, the whole Maharashtra state was classified into 5 regions, i.e. Northern Maharashtra, Southern Maharashtra, Eastern Maharashtra, Western Maharashtra and Central Maharashtra. From each region, two well-known cities were selected. Further, from each city, one retail store was selected for the study (i.e. five regions * two retail stores per region = ten retail stores). Those retail stores are Big Bazaar, NEXT, HyperCITY, Max, more.MEGASTore, D Mart, Star Bazaar, Reliance Digital, Big Megamart and **W**est Side. Out of total 10 retail stores, 5 were hyper stores and remaining 5 were super stores. These hyper and super

stores have also been selected by a planning that from each region one hyper and one super store must be selected for the study. The 5 hyper stores, namely Big Bazaar, HyperCITY, More.MEGASTore, Star Bazaar, and Big MegaMart have been selected while NEXT, Max, D-Mart, Reliance Digital and Westside have been selected as the representative of super stores (refer table 4.1).

4.8 Sampling design and selection of samples

For the present study, a *non-probability convenience sampling* technique was resorted for institutional (i.e. store personnel) and individual (i.e. customers) respondents. The non-probability sampling is a subjective approach in which the probability of determination of the population units cannot approximate. The suitability or convenience of the researcher constructs the conjuncture for determining a sample of units in convenience sampling (Parasuraman *et al.*, 2007).

S.N.	Region	City	Retail Store	Type	Sample Size (Customers)
1	Eastern Maharashtra	Nagpur	Big Bazaar	Hyper Store	200
		Amravati	NEXT	Super Store	200
2	Western Maharashtra	Navi Mumbai	HyperCITY	Hyper Store	200
		Thane	Max	Super Store	200
3	Northern Maharashtra	Nashik	More.MEGASTore	Hyper Store	200
		Jalgaon	D-Mart	Super Store	200
4	Southern Maharashtra	Kolhapur	Star Bazaar	Hyper Store	200
		Sangli	Reliance Digital	Super Store	200
5	Central Maharashtra	Pune	Big Megamart	Hyper Store	200
		Aurangabad	West Side	Super Store	200
Total	5	10	10	5 + 5	2000

Total 10 retail stores, namely Big Bazaar, NEXT, HyperCITY, Max, more.MEGASTore, D-Mart, Star Bazaar, Reliance Digital, Big Megamart and West Side were selected for the study. From each retail store, an institutional questionnaire got filled up by store personnel (i.e. store manager or assistant store manager or

representative of the store) to receive accurate data about various products, services and retailing strategies introduced by the respective retail store.

In total 2000 customers of retail stores (i.e. 10 retail stores * 200 customers) were contacted. Only those respondents were selected, who were willingly agreed to respond and had a positive outlook toward the problem. From the area of each selected retail stores 200 respondents contacted at a convenient basis for obtaining data about their buying behaviour, factors influencing their buying behaviour, and satisfaction level pertained to products and services offered by retail stores. Detail plan for selection of respondents has been mentioned in table 4.1.

4.9 Collection of data

Neelankavil (2007) discussed that one among the cardinal rules in data accumulation is to deplete all secondary data stimuli before endeavouring a primary study. The present study is based on both secondary and primary data. To achieve the objectives of the present study both primary and secondary data were collected from various sources.

The **secondary data** played a vital role in a review of the literature, formulate hypothesis and questionnaire preparation. It was accumulated from various libraries, books, journals, magazines, Retail Association of India, FICCI, websites and other published sources available, references of the same have been cited at the end of conclusion. Utilising the information from the secondary data, two sets of structured questionnaire were prepared for respondents to accumulate the **primary data**, comprising open & close ended questions. Self-structured questionnaires were prepared to collect the data from institutions (i.e. personnel of retail stores) and individual customers of stores. Two retail stores from five regions of Maharashtra namely eastern, western, northern, southern and central were selected to collect the primary data.

4.10 Tools for data collection

Two instruments, one for personnel of retail stores (i.e. institutional questionnaire) and another for customers of retail stores (i.e. individual questionnaire), were constructed to accomplish the objectives of the study.

4.10.1 Institutional questionnaire

The institutional questionnaire was used to know the views of the respondents (i.e. personnel of retail stores) on retailing strategy. This questionnaire consists of 69 items (questions) in all, however, mostly questions also comprise the succeeding and sub-questions. The responses of the respondents have been received on the nominal and ordinal scales in this instrument. The validity, reliability of the scales and internal consistency of reliability were also established.

4.10.2 Individual questionnaire

The individual questionnaire was used to know the views of the respondents (i.e. customers of retail stores) on product and service, buying behaviour influencing factors and satisfaction level. The basic purpose of the questionnaire was to analyse the customer profile, buying behaviour of customers, factors influencing buying behaviour, the customer satisfaction with the product and service offered by retail stores. This questionnaire consists of 33 items (questions) in all, however, mostly questions also comprise the succeeding and sub-questions and pattern of questions is different from another. The responses of the respondents have been received on the nominal scales, ordinal scales and Likert's (1970) five point scale (basically an ordinal scale) in this instrument. The validity, reliability of the scales and internal consistency of reliability were also established.

4.11 Pilot study

It is necessary to design a suitable questionnaire, conducting a pilot study and undertake a pre-testing of the questionnaire (Beri, 2000). Both questionnaires were tested by conducting a pilot study of the few respondents selected on a random basis. The institutional questionnaire was pre-tested with personnel of Big Megamart, Star Bazaar and NEXT. Taking the insight from this pre-testing of the institutional questionnaire, certain items were included and even excluded to modify the questionnaire for the final study.

The individual questionnaire was also pre-tested with customers 200 customers of organised retail stores selected on a random basis. Utilising the insight from pre-testing of the individual questionnaire, certain items were included and even excluded to modify the questionnaire for the final study.

4.12 Scales used for accumulating the responses

In the institutional questionnaire, the responses of the respondents have been received on the nominal and ordinal scales. In few questions, the respondents have been asked to rate the variables of 4-point importance scale (basically an ordinal scale), which is ranging like extremely important (4), important (3), partially important (2) and not important (1). While, in few other questions, the respondents have been asked to rate the variables of 4-point agreement scale (basically an ordinal scale), which is ranging like extremely agree (4), agree (3), partially agree (2) and not agree (1).

In the individual questionnaire, the responses of the respondents have been received on the nominal scales and ordinal scales. However, the responses pertained to the factors influencing the buying behaviour have been taken on Likert's (1970) five point scale (basically an ordinal scale) ranging from extremely influenced (2) to not at all influenced (-2) with the middle of the scale recognised by the response alternative neither influenced nor uninfluenced (0). And the responses pertained to the customer satisfaction have been collected on five point expectation cum satisfaction scale (basically an ordinal scale) ranging from greatly exceeding expectations and delighted (5), to much less than expectations and disappointed (1) with the middle of the scale identified by the response alternative matching expectations and satisfied (3).

4.13 The validity of scales

The face & content validity method was employed to measure the validity of the scales used both individual and institutional questionnaires. "Face validity is the dimension to which a measurement scale seems to measure what is hypothesised to measure" (McDaniel and Gates, 2001). Face validity is determined by the assessment of the researcher, who constructed the questionnaire with divergent scales, which rationally exhibited to correctly reflect what the researcher was hypothesised to evaluate and to evaluate the validity of the content, first researcher signified what precisely required being evaluated.

For the topical study, essential variables were determined through the objectives along with hypothesis formulated, which assisted in discovering what

required being evaluated. Secondly, by a comprehensive review of the literature to determine all potential items were ascertained. Third, opinions from subject experts, retail store personnel and customers were taken into the consideration on whether conclusive items should be included or even excluded.

4.14 The reliability of scales and internal consistency of reliability

Reliability is synonymous with repeatability. It is an evaluation that confirms coherent outcomes over time is remarked to be reliable. When an evaluation is plausible to random error, it shortfalls the reliability. The reliability of an instrument attributes an upper limit on its validity. An evaluation that shortfalls the reliability will also shortfalls the validity. If the scale of reliability is adjacent to 1, it ensures an evidence of good reliability. Reliability analysis is a distinguished and commonly facilitated mechanism for estimating the internal consistency of the variables. The reliability of the scale was computed through the adoption of the research of Copper and Schindler (2006).

Cronbach (1951) Alpha (α) is designed as a measure of internal consistency. The alpha values closer to 1, the greater the internal consistency of items in the instrument being considered. The internal consistency of reliability of the scales used in both questionnaires was measured through Cronbach's Alfa. The Alfa values for all importance scales and agreement scales used in the institutional questionnaire are ranging from 0.601 to 0.805, which is an indication of the good internal consistency of reliability of the scales used in the questionnaire. In the case of scales used in the individual questionnaire, the Alfa value of influence scale was 0.791 and for expectation cum satisfaction scale was 0.823, which is an indication of the good internal consistency of reliability of the scales used in the questionnaire.

4.15 The method used for collecting the data

Survey method and printed questionnaires were employed in accumulating the primary data. "The personally administrated questionnaires ascertain rapport as well as encourage respondents, moreover hereto, elucidate the questions expeditiously" (Sekaran, 2003). Therefore, the questionnaires were supervised individually practicing the face to face approach to enhance response rate, encourage respondents and elucidate the doubts instantly. The data was collected over a span of 12 months. A

survey was done in all seven days, but especially survey has also been done on Saturday and Sunday to get more positive responses.

4.16 Methods of reporting / presenting data

The research report text consists of tables and charts for better presentation and understanding of context. The data has been presented with the help of univariate as well as bivariate or multivariate tabulation. The univariate tabulation is also known as one-way tabulation and bivariate or multivariate tabulation is known as cross tabulation (Beri, 2000). Moreover, the data has also been presented with the help of 3D pie charts, 3D clustered column charts, radar with markers charts and line charts.

4.17 Statistical analysis of data

The data obtained in the present study were analysed using suitable statistical tools to appraise the various retailing strategies introduced by organised retail industry and assess the customer satisfaction level with regards to various merchandise (products) and services introduced by organised retail industry. The following statistical tools were used for interpretation of data.

- **Parametric test:** One sample t-test
- **Nonparametric test:** Kolmogorov-Smirnov one-sample test
- **Other statistical tools:** Simple percentage method, mean, standard deviation, and weighted average method

4.17.1 Simple percentage method

It has been used to analyse the data pertained to the customer profile, buying behaviour, factors affecting buying behaviour and customer satisfaction.

4.17.2 Mean and standard deviation

It has been used to analyse the data pertained to the customer profile, buying behaviour, factors affecting buying behaviour and customer satisfaction.

4.17.3 Weighted average method

It has been used to analyse the data pertained to factors affecting the buying behaviour of customers of retail stores and satisfaction of customers.

4.17.4 Kolmogorov-Smirnov one-sample test

It is similar to the Chi-Square test of goodness of fit. It has been used to analyse the data collected on importance and agreement scales in the institutional questionnaire and also utilised in the individual questionnaire to analyse the data pertained to customer satisfaction.

4.17.4 One sample t-test

It has been used to analyse the data collected on five point expectation cum satisfaction scale pertained to customer satisfaction.

Section 2

Data Analysis, Results & Discussion

CHAPTER 5: Merchandises (products) & customer services in organised retail industry

CHAPTER 6: Retailing strategies introduced by organised retail industry

CHAPTER 7: Changing buying behaviour of customers in the organised retail industry

CHAPTER 8: Customer satisfaction with the merchandise (products) and services offered by organised retail industry and testing of hypotheses

CHAPTER 9: Conclusion and recommendations

Chapter 5

Various Products & Customer Services in Organised Retail Industry

- Merchandise (products) offered by organised retail industry
 - Merchandise offered by multi-format organised retailers
 - Merchandise offered by fashion-organised retailers
 - Merchandise offered by electronics-organised retailers
- Customer services introduced by organised retail industry
 - Services introduced by multi-format organised retailers
 - Services introduced by fashion-organised retailers
 - Services introduced by electronics-organised retailers

CHAPTER 5

MERCHANDISE (PRODUCTS) & CUSTOMER SERVICES IN ORGANISED RETAIL INDUSTRY

Introduction

This chapter incorporates the analysis of assorted data pertained to merchandise and services introduced by organised retail industry, which have been accumulated through secondary data sources and personal interaction with responsible personnel of the respective organised retail store. Merchandise portfolio analysis of merchandise offered by organised retail industry has been presented through BCG Matrix. Further, results have been interpreted and discussed to reach on some inferences at the end of the different sections. This chapter has been segregated into two sub-sections as follows:

5.1 Merchandises offered by organised retail industry

5.2 Customer services introduced by organised retail industry

MERCHANDISE OFFERED BY ORGANISED RETAIL INDUSTRY

This sub-section encompasses the data associated with various merchandise offered by organised retailers to their customers. It is not possible to incorporate all the merchandise offered by organised retailers because multi-format organised retailers (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and Big Bazaar) offers more than 30000 merchandise to their customers. Therefore, merchandise lines offered by organised retailers are determined in this chapter for the study of merchandise offered by organised retailers. Few types of merchandise have also been presented under these merchandise lines as indicators (representative) of respective merchandise lines. The merchandise offered by organised retailers (included in the study) has been exhibited as follows:

Merchandise offered by multi-format (item) organised retailers

- 5.1.1 Merchandise offered by HyperCITY
- 5.1.2 Merchandise offered by Star Bazaar
- 5.1.3 Merchandise offered by more.MEGASStore
- 5.1.4 Merchandise offered by Big Bazaar
- 5.1.5 Merchandise offered by D⁺Mart

Merchandise offered by fashion item organised retailers

- 5.1.6 Merchandise offered by Big Megamart
- 5.1.7 Merchandise offered by **W**est Side
- 5.1.8 Merchandise offered by Max

Merchandise offered by the electronics item organised retailers

- 5.1.9 Merchandise offered by Reliance Digital
- 5.1.10 Merchandise offered by NEXT

Moreover, the merchandise portfolio analysis has also been done through the BCG Matrix to comprehend the merchandise portfolios of different organised retailers included in this study.

5.1.1 Merchandise offered by HyperCITY

HyperCITY offers merchandise under the merchandise lines like food & grocery, health & beauty, home & furniture, fashion, electronics, toys, sports and private (store-level) brands.

Merchandise lines of HyperCITY

- **Food & Grocery** – Fruits & vegetables (onion, cabbage, watermelon, potato, blueberry, royal gala apple, ladyfinger, broccoli, yellow pears and so on), meat & fish (specialty eggs range, chicken salami, chicken cut portions, seer fish, sausages, mutton chops, pomfrets, marinated chicken and so on), ready & instant food (cornflakes, jams, noodles, chocolate spread, muesli, choco pie, pastas, snacks & chips, soups, baked potato chips, chocolates, tomato ketchup, choco fills, cakes & deserts, health foods, pickles & papads, honey, instant & gravy mixes, breakfast and cereals, canned foods, biscuits, popcorns and so on), staples (ghee & vanaspati, olive oils, edible oils, rice, pulses, soya chunks, wheat flour, maida, peanuts, besan, suji, ready spices, whole spices, mukhwas, dry fruits, pohas, Sabu dana, sugar, salt and so on), beverages (cold drink, tea bag, milk, coffee, bournvita, tade, mineral water, squashes, syrups, juices & health drinks, floured milk, etc.), International foods (olive oils, tomato soups, beans, walnuts, different type of olives, tea, bread pieces, sweet corns and so on)
- **Health & Beauty** - Fragrances (deos, perfumes, premium perfumes and so on), cosmetics (eye range, lip range, make up remover, eyeliner kajal, nail colour remover and so on), dental & oral care (toothpaste, mouthwash, toothbrush and so on), hair care (hair gel range, silky potion, coconut hair oil, shampoos, conditioner, hair colour, OTC and so on), skin care (talcum, hair removal strips, nose strip, disposable razor, fairness cream & lotions, body lotion, lip care, day cream, herbal cosmetics, colour cosmetics, sanitary needs, grooming and so on) personal hygiene (hand sanitiser, body wash range, soap regular, moist soap, germ shield soap, hand washes, neem face pack, whisper ultra and so on), baby care (Lal tail, baby soap, Mamy Poko pants, baby top2toe wash, Woodward gripe water, baby buds, baby wipes / diapers, baby foods, baby / kids grooming and so on)

- **Home & Furniture** – Homeware (travel goods, bag packs, outdoor bags, link bags, glassware range, utensils range, bath accessories, non-stick cookware, crockery range, kitchen implements, home decor range, bake wares range, storage / plastics, cutlery range, tumblers, plates, bowls, storage & nonstick containers, lunch boxes, hard & anodised cookware, cookers & cooking vassals, dinner sets, loose crockery, mugs, cups, soccer and so on), home needs (gardening range, tools range, bags and covers range, pet care range, electrical items and lighting, CFL, extension board, hangers, dryers and cleaning solutions, home care range, detergents, bath accessory, cabinet & mirrors, laundry aids, agarbatties, pooja needs, room fresheners, pesticides, scrubs, brooms, brushes, disposable wares, parties napkins, facial & car tissues, toilets & kitchen tools, foils, garbage bags, ladders, slopes, bath ware, artificial flowers, wall frames and so on), home linen (bath towels, cushion fillers, bedding set, bath mats, table covers, pillow covers, curtains, hand towels, pillow fillers, cushion filler, door mats, table mats, cushion covers, face towel, quilts, bed sheets, rugs & carpets, table cloths & napkins, apron, deabaan set, lying and so on), furniture (stools, accessories, corner sofa w/d cushion, night stand, wardrobes, sofa beds, dining sets, TV units, sofa sets, bean bags, dresser, recliner, kids bunk beds, beds, corner sofas and so on), stationery (gifting needs, stationery set, school needs, pencil case metal, party items, office supplies, school bags, etc.), household and cleaning needs (mini pen, aluminium foil, dish wash liquid, toilet cleaner, detergent, all out refill, all out ultra-smart chip, fabric conditioner, household cleaning and so on)
- **Fashion-** Men's (formal shirt, corduroy trouser, formal trousers, casual shirts, striped T-shirts, jacket, jeans, denim, ties, belts, shorts, boxer shorts, hanky, cargos, undergarments, sweaters, wind cheaters, track-pants, caps, hand globs, accessories and so on), women's (printed kurta, dupatta, corduroy trouser, knit Churidar, house coat, nightys, leggings, salwar, denim, hanky, frocks, striped T-shirts, tops, woven pyjama jeans, skirts, inner wears, jackets, sweaters, wind cheaters, stole, ribbons, shorts, checked capris, bags, top with pants, bottom jegging, accessories and so on), boys (shirts, T-shirts, track pants, jeans, cargos, denim, jacket, caps, sweaters, accessories and so on), girls (tops, T-shirts, frocks, jackets, sweaters, ribbons, shorts, jeans, denims, leggings, skirts, inner wears, accessories and so on), newborn baby garments (infant

wears, diapers, accessories and so on), men's footwear (formal shoes, sport shoes, sandals, slippers, socks, casual footwear, accessories and so on), women's footwear (fashion footwear, shoes, flip flop, slippers, sandals, socks, accessories and so on), kids footwear (sport shoes, formal, school, sandals, socks, accessories and so on)

- **Electronics** – Large appliances (microwaves, air conditioners, refrigerators, washing machines and so on), small appliances (mixer grinder & blender, juicers, toaster, vacuum cleaner, rice cooker, irons, water purifier, personal care, kettle & coffee maker, telephones, CD players, DVD players, printers, mobile & accessory, gas stove, induction earphone and so on), electronics (cameras, camcorders, laptops, accessories and so on), home entertainment (home theatres, LCD TV, flat panel TVs, LCD TVs, 3D TVs, speakers and so on)
- **Toys** - Cars & jeeps, ball toys, board game, puzzles & board games, teddy bears, remote control toys, blocks & sorting, other sports, play sets, action figures, inflatable, soft cushions, do it yourself, other soft toys, track sets, infant utility, clay sets, guns & accessories, beach toys, helicopter auto frequency, cars & bikes, dolls and so on.
- **Sports** - Health & fitness (fitness accessories, home gyms, weights, treadmills, health formulas, exercise bike and so on), sports (darts, tennis, badminton, boxing, volleyball, cycles, camping, carom, football, hockey, baseball, swimming, table tennis, cricket, squash, basketball, kids cycles, soccer table and so on)
- **Private (store-level) Brands** - Fresh Basket, Everyday (Everyday tissue hamper, coffee mug, range of Everyday fryums, Everyday range of jams, range of Everyday soups, Everyday range of dry fruits, Everyday range of pulses, ghee, rice and so on), Terzo (scrub pad, wipe and so on), Avorio (bath towel, single & double bed sheet and so on), Ebano (kasroll, porcelian dinner set, duffel, trolley and so on), Technix (Hb, Vc compact, kettle), Maxit (enduro cycle, exercise bike, treadmill kl), Waitrose (cornflakes, baked beans in tomato, porridge oats, olive oil, fusilli penne spaghetti, mince pies, puddings, cakes, biscuits & cookies, confectionery and so on)

Merchandise portfolio analysis of HyperCITY through BCG Matrix

		Market Share	
		High	Low
Market Growth	High	Food & Grocery Health & Beauty Home & Furniture Fashion Stars	Electronics Toys Question Marks
	Low	Private Brands Cash Cows	Sports Dogs

Figure 5.1: Merchandise portfolio analysis of HyperCITY

Food & grocery, health & beauty, home & furniture and fashion merchandise lines of HyperCITY are in star position in BCG Matrix, which reflects the high market share of merchandise under these lines and high market growth denotes an increase in the sales of these merchandise lines from past years. Electronics and toy merchandise lines of HyperCITY are in question mark position in BCG Matrix that shows the low market share of merchandise under these lines and high market growth represents an increase in the sales of these merchandise lines from past years.

Private brands merchandise line of HyperCITY falls under the category of a cash cow in BCG Matrix that reveals the high market share of merchandise under this line and low market growth denotes that there is no increase in the sales of this merchandise line from past years. Sports merchandise line of HyperCITY is part of dog position in BCG Matrix, which demonstrates low market share and low market growth describes that there is a decrease in the sales of these merchandise lines from past years.

5.1.2 Merchandise offered by Star Bazaar

Star Bazaar offers merchandise under the merchandise lines like food & grocery, personal & home care, home & kitchen needs, fashion & accessories, international zone (merchandise) and star bazaar (store level) brands.

Merchandise lines of Star Bazaar

- **Food & Grocery** – Staples (pulses, cereals & flours, rice, basmati rice, spices, sugar, edible oil (sunflower oil, soybean oil, olive oil), ghee, dry fruits, flour, grains, sugar, Toor dal, Moong dal, Kabuli chana, green whole moong, chana dal, urad dal, red masoor, raw peanuts, floor lokwan, boiled rice, pohe, many more...), packaged food (biscuits & confectionery, cereals, sauces, jams, breakfast, noodles & vermicelli, soups, chips & savouries, papad & pickles, ready-to-eat preparations, pickles, ketchups, noodles, cornflakes, Indian sweet dessert, ready to mix, breakfast needs, many more...), beverages (tea & coffee, juices, aerated drinks, health drinks, cold drinks, flavoured milk, soya milk, squashes, cold coffee, coconut, many more...), dairy (milk, butter, cheese, dahi & yoghurt, shrikhand, paneer, lassi & chaas, ice cream and many more...), bakery & deli (pastry, cake, bread, toast, buns & breads, mousse, cakes, rolls, veg-mini meals, non-veg mini meals, sweets, veg pizza, pizza paneer, no-veg pizza, veg & chicken burger, chicken biryani, tandoori chicken, many more...), non-veg (meat, chicken, seafood, many more...), fruits & vegetables (fresh fruits and vegetables, imported fruits and vegetables, chopped and packed fruits and vegetables, many more...), frozen (veg snacks, non-veg snacks, green peas, paneer, srikhand, dahi, ghee, milk, cheese, creams & pet needs many more..).
- **Personal & Home Care** – Cleaning aids (detergents - powder & bars, floor cleaners, toilet cleaners, bathroom cleaners, insect repellents, room fresheners, disposable rags, mops, brushes, scrubs, pooja needs, many more...), health & beauty (bathing soap, face pack, shower gel, shampoo & conditioners, creams, lotions & scrub, hand wash, hair care products, men's grooming, sanitary needs, body wash, hair oil, razor, shaving gel & cream, moisturiser, baby care, diapers, body sprays & deodorants, many more...).
- **Home & Kitchen Needs** – Kitchenware (cookers, container sets, non-stick sets, utensils, kitchen, appliances, dinner sets, crockery, glassware, home plastics, hangers, buckets, bath mug, clip hangers, fridge bottles, lunch boxes,

microwave safe lunch boxes, knife, tea & coffee wares nonstick wares, cook & serve wares, drink wares, tray, glasses, cattle, cups, mugs, many more...), electronics (fans, bells, switches, extension board, CFL, batteries, dry & steam irons, mixer-grinders, gas burners, microwaves, vacuum cleaners, power strips, water purifiers, rice cookers, toasters, fans, small fans, table lamp, water heater, cooler, pedestal fans, table & tower fans, gas stoves, food processor, sewing machine, sandwich maker, speakers, DVD players, telephones, music system, OTG, watches, many more...), home décor (bed sheets, blankets, mats, pillow, pillow covers, bath towels, hand towels, cushion covers, curtains, dining linen, decorative plants, floating stool, floor carpet, plastic table chair, almirah, door mats, floor mats, window curtains, door curtains, artificial flowers, many more...), luggage (baby buggies & with umbrella, strollers, trolley bags, laptop bags, duffel bags, office bags, backpacks, travel bags, helmets, many more...), toys (toys for different age groups below 1 to 10+, trolley, bag trolley, remote control games, friction car, soft toys, board games, dolls, building blocks, ball, educational toys, infant toys, plastic toys, computer games, bat balls, rackets, table tennis, pads, cycle of children, football, volleyball, many more...), stationery (school needs, office needs, writing implements, creative stationery, books, magazine, computer stationery, letter pad, papers, gum, pen, pencil, sketches, pencil box, notebook, diary, stickers, boxes, calculators, box files, story books, books for small children & children, novels, bottles for students, many more...)

- **Fashion & Accessories** – Men's wear (western wear, formal wear, ethnic wear, shirts, T-shirts, fashion shirts, denim jeans, duke T-shirts, denim T-shirts, casual shirts, plain shirts, party wear, trousers, casual pants, shirts, undergarments, shorts, briefs, bath towel, track pants, checked printed shirts, short track pants (of John Player, Belmonte, Perter England brand) & many more.....), women's wear (western wear, formal wear, ethnic wear, T-shirts, printed T-shirts, kurta, stretch leggings, shorts, long sleeveless nighty, plan bra, printed woven pyjama, full pyjamas, leggings, short pyjamas, gagharas, branded kurtas, churidars, dress materials, silk printed sarees, sarees, & many more...), kid's wear (western wear, formal wear, ethnic wear, fashion T-shirts, tops, printed T-shirts, junior boys shirts, track pants, knit Capri, knit shorts, infant wears & utilities, katmos brand for kids and many more.....),

accessories (fashionable belts, bags, earrings, bracelets, wallets, handbags, lockets, hair bands, goggles, hanky, many more...), footwear (formal footwear, casual footwear, ethnic footwear, fashion footwear, women sandals, home footwear, kids footwear, fashion sandals, formal shoes, casual buddy shoes, sport shoes, casual shoes, men's sleeper, chappals, flatter for men, men's sport shocks, many more...)

- **International Zone (Merchandise)** – Brands of Tesco, blueberry, strawberry, peaches, tomato soups, pears, salsa, cookies, vegetable soups, mushrooms, tomato purees, almonds, vegetables, cashews & many more...
- **Star Bazaar (Store Level) Brands** – In the categories like food & grocery, cleaning aids, packaged food and beverages, personal care, men's wear, women wear, kid's wear, pooja needs, tea, jams, corn flakes, snacks, sugar, pulses, flour, suji, rice, pohe & many more...

Merchandise portfolio analysis of Star Bazaar through BCG Matrix

Market Share

		High	Low
Market Growth	High	Food & Grocery Fashion & Accessories Personal & Home Care	
	Low	Home & Kitchen Needs Star Bazaar Brands	International Zone (Merchandise)
		Stars	Question Marks
		Cash Cows	Dogs

Figure 5.2: Merchandise portfolio analysis of Star Bazaar

Food & grocery, fashion & accessories and personal & home care merchandise lines of Star Bazaar are in star position in BCG Matrix, which reflects the high market share of merchandise under these lines and high market growth denotes an increase in the sales of these merchandise lines from past years. No merchandise line of Star Bazaar is in question mark position in BCG Matrix.

Home & kitchen needs and Star Bazaar brands (store level brands) merchandise lines of Star Bazaar fall under the category of a cash cow in BCG Matrix that shows the high market share of merchandise under this line and low market growth denotes that there is no increase in the sales of this merchandise line from past years.

International zone (International merchandise) merchandise line of Star Bazaar is part of dog position in BCG Matrix, which demonstrates low market share and low market growth describes that there is a decrease in the sales of these merchandise lines from past years.

5.1.3 Merchandise offered by more.MEGASTore

more.MEGASTore offers merchandise under the merchandise lines like grocery, home & personal care, fruits & vegetables, general merchandise, electronic

merchandise, computers & accessories, mobile phones & accessories, apparels, footwear and sports.

Merchandise lines of more.MEGAStore

- **Grocery:** Frozen & dairy products, beverages, imported food, FMCG products, processed food, prepared food, ready to cook / prepared food, packaged & loose staples, milk, butter, curd, ghee, paneer, cheese slices, cornflakes, choco marvel, pickles, fruit drinks, jams, instant soups, honey, papads, oats, pasta, cola, premium tea, green tea, CTC tea, coffee, namkeens, ketchups, noodles, cheese balls, vermicelli, regional specialties, instant mixes, soan papdi, rice, pulses, sugar, salt, flour, refined oil, wheat, bread, spices and so on...
- **Home & Personal Care:** Home needs & home upkeep, cosmetics, toilet cleaners, phenyl, surface cleaners, scouring pads, detergents, detergent bars, dish wash bars, tissues, steel scrubber, room freshener, insect repellants, naphthalene balls, dish wash liquid, soap, facial tissue, toothbrushes, liquid hand wash, deodorants, shaving razor, baby diapers and so on...
- **Fruits & Vegetables:** Onion, cabbage, watermelon, potato, blueberry, royal gala apple, ladyfinger, broccoli, yellow pears, fresh non-vegetarian and so on
- **General Merchandise:** books, crockery, cookware, do it yourself & auto accessories, furniture, home decor products, luggage, stationery, toys and so on.
- **Electronic Merchandise:** Audio & video merchandise, information technology merchandises, large white appliances, small white appliances and so on
- **Computers & Accessories:** Laptops, Printers & Scanners, Software, Memory & Storage devices, Cables & Connectors, Chargers & Adaptors, Headphones & Headsets, Keyboards, Mouse & Mouse Pads, Webcams, CD/DVD Drives & Writers, Routers and so on
- **Mobile Phones & Accessories:** Smartphones, tablets, memory card, car charger, Bluetooth headset, corded phone, cordless phone and so on...
- **Apparels:** Men, women, infant & children's apparels i.e. western wear, formal wear, ethnic wear, shirts, T-shirts, fashion shirts, denim jeans, duke T-shirts, denim T-shirts, casual shirts, plain shirts, party wear, trousers, casual pants,

shirts, undergarments, shorts, briefs, bath towel, track pants, checked printed shirts, short track pants...

- **Footwear:** Footwear & accessories for men, women, kids and infants i.e. casual shoes, formal shoes, sandals, slippers & flip-flops, sports shoes, flats, low heels, mid heels, flip-flops, chappals, infant shoes and so on..
- **Sports:** Fitness (home gyms, weights, fitness accessories, treadmills, exercise bike and so on), sporting goods (squash, basketball, darts, boxing, volleyball, cycles, camping, carom, baseball, swimming, tennis, badminton, table tennis, cricket, kids cycles, soccer table, football, hockey and so on).

Merchandise portfolio analysis of more.MEGAstore through BCG Matrix

Market Share	
	High
	Low

Market Growth	High	Grocery Home & Personal Care Apparels	General Merchandise Mobile Phones & Accessories Computers & Accessories
	Low	Footwear Electronics Merchandise	Fruits & Vegetables Sports
		Stars	Question Marks
		Cash Cows	Dogs

Figure 5.3: Merchandise portfolio analysis of more.MEGASStore

Grocery, home & personal care and apparels merchandise lines of more.MEGASStore are in star position in BCG Matrix, which exhibits the high market share of merchandise under these lines and high market growth denotes an increase in the sales of these merchandise lines from past years. General merchandise, mobile phones & accessories and computers & accessories merchandise lines of more.MEGASStore are in question mark position in BCG Matrix that presents the low market share of merchandise under these lines and high market growth represents an increase in the sales of these merchandise lines from past years.

Footwear and electronics merchandise lines of more.MEGASStore fall under the category of a cash cow in BCG Matrix that tenders the high market share of merchandise under this line and low market growth denotes that there is no increase in the sales of this merchandise line from past years. Fruits & vegetables and sports merchandise lines of more.MEGASStore are part of dog position in BCG Matrix, which reflects low market share and low market growth describes that there is a decrease in the sales of these merchandise lines from past years.

5.1.4 Merchandise offered by Big Bazaar

Big Bazaar offers merchandise under the merchandise lines like grocery & staples bazaar, fashion bazaar, electronics bazaar, personal bazaar, kitchen & dining bazaar, bed & bath bazaar, home bazaar, mobile bazaar, furniture bazaar, toys, sports

& outdoors, gifts, office bazaar and luggage bazaar, farm fresh and books, magazines & stationary bazaar.

Merchandise lines of Big Bazaar

- **Grocery & Staples Bazaar:** Golden harvest (rice, flour, staples, carrels, cooking mediums, spices, loose grocery etc.), dry fruits, refrigerated products (milk, fruit juices, tea, coffee, cold drinks etc.), biscuits, breakfast products, carrels, canned foods, namkeen, chips & wafers, ready meals, chef's needs (chocolate, jams, salad dressing, pickles, breads, desserts, spices mixes, pastes, Chinese noodles etc.), International foods (Thai, Italian, Chinese, Mexican, Continental etc.), gourmet food (beverages, daily needs, edible oil, grains, health products, herbs & powders, instant food, spices, pickles & sauces, pulses, refreshments, snacks, etc.) and so on...
- **Farm Fresh:** Fruits & vegetables
- **Kitchen & Dining Bazaar:** Kitchen linen (aprons, coasters, napkins, sets, table, clothes etc.), cookware (bake ware, kadai, pans, pots, pressure cookers, sets, tawa, tops etc.), serve ware (beverage dispensers, casseroles, jugs, serving bowls, serving dishes, sets, tea pots, trays & platters, etc.), crockery (bowls, cups & mugs, drinkware, plates, sets, etc.), cutlery (children's cutlery, chopsticks, forks, knives, ladles, servers, sets, spoons, tongs, etc.), storage & containers (canisters, food storage, garbage bins, microwave sets, racks & holders, sets, storage bags, tiffin, vacuum flasks, water bottles & jugs, etc.), kitchen utilities (plates, bowls, glasses, baking tools, bar accessories, choppers, graters & slicers, cutters, cutting boards, more utensils & tools, openers, peelers, sieves & spinners, whisks & spatula, etc.) and so on...
- **Bed & Bath Bazaar:** Bed sheets (single bed sheets, double bed sheets), bed covers, pillows & inserts, blankets & quilts, bedding collections (bedding sets, divan sets etc.), towels (bath towels, hand towels, face towels etc.), bath accessories (holders & dispensers, shower accessories, toilet accessories, bathroom sets etc.) and so on...
- **Books, Magazines & Stationary Bazaar:** Books (children, comics, educational, fiction, non-fiction etc.), magazines (auto, b2b, business, children, current affairs, fashion, home, lifestyle, photography, technology, travel etc.),

stationary (boards & pads, key chains, notebooks & diaries, office stationery, papers, pens, tapes & adhesives, etc.) & so on...

- **Luggage Bazaar:** Airbags & duffel bags, backpacks, briefcases, cabin trolley, hiking bags, luggage sets, messenger bags, suitcases, travel accessories, trolleys & so on...
- **Home Bazaar:** Home décor (albums & photo frames, art & wall décor, artificial flowers & potpourri, candles & candle stands, clocks, collectables, decorative storage, devotional products, handicrafts, home fragrances, hukkas, lamps & shades, metal ware & antiques, sculptures & figurines, vases, wind chimes & bells, etc.), home furnishing (carpets, rugs & durries, curtains, cushion covers, cushions, doors and bath mats, etc.), auto care (bike, car audio, car exterior, car interior, cleaning, navigation etc.), tools & hardware (bath ware, cleaning, gardening, hand tools etc.), storage & organisers (baskets & containers, cloth hangers & racks, grab n go furniture, laundry organisers, racks & holders, safes & lockers, trash cans, etc.), wedding collection & wedding accessories, utilities, cleaning aids (whitening agents, fabric softness, starch, detergents bars, liquid, powders etc.), pet care & so on...
- **Personal Bazaar:** Haircare (hair colours, hair conditioners, hair gels & creams, hair oil, shampoos and so on), skin care (body lotions, creams, face wash, shower gel, skin care accessories, soaps, sunscreens etc.), oral care (toothbrush, toothpaste, tongue cleaner, mouth fresheners etc.), medicare products, saving needs, deodorants, perfumes, beauty and wellness for women- eye care, hair care, lip care, makeup, nail care, perfumes, skin care, spa products & so on...
- **Furniture Bazaar:** Stools, accessories, corner sofa w/d cushion, night stand, wardrobes, sofa beds, dining sets, TV units, sofa sets, bean bags, dresser, recliner, kids bunk beds, beds, corner sofas etc.
- **Electronics Bazaar:** Appliances - geysers & heaters, air conditioners (split ACs, window ACs), fans & air coolers, irons (dry iron, steam irons), vacuum & floor care (steam & carpet cleaners, vacuum cleaners), washing & drying (dryers, washing machine), lighting & power, personal grooming (epilators, hair curlers, hair dryers, hair straighteners, hair stylers, massagers, shavers, skin care, trimmers, etc.), kitchen appliances (blenders, coffee makers, electric cookers, electric kettle, food processors, juicer, mixer, grinder, microwave &

oven, pop-up toasters, refrigerators, roti makers, sandwich makers, water purifiers etc.), stoves (chimneys, cooktops, gas stoves), sewing machines, insect killers; entertainment - TV & entertainment (audio video accessories, home audio, home theatre, LCD & LED, media players, sound machine, DJ consoles, DJ control, microphone, 3D glasses, etc.), cameras (camcorders, camera accessories, camera bags & cases, digital cameras, DSLR cameras, flashes, lens accessories, lenses, tripods & monopods, etc.), i-pods & music players, MP3/MP4 players, gaming (games, gaming accessories, gaming consoles, etc.) & so on...

- **Office Bazaar:** Laptops & tablets (computer accessories, desktops, laptop accessories, laptops, tablet accessories, tablets), memory & storage (hard drives, memory cards, and USB flash drives etc.), IT hardware (routers), printers & cartridges, scanners & copiers, software and so on...
- **Mobile Bazaar:** Mobiles, telephones, batteries & chargers, Bluetooth, covers & cases, headsets, mobile accessories and so on...
- **Toys, Sports & Outdoors:** Battery operated toys, blocks, puzzles & learning, board games, CDs & DVDs, dolls & accessories, fun games & toys, guns & action figures, musical, play sets, ride-on, push & pulls, soft toys, sports, vehicles, gear, gym, health care, sports, supplements, digital blood pressure monitor, ladies umbrella, soccer, yoga mat, cricket set, kids umbrella, auto glucose monitor, glucose monitoring system, tennis racket, titanium ball, mega gains, skateboard, rubber roller skates, inflatable ball and so on...
- **Fashion Bazaar: Apparel & Accessories Men's** - Ethnic wear, innerwear, jeans, shirts, shorts, swimwear, sportswear, sweatshirts, T-shirts, trousers, denim, casuals, formals, accessories (bags, belts, caps, cufflinks, gift sets, handkerchiefs, socks, sunglasses, ties, wallets, men's fashion watches & sunglasses, men's luxury watches, men's sports watches & sunglasses), **Footwear:** casual shoes, formal shoes, sandals, slippers & flip-flops, sports shoes, **Apparel & Accessories Women's** - Dresses, ethnic wear, jeans, lingerie, salwar kameez, sarees, shorts, sleepwear, sportswear, swimwear, T-shirts & tops, trousers, night wears, fit & healthy wear, casual wear, fashion wear, accessories (scarf & stoles, socks & hosiery, women's fashion watches & sunglasses, women's luxury watches, handbags (clutches, handbags, hobos, sling bags, totes, wallets & pouches), jewelry (anklets, bangles,

bracelets, combo sets, earrings, necklaces, nose pins, pendants, rings, sets, jewelry cleaners), **Footwear:** Women's - flats, low heels, mid-heels, sandals, slippers & flip-flops, sports shoes, chappals, **Apparel & Accessories Kids** – girls & boys jeans, shorts, skirts, T-shirts, tops, trousers, accessories (sunglass, women's sunglasses, kids watch), **Footwear:** sandal, slipper, shoes, chappals, **Apparel Baby** – infant clothing, **Footwear Baby** – infant shoes and so on...

- **Gifts:** Cakes & chocolates, gift vouchers, gift sets, valentine's day, Diwali, charity, flowers, greeting cards, seasonal gifts, sweets & dry fruits

Merchandise portfolio analysis of Big Bazaar through BCG Matrix

Market Share		
	High	Low

Market Growth	High	Grocery & Staples Bazaar Fashion Bazaar Electronics Bazaar Personal Bazaar Kitchen & Dining Bazaar	Bed & Bath Bazaar Home Bazaar Mobile Bazaar Furniture Bazaar
		Stars	Question Marks
	Low	Toys, Sports & Outdoors Gifts Office Bazaar Luggage Bazaar	Farm Fresh Books, Magazines & Stationery Bazaar
		Cash Cows	Dogs

Figure 5.4: Merchandise portfolio analysis of Big Bazaar

Grocery & staples bazaar, fashion bazaar, electronics bazaar, personal bazaar and kitchen & dining bazaar merchandise lines of Big Bazaar are in star position in BCG Matrix, which reflects the high market share of merchandise under these lines and high market growth denotes an increase in the sales of these merchandise lines from past years.

Bed & bath bazaar, home bazaar, mobile bazaar and furniture bazaar merchandise lines of Big Bazaar are in question mark position in BCG Matrix that presents the low market share of merchandise under these lines and high market growth represents an increase in the sales of these merchandise lines from past years.

Toys, sports & outdoors, gifts, office bazaar and luggage bazaar merchandise lines of Big Bazaar fall under the category of a cash cow in BCG Matrix that shows

the high market share of merchandise under this line and low market growth denotes that there is no increase in the sales of this merchandise line from past years.

Farm fresh and books, magazines & stationery bazaar merchandise lines of Big Bazaar are part of dog position in BCG Matrix, which reflects low market share and low market growth describes that there is a decrease in the sales of these merchandise lines from past years.

5.1.5 Merchandise offered by DTMMart

DTMMart offers merchandise under the merchandise lines like foods, garments, toiletries & beauty merchandise, kitchenware, home appliances, bags & trolleys, footwear, bed & bath linen, frozen, toys & games and stationery.

Merchandise lines of D[▲]Mart

- **Foods-** Ready to cook & eat, noodles, pickles, jams, ketchups, papad, fryams, ghee, sweets, farshan, health drinks, baby foods, grocery items, masala, breakfast items, dry fruits, chocolates, loose grocery, tea, coffee, biscuits, fruits, bakery, vegetables, insecticides and many more
- **Frozen-** Milk, curd, whey, lassi, paneer, cream, cheese, butter, amrakhand, srikahnd, ice creams, pee, ready to eat and much more
- **Toiletries & Beauty Merchandises-** Sanitary, talc, deo, cosmetics, dental care, tissues, hair care, fem care, detergents, hand washers, bath soaps, OTC, household cleanings, accessories, jewellery, bangles and many more
- **Garments-**
 - **Men's-** Shirt, casual shirts, T-shirts, kurta, jacket, trousers, jeans, ties, belts, shorts, boxer shorts, hanky, cargos, pajamas, undergarments, dress materials, sweaters, windcheaters, track-pants, caps, hand gloves, accessories and many more
 - **Ladies-** Kurta, kaftan, house coat, nighty, leggings, salwar, hanky, dress materials, frocks, tops, jeans, skirts, inner wears, jackets, sweaters, sarees, windcheaters, stole, ribbons, shorts, dupattas, accessories and many more
 - **Boys-** Shirts, T-shirts, jeans, cargos, denim, jacket, dhoti-kurta, caps, sweaters, accessories and many more
 - **Girls-** Tops, frocks, jackets, sweaters, ribbons, shorts, jeans, denim, salwar-kurtas, ghagra-choli, leggings, skirts, inner wears, accessories and many more
 - **New Born Baby Garments-** Infant wears, diapers, accessories and many more
- **Bed & Bath Linen-** Hand towels, bath towels, kitchen towels, bedsheets, pillows, cushions & covers, curtains, blankets, matrices, door mats, dusters, mops & cleaners, brushes & scrubbers, dustbins, tubs & buckets, accessories and many more
- **Footwear-**

- **Men's-** Formal shoes, sports shoes, sandals, slippers, socks, casual footwear, accessories and many more
- **Ladies-** Shoes, slippers, sandals, socks, accessories and many more
- **Kids-** Sports shoes, slippers, sandals, socks, accessories
- **Kitchenware-** Induction cooktop, cookware, steel, non-sticks, pans & tawas, kadais, pressure cookers, gas stoves & lighters, kitchen utilities, containers, microwave safeware, Tiffin, crockery, plates & bowls, cutlery, dinner sets, accessories
- **Home Appliances-** Iron, fans (ceiling and table), food processors, music system, rice cookers, torch, bells, water purifiers, toasters, juicer mixer & grinders, sandwich makers, plastic chairs, accessories
- **Bags & Trolleys-** Shopping bags, college bags, laptop bags, office bags, air bags, trolleys, suitcases accessories
- **Stationery-** Books, novels, notebooks, pen, pencils, papers, pen stands, punch machine, staplers, pen drives, CD & DVDs, accessories
- **Toys & Games-** Soft toys, plastic toys, wood toys, mind games

Merchandise portfolio analysis of D⁺Mart through BCG Matrix

Market Share

		High	Low
Market Growth	High	Foods Garments Toiletries & Beauty Merchandise Kitchenware Stars	Home Appliances Bags & Trolleys Question Marks
	Low	Footwear Bed & Bath Linen Cash Cows	Frozen Toys & Games Stationery Dogs

Figure 5.5: Merchandise portfolio analysis of D Mart

Foods, garments, toiletries & beauty merchandise and kitchenware merchandise lines of D Mart are in star position in BCG Matrix, which reflects the high market share of merchandise under these lines and high market growth denotes an increase in the sales of these merchandise lines from past years. Home appliances and bags & trolleys merchandise lines of D Mart are in question mark position in BCG Matrix that shows the low market share of merchandise under these lines and high market growth represents an increase in the sales of these merchandise lines from past years.

Footwear and bed & bath linen merchandise lines of D Mart fall under the category of a cash cow in BCG Matrix that presents the high market share of merchandise under this line and low market growth denotes that there is no increase in the sales of this merchandise line from past years. Frozen, toys & games and stationery merchandise lines of D Mart are part of dog position in BCG Matrix, which reflects low market share and low market growth describes that there is a decrease in the sales of these merchandise lines from past years.

5.1.6 Merchandise offered by Big Megamart

Big Megamart offers merchandise under the merchandise lines like youth wear, women's wear, men's wear, kid's wear, home mart, travel mart, footwear, fashion mart and toys.

Merchandise lines of Big Megamart

- **Women's Wear** – Ethnic wear (brands- Karigari, W, Nayans, Sushilas, Aurelia, Huur, Neerus, Zariwala, Estyle, Charms by Prafful, Leisha), western wear (brands- Cherokee, Allen Solly, Scullers, Auburn Hill, Expozay, Tantra, Miss Players, Global Trendz), lingerie (brands- Amante, Lovable, City Girl, Juliet)
- **Men's Wear** - Formal wear (brands- Louis Philippe, Ruggers, Van Heusen, Peter England, Excalibur Elitus, Auburn Hill, Pan America, Park Avenue, Celebrity, Options, Wills Lifestyle), casual wear (brands- Cherokee, US Polo, Scullers, Fahrenheit, Indigo Nation, Allen Solly, Parx, Enryca, V., Colour Plus, Classic Polo, Lerros, Giordano, Dockers, Kmark, Tantra, Prostyle, Allen Solly Youth), ethnic wear (brands- Manu, Karigari, Yash), suits & blazers (brands- Parx, Auburn Hill, Excalibur, Elitus, Belmonte, Shapes, Thomas Scott, Wills Lifestyle, John Players, Notting Hill), innerwear (brands- VIP, Hanes, Skinn, Euro)
- **Youth Wear** – Denims (brands- Colt, Pepe, Newport, Wrangler, Lee, Levis, Lemax, Cherokee, Signature, Spykar, Jealous 21, Flying Machine), casual wear (brands- Ruggers, Dockers, Kappa, Indian Terrain, Colt, Spykar, Flying Machine, Lee, Wrangler, Levis, V., Stori, Bossini, MTV, Bay Island, Cherokee, UCB, Basics, Tantra, Crocodile, Classic Polo, Greg Norman), sportswear (brands- Edge, Reebok, Nike),
- **Kid's Wear** - Apparel wears (brands- Gini & Jony, Drop, Seals, Globe, Disney Kids, Isabelle, Karigari, Myfaa, UCB Kids),
- **Toys** - (Brands - Mera Toys)
- **Footwear** – (brands- Bata, Adidas, Fila, Action and exclusive international brands)
 - **Men's-** Formal shoes, sports shoes, Sandals, Slippers, socks, Casual Footwear, accessories and so on
 - **Ladies-** Shoes, Slippers, Sandals, shocks, accessories and so on

- **Kids-** Sports shoes, formal, school, Sandals, socks, accessories and so on
- **Fashion Mart** – Fashion mart offers a complete range of fashion accessories like jewellery, stoles and scarves, handbags & clutches, belts, fragrances, wallets, sunglasses, watches, cosmetics and beauty care products. watches (brands - Fastrack, Sonata, Titan, Casio, Citizen, Tommy Hilfiger), sunglasses (brands - Fastrack I Gear, Sorrento, Spykar, Sprint, Scott), jewellery (brands - Zaveri Pearls, Mystic, Adrika), fragrances & deos (brands - Reebok Deos, Udv, Deo Mania Deos, Ferrari, Mango, Antonio Banderas, Bogart, Nautica, Chevignon, Formula 1, Stone Deos, Tommy Hilfiger, Fcuk, Evaflor, Slazenger, Yacht Man, So, Jaques M, Aqua Brava, David Beckham, Xaver Laurent), cosmetics (brands - Lakme, Revlon, Chambor, Diana of London, Ponds)
- **Home Mart** - Living & dining (complete range of kitchenware like crockery, mugs, non-stick cookware, storage containers, curtains and a complete range in kitchen linen (brands - Nirlep, Prestige), bed & bath (bed sheets, comforters, pillow fillers, cushion fillers, towels etc.) (brands - Welhome, Portico, Cherokee, Home Mart, Impulse, Diviniti, Trance, Portico, All Time, Laopala, Crystal)
- **Travel Mart** – Wide range of travel gear like suitcases, backpacks, duffle bags, strollers and attractive range of travel accessories like locks, key chains, laptop bags etc., luggage (brands - American Tourister, F Gear, Cherokee, Ruggers Gear)

Merchandise portfolio analysis of Big Megamart through BCG Matrix

		Market Share	
		High	Low
Market Growth	High	Youth Wear Women's Wear Men's Wear Kid's Wear Stars	Home Mart Travel Mart Question Marks
	Low	Footwear Fashion Mart Cash Cows	Toys Dogs

Figure 5.6: Merchandise portfolio analysis of Big Megamart

Youth wear, women's wear, men's wear and kid's wear merchandise lines of Big Megamart are in star position in BCG Matrix, which reflects the high market share of merchandise under these lines and high market growth denotes an increase in the sales of these merchandise lines from past years. Home mart and travel mart merchandise lines of Big Megamart are in question mark position in BCG Matrix that shows the low market share of merchandise under these lines and high market growth represents an increase in the sales of these merchandise lines from past years.

Footwear and fashion mart merchandise lines of Big Megamart fall under the category of a cash cow in BCG Matrix that presents the high market share of merchandise under this line and low market growth denotes that there is no increase in the sales of this merchandise line from past years. Toys merchandise line of Big Megamart is part of dog position in BCG Matrix, which proposes low market share and low market growth describes that there is a decrease in the sales of these merchandise lines from past years.

5.1.7 Merchandise offered by West Side

West Side offers merchandise under the merchandise lines like women's wear, youth wear, men's wear, cosmetics & fragrances, kid's wear, home & gift, accessories and footwear and luggage.

Merchandise lines of West Side

- **Men's Wear-** Casual, formal, sports like colour jeans, sweaters, jackets, checks shirts, stripes shirts, dots shirts, textures or plain shirts, Chinese collar shirts, crafted shirts and trousers, checked shirts, woollens, mufflers, ascot sport, graphic printed tees, sports casual, chest printed T-shirts, classic jeans, Nuon denim, undergarments & briefs, suits, T-shirts, kurta, jacket, trousers, jeans, shorts, boxer shorts, cargos, pajamas, wind cheaters, track-pants, & many more
- **Women's Wear-** Indian, western, casual like salwar kamej, blouses, formal shirts, coloured jeans, regular jeans, slim fit jeans, dhoti pants, chudidhar, hand-woven fabrics, dupattas, coloured chinos, snazzy jackets, gowns, scarf, jeggings, leggings or tregging, sweaters, printed tops, tunics, jumpsuits & bottoms, denim, plus size dress, vest, lingerie, kaftan, house coat, nightys, dress materials, frocks, tops, wind cheaters, stole & many more
- **Youth Wear -** Men's & women's like shirts, T-shirts, jeans, cargos, denim, jacket, dhoti-kurta, caps, sweaters, tops, frocks, jackets, sweaters, ribbons, shorts, jeans, denim, salwar-kurtas, ghagra-choli, leggings, skirts, inner wears, & many more
- **Kid's Wear-** For infant (0-2 yrs), junior (2-6 yrs), senior (7-14 yrs) like coloured denim, kids ethnic wear collection, salwar, kurta and leggings, kurta pyjama, & many more
- **Accessories-** Ties, napkins, belts, handbags, jewellery, sunglasses, bracelet, wallet, chic and fun bags, caps, hand globs, ribbons, stole, shocks & many more
- **Footwear-** Men's footwear, shoes, boots, flip-flop, Nuon footwear, Lilliput brand footwear for kids, kids footwear (India Size: 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13; International Size: 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36), women's footwear (India Size: 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10; International Size: 36, 37, 38, 39, 40, 41) & formal shoes, sport shoes, sandals, slippers, casual footwear, slippers, many more

- **Cosmetics & Fragrances-** Deo, perfumes, international brands in cosmetics, bath and body products, lotions, creams body washes and balms, & many more
- **Home & Gift-** Kitchenware, household, linen, towels (hand, face, bath), bed covers, bed sheets, bottles & bowls, play shop (toys, dolls, soft toys & so on), mugs, chic & sophisticated home décor), Turkish range of home (collection lamps, candle stands, bed sheets and cushion), table linens, artefacts, home accessories and furnishings, many more
- **Luggage-** Trolley, school bags, office bags, travel bags, briefcases

Merchandise portfolio analysis of West Side through BCG Matrix

		Market Share	
		High	Low
Market Growth	High	Women's Wear Youth Wear Men's Wear Cosmetics & Fragrances Kid's Wear Stars	Home & Gift Question Marks
	Low	Accessories Footwear Cash Cows	Luggage Dogs

Figure 5.7: Merchandise portfolio analysis of West Side

Women's wear, youth wear, men's wear, cosmetics & fragrances and kid's wear merchandise lines of West Side are in star position in BCG Matrix, which reflects the high market share of merchandise under these lines and high market growth denotes an increase in the sales of these merchandise lines from past years. Home & gift merchandise line of West Side is in question mark position in BCG Matrix that shows the low market share of merchandise under these lines and high market growth represents an increase in the sales of these merchandise lines from past years.

Accessories and footwear merchandise lines of West Side fall under the category of a cash cow in BCG Matrix that proposes the high market share of merchandise under this line and low market growth denotes that there is no increase in the sales of this merchandise line from past years. Luggage merchandise line of West Side is part of dog position in BCG Matrix, which tables low market share and low market growth describes that there is a decrease in the sales of these merchandise lines from past years.

5.1.8 Merchandise offered by Max

Max offers merchandise under the merchandise lines like ladies' wear, men's wear, children's wear, footwear and accessories.

Merchandise lines of Max

- **Children's Wear:** Infant wears, 2-8 years old girls & boys wear, 8-14 years old girls & boys wear like, prints jersey, badges jersey, embroidery jersey, mock jersey, T-shirts, hoodies and jackets, knit gloves, knit top, denim bottom, ballerina, denim, girl's top, boys T-shirts, infant tops, shirts, capris, woven top, woven bottom, polo tee, fashion denim & so on...
- **Ladies' Wear:** Ethnic & fusion wear, western wear, young wear, active wear, sleepwear, lingerie like ethnic fusion outfits, jumpsuits, checked shirt, animal prints dress, pyjamas, denims & coloured bottoms, bird prints dresses, woolen jacket, skirt & shirt, shorts, tees, sheer shirt, skinny jeans, dupattas, kurta and Patiala salwar, blazer, graphic tees, semi-formal, rainbow-hued pants, shorts and capris, girl skirts, tennis dresses and jumpers, sheer blouse, lace skirt, chiffon dress, leggings, classic churidars, salwar kameez dupatta, sweater, knit pullovers, v-neck sweater, woolen trousers, embellished blouse, kalidar kurta, tops, cocktail dresses, prom dresses, formal, casual and fusion party wear, candy striped tee, tropical striped jumpsuits, top with lace, dress with belt, loose top with cutwork, knit top, ballerina, woven top, knit bottom, denim bottom, fashion jeans, sweaters, knit pyjama, printed bottom, woven bottom, pencil fit jeans, knit capris, jackets, medium kurta, fashion top, knit chudidar, printed tee, pite polo, chest print tee, rugby polo tee, chudidar kurta, woven jacket, short kurta, & so on...
- **Men's Wear:** Formalwear, semi-formal wear, casual wear, denim, active & sportswear, innerwear, ethnic like shorts and capris, solids and checks shirts, casual shirts range, stripes and patterns shirts, cotton and linens shirts, short sleeve check shirt and solid colour T-shirt, jeans, casual cotton shirts, coats, T-shirt, kappa track pants, T-shirts, denim, shorts, semi-formal trousers, woven bottom, formal trousers, woven top, jackets, track pants, boxer shorts, top knitted track, bottom-shorts, men's woven shorts, kappa track pants, short track pants, woven shorts, knit top, Capri for home, casual knit top, casual bottom, chest print tee, ringer tee, short tee & so on...

- **Footwear:** Men, women, children like infant shoes, kids shoes (in different size 1 to 13 no.), ankle boot, casual shoe, leather slipper, formal slip-on, sports shoes, women - killer heels, shoes, wedges with bow, stilettos, wedges, pumps, ballerina, moccasins, jello shoe, haute wedge heels, catwalk leather wedges, children - casual shoe, girl sleeper, kids ballerina shoes, and so on...
- **Accessories:** Eye-wear girls, neckpiece, bangles, jewelry, bracelets, brooches, nail paints, elephant bangle, handbags (tote bag, tote bag, shoulder bag, laser cut bag, 2 in 1 bag, satchel bag, studded pink bag, leather bag, sling bag, floral printed bag, floral sling bag, tribal printed tote, clutch bags), sunglasses, watches, pens, ring, earring, flowers, umbrellas/boots/raincoats, nail stones, fragrances, colour cosmetics, skin care, scarf, mufflers and scarves, school & stationary, toys of boys & girls, travel items, wallets, belts and accessories, crafted in exclusive, luxurious synthetic leather, ties, metal earrings, metal & stone necklace, roselle, cleo, pencil box, lunch box, water bottle, trolley bags, soft toys, school bags, belt for kids, ladies & gents socks, hair bands & clips, handkerchiefs and so on...

Merchandise portfolio analysis of Max through BCG Matrix

		Market Share	
		High	Low
Market Growth	High	Ladies' Wear Men's Wear Stars	Children's Wear Footwear Question Marks
	Low	Accessories Cash Cows	Dogs

Figure 5.8: Merchandise portfolio analysis of Max

Ladies' wear and men's wear merchandise lines of Max are in star position in BCG Matrix, which reflects the high market share of merchandise under these lines and high market growth denotes an increase in the sales of these merchandise lines from past years.

Children's wear and footwear merchandise lines of Max are in question mark position in BCG Matrix that tables the low market share of merchandise under these lines and high market growth represents an increase in the sales of these merchandise lines from past years.

Accessories merchandise line of Max falls under the category of a cash cow in BCG Matrix that shows the high market share of merchandise under this line and low market growth denotes that there is no increase in the sales of this merchandise line from past years.

No merchandise line of Max is part of dog position in BCG Matrix.

5.1.9 Merchandise offered by Reliance Digital

Reliance Digital offers merchandise under the merchandise lines like TVs & audio, kitchen appliances, home appliances, mobile phones, computers, accessories, cameras and gaming.

Merchandise lines of Reliance Digital

- **Mobile Phones:** Smartphones [life style & value (brands- Apple, BlackBerry, HTC, Huawei, LG, Nokia, Reconnect, Samsung, Sony, ViewSonic, Karbonn)], feature phones (brands- Nokia, Reconnect, Samsung, Sony), mobile accessories [chargers & adapters, screen guards & protectors, cases & pouches, memory cards (Brands- Targus, Apple, Belkin, Samsung, SanDisk, Sony, Transcend, Capdase, Molife)].
- **Computers:** Tablets (brand- Milagrow, Acer, Apple, I-ball, Reconnect, Reliance, Samsung, Sony, Micromax, Amazon, Karbonn, HCL), laptops (brands- Acer, HP, Samsung, Sony, Dell, Lenovo), desktops (brand- Reconnect), printers & scanners (brands- Epson, Canon, HP), Monitors (Brands- BenQ, Others), software (others, Trend micro, Apple, Microsoft, Norton, McAfee), memory & storage (brands- SanDisk, Transcend), hard drives (brands- Others, Seagate, Western Digital), computer accessories [cables & connectors, chargers & adapters, headphones & headsets, keyboards, mouse & mouse pads, webcams, CD/DVD drives & writers, routers (brands- D-Link, Targus, Apple, Belkin, B-Speech, Bose, HP, I-ball, Jabra, JBL, Logitech, Nokia, Panasonic, Philips, Plantronics, Reconnect, Samsung, Sennheiser, Sony, Transcend, Microsoft, Bandridge, Mitashi, ENON, Capdase, Beats by Dr. Dre).
- **TVs & Audio:** Televisions [LCD, LED, plasma, smart, flat (Brands- Onida, Sansui, LG, Panasonic, Philips, Reconnect, Samsung, Sony, Sharp)], Blu-ray & DVD players (brand- Pioneer, LG, Panasonic, Philips, Reconnect, Samsung, Sony, Mitashi), home theatres (brand- Pioneer, LG, Onkyo, Panasonic, Philips, Reconnect, Samsung, Sony, Mitashi, DENON), HiFi systems (brand- Philips, Sony), av receivers (brands- YAMAHA, DENON, HARMAN KARDON), specialty speakers (brand- JAMO), portable audio-video players (brand- Philips, Sony), MP3 players (brands- Apple, Philips, Sony, Transcend), specialty audio.

- **Cameras:** Digital cameras [point & shoot, prosumer, mirrorless (brands- Canon, Reconnect, Samsung, Sony, Nikon, Olympus, FUJIFILM), DSLR cameras (brand- Canon, Sony, Nikon), camcorders (brand- Sony), digital camera accessories [batteries & chargers, bags, cases & pouches, cables & cords, digital photo frames, memory cards, tripods & monopods (brands- Belkin, Reconnect, SanDisk, Sony, Transcend, Benro, Slik, Bandridge, Lowepro, Capdase)]
- **Home Appliances:** Air conditioners (split, window, wall mounted) & coolers (brands- Hitachi, LG, Panasonic, Reconnect, Voltas), washing machines (brands- Godrej, LG, Panasonic, Reconnect, Samsung, BOSCH, IFB, Whirlpool, Siemens), fans (brand- Crompton Greaves, Usha, Havells), vacuum cleaners (brands- Eureka Forbes, Panasonic), irons (brand- Panasonic, Philips, Reconnect, Usha, Morphy Richards, Havells), geysers & heaters (brand- A. O. Smith, Crompton Greaves, Reconnect), personal care, satellite receivers, DTH
- **Kitchen Appliances:** Refrigerators (brand- Godrej, Hitachi, LG, Panasonic, Reconnect, Samsung, Whirlpool), microwave ovens (brand- Onida, LG, Panasonic, Reconnect, Samsung, IFB), juicers (brand- Philips, Reconnect, Usha, Morphy Richards, Havells), juicer mixer grinder (brand- Panasonic, Philips, Reconnect, Bajaj, Usha, Maharaja Whiteline, Morphy Richards, Preethi, Wonderchef, Havells, Inalsa), food processors (brand- Philips, Bajaj, Inalsa, Kenstar, Kenwood, Usha, Inalsa), blenders (brand- Philips, Reconnect, Kenstar, Kenwood, Morphy Richards, Braun, Havells, Inalsa), OTGs (Brands- Reconnect, Usha, Morphy Richards), rice cookers (brand- Panasonic, Reconnect), induction cookers (brand- Philips, Reconnect), sandwich makers (brand- Reconnect, Havells, Morphy Richards), toasters (brand- Reconnect, Usha, Havells), electric kettles (brand- Havells, Morphy Richards), water purifiers / dispensers (brand- Eureka Forbes, HUL, Kent), dishwashers.
- **Gaming:** Gaming consoles (brand- Sony, Microsoft), gaming titles (game franchise- Angry Birds, Assassins Creed, Call of Duty, HALO, Hitman, Medal of Honor, Need for Speed, WWE; Gaming Platform- PC, PS3, XBOX 360), gaming mouse & mouse pads (brand- Reconnect, mouse type - gaming optical tracking)

- **Accessories:** Memory & storage (memory cards, micro SD, SD cards, pen drives, hard drives, memory card readers), headsets, multimedia speakers, screen guards & protectors, cables & connectors, computer accessories (mouse & mouse pads, webcams, keyboards, CD /DVD drives & writers, printers, memory cards, peripherals, networking devices), chargers & adapters, batteries, software bags, cases & pouches hubs & routers, power & protection, power units (UPS, surge protectors, stabilisers, camera accessories (digital photo frames, tripods & monopods), gaming accessories (gaming mouse & mouse pad), mobile accessories (mobile chargers & adapters, mobile cases & pouches, memory cards)

Merchandise portfolio analysis of Reliance Digital through BCG Matrix

		Market Share	
		High	Low
Market Growth	High	TVs & Audio Kitchen Appliances Home Appliances	Mobile Phones Computers
	Low	Accessories Cameras	Gaming
		Stars	Question Marks
		Cash Cows	Dogs

Figure 5.9: Merchandise portfolio analysis of Reliance Digital

TVs & audio, kitchen appliances and home appliance merchandise lines of Reliance Digital are in star position in BCG Matrix, which reflects the high market share of merchandise under these lines and high market growth denotes an increase in the sales of these merchandise lines from past years.

Mobile phones and computer merchandise lines of Reliance Digital are in question mark position in BCG Matrix that shows the low market share of merchandise under these lines and high market growth represents an increase in the sales of these merchandise lines from past years.

Accessories and cameras merchandise lines of Reliance Digital fall under the category of a cash cow in BCG Matrix that puts the high market share of merchandise under this line and low market growth denotes that there is no increase in the sales of this merchandise line from past years.

Gaming merchandise line of Reliance Digital is part of dog position in BCG Matrix, which sets low market share and low market growth describes that there is a decrease in the sales of these merchandise lines from past years.

5.1.10 merchandise offered by NEXT

NEXT offers merchandise under the merchandise lines like home entertainment, home appliances, phones & accessories, computers & tablets, personal care, cameras & camcorders, games & consoles, fragrances and writing instruments .

Merchandise lines of NEXT

- **Home Entertainment:** Televisions [LCD, LED, plasma, DDB, (brands- Akai, Hyundai, LG, Onida, Panasonic, Philips, Samsung, Sansui, Sony, Videocon)], home cinema systems [home theatre systems, speakers (brands- Akai, Genius, LG, Philips, Sony)], video players [DVD players, Blu-ray players, (brands- LG, Philips, Sony), MP3/MP4 players & ipods (brands- Apple, Creative, Philips, Sony, Transcend), D2H (DishTV, Videocon)]
- **Home Appliances:** Air conditioners [split, window, (brand- Electrolux, Godrej, Onida, Samsung, Videocon, Voltas, Whirlpool)], refrigerator [direct cool, frost free, side by side (brands- Electrolux, Godrej, Kelvinator, LG, Samsung, Sansui, Videocon, Whirlpool)], washing machines [fully automatic, semi-automatic (brands- Electrolux, Godrej, IFB, Kelvinator, LG, Onida, Samsung, Videocon, Whirlpool)], microwaves & OTG (brands- Electrolux, Godrej, IFB, Kenstar, LG, Morphy Richards, RussellHobbs, Samsung, Videocon, Whirlpool), small home appliances [iron, toaster, rice cooker, coffee maker, tea maker, induction cooker, sandwich maker, water heaters, electric kettles, juicer mixer grinders, water purifiers, vacuum cleaners, hand blenders, food processor, room heater (brands- AOSmith, Bajaj, Black & Decker, Eureka, Eurolex - Usha Shriram, HUL Pureit, Inalsa, Kenstar, Kent, Maharaja, Morphy Richards, Nasaka, Panasonic, Philips, Prestige, Racold, RussellHobbs, Whirlpool)],
- **Phones & Accessories:** Smartphones [android phones, Blackberry, I-phones, Symbian phones, windows phones (brands- Apple, Blackberry, HTC, Huawei, iBall, Karbonn, Lava, Lenovo, LG, Micromax, Nokia, Samsung, Sansui, Sony, Videocon)], value phones (brands- Huawei, iBall, Karbonn, Lava, Micromax, Nokia, Salora, Samsung, Sansui, Swissvoice, Videocon), tablets (brands- Apple, HCL, iBall, Karbonn, Micromax, Milagrow, Samsung, Videocon), mobile accessories [memory card, car charger, Bluetooth headset, (brands- Callmate, Jabra, Nokia, Sony, Transcend)], landline phones [corded phone, cordless phone, (brands- Panasonic, SPCTelecom, Swissvoice)].

- **Cameras & Camcorders:** Point & shoot (brands- Canon, Fujifilm, Nikon, Olympus, Panasonic, Samsung, Sony), DSLR (brands- Canon, Nikon, Sony), mirrorless cameras (brands- Fujifilm, Nikon, Olympus), camcorder (brands- Panasonic, Sony).
- **Games & Consoles:** Games [platform- DS, PC, PS Vita, PS2, PS3, PSP, Wii, Xbox (genre- action, fighting, others, puzzle, racing, shooter, sports)], gaming consoles (brands- HCL, Microsoft, Nintendo, Sony, Zapak)
- **Computers & Tablets:** Laptops (brand- Sony), tablets (brands- Apple, HCL, iBall, Karbonn, Micromax, Milagrow, Samsung, Videocon), computer accessories [handheld scanner, pen drive, surge protector, HDMI cable, mouse, (brands- Avision, Belkin, Moserbaer, Quantum, Transcend)]
- **Personal Care:** Hair dryer, hair styler, shaver, hair straightener, epilator, trimmer, grooming kit, hair dryer, hair styler (brands- Andis, Braun, Corioliss, Inalsa, Panasonic, Philips, Remington, Trisa, Wahl)
- **Writing Instruments:** Fountain pens (brands- Cross, Lamy, Parker, Sheaffer, Waterman), Ball Pens (Brands- Cross, Lamy, Parker, Sheaffer, Waterman), roller ball pens (brands- Cross, Lamy, Parker, Sheaffer, Waterman), multi-system pens (brand- Lamy), mechanical pencils (brand- Lamy), gift sets (brands- Parker, Sheaffer)
- **Fragrances:** Fragrances, valentine special

Merchandise portfolio analysis of NEXT through BCG Matrix

		Market Share	
		High	Low
Market Growth	High	Home Entertainment Home Appliances Phones & Accessories	Computers & Tablets Personal Care
		Stars	Question Marks
	Low	Cameras & Camcorders Games & Consoles	Fragrances Writing Instruments
		Cash Cows	Dogs

Figure 5.10: Merchandise portfolio analysis of NEXT

Home entertainment, home appliances and phones & accessory merchandise lines of NEXT are in star position in BCG Matrix, which reflects the high market share of merchandise under these lines and high market growth denotes an increase in the sales of these merchandise lines from past years.

Computers & tablets and personal care merchandise lines of NEXT are in question mark position in BCG Matrix that shows the low market share of merchandise under these lines and high market growth represents an increase in the sales of these merchandise lines from past years.

Cameras & camcorders and games & consoles merchandise lines of NEXT fall under the category of a cash cow in BCG Matrix that sets the high market share of merchandise under this line and low market growth denotes that there is no increase in the sales of this merchandise line from past years.

Fragrances and writing instrument merchandise lines of NEXT are part of dog position in BCG Matrix, which reflects low market share and low market growth describes that there is a decrease in the sales of these merchandise lines from past years.

CUSTOMER SERVICES INTRODUCED BY ORGANISED RETAIL INDUSTRY

This sub-section encompasses the data pertained to the various customer services introduced by organised retail industry, which have been collected through secondary data sources and personal interaction with responsible personnel of the respective organised retail store. Services introduced by organised retailers (included in the study) have been flaunted as follows:

Services introduced by multi-format (item) organised retailers

- 5.2.1 Services introduced by HyperCITY
- 5.2.2 Services introduced by Star Bazaar
- 5.2.3 Services introduced by more.MEGASStore
- 5.2.4 Services introduced by Big Bazaar
- 5.2.5 Services introduced by D▲Mart

Services introduced by fashion item organised retailers

- 5.2.6 Services introduced by Big Megamart
- 5.2.7 Services introduced by **W**est Side
- 5.2.8 Services introduced by Max

Services introduced by electronics item organised retailers

- 5.2.9 Services introduced by Reliance Digital
- 5.2.10 Services introduced by NEXT

5.2.1 Services introduced by HyperCITY

HyperCITY provides following services to their customers within the store premises.

- Credit (finance on 0 % interest, easy monthly installments on electronics and furniture items),
- Home delivery,
- Alteration facilities,
- Installations of electronics and consumer durables,
- Packaging / gift wrapping (a separate cell within a store),
- Complaints & exchange handling (as per the return policy),
- Personal shoppers,
- Parking,
- Baby strollers,
- Babysitting,
- Fitting / trial rooms,
- Information,
- Safety of personal things,
- Lift (3 big size) & staircase facility,
- After sale service for electronics and durables,
- Demonstrations of merchandise,
- Entertainment facilities,
- Special facilities for physically handicapped,
- Acceptance of all international credit & debit cards,
- Shopping carts,
- Warranties on merchandise,
- Well-maintained washrooms & drinking facilities (outside the store),
- Air-condition environment,
- Music,
- Loudspeaker announcements about discounts and schemes for the day,
- More than 10 billing-counters,
- CCTV for security,
- Fire safety arrangement,
- Back office for support,

- ATM terminal of ING Vaisya Bank within the store,
- Customers care service with toll free number 18002097172 & 18001020468,
- Repairing services,
- Gift certificate (of ₹ 50, 100, 250, 500, 1000, 2000),
- Trial purchase,
- Special sales for regular customers,
- Bridal registry,
- Restaurants (food planet within the store),
- Beauty salon (Kapil's salon),
- Shopping bags,
- Refreshment facilities,
- Extended warranties on electronics merchandise.

5.2.2 Services introduced by Star Bazaar

Star Bazaar provides following services to their customers within the store premises.

- Home delivery,
- Alteration facilities,
- Installations,
- Complaints & exchange handling (as per the return policy),
- Extended store hours (8.30 am to 10.30 pm),
- Personal shoppers,
- Parking,
- Fitting / trial room,
- Information,
- Safety of personal things on baggage counter,
- Escalator & staircase facility,
- After sale service on electronics items,
- Demonstrations,
- Entertainment facilities,
- Acceptance of all international credit & debit cards,
- Shopping carts,
- Warranties by manufacturer,
- Washroom & drinking water facility,
- Air-condition environment,
- Lighting arrangements,
- Music,
- More than 15 billing-counters with 2 express counters for less than 10 items,
- CCTV for security,
- Fire safety arrangement,
- Back office support,
- More than 5 weight counters for loose grocery items,
- ATM terminal of Deutsche Bank,
- Customer service desk,
- Customer loyalty desk,
- Eye testing service through Vision Eyecare centre,
- Guarantee on Star branded merchandise,
- Special sales for regular customers,
- Restaurants (Live Bakery, Dali),

- Fresh grinding service (Chakki),
- Sodexo,
- Shopping bags,
- Refreshment facilities (Coffee Café Day, Confectionary),
- Tata credit card desk

5.2.3 Services introduced by more.MEGASTore

more.MEGASTore provides following services to their customers within the store premises.

- Credit (easy finance),
- Home delivery,

- Cash on delivery,
- Alteration,
- Installation,
- Packaging / gift wrapping,
- Complaints & return handling (as per return policy),
- Trial purchase,
- Phone orders,
- Personal shoppers,
- Parking,
- Baby strollers,
- Fitting rooms,
- Fur storage,
- Information,
- Safety of personal things on baggage counter,
- Lift, escalator & staircase facility,
- After sales service & support,
- Demonstrations,
- Entertainment facilities,
- Acceptance of all international credit & debit cards,
- Special facilities for physically handicapped,
- Toilets & drinking water facility,
- Air-condition environment,
- Lighting & music,
- More than 5 billing-counters with 2 express checkout counters,
- CCTV for security,
- Fire safety arrangement with fire alarm,
- Customers support service centre / desk,
- Customer helpline number service centre (08652906676),
- Back office,
- Easy 0 % interest, EMI & spot finance facility,
- Shopping carts,
- Free testing of the products,
- Free recipes on store website,

- SMS facility to find out the nearest store via SMS, type more (space) <yourpincode> and sent to 56070,
- To give feedback SMS more<fdbk><yourcomment> to 56070,
- Gift certificates,
- Special sales for regular customers,
- Restaurant & refreshment facility - live bakery,
- Shopping bags,
- Repairing.

5.2.4 Services introduced by Big Bazaar

Big Bazaar provides following services to their customers within the store premises.

- Credit (through Capital First),
- Home delivery,
- Cash on delivery,
- Alteration,

- Installation,
- Packaging / gift wrapping,
- Complaints & return handling (as per exchange policy),
- Trial purchase,
- Phone orders,
- Personal shoppers,
- Parking,
- Baby strollers,
- Babysitting,
- Fitting rooms,
- Fur storage,
- Information,
- Safety of personal things on baggage counter,
- Lift, escalator & staircase facility,
- After sales service & support,
- Demonstrations,
- Entertainment facilities,
- Medical facilities,
- Acceptance of all international credit & debit cards,
- Special facilities for physically handicapped,
- Exchange counter during 10.30 am to 8.30 pm,
- Ladies & gents toilets,
- Drinking water facility,
- Air-condition environment,
- Lighting & music,
- TV sets at different places in the store,
- More than 10 billing-counters with 1 priority billing counter for senior citizen, pregnant ladies and physically challenged people, 1 billing counter of electronics bazaar items, 1 billing counter for dry fruits,
- CCTV for security,
- Fire safety arrangements with fire exit,
- Back office with warehouse,
- Weight counter for loose grocery,
- Idli & dosa paste grinding,

- Loudspeaker announcement,
- Mirrors in fashion bazaar section,
- Loan facility through Capital First,
- Customer service desk,
- Loyalty card desk,
- Foreign currency exchange counter,
- ATM terminal of YES BANK,
- Customer helpline number service centre (18002002255),
- Easy 0 % interest, EMI & spot finance facility,
- Shopping carts,
- Free testing of the products,
- Free talk time for TATA DOCOMO mobile number (shopping of worth ₹ 400 = ₹ 10 talk time free),
- Acceptance of meal vouchers of Sadox & Accor,
- Gift certificates,
- Special sales for regular customers,
- Restaurants & refreshment facility (Foodi Counter),
- Beauty salon (Javed Habib Hair Expresso),
- Shopping bags,
- Mehndi corner,
- Weight-checking machines,
- NAVRAS – Jewellery Bazaar,
- Fixed deposit with the guaranteed rebate service.

5.2.5 Services introduced by D⁺Mart

D⁺Mart provides following services to their customers within the store premises.

- Complaints & return handling (as per the return policy),
- Packaging / gift wrapping,
- Parking,
- Baby strollers,
- Fitting / trial room,
- Information,
- Safety of personal things,

- Acceptance of credit & debit cards,
- Personal assistance in selecting merchandise,
- Shopping carts,
- Warranties,
- Toilet room,
- Drinking water,
- Air-condition environment,
- Music,
- Loudspeaker announcements,
- More than 20 billing-counters,
- CCTV for security,
- Fire safety arrangement,
- Alteration,
- Shopping bags,
- Refreshment facilities.

5.2.6 Services introduced by Big Megamart

Big Megamart provides following services to their customers within the store premises.

- Alteration facilities (separate alteration cell),
- Packaging / gift wrapping,
- Complaints & return handling (as per the return policy),
- Personal shoppers,
- Parking,
- Baby strollers,
- Babysitting,
- Fitting / trial room (more than 20),

- Information,
- Safety of personal things on baggage counter,
- Lift, escalator facility & stairs,
- After sale service,
- Demonstrations,
- Entertainment facilities (TV and music),
- Game zones,
- Music zone (Karaoke, etc.),
- Special facilities for physically handicapped,
- Acceptance of credit & debit cards,
- Shopping carts,
- Warranties,
- Well maintained toilet room,
- Drinking water,
- Air-condition environment,
- Music,
- Loudspeaker announcements,
- More than 10 billing-counters,
- CCTV for security,
- Fire safety arrangement,
- Gift certificate,
- Trial purchase,
- Bridal registry,
- Restaurants,
- Beauty salon,
- Shopping bags,
- Refreshment facilities.

5.2.7 Services introduced by West Side

West Side provides following services to their customers within the store premises.

- Home delivery of altered garments,
- Alteration facilities,
- Installations,
- Packaging / gift wrapping (a separate cell),
- Complaints & exchange / return handling (as per the customer service policy),
- Staff on late hours for members,
- Extended store hours for members,
- Personal shoppers,
- Babysitting,
- Fitting / trial room (15),
- Information,

- Safety of personal things on baggage counter,
- Lift, escalator & staircase facility,
- Demonstrations,
- Entertainment facilities,
- Acceptance of all international credit & debit cards,
- Pulling shopping carts,
- Quality assurance,
- Drinking water facilities,
- Well maintained washrooms within the store,
- Air-condition environment,
- Music - Radio West side,
- More than 5 billing counters and one express billing counter for members,
- CCTV for security,
- Fire safety arrangements with exit point,
- Mirror on every floor,
- Back office & management office for support,
- Sensormatic system (tag) for products,
- Customer service desk,
- Easy search option facility (if customers cannot find their size & colour, let West side know, they will make available the same for customers),
- Gift certificate (of ₹ 50, 100, 500, 1000 in the denomination),
- Trial purchase,
- Special sales for regular customers,
- Parking,
- Restaurants (food café, coffee parlour, gourmet West – food section within the store),
- Shopping bags,
- Refreshment facilities.

5.2.8 Services introduced by Max

Max provides following services to their customers within the store premises.

- Home delivery (if customers could not find their size),
- Alteration facilities,
- Packaging / gift wrapping,
- Complaints & exchange handling (as per the guarantee & exchange policy),
- Personal shoppers,
- Parking,
- Fitting / trial room (separate for men, women & children),
- Information,
- Safety of personal things on baggage counter,
- Lift, escalator & staircase facility,
- Demonstrations,
- Entertainment facilities,
- Acceptance of all international credit & debit cards,
- Pulling shopping carts,

- Well maintained washrooms & drinking water facilities (outside the store),
- Air-condition environment,
- Lighting & western music,
- 4 billing-counters,
- CCTV for security,
- Fire safety arrangements with exit point,
- Mirrors in store,
- Sensormatic system (tag) for products,
- Customer service associate on desk,
- Easy search option facility (if customers cannot find their size & colour, let **Max** know, they will make available the same for customers),
- TV sets at billing counters,
- Loudspeaker announcement,
- Pass of different activities where Max is the sponsor,
- SMS service to know the store location & reward points (SMS 'TIC' to 56767),
- Gift certificate (of ₹ 100, 250, 500, 1000, 2000 and 5000 in the denomination),
- Special sales for regular customers,
- Restaurants (outside the store),
- Shopping bags,
- Refreshment facilities.

5.2.9 Services introduced by Reliance Digital

Reliance Digital provides following services to their customers within the store premises.

- Credit (EMI facility - through Bajaj FinanceV on the credit card of HDFC, City, ICICI, Kotak, Axis, HSBC Bank credit card),
- Home delivery,
- Installation through resQ,
- Packaging / gift wrapping,
- Complaints & return handling (as per return policy),
- Personal shoppers,
- Parking,
- Restroom,
- Babysitting,
- Fur storage,
- Information,
- Safety of personal things on baggage counter,
- Staircase facility,

- After sales service & support through resQ for 365 days between 10 am to 10 pm,
- Demonstrations (the digital zone),
- Entertainment facilities (play station),
- Acceptance of all international credit & debit cards,
- Game zone (play station),
- Washrooms & drinking water facility,
- Air-condition environment,
- Lighting & music,
- 4 billing-counters,
- CCTV for security,
- Good fire safety arrangement with exit point,
- The Sensormatic system (tag) for merchandise,
- My assist- customer service centre / desk,
- Home Theater experience zone,
- Customer care service centre (02267276727),
- My finance desk,
- Back office,
- Easy EMI & spot finance facility (through Bajaj FinanceV on credit card of HDFC, City, ICICI, Kotak, Axis, HSBC Bank credit card),
- Online green room service,
- Online reliance digital solution box,
- Maintenance & repair,
- Specialised customer training,
- One stop solution for repairs of all reconnect brands,
- Gift certificate (of ₹ 500 to 10000 in the denomination),
- Special sales for regular customers,
- Shopping bags,
- Health checkup plan – a preventive maintenance,
- Enhanced utility through resQ accessories and extended warranty service: a resQ care plan (investing ₹ 2* per day can free you from the worries of repairs and maintenance! resQ care plan (RCP) takes the hassles and expense out of unexpected product failures, break down and malfunctions long after the manufacturer's warranty has expired, RCP includes 5 bonus coupons that offer

you range of benefits i.e. 10% discount coupon on. resQ range of accessories, ₹ 250 discount coupon on labour charges (only for repairs), one free preventive maintenance service (PMS) coupon, 10% discount coupon on purchase of RCP for any other product, 15% discount coupon on renewal of RCP)

5.2.10 Services introduced by NEXT

NEXT provides following services to their customers within the store premises.

- Credit (EMI facility through credit card),
- Home delivery,
- Cash on delivery,
- Installation,
- Packaging (gift wrapping),
- Complaints & return handling (as per return policy),
- Mail & phone orders with advance payment,
- Personal shoppers,
- Parking,
- Fur storage,
- Information,
- Safety of personal things on baggage counter,
- Staircase facility,
- After sales service & support,
- Demonstrations,
- Entertainment facilities (play station),

- Acceptance of all international credit & debit cards,
- Game zone (play station),
- Washrooms & drinking water facility,
- Air-condition environment,
- Lighting & music,
- 4 billing-counters,
- CCTV for security,
- Fire safety arrangements,
- Sensormatic system (tag) for merchandise,
- Customers service centre / desk,
- Customer helpline number service centre during 8 am to 8 pm (0124-4993500),
- Back office,
- Easy 0 % interest, EMI & spot finance facility,
- Free gifts,
- Online information regarding product care,
- 30 day replacement guarantee policy,
- 30 days change of mind policy,
- Shopping bags,
- Gift certificate (of ₹ 500 to 10000 in the denomination),
- Special sales for regular customers,
- Maintenance & repair,
- Extended warranty,
- Recharge your mobile phone, DTH & pay mobile & landline bills.

Chapter r 6

Retailing strategies introduced by organised retail industry

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- Retail marketing strategy
 - Segmentation strategy
 - Targeting strategy
 - Positioning strategy
 - Defensive strategy
 - Strategic tools
 - Generic (business-level) strategy
 - Retail marketing mix
 - Merchandise planning
 - Retail assortment strategy
 - Stock planning
 - Pricing strategy
 - Price-adjustment strategy
 - Promotional strategy
 - Customer service strategy
 - Customer relationship management
 - Store design
 - etc.

CHAPTER 6

RETAILING STRATEGIES INTRODUCED BY ORGANISED RETAIL INDUSTRY

Introduction

This chapter comprises an analysis of the various data related to retailing strategies introduced by organised retail industry, which have been collected through the institutional questionnaire by personal interaction with responsible personnel of the respective organised retail store. Further, results have been interpreted and discussed to reach on some inferences at the end of the different sections.

6.1 Retail market segmentation

All the organised retailers (included in the study) use demographic, psychographic and behavioural variables in order to segment the retail market. Age, family life cycle, gender, income, occupation and education are most the common variables for demographic segmentation while lifestyle and personality are most common variables for psychographic segmentation and usage rate, loyalty status, occasions, benefits and innovativeness are the most common variables for behavioural segmentation of the retail market.

All the organised retailers (included in the study) do demographic segmentation on the basis of *gender* (male and female); *income* (low, lower middle, middle, upper middle, high...); *age* (infants, 2-5 years, 5-10 years, 11-21 years,, 60+ years) except Reliance Digital and NEXT; *family life cycle* (young, single; young, married, no children; young, married, child....) except Star Bazaar; *occupation* (unskilled worker, skilled worker, students, self-employed, homemaker, retired) except West Side and Max; and *education* (illiterate, school, non-graduate, graduate / postgraduate - general/professional)) except West Side, Max and NEXT.

While *lifestyle* (culture oriented, sport oriented, outdoor oriented....) and *personality* (compulsive, gregarious, authoritarian, ambitious, aggressive, shy, emotional....) for psychographic segmentation and *occasions* (regular/special);

benefits (quality, service, economy, speed...); *usage rate* (light, medium & heavy) except Big Megamart, HyperCITY and NEXT; *loyalty status* (none, medium, strong & absolute) except D-Mart and Big Megamart; *innovativeness* (innovator, early adopter, early majority, late majority, laggard) except D-Mart; for behavioural segmentation of retail market. Apart from most common variables for behavioural segmentation, some of the organised retailers use other variables like *attitude towards the merchandise* (enthusiastic, positive, indifferent, negative & hostile) by Big Bazaar; *perceived risk* (high, medium and low) by D-Mart, Reliance Digital, NEXT, more.MEGASStore; *user status* (non-user, ex-user, potential user, first time user & regular user) by West Side, Max, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar; and *readiness stage* (unaware, aware, informed, interested, desirous & intending to buy) by Big Megamart, HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, Reliance Digital, more.MEGASStore.

6.2 Segmentation strategy

All multi-format organised retailers (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar and D-Mart) adopt *full market coverage segmentation strategy* in order to segment the retail market. HyperCITY covers the full retail market in the category of food & grocery, health & beauty, home & furniture, fashion, electronics, toys and sports while Star Bazaar covers whole retail market with following merchandise categories, i.e. food & grocery, personal & home care, home & kitchen needs and fashion & accessories.

Merchandise categories like grocery, fruits & vegetables, home & personal care, general merchandise, electronics merchandise, computer & accessories, mobile phone & accessories, apparel, footwear and sports are offered by more.MEGASStore in order to cover the full retail market. Big Bazaar covers the full retail market by offering the merchandise in following categories like grocery & staples bazaar, farm fresh, kitchen & dining bazaar, bed & bath bazaar, books, magazines & stationery bazaar, luggage bazaar, home bazaar, personal bazaar, furniture bazaar, electronics bazaar, office bazaar, mobile bazaar, toys, sports & outdoors, fashion bazaar and gifts. And superstore D-Mart covers the whole retail market in segments like grocery, foods, toiletries, beauty merchandise, garments, kitchenware, bed & bath linen, footwear, toys & games, water purifiers, baby foods, stationery and electronic items.

All the fashion-item organised retailers (i.e. Big Megamart, West Side and Max) prefer *selective specialisation segmentation strategy* to segment the retail market. Big Megamart offers the merchandise in selective merchandise segments like footwear, apparels, fashion, toys, home and travelling accessories. West Side fulfils the needs of the customers in selective segments like apparel, footwear, cosmetics, home & gift items, luggage items and accessories while Max operates in segments like apparel, footwear and accessories for men, including women, children and infants. Superstore based electronics-item organised retailers (i.e. Reliance Digital and NEXT) adopt *market specialisation segmentation strategy* while segmenting the retail market. Reliance Digital operates in the electronics market, especially in consumer durables & information technology segments while NEXT concentrates on consumer electronics, small home appliance and mobile phones market segments.

6.3 Targeting strategy

Multi-format organised retailers (i.e. Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar and D▲Mart) adopt an *undifferentiating targeting strategy or mass retailing* in order to target the retail market. However, HyperCITY prefers *multi-segment targeting strategy*. Star Bazaar covers mass retail market by offering staples, packaged foods, beverages, dairy, bakery, frozen merchandise, non-vegetation, fruits & vegetables, cleaning aids, health & beauty merchandise, kitchenware, electronics, home decor, luggage items, toys, stationery, men's wear, women's wear, kid's wear, footwear and accessories. more.MEGASStore focuses on mass retailing by offering merchandise like apparels, audio & video, live bakery, beverages, books and audio & video merchandise, computer & accessories, crockery, cookware, do it yourself & auto accessories, electronics, FMCG merchandise, footwear, frozen & dairy merchandise, fresh fruit & vegetables, fresh non-vegetarian, furniture, general merchandise, fitness, home care merchandise, home decor merchandise, home needs & home upkeep, imported food, footwear & accessories, infant & children's apparels, information technology merchandise, large white appliances, luggage, mobile phone & accessories, personal care & cosmetics, prepared food, ready to cook or prepared food, processed food, small white appliances, sporting goods, packaged & loose staples, stationery and toys etc. Big Bazaar focuses on mass retailing by offering something (merchandise) for everyone in a different category of the merchandise. While, D▲Mart does not offer specific mix for any segment and covers the whole

market with their selected merchandise for different segments and HyperCITY offers merchandise and services to the multi-segments of customers according to their age groups, gender, income, occupation, lifestyle, loyalty status, benefits and so on.

West Side, Max and NEXT adopt *concentrated targeting strategy*, which is mostly adopted strategy among superstore organised retailers. West Side carved a niche for its brand of merchandise to create loyal customers. They offer a variety of designs & style. Everything in their stores is exclusively designed & the merchandise range, from stylised clothes, footwear and accessories for men, women, children, too well-coordinated table Lenin, artefact, home accessories and furnishing. Max focuses on niche retailing and concentrates towards few segments like apparel, footwear & accessories for the entire family while NEXT concentrate on mobile phones, home appliances and consumer electronics. Other organised retailers (i.e. Big Megamart and Reliance Digital) adopt *differentiating targeting strategy or selective retailing*. Big Megamart offers a specific mix to their different customer segments while Reliance Digital offers a complete solution through the specific mix to their targeted customers.

6.4 Positioning strategy

Value Proposition		Price		
		More	The same	More of less
Benefits	More	More for More	<u>More for Same</u> Big Megamart and West Side	<u>More for Less</u> HyperCITY, more MEGASore, Big Bazaar, DMart, Max and Reliance Digital
	The same			<u>The Same for Less</u> Star Bazaar and NEXT
	More of less			Less for Much Less

Figure 6.1: Positioning strategies of organised retailers

More for less is the most popular positioning strategy among both hyper & super store organised retailers and adopted by most of the organised retailers i.e., HyperCITY, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar, D-Mart, Max and Reliance Digital in order to position their offerings to the targeted customers. Hyper stores like HyperCITY use *more for less* strategy to position their offerings to the customers with more than 40000 quality merchandise and unmatched values/benefits & price while more.MEGASStore by offering more than 35,000 merchandise & services of great quality with an unbelievable price to keep their promise that Hamesha Extra for customers. Big Bazaar uses this strategy by offering merchandise & services of best quality with the best price guaranteed. Superstore (i.e. D-Mart) uses strategy to position their offerings to the customers by offering more benefits for less price while Max by offering international fashion from around the globe & an excellent range of merchandise with a great price in the world-class shopping experience. Moreover, Reliance Digital by offering more than 4000 quality merchandise with more than 200 national & international brands and the lowest price guaranteed.

However, some organised retailers (i.e. Star Bazaar and NEXT) adopt *same for less* positioning strategy while others (Big Megamart and West Side) *more for same positioning strategy* to position their offerings to the target market. Star Bazaar uses *same for less* strategy to position their offerings to the customers to keep their promise to their customers “Helping You Spend Less” while NEXT to keep their promise to their customers “Best Brand & Best Bargains”. Moreover, Big Megamart uses *more for same* strategy to position their offerings to the customers by offering more benefits/quality for the same price in comparison to the competitors while West Side by understanding the customer’s needs, strive to win customers’ confidence and offer best-in-class-merchandise & services at affordable prices.

6.5 Retail marketing strategy

Both hyper & superstores / multi-format & specialised organised retailers (like HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, Big Bazaar, Max, Reliance Digital and NEXT) adopt a *retail market penetration strategy* in order to grab growth opportunities. All these organised retailers penetrate the retail market by displaying merchandise in an attractive way to increase impulse purchase and training to personal shoppers/sales staff for cross & add-on selling. Moreover, these organised retailers also penetrate the

retail market by opening the stores for longer hours except HyperCITY and by opening more stores in the same target retail market except HyperCITY and Star Bazaar.

Growth Opportunities		Target Market	
		Existing	New
Retail Format	Existing	<p><u>Market Penetration</u></p> <p>HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, Big Bazaar, Max, Reliance Digital and NEXT</p>	<p><u>Market Expansion</u></p> <p>More.MEGASStore, D▲Mart and West Side</p>
	New	<p><u>Format Development</u></p> <p>Big Megamart</p>	<p><u>Diversification</u></p> <p>Related/unrelated</p>

Figure 6.2: Retail marketing strategies of organised retailers

While other organised retailers (i.e. more.MEGASStore, D▲Mart and West Side) adopt a *retail market expansion strategy* in order to grab the opportunities available in the market. All these retailers hope to expand rapidly with similar format stores in the next few years to grave growth opportunities. However, Big Megamart adopts *retail format development strategy* by offering merchandise & services with the new retail format, i.e. footwear to same target retail market.

6.6 Defensive strategy

The most favourable defensive choice is a *preemptive defence strategy* among both hyper & super store organised retailers (i.e. Big Megamart, HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, Big Bazaar, Max and Reliance Digital). All these attack on competitors more aggressively by launching a wide range of merchandise and brands in different categories.

HyperCITY uses *preemptive defence* by attacking competitors more aggressively by launching more than 40000 merchandise to their customers with a wide range of local, national, international, exclusive and store label brands. Star

Bazaar uses this defensive strategy by spreading their store over a large area 40000-80000 square feet and offering the entire spectrum of merchandise categories ranging from fresh foods, grocery, apparel, general merchandise and consumer durables with a range of more than 30000 items at great price, modern shopping environment and backed by strong values of TATA group. Big Bazaar uses by offering the entire spectrum of merchandise categories with more than 15 merchandise lines ranging from grocery to gifts and Max, by offering a fresh collection of international designs specially customised to the Indian market in every season (autumn, winter and spring-summer). Moreover, Reliance Digital uses by offering more than 200 international & national brand with 4000 merchandise along private label brand 'Reconnect' in the category like mobile phones, tablets, TVs, camera, DVD player, home appliances, kitchen appliances and accessory.

The mobile defence strategy is second most favourable defensive choice among some superstores organised retailers (i.e. D⁺Mart, West Side and NEXT) and they hope to expand rapidly by stretching its domain to new territories with the similar format store.

However, more.MEGASTore (a multi-format hyper store organised retailer) uses *contraction defence strategy* as they give up from the weaker territories from where the company is not getting sufficient ROI, for example, Aurangabad's more.MEGASTore.

6.7 Strategic tools used to perform store-level planning

SWOT analysis is the most favourable tool to perform store-level planning and all the organised retailers use it except D⁺Mart. *Five force analysis* is also a preferred tool and both hyper & super store organised retailers included in the study use it except D⁺Mart, Star Bazaar and NEXT.

However, some organised retailers use some more tools to perform store-level planning, i.e. West Side uses *ETOP analysis and PEST analysis* while Big Bazaar uses a *PEST analysis* and Reliance Digital uses *ETOP analysis* in order to perform store level planning.

6.8 Retail store position in Boston matrix

BCG Matrix		Market Share	
		High	Low
Market/Business Growth	High	Big Bazaar, West Side, NEXT	Big Megamart, HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, D Mart, Max, Reliance Digital
		Stars	Question Marks
	Low		
		Cash Caws	Dogs

Figure 6.3: Retail store position in Boston matrix

Big Bazaar, West Side and NEXT stand in *star category*, which is characterised by high market growth & the high market share while others, i.e. Big Megamart, HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, D Mart, Max and Reliance Digital belong to the *question mark* category that is characterised by high market growth but low market share.

6.9 Generic (business-level) strategy

Figure 6.4: Generic (business-level) strategies of organised retailers

Cost leadership strategy is a common choice as a business level strategy at store-level among all the multi-format organised retailers (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASTore, Big Bazaar and D⁺Mart), which is characterised by the broad target with lower cost. All these organised retailers adopted this strategy in order to utilise a broad target competitive scope and lower cost competitive advantage. However, Big Megamart (a hyper store fashion-item organised retailer) follows *differentiation strategy* at store-level that is characterised by the broad target with differentiation. Moreover, West Side (a super store fashion-item organised retailer) follows *differentiation focus strategy* at store-level by doing niche retailing with differentiation.

While other specialised superstore organised retailers (i.e. Max, Reliance Digital and NEXT) prefer *cost focus* strategy at store-level, which is characterised by the narrow target with lower cost. Max follows this strategy by targeting narrowly in selective areas like apparel, footwear, & accessory with lower cost while Reliance Digital, by targeting a niche segment, i.e. electronics, especially consumer durables & information technology with lower cost and NEXT, targeting niche segment i.e. consumer electronics, home appliance and mobile phones with lower cost.

6.10 Problems faced in framing overall retailing strategy

The high price of real estate, lack of preferred locations and retail space, high cost of space and location, trained workforce, multiple & a complex taxation system of India, many entrants as online retailers, high demand for service standards as consumerism is shifting in India are some common problems faced by all the organised retailers. Apart from these most common problems, D⁺Mart faces problems in handling customer complaints while Big Megamart needs bigger premises to operate and Star Bazaar stuck with the inefficiency of the supply chain.

Moreover, West Side faces problems due to lack of adequate infrastructure and changing behavioural forces among consumers while Max and Reliance Digital are facing stiff competition and problems due to changing the demand pattern of Indian consumers because of changing demographics of Indian consumers and NEXT is facing stiff competition due to many entrants as online retailers of electronics items. Big Bazaar is facing the problems while framing overall retailing strategies like

changing demand pattern of Indian consumers, demand for higher wages by the workforce and stiff competition.

6.11 Core advantages

Efficient operations are the core advantages of all the organised retailers included in the study while the image of the retailers is the second most common advantage of organised retailers (i.e. Big Megamart, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar, West Side, Max, Reliance Digital and NEXT). Moreover, strong private (store-level) brands are also the core advantage of Big Megamart, HyperCITY, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar, West Side, Max and Reliance Digital while low cost is also a common core advantage of organised retailers like more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar, D-Mart, Max, Reliance Digital and NEXT. Apart from most common advantages, Big Megamart, West Side and Max have a strong fashion reputation among consumers. Moreover, category dominance is also the core advantage of West Side and NEXT. West Side has dominance in the fashion category, while NEXT, in electronics.

6.12 Retail Marketing Mix (RMM) on importance scale

Table 6.1: Retail marketing mix (RMM) on importance scale						
Sr. No.	Variables	Importance Scale*				K-S <i>D</i> value calculated
		4	3	2	1	
1.	Product (Merchandise)	10	00	00	00	0.750
2.	Price	08	02	00	00	0.550
3.	Promotion	09	01	00	00	0.650
4.	Premises / Place	07	02	01	00	0.450
5.	Personnel / People	08	02	00	00	0.550
6.	Presentation	07	01	02	00	0.450
7.	Physical Evidence	00	09	01	00	0.400
* 4- extremely important, 3- important, 2- partially important, 1- not important						
Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) <i>D</i> value tabulated = 0.410; Level of significance (α) = 5 % (0.05)						

Product (merchandise) is an extremely important element of the retail marketing mix for all the organised retailers included in the study. Price is also an extremely important element of RMM for all the organised retailers except Big Megamart and West Side as it is an important for them. All the organised retailers except Big Megamart consider promotion as an extremely important element of

RMM; however, it is important for Big Megamart. The premises / place is an extremely important element of RMM for all the organised retailers except D▲Mart, Max and NEXT, however, it is an important element for D▲Mart and Max, while partially important for NEXT. Personnel / people are considered as the extremely important element of RMM by all the organised retailers, except D▲Mart and Max. For D▲Mart and Max, it is an important element. The presentation is an extremely important element of RMM for all the organised retailers, except more.MEGASStore, D▲Mart and NEXT as it is important for more.MEGASStore and partially important for D▲Mart and NEXT. Physical evidence is an important element of RMM for all the organised retailers included in the study, except NEXT, as it is partially important.

6.13 Management of retail marketing mix

Multi-format organised retailers manage their retail marketing mix as follows. HyperCITY manages its RMM by offering more than 40000 quality merchandise with an unbeatable price to their target customers with a wide range of local, national, international & private brands. Star Bazaar manages its RMM by operating in more than 40000 square feet stores and offering the entire spectrum of merchandise categories ranging from fresh foods, grocery, apparel, general merchandise and consumer durables with a range of more than 30000 items at a great price, modern shopping environment and backed by strong values of TATA.

more.MEGASStore manages its RMM by offering Extra quality, Extra choice with Extra savings on merchandise at the same time Extra Care of customers & Extra rewards to customers while Big Bazaar manages its RMM by offering best quality merchandise with the lowest price at any cost for guaranteed customer satisfaction. Superstore, D▲Mart manages its RMM with a variety of merchandise, less price, significant promotions, proper display and helping personal shoppers.

Fashion-item organised retailers manage their retail marketing mix as follows. Big Megamart manages its RMM by offering a specific mix to their target customers while super-stores like West Side manages its RMM by operating in 15,000 - 30,000 square feet stores and offering a differentiated retail marketing mix to their target customers with a variety of designs, styles and exclusively designed. Well-designed interiors, sprawling space, prime locations, strong values of TATA and coffee shops

are to enhance the customers' shopping experience. In addition, Max manages its RMM by bringing to customers the most dynamic offering of the value in fashion merchandise to stringent quality standard and offers latest international trends with great variety & affordable price & a holistic shopping experience. Their sales advisors & visual merchandising team ensure that every Max store represent the spirit of their brand promise "Look Good, Feel Good".

Electronics-item organised retailers manage their retail marketing mix as follows. Reliance Digital manages its RMM by offering the merchandise that best suit to the customer's lifestyle needs with the latest & widest, digital service, friendly counselling, and best value for money in terms of total cost of ownership and provide total solutions with the lowest price guaranteed. Every Reliance Digital store represents the spirit of their brand promise "We bring technology to life for you". NEXT manages its RMM by offering multi-brand and multi-merchandise with an entire range of consumer durables with affordable price.

6.14 Brands offered

A *heterogeneous mix of brands* is the first choice among the all the multi-format organised retailers (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASTore, Big Bazaar and D-Mart). However, Big Megamart (a fashion store organised retailer) also offers a heterogeneous mix of brands to targeted customers. The offering basket of all these retailers contains generic, local, regional, national, copycat, international and private/store brands.

While fashion-item superstores (i.e. West Side and Max) choose a *blend of private label & other brands* to offer and their offering basket contains private (store label) in all categories offered, exclusive, national (manufacturers) and international brands. Moreover, electronics superstores (i.e. Reliance Digital and NEXT) offer *multi-brands* in different categories of the merchandise and their offering basket contains all the leading (world's most popular brands) national and international brands like LG, Samsung, Electrolux, Sony, Philips, Whirlpool, Videocon, Onida, Kelvinator, Kenstar, Sansui and private brands.

6.15 Important factors while planning merchandise

Table 6.2: Important factors while planning merchandise
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Sr. No.	Factors	Importance Scale*				K-S D value calculated
		4	3	2	1	
1.	Target market	09	01	00	00	0.650
2.	Goods & service growth potential	07	03	00	00	0.500
3.	Trends (fashion)	08	02	00	00	0.550
4.	Image of retailer	09	00	01	00	0.650
5.	Competition	00	06	03	01	0.150
6.	Customer segments	07	02	01	00	0.450
7.	Responsiveness to customers	07	03	00	00	0.500
8.	Amount of investment	01	02	07	00	0.250
9.	Profitability	01	04	05	00	0.250
10.	Risk	04	03	03	00	0.250
* 4- extremely important, 3- important, 2- partially important, 1- not important						
Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) D value tabulated = 0.410;						
Level of significance (α) = 5 % (0.05)						

The target market is an extremely important factor for all the organised retailers included in the study except D▲Mart, as it is important for them while *trends* (fashion) are extremely important for all the organised retailers except Reliance Digital and NEXT as it is important for them to plan merchandise for retail store customers. *Image* (of retailers) is also an extremely important factor for all the organised retailers except D▲Mart as it is partially important for them while *goods & service growth potential* is extremely important for all the organised retailers except Big Megamart, HyperCITY and West Side as it is important for them to plan merchandise. *Responsiveness to customers* and *customer segments* are extremely important factors for all the organised retailers except HyperCITY, Star Bazaar and D▲Mart, as these are important factors for HyperCITY and Star Bazaar while *responsiveness to customers* is important for D▲Mart and *customer segments* is a partially important factor in planning store merchandise. *The risk* is an extremely important for HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, D▲Mart and West Side while important for Big Megamart, Reliance Digital and NEXT and partially important for more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar and Max to plan store merchandise. *Profitability* is partially important for most of the organised retailers (i.e. Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar, West Side and NEXT) while important for others (i.e. D▲Mart, Big Megamart, Max, and Reliance Digital); however, it is extremely important for HyperCITY. *The amount of investment* is a partially important factor for most of the organised except Reliance Digital, NEXT and D▲Mart because it is important for Reliance Digital and NEXT; while, it is extremely important for D▲Mart to plan store merchandise. *Competition* is an important factor for most of the

organised retailers except HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, NEXT and D▲Mart as it is partially important for HyperCITY, Star Bazaar and NEXT while not important for D▲Mart in order to plan store merchandise.

6.16 Important factors while planning merchandise quality

Table 6.3: Important factors while planning merchandise quality						
Sr. No.	Factors	Importance Scale*				K-S <i>D</i> value calculated
		4	3	2	1	
1.	Target market	09	01	00	00	0.650
2.	Competition	01	07	02	00	0.300
3.	Retailer's image	09	01	00	00	0.650
4.	Store location	00	01	08	01	0.300
5.	Stock turnover	01	07	01	01	0.300
6.	Profitability	01	02	07	00	0.250
7.	Manufactures V/S private brands	06	03	01	00	0.400
8.	The customer service offered	08	01	01	00	0.550
9.	Personnel	02	06	02	00	0.300
10.	Perceived goods/service benefits	07	03	00	00	0.500
* 4- extremely important, 3- important, 2- partially important, 1- not important						
Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) <i>D</i> value tabulated = 0.410; Level of significance (α) = 5 % (0.05)						

Target market is an extremely important factor for all the organised retailers included in the study except D▲Mart, as it is important to them while *image* (of retailers) is also an extremely important for all the organised retailers except HyperCITY, it is important for them in order to plan quality of merchandise offered to customers. *Perceived goods/service benefits* is extremely important for all the organised retailers except HyperCITY, D▲Mart and West Side, as it is important to them while *customer service offered* is an extremely important for all the organised retailers except Big Megamart and D▲Mart, as it is important for D▲Mart and partially important for Big Megamart. *Manufacturers Vs private brands* is an extremely important factor for all the organised retailers except Big Megamart, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and D▲Mart, as it is important for Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and D▲Mart; while partially important for Big Megamart to plan the merchandise quality. *Competition* is an important for all the organised retailers except HyperCITY, Star Bazaar and D▲Mart, as it is partially important for HyperCITY and Star Bazaar while extremely important for D▲Mart to plan the merchandise quality. *Personnel* is extremely important for West Side and Reliance

Digital, while important for all the organised retailers except HyperCITY and D▲Mart, as it is partially important to them in order to decide the merchandise quality. *Stock turnover* is extremely important for more.MEGASStore while important for all other organised retailers except Max and D▲Mart as it is partially important for Max and not important for D▲Mart to plan merchandise quality. *Profitability* is an extremely important factor for HyperCITY and important for Big Megamart and Max, while partially important for all the other organised retailers. *Store location* is important for West Side, while partially important for all the other organised retailers except D▲Mart, as it is not important to them for taking a decision about the merchandise quality.

6.17 Retail assortment strategy

All the hyper store organised retailers included in the study (i.e. Big Megamart, HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and Big Bazaar) adopt *wide variety & a deep assortment strategy*, which is characterised by many goods/service categories & a large assortment in each category.

While, super store organised retailers included in the study prefer *narrow variety & a shallow assortment strategy* characterised by few goods/service categories & a limited assortment in each category and *narrow variety & a deep assortment strategy* characterised by few goods/service categories & a large assortment in each category. D▲Mart and NEXT opt *narrow variety & a shallow assortment strategy* while others (i.e. West Side, Max and Reliance Digital) *narrow variety & a deep assortment strategy*.

6.18 Categories of merchandise offered

Multi-format organised retailers included in the study (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar and D▲Mart) offer *staples (basic), fashion, consumer durable and seasonal merchandise categories* to their customers. Size, price, quality, brand, customer segments, discounts and schemes are the most common base to categorise the merchandise while displaying in the store by these organised retailers. However, all these organised retailers also categorise the merchandise based on the design except D▲Mart. Moreover, all these organised retailers categorise the merchandise based on customers' needs except HyperCITY

while colour is also used as a base by more.MEGASStore and Big Bazaar in order to categorise the merchandise while displaying in the store.

While, fashion-item organised retailers (i.e. Big Megamart, West Side and Max) offer *fashion merchandise categories* to their customers and use size, colour, design, price, quality, brand, customer needs, discounts and schemes as a base to categorise the merchandise while displaying in the store. However, West Side and Max also use customer segment as a base for categorization of merchandise.

Moreover, electronics superstores (i.e. Reliance Digital and NEXT) offer *consumer durables merchandise categories* and categorise the merchandise based on size, design, price, quality, brand, customer segments, customer needs, discounts and schemes to display in the store.

6.19 Merchandise lines offered

The industry is in for huge challenges in terms of targeting customers because of different and changing consumer behaviour regularly. Therefore, multi-format organised retailers included in the study (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar and D⁺Mart) offer a wide range of merchandise in each category under the different merchandise lines. HyperCITY offers foods & grocery, health & beauty, home & furniture, fashion, electronics, toys and sports while Star Bazaar offers foods & grocery, personal & home care, home & kitchen needs, fashion & accessory merchandise lines to their targeted customers.

more.MEGASStore's offering basket contains grocery, fruits & vegetables, general merchandise, home & personal care, electronics, computer & accessories, mobile phone & accessories, apparels, footwear and sports merchandise lines. While Big Bazaar's offering basket contains grocery & staples bazaar, farm fresh, kitchen & dining bazaar, bed & bath bazaar, books, magazines & stationery bazaar, luggage bazaar, home bazaar, personal bazaar, furniture bazaar, electronics bazaar, office bazaar, mobile bazaar, toys, sports & outdoors, fashion bazaar and gift merchandise lines. And, D⁺Mart offers foods, toiletries & beauty merchandise, garments, bed & bath linen, kitchenware, toys & games, stationery, home appliances, baby care,

footwear, gifts and insecticides merchandise lines to targeted customers in their stores.

Fashion-item organised retailers (i.e. Big Megamart, West Side and Max) categorise their offerings under the following different merchandise lines. Hyper store organised retailer, Big Megamart offers footwear, women's wear, men's wear, youth wear, kids wear, fashion mart, home mart and travel mart merchandise lines to their target customers in their stores. While, West Side (super store) offers women's wear, men's wear, kid's wear, cosmetics & fragrances, footwear, accessories, home & gift and luggage and Max offers men's wear, ladies wear, children's wear, footwear and accessory merchandise lines to their target customers in their stores.

Electronics superstores, Reliance Digital offers mobile phones, computers, TVs & audio, camera, home appliances, kitchen appliances, gaming and accessories while NEXT offers home entertainment, home appliances, phones & accessories, camera & camcorder, game & console, computers & tablets, personal care and writing instruments merchandise lines to their target customers in their stores.

6.20 Brands availability in each category of merchandise

All the organised retailers make available generic, most of leading local, regional, national & international brands in different categories of the merchandise. Apart from these brands, fashion store organised retailers (i.e. Big Megamart, West Side and Max) also offer exclusive brands to their customers. Big Megamart offer Elitus, Leisha, Auburn Hill, Colt, Bay Island, Mea Casa, Karigari, Donuts, Ruggers, Skinn, and Edge as exclusive brands in their store while West Side offers Lovable, NUON, Gia, Fiorelli from London, Sidney, Frankfurt, Ascot, Richmond, L.O.V., Wardrobe, Westport, Zuba, Meenakari etc. as exclusive brands in their store. Max offers following exclusive brands like mélange, Code, Ginger, Fame, Forever, Forca and Juniors.

Moreover, some organised retailers (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar, Reliance Digital and NEXT) also offer store label brands to their customers. HyperCITY offers Fresh Basket, Everyday, Terzo, Avorio, Ebano, Technix, Maxit and Waitrose store label brands while Star Bazaar offers the

store label in different categories with name “Star Bazaar”. More.MEGASTore offers Feaster, Kitchenpromise and Selecta, etc. as store label brands while Big Bazaar with name “Such”. Reliance Digital offers store label brand, i.e. ‘Reconnect’ while NEXT offers under the name ‘NEXT’.

6.21 Availability of newly launched merchandise/brands & customisation

All the organised retailers included in the study make sure the availability of newly launched merchandise/brands as soon as possible if falls in the categories of the merchandise they offer. Multi-format hyper store organised retailers like, HyperCITY offers the customised merchandise in the categories like clothing, footwear, jewellery, foods, toys, sports and fashion while Star Bazaar offers the customised merchandise in the categories like bakery, staples, non-vegetation, cleaning aids, health & beauty, kitchenware, electronics, home decor, stationary, apparel, footwear. more.MEGASTore offers the customised merchandise in the categories like computers, grocery, general merchandise, staples, non-vegetation, kitchenware, electronics, home decor, apparel while Big Bazaar offers the customised merchandise in the categories like computers, footwear, grocery, kitchen & dining, stationery, home & personal category etc. and multi-format superstore organised retailer (i.e. D Mart) offers the customised merchandise in some categories of the merchandise.

Fashion-item organised retailer (i.e. Big Megamart) offers the customised merchandise in the categories like clothing, footwear, jewellery and fashion. While fashion-item superstores like West Side offers the customised merchandise in the categories like accessories; apparels, home & gift under the *EASY SEARCH OPTION* (If customers cannot find their size & colour, let them know, they will arrange it for customers, contact with sales staff on the floor for the same). Max offers the customised merchandise in the categories like accessories, apparels and footwear under the *SEARCH OPTION* (If customers cannot find their size & colour, let them know, they will arrange it for customers).

Electronics superstores; Reliance Digital offers the customised merchandise in the category like accessories while NEXT offers the customised merchandise in the category like phones & accessories, game & console, computers etc.

6.22 Unique and complementary merchandise / brands

Hyper stores organised retailers like, HyperCITY offers some unique brands exclusively available in their store, i.e. Everyday, Fresh Basket, Terzo, Waitrose, Ebano, Avorio, City Style, Joojoobs, River Inc., Technix, Raleish, Maxit and also offers complementary merchandise like shoes, socks, pant & shirts, foam, shaving cream & razor, cookware, pet needs, vegetables, electronics and so on.....while Star Bazaar offers unique brand *Star Bazaar's* exclusively available in their store in some categories like food & grocery, cleaning aids, packaged foods, beverages, personal care, Pooja needs, men's, women's & kid's wear and also offers complementary merchandise in categories like cookware, pet needs, vegetables, electronics, cleaning aids, health & beauty, toys, kitchenware and so on.....

more.MEGASTore offers some unique brands exclusively available in their store in food category - more., Feasters, Kitchen's Promise, Best of India and in home & personal care category - more., Enriche, 110%, Pestex, Paradise, Germex and also offers complementary merchandise in categories like accessories, shoes, socks, cookware, electronics, cleaning aids, health & beauty, toys, kitchenware and so on.....while Big Bazaar offers some unique brands exclusively available in their store (like **Such** in personal category) and also offers complementary merchandise in the categories like utensils, cookware, electronics, computers & mobile accessories and so on.....

Fashion based hyper store organised retailer, Big Megamart offers some unique brands exclusively available in their store by Arvind Mills like Skinn, Elitus, Colt, Leisha, Donuts, Karigari, Bay Island, Ruggers, Mea Casa, Auburn Hill and Edge and also offers complementary merchandise like shoes, socks, pant & shirts, shaving cream & razor and so on..... While superstores like West Side offers some unique brands like Lovable, NUON, Gia, Fiorelli from London, Sidney, Frankfurt, Ascot, Richmond, L.O.V., Wardrobe, Westport, Zuba, Meenakari etc. and also offers complementary merchandise in categories like accessories, gifts, home accessories and so on..... Max offers some unique brands like mélange, Code, Ginger, Fame, Forever, Forca and also offers complementary merchandise in categories like accessories, footwear and apparels.

While electronics based superstore Reliance Digital offers a unique brand ‘Reconnect’ in different categories of the merchandise and offers a host of utility merchandise and accessories that are compatible with customers own merchandise & help customers get more of them. While superstores D▲Mart and NEXT do not offer any unique merchandise/brand to their customers. But, D▲Mart offers complementary merchandise in some categories of merchandise like foods, toiletries & beauty merchandise, garments, bed & bath linen, kitchenware, toys & games, stationery, home appliances, baby care, footwear while NEXT offers various utility merchandise with core merchandise like utensils with Microwave Owen as complementary merchandise.

6.23 Management of unprofitable merchandise

Some organised retailers (i.e. Big Bazaar, more.MEGAStore, West Side, Max and Reliance Digital) try to find the way to convert unprofitable merchandise into profitable merchandise and then determine that whether unprofitable merchandise relates to profitable business relationships or not; if not then they drop them from the assortment. While, some organised retailers (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, D▲Mart and NEXT) do not try to find the way to make them profitable, but directly determine that whether unprofitable merchandise relates to profitable business relationships or not; if not then they drop them from the assortment. However, Big Megamart usually drops unprofitable merchandise from the assortment.

6.24 Major suppliers & discounts

Manufacturers are first major suppliers of all the organised retailers included in the study while wholesalers are second major suppliers of all the organised retailers except West Side, Max and Reliance Digital and merchandise brokers are third major suppliers of all the organised retailers except Big Megamart, Star Bazaar and D▲Mart. However, most of the organised retailers also rely on commission agents to supply international brands except Star Bazaar, Big Bazaar and D▲Mart. Moreover, Star Bazaar also gets supplies for some cooperatively & individually owned offices.

All the organised retailers get a trade, quantity and seasonal discounts from their suppliers. Moreover, most of the organised retailers also get promotional discounts except few (i.e. HyperCITY, Big Megamart and D▲Mart).

6.25 Important characteristics while selecting a vendor

Table 6.4: Important characteristics while selecting a vendor						
Sr. No.	Characteristics	Importance Scale*				K-S <i>D</i> value calculated
		4	3	2	1	
1.	Reliability	10	00	00	00	0.750
2.	Price-quality	10	00	00	00	0.750
3.	Order-processing time	08	02	00	00	0.550
4.	Exclusive rights	01	02	05	02	0.050
5.	Functions provided	03	05	02	00	0.300
6.	Information	03	06	01	00	0.400
7.	Ethics	03	05	02	00	0.300
8.	Guarantee	08	02	00	00	0.500
9.	Credit	02	03	05	00	0.250
10.	Long-term relationship	08	02	00	00	0.550
11.	Reorders	08	02	00	00	0.550
12.	Markup	03	03	04	00	0.250
13.	Innovativeness	08	01	01	00	0.550
14.	Local advertising	03	03	04	00	0.250
15.	Investment	01	04	05	00	0.250
16.	Risk	03	05	02	00	0.300
* 4- extremely important, 3- important, 2- partially important, 1- not important						
Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) <i>D</i> value tabulated = 0.410; Level of significance (α) = 5 % (0.05)						

Reliability and price-quality are extremely important characteristics for all the organised retailers while selecting a vendor. Apart from reliability and price-quality, for HyperCITY, information, credit, long-term relationship, reorders, markup, investment and risk are extremely important characteristics; order-processing time, functions provided, ethics, guarantee, innovativeness and local advertising are important characteristics while exclusive rights are partially important characteristics of a vendor for selection. For Star Bazaar, order-processing time, long-term relationship, reorders, and innovativeness, are extremely important characteristics; functions provided, information, ethics, guarantee, markup, risk and local advertising are important characteristics while exclusive rights, credit and investment are partially important characteristics of a vendor for selection.

Order processing time, information, guarantee, long-term relationship and innovativeness are extremely important characteristics; functions provided, ethics, credit, reorders and local advertising are important characteristics while exclusive

rights, markup, investment and risk are partially important characteristics for more.MEGASStore to select a vendor. While, for Big Bazaar, order-processing time, ethics, guarantee, long-term relationship and innovativeness are extremely important characteristics; functions provided, information and reorders are important characteristics while credit, markup, local advertising, investment and risk are partially important characteristics and exclusive right is not important characteristics of a vendor to be selected. However, credit, reorders, markup and local advertising are extremely important characteristics; order processing time, functions provided, information, guarantee, long-term relationship, investment, risk are important characteristics; ethics and innovativeness are partially important characteristics and exclusive rights is not important characteristics for D-Mart while selecting a vendor.

Fashion hyper store organised retailer, i.e. Big Magamart pays importance to order-processing time, ethics, guarantee, reorders, markup, innovativeness and risk extreme level; while to information, credit, long-term relationship and investment are important levels and to exclusive rights, functions provided, local advertising at partial level in order to select a vendor. While, order-processing time, exclusive rights, functions provided, information, ethics, guarantee, long-term relationship, reorders, innovativeness and risk are extremely important characteristics; markup and investment are important characteristics while credit and local advertising are partially important characteristics for fashion based superstore West Side while selecting a vendor.

And for another fashion-based superstore organised retailer, i.e. Max, order-processing time, guarantee, long-term relationship, reorders and innovativeness are extremely important characteristics; exclusive rights, ethics, and risk are important characteristics while functions provided, information, credit markup, local advertising and investment are partially important characteristics of a vendor for selection.

Superstore based electronics-item organised retailers (i.e. Reliance Digital and NEXT) give importance to different characteristics in this manner. For Reliance Digital, order-processing time, functions provided, guarantee, long-term relationship, reorders, innovativeness and local advertising are extremely important characteristics; exclusive rights, information, ethics and risk are important characteristics while credit, markup and investment are partially important characteristics while selecting a

vendor. For NEXT, order-processing time, functions provided, guarantee, long-term relationship, innovativeness and local advertising are extremely important characteristics; information, credit, reorders, markup, investment and risk are important characteristics while exclusive rights and ethics are partially important characteristics of a vendor for selection.

6.26 Collaborate (partner) relationship management (PRM)

All the hyper & super store organised retailers show a keen interest in collaborate (partner) relationship management. They pay attention to maintaining the long-lasting relationship with all their partners, especially suppliers/vendors.

6.27 Stock planning

All the organised retailers prefer weekly and monthly stock planning of merchandise. However, multi-format organised retailers (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASTore, Big Bazaar and D-Mart) do daily planning in case of perishable merchandise, frozen, vegetables, fruits, other farm merchandise, non-vegetables, etc. Moreover, Max also does quarterly planning for the stock as they make available different merchandise as per the different season.

6.28 Pricing objectives and approaches

Most of the organised retailers included in the study (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, D-Mart, Max, Reliance Digital and NEXT) adopts *maximising market share* as pricing objective. HyperCITY offers the guarantee of the best price & claims that find a lower price elsewhere & they will double the difference in the case of branded consumer durables, home entertainment & technology merchandise. They also offer the best price & a quality guarantee in case of fruits & vegetables in order to achieve pricing objective. Star Bazaar offers more than 30000 merchandise in different of the merchandise categories with great quality and great price; moreover modern shopping environment backed by the strong value of TATA for achieving pricing objective. Max offers international fashion merchandise at affordable prices while Reliance Digital offers the widest & the latest range of merchandise at the lowest price guaranteed and NEXT offers merchandise & services at affordable price in order to be the market leader in the field of value retailing.

Other organised retailers (i.e. more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar, Big Megamart and West Side) adopt *merchandise quality leadership* as a pricing objective. more.MEGASStore offers great quality merchandise & services with everyday lowest prices guaranteed while Big Megamart offers mega brands which are known for their quality in order to be the merchandise quality leader in the market. Big Bazaar offers merchandise & services with price & quality guarantee to achieve the pricing objective. Quality guarantee explains that all merchandise are sold at Big Bazaar are guaranteed to be at the best price & of good quality. Price guarantee explains that if within two days of purchase customers find a merchandise of the same brand, the quality level at lesser price return it within a day along with cash memo & Big Bazaar will double the value of the price difference. In order to achieve pricing objective, West Side introduced the policy to satisfy their customer with quality & value of the merchandise. Further, they offer return guarantee, if there is any quality grievance in order to merchandise quality leader in the field of fashion retailing.

Most of the organised retailers included in the study use *leadership-oriented pricing approach* except Big Megamart, D-Mart, West Side and NEXT as they use *cost-oriented pricing approach* in order to price the merchandise.

6.29 Pricing strategy

High-low pricing strategy (a form of value pricing strategy) is the most popular pricing strategy among organised retailers and adopted by HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, D-Mart, Big Megamart and NEXT while more.MEGASStore and Big Bazaar adopt another form of value pricing strategy i.e. *everyday low pricing strategy*. However, *perceived value-pricing strategy* is also popular among superstore organised retailers (i.e. West Side, Max and Reliance Digital) in order to keep a promise to provide customers well-differenced value & experience in their stores.

6.30 Price-adjustment strategy

Discount & allowance pricing (reducing the prices to reward customer responses), *psychological pricing* (adjusting prices for psychological effects) and *promotional pricing* (temporarily reducing the prices) are most common price-adjustment strategies among all the hyper & super store organised retailers and adopted by all of them in order to adjust or reduce the price of the merchandise and

services. However, all these organised retailers also adopt a *segmented pricing strategy* (adjusting the price to allow for the difference in customers, merchandise or locations) except D-Mart. Moreover, some organised retailers (i.e. Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar, West Side, Max and Reliance Digital) also opt *dynamic pricing strategy* (adjusting prices continually to meet the characteristics and needs of individual customers and situations).

6.31 Tactics followed to fight Price war

Value added retailing is most preferred tactics by all the organised retailers except D-Mart and NEXT as they follow to *maintain and grow* tactics to fight a price war. HyperCITY adds value by offering unmatched value (price-quality) merchandise & services while Star Bazaar, by offering great quality with the great price of the merchandise to their customers. more.MEGASStore enhances the value by offering great quality with an unbelievable price to their customers while Big Bazaar, by offering merchandise with price & quality guaranteed to the target market.

Big Megamart adds the value by offering best quality while West Side by offering best-in-class merchandise & services at affordable price to their customers. Max enhances the value by the constant focus to develop the best merchandise & value offered to their customers while Reliance Digital follows the customer value proposition strategy in order to ensure value added retailing.

6.32 Customer response before Price change

No organised retailers take concern of customer before changing the price of merchandise & services, but all these retailers take the response of customers through feedback and consider for the future course of action except D-Mart and NEXT. Even, D-Mart and NEXT do not take feedback to know the response of the customers after the price change.

6.33 Price charged & maximum retail price (MRP)

HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar, Max and Reliance Digital always charge less than the MRP of most of the merchandise due to leadership-oriented approach, but some merchandise are still sold at MRP. While Big Megamart, D-Mart, West Side and NEXT charge less than the MRP on most of the

merchandise, but due to cost-oriented approach, they charge equal to MRP to recover the margin on the merchandise.

6.34 Methods to develop brand image & customer loyalty (promotional strategy)

HyperCITY, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar and Reliance Digital appeal to *reason*; Star Bazaar, D⁺Mart, Max and NEXT appeal to *emotion* while Big Megamart and West Side appeal to *sense* in order to create a brand image among targeted customers. All the organised retailers use advertising, sales promotion, direct retailing, personal retailing, public relation / publicity and internet / interactive retailing methods for developing brand image and customer loyalty among existing & potential customers.

6.34.1 Advertising

All the organised retailers do both indoor (in-store) as well as outdoors (out-store) advertising.

Indoor (in-store) Advertising

All the organised retailers included in the study use visual display, signage, point of purchase material, secondary packaging, and cross promotion methods of in-store advertising. However, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar and Reliance Digital also use pamphlets, while Big Megamart, HyperCITY, Big Bazaar and Max do loud speaker announcement about various discounts & schemes for the day in order to advertise. Moreover, Big Megamart, Big Bazaar and Reliance Digital also use electronic signage to advertise within the store.

Outdoor (out-store) advertising

Yellow page advertising is first while the newspaper and hoardings advertising are second most preferred modes of outdoor advertising among all the organised retailers, except Star Bazaar. Moreover, online advertising is also a common method adopted by organised retailers except Big Megamart, HyperCITY and D⁺Mart. However, Big Megamart, Big Bazaar, D⁺Mart, West Side, Max and Reliance Digital also advertise in magazines & journals. Some other methods of outdoor advertising are also used by organised

retailers i.e. television ads by Big Bazaar, West Side, Max and Reliance Digital; radio ads by Big Bazaar, D-Mart and Reliance Digital; pamphlets / propaganda by HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and NEXT; LCD screening by Big Megamart, Big Bazaar and Reliance Digital; wall paintings by D-Mart, Max and Reliance Digital; fair & exhibitions by Max and cinema advertising by Big Bazaar.

Advertising Budget

No retail store's management has provided information in this regard as it is not planned at store level. However, all the organised retailers spend less on advertising in comparison to any other industry especially outdoor advertising. Some organised retailers (i.e. Big Megamart, HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, D-Mart and NEXT) spend less in comparison to others organised retailers included in the study.

6.34.2 Sales Promotions

Schemes, gifts, rebates, discounts, loyalty programs, premiums, prizes, rewards and contests are some popular tools opted by all the organised retailers included in the study. However, some organised retailers i.e. Big Megamart, HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and Big Bazaar also provide a free sample as an integral part of the sales promotion.

Schemes

Buy & get free, bulk purchase discount, value / combo pack (offer) discount / deal, percentage off (discount) on MRP, up to percentage price off, flat percentage off / discount, price (₹) off / discounts, buy more and pay less (get more), flat price, starting at ₹, only / just for ₹, save ₹, ₹ onward / approx, fixed price scheme, ₹ to ₹, limited offer, offer / deal of the day or today's offer, store (our) price and special offer schemes are some common sales promotion schemes introduced by all the organised retailers. However, these organised retailers also introduced a membership scheme and exclusive schemes for customers who wish to enrol for membership except D-Mart in order to create some loyal customer base.

Moreover, hyper stores like HyperCITY introduces schemes like additional percentage off for Discovery Club Members and buy and get a percentage off schemes while Star Bazaar, weekly shopping scheme, best buys of the week schemes, *Wow Wednesday* - A Exclusive schemes for members, best price schemes, seasonal special schemes, weekend (Saturday & Sunday) offer schemes, mega offers schemes as additional sales promotion schemes. Monthly shopping (saving), best buys of the month, weekly shopping, the offer of the week, best price, super offer, best buys and offer price are some common sales promotion schemes among more.MEGASStore and Big Bazaar. However, more.MEGASStore also introduces schemes like club deals scheme, everyday lowest prices guaranteed scheme, Special occasion (March Mela) scheme, introductory price scheme, compare & save scheme, smart shopper scheme, goodbye MRP scheme (minimum 5% discount for members on selected merchandise), mega buy scheme, more value scheme, cash back offer scheme while Big Bazaar, lowest price scheme, Sabse Saste 5 Din scheme, public holiday sale scheme, the great exchange scheme, percentage extra discount scheme, exchange price scheme, Wednesday Bazaar – Hafte ka sabse sasta din scheme, Bachat Bazaar scheme, great discount scheme, never before price scheme, fashion weekend dhamaka scheme. Free item + Percentage price discount scheme and 2 % assured discount on all private-label brands are other sales promotion schemes introduced by D⁺Mart.

Fashion based organised retailers like Big Megamart introduces buy and get a percentage off scheme, value price scheme while West Side, up to percentage off sale schemes, sale schemes, additional 5 % discount for *ClubWest Gold Card Members* scheme, additional 5 % discount on ICICI Bank credit & debit card scheme (on purchase of 5000 & more, maximum discount ₹ 500) and Max, end of season sale scheme, hot deals scheme, best buy scheme, shop & get gift voucher, shop & get free gift scheme as additional sales promotion schemes.

Electronics-item organised retailers like Reliance Digital introduces saving percentage scheme, best seller scheme, top deals scheme, freebie offer

scheme, Monsoon offer scheme, the greatest mismatch exchange sale scheme, easy EMI scheme while NEXT, assured gift scheme, best price scheme, lowest ever price scheme, lowest price guaranteed scheme and easy EMI scheme as additional sales promotion schemes.

Free Samples

Providing free samples to the customers is not so much popular sales promotion technique among organised retailers. However, some organised retailers (i.e. Big Megamart, HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and Big Bazaar) provide a free sample. Big Megamart provides free samples in some fashion merchandise like perfumes, beauty merchandise, etc. while HyperCITY, in some categories like beauty & personal care. Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and Big Bazaar provide free samples of some merchandise in categories like grocery, FMCG etc.

Gifts

All the organised retailer included in the study give free gifts on the purchase of specific items, assured gifts and premiums to their customers while promotion like West Side gives a free gift on purchase of ₹ 1000 & above of cosmetics. Max gives free gold plated earrings' set worth ₹ 195 for shopping of ₹ 1200 & above and assured gift & premiums like shop for ₹ 1999 & get a Max gift voucher. Reliance Digital gives free microwave-safe utensils on the shopping of Reconnect Microwave Owen. **more.MEGASStore** gives free gifts on the purchase of specific items (Brooke Brand Red Label Natural care 50 gm on the purchase of Brooke Brand Red Label 250 gm; Glucose D 100 gm on the purchase of Complain Chocolate 500 gm; Safola Gold 1 lt. pp on the purchase of Safola Gold 5 lt. Jar; Pedigree Denta Stick on the purchase of Pedigree 1.5 Kg and assured gift & premiums like Casserole of ₹ 200 on the purchase of ₹ 2000 & more for members. Big Bazaar gives free gifts on the purchase of specific items and assured gift like shop for ₹ 499, get great prizes.

While some organised retailers (i.e. more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar, West Side, Reliance Digital and NEXT) provide gift hampers on special occasions like Ganesh Chaurthi and Krishna Janmashtami etc. to their customers while promoting.

Rebates & Discounts

All the organised retailers offer bulk purchase discount, value-pack (combo-pack) discount / bundle offer discount, discounts on the purchase of specific items, vouchers and coupons to their customers in order to promote sales. West Side offers gift vouchers in the denomination of ₹ 1000, 500, 100, 50 and a gift card can only be used when loaded with a minimum value of ₹ 250/-. Max offers gift vouchers in convenient denominations of ₹ 100, ₹ 250, ₹ 500, ₹ 1000, ₹ 2000 and ₹ 5000 to their customers. Reliance Digital offers gift vouchers in denominations of ₹ 500 to ₹ 10000 and coupons (like 10 % discount coupon for resQ range of accessories, ₹ 250 discount on labour charges, One free preventive maintenance service, 10 % discount on purchase of RCP for any other merchandise, 15 % discount on renewal of the RCP) to their customers. NEXT offers gift vouchers in denominations of ₹ 500 to ₹ 10000 to their customers. Big Bazaar offers vouchers in the denomination of ₹ 100 to 2000 & coupons to their customers to promote the sale.

Moreover, some organised retailers (i.e. Big Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, Reliance Digital and NEXT) also offer the EMI facility to their customers in order to promote sales. HyperCITY offers EMI facility on furniture & electronics items to their customers while Star Bazaar offers EMI facility on durables to their customers. Big Bazaar offers EMI facility through Capital First, while more.MEGASStore offers EMI facility on electronics merchandise such as: Audio & Video and Large White Appliance. Reliance Digital offers EMI facility through Bajaj FinancerV on a credit card, HDFC, City, ICICI, Kotak, Axis HSBC credit card while NEXT offers EMI facility through credit card.

Contests and other activities

HyperCITY organises holiday's activities like Janmashtami, Ganpati Bappa Morya and contests like Ganesh Chaturthi contests for the customers to promote sales while Star Bazaar organises fun activities for the whole family to attract the customers. more.MEGAStore conducts lucky draws like Tata Indica lucky draw, Sweepstakes, holiday activities and contests (name their mascot contest to promote sales among customers. While, Big Bazaar organises lucky draws like bumper draw prizes, sweepstakes, holiday activities like Big Bazaar the great kitchen awards, great Indian kitchen festival and contests (back to school contest, India's most stylist home contests, cricket contest in order to promote sales among customers. While, D Mart does not organise contests to attract the customers.

Fashion-item organised retailers e.g. Big Megamart (a hyper store) organises lucky draws and fashion shows in order to promote sales among customers. While superstore organised retailers like West Side organised in association with KGAF hosted chef Vikas from Sanchos demonstrated easy Mexican cooking for Mumbai Janta!, GourmetWest in association with a Kala Ghoda arts festival brings an event on food with culinary experts in the varied fields! Max organises fashion shows, Max fashion icon contest, Max little icon contest, Max femina miss fashion icon contest, Max Manson cover girl contest, Max kids festivals, Max fluent your style contest, Max Indian kids fashion week, Max corporate style checks contest, Max colour crazy mania contests to promote sales.

While Superstore based electronics-item organised retailers as Reliance Digital organises games & activities, holiday activities and film star are invited and the Maha mismatch exchange festival while NEXT organises lucky draws, sweepstakes, holiday activities and contests in order to promote sales among the customers.

Customer loyalty programs, premiums, prize & reward

All the organised retailers included in the study introduce membership as a part of loyalty programs in order to provide premiums, prizes and rewards to their customers.

Multi-format hyper stores like HyperCITY offers the *discovery club membership card* for their loyal customers. This card & membership facility can be availed free of cost. Members will get discovery points on the purchase of specific items. 1 discovery point = ₹ 1, these points are redeemable on the next or further purchasing. If discovery club member will shop of worth ₹ 3000/- & more with Axis Bank credit card/ debit card, customer/member will get additional 5% cash back and 10 % point back, while, Star Bazaar offers a *club card program* for their loyal customers. This program offers membership facility to their loyal customers, which can be availed free of cost. Members will get club card points on purchasing. ₹ 200 = 1 Club Card point = ₹ 1, these points are redeemable on the next or further purchasing. Special privileges for Club Card Members on Wednesday, double club card points for all your shopping and special offers for club card members.

more.MEGASTore offers *clubmore. a membership program* for their loyal customers to SHOP more, SAVE more and EARN more. This program offers membership facility to their loyal customers, which can be availed free of cost. 'clubmore.' the membership card is valid for a lifetime. Every ₹ 100 worth purchase will give 10 reward points. At 500 reward points, members can redeem them and 1 point = 5 paisa. The points are valid for 2 years. The card can be used at any store of more. As other benefits, customers can enjoy a range of exclusive promotion & offers, get details on the latest clubmore. Events & news, get mouthwatering recipes, sparkling home care tips, special benefits besides the regular offers & promotions, SMS alerts and emails regarding special offers on merchandise & services, special clubmore. member section at more. store, members can know their points by SMS more<space><clubmore.card no.> to 565070 and alternatively members can also login to <http://clubmore.morestore.com>. These benefits are subject to change by time to time. While, Big Bazaar introduces membership program by offering *payback card & profit club card* for their loyal customers. Payback card is free of cost and valid for a lifetime. Every ₹ 40 worth purchase will give 1 reward points and 200 points = ₹ 40. As other benefits, customers can enjoy a benefit from exclusive as well as bonus point offers, attractive possibilities to redeem your points. Profit club card is one type of fixed deposit

with guaranteed rebate paid service (at ₹ 100), by which customers can pay ₹ 10000 and they will get the value card of ₹ 12000. Members can use up to ₹ 1000 for shopping per month. A card will be valid for 18 months. These benefits are subject to change by time to time. Nevertheless, multi-format superstore D-Mart does not introduce customer loyalty programs, which is quite unexpected in the contemporary retailing scenario.

Fashion-item organised retailers as Big Megamart introduces *smart one card* for their loyal customers. This card facility can be availed by making purchases of ₹ 1500 on a single invoice and get 26 % additional discount on regular purchase and flat 50 % discount on your birthday. West Side has introduced *clubWest membership program* for their loyal customers. ClubWest is a two-tier program, which consists clubWest classic and clubWest gold. A purchase of ₹ 2000/- on the same day entitles customers to a complimentary membership into a clubWest classic. Alternatively, customers can enrol by paying a nominal one-time fee of ₹ 150/- & avail ₹ 100 vouchers. For classic members ₹ 100 = 1 reward point = ₹ 1 at the time of redemption. While a purchase of ₹ 5000/- on the same day entitles customers to a complimentary membership into clubWest gold. For gold members ₹ 80 = 1 reward point = ₹ 1 at the time of redemption. Reward points can be viewed by logging on to www.mywestside.com. Other advantages of membership are dedicated clubWest desk for a member's assistance at each of the stores, Exclusive shopping hours only for members during sales, unprecedented access to a host of privileges and services through our exclusive tie-ups from time to time, advance intimation of all in-store promotions and special offers through direct mailers, special offers during promotions, gift vouchers from time to time, special birthday offer, get invited through special events & previews, year-round discount at selected premium restaurant and special offers from their partners. These benefits are subject to change by time to time. HSBC West Side credit card – Customer can enjoy shopping advantages like 4 reward points for every ₹ 100 spent at West Side, complimentary gift vouchers, priority billing counters, home delivery of altered garments and exclusive sale previews.

Max introduces *The Inner Circle card program* for their loyal customers. This program offers membership facility to their loyal customers, which can be availed free of cost. ‘The Inner Circle’ membership card has a lifetime validity. But, if a member in Silver tier does not shop for 12 months, the membership may be deactivated. Even, the member wishes to reactivate the membership, a fee of ₹ 200 will be levied. *The Inner Circle membership program* is a three-tire program, i.e. Silver, Gold and Platinum. If any customer spends below ₹ 15000/- will be eligible for Silver Card, between ₹ 15000 to ₹ 6499/- will be eligible for Gold card and above ₹ 65000/- will be eligible for a Platinum card. Cardholders will get 2 reward points on the purchase of ₹ 100, exclusive promotions for them, off the sale preview, out of the store offers (at other Landmark companies) are some common benefits of the cards but gold & a platinum card holder will get 100 & 300 birthday bonus points.

While Superstore based electronics-item organised retailers like Reliance Digital introduces a *RelianceOne card membership program* for their loyal customers. This program offers membership facility to their loyal customers, which can be availed free of cost. ‘*RelianceOne*’ membership card is valid for a lifetime. If any customer shops for ₹ 100, the customer will get 70 paisa back in his/her account, this money can be used for purchasing at any reliance store. Members also get lifetime reward point’s validity, monthly account e-mail updates, special offer updates via SMS and E-mails, festive & monthly promotion catalogue. These benefits are subject to change by time to time. NEXT introduces *My Card membership program* for their loyal customers. This program offers membership facility to their loyal customers, which can be availed free of cost. ‘My Card’ membership card is valid for a lifetime. If any customer shops for ₹ 100, the customer will get 1 reward point which is equal to ₹ 1, these points can be redeemed for purchasing at any NEXT store.

Table 6.5: Impact of sales promotion						
Sr. No.	Statements	Agreement Scale*				K-S D value calculated
		4	3	2	1	

1.	Sales Promotions influence customer purchase intention.	05	05	00	00	0.500
2.	Sales Promotions increase customer satisfaction level.	00	00	07	03	0.050
3.	Sales Promotions affect the frequency to visit the outlet.	04	03	02	01	0.200
4.	Sales Promotions play a vital role to spend more.	02	05	02	01	0.200
5.	Sales Promotions entice to repurchase.	00	00	03	07	-0.250
6.	Customers purchase more quantity due to sales promotion.	03	04	02	01	0.200
7.	Your store does adequate sales promotion activities.	07	03	00	00	0.500
8.	Your store justifies its punch line.	10	00	00	00	0.750
* 4- extremely agree, 3- agree, 2- partially agree, 1- not agree						
Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) <i>D</i> value tabulated = 0.410; Level of significance (α) = 5 % (0.05)						

6.34.3 Direct Retailing

Direct emails and mail order catalogues are most common direct retailing techniques adopted by all the organised retailers except Big Megamart. While SMS retailing is also most adopted direct retailing technique among organised retailers except Star Bazaar. The customer can SMS WS<Space><City Name> to 5676714 to know about great offers and promotions at West Side and MF<City Name> to 56070 to know about nearer store, great offers and promotions at Max. However, some organised retailers (i.e. HyperCITY, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar, Reliance Digital and NEXT) are also involved in tele-retailing / mobile retailing form of direct retailing.

6.34.4 Personal Retailing

All the organised retailers (included in the study) adopt the face-to-face retailing technique of personal retailing within the store.

6.34.5 Public Relation/Publicity

Corporate brochures, annual reports, press release, press conferences, video press conferences are some most common medium to maintain relation with public and adopted by all the organised retailers. An internet release is also a preferred medium for publicity and adopted by all the organised retailers except D▲Mart. Some organised retailers i.e. Big Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, Reliance Digital and D▲Mart use posters to make publicity.

Some organised retailers (i.e. HyperCITY, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar, West Side, Max and Reliance Digital) organise and sponsor special events. HyperCITY organises Ganesh Chaturthi Contests, Janmashtami, Ganpati Bappa Morya as special events while more.MEGASStore organises fruit art activity. Big Bazaar organises cricket contest while Reliance Digital organises events and calls

celebrities i.e. Saif Ali Khan, Kareena Kapoor, Ranveer Singh, John Abraham, Arjun Kapoor, Parneeti Chopra, Priyanka Chopra, Shahid Kapoor, Bipasha Bashu, Emraan Hashmi, Esha Gupta and so on...

Fashion superstore organised retailers as West Side conducts special events like *Light a Diya - Help a Child* – Purchase a Diya and Light it at Westside during the Diwali Promotion. The fund collected is donated to NGOs to bring smiles to the faces of underprivileged children and *Angels Tree* – Purchase a “Silver Star” or a “Gold Star” during our Christmas Promotion, and decorate our Angels Tree. The money collected is donated to various NGOs across the country working with underprivileged children. Max is a fashion partner in Ponds Femina Miss India 2013 and Max was a fashion partner in the Cosmopolitan Fun fearless female & male Award 2012 as special events and sponsorship in order to publicity.

Some multi-format organised retailers (i.e. HyperCITY, Big Bazaar, more.MEGASTore) and fashion-item organised retailers (i.e. Big Megamart, West Side, Max) conduct social events & social development programmes for publicity. HyperCITY conducts social development programmes in association with Sathi Foundation, org, blood donation camp in HyperCITY July 16, 2012, collaboration with Nanhi Kali, a well-known girl NGO, HyperCITY associates with Childline India Foundation. Big Bazaar organises social events like The Great Indian Kitchen Awards, International Yoga week. More.MEGASTore organises social events like craft workshops.

Fashion superstore organised retailers as West Side organises social development programs like *Dil Se Dejiye Das Rupees* – They ask to add just ₹ 10 to the bill of their customers to help & treat underprivileged cancer patients at the *Tata medical centre, Kolkata*; www.tmckolkata.com while Max organises social events and social development programs like *LIFE Trust* (an NGO) to introduce various programs at the school and pre-school level to improve the quality and accountability of the educational system for the underprivileged children, *beat diabetes campaign*, *Max wildlife campaign*, and *other programs* like - blood donation drives, clothes

donation drive, go green - an effort to save the environment, Max participated in the Sunfeast Marathon 2010 for publicity among public.

6.34.6 Internet/Interactive Retailing

All the organised retailers (included in the study) prefer e-mails and websites as interactive retailing tools in order to create a brand image. Multi-format organised retailers as HyperCITY's e-mail id is feedback@hypercityindia.com and website is www.hypercityindia.com; Star Bazaar's e-mail id is starhelp@trent-tata.com and website is <https://www.starbazaarindia.com>; more.MEGASTore's e-mail ids are contactus@morestore.com and feedback@morestore.com and the website is www.morestore.com; while Big Bazaar's e-mail ids are csd.bb@futuregroup.com and writeus@fvrl.in and website is www.bigbazaar.com and D⁺Mart's e-mail id is suggestion@dmartindia.com and website is www.dmartindia.com. Fashion based organised retailers i.e. Big Megamart's e-mail id is customercaremegamart@arvindbrands.com and website is <http://megamartstores.com>; West Side's e-mail id is mywestside@trent-tata.com and website is <http://www.mywestside.com> while Max's e-mail id is customercare@maxretailstores.com and website is www.maxfashionindia.com. Electronics based organised retailers i.e. Reliance Digital's e-mail id is reliancedigital@ril.com, customersupport@resq.in and website is www.reliancedigital.in while NEXT's e-mail id is customercare@next.co.in and website is www.next.co.in.

Use of social networking sites is also popular among all the organised retailers except D⁺Mart to create a brand image. Multi-format hyper store organised retailers as HyperCITY uses Facebook (www.facebook.com/HyperCITY), twitter (www.twitter.com/HyperCITYindia) & YouTube (www.youtube.com/hypercityindia); Star Bazaar also uses Facebook (www.facebook.com/starbazaarindia), twitter (www.twitter.com/starbazaarindia) and YouTube (www.youtube.com/starbazaarindia) social networking sites; while more.MEGASTore and Big Bazaar use only Facebook i.e. respectively www.facebook.com/morestore and www.facebook.com/BigBazaar. Fashion based superstore organised retailers i.e. Big Megamart uses Facebook (<https://www.facebook.com/BigMegamartDapodi>), twitter

(www.twitter.com/BigMegamartDapodi) and YouTube (www.youtube.com/BigMegamartDapodi), West Side uses only Facebook (www.facebook.com/westsidefanpage) while Max uses Facebook (www.facebook.com/maxfashion), twitter (www.twitter.com/maxfashion), YouTube (www.youtube.com/maxfashionindia), flicker (www.flickr.com/maxfashionindia), and Pinterest (www.pinterest.com/maxfashionindia) as social networking sites. Electronic based superstore organised retailers i.e. Reliance Digital uses Facebook (www.facebook.com/reliancedigital), twitter (<https://twitter.com/reliancedigital>), YouTube (www.youtube.com/user/reliancedigitaltimes), and foursquare (www.foursquare.com/reliancedigital) while NEXT uses Facebook (www.facebook.com/next.co.in?sk=wall), twitter (www.twitter.com/next_retail), and YouTube (www.youtube.com/nextretail) as social networking sites to create a brand image.

Online feedback is also a popular tool of interactive retailing among all the organised retailers except Big Megamart and West Side. Moreover, electronics super store organised retailers (i.e. Reliance Digital and NEXT) take online feedback on Facebook. However, some organised retailers (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar and Max) use online discussion forum while Superstore based electronics-item organised retailers use e-pay as interactive retailing tools to create a brand image among customers.

6.35 Celebrity services for promotions

Use of celebrity services is not so popular among organised retailers. However, Big Bazaar used the services of actors (Hussain), actresses (Asin) and cricketers like MS Dhoni (Indian Cricket Team), Irfan Pathan, Mohd. Kaif, Parthiv Patel, Murli Kartik for promotion. Reliance Digital calls actors and actresses like Saif Ali Khan, Kareena Kapoor, Ranveer Singh, John Abraham, Arjun Kapoor, Parneeti Chopra, Priyanka Chopra, Shahid Kapoor, Bipasha Bashu, Emraan Hashmi, Esha Gupta and so on... to visit their store as part of a promotion.

Fashion-item organised retailers i.e. Big Megamart, West Side and Max use celebrity services for promotions. Big Megamart uses the services of models for the

promotion of their brands at fashion shows, while, West Side and Max use services of models, actors and actresses in TV commercials.

6.36 Tag line and logo

All the organised retailers use customer-centric tagline except HyperCITY, West Side, Reliance Digital and NEXT as these use store-centric tagline.

Star Bazaar uses customer-centric tagline, i.e. HELPING YOU SPEND LESS!

more.MEGASTore uses customer-centric tagline, i.e. Hamesha Extra.

Big Bazaar uses customer-centric tagline, i.e. Naye India Ka Bazaar.

D▲Mart uses customer-centric tagline, i.e. Daily Discounts Daily Savings...!!!

Big Megamart uses customer-centric tagline, i.e. *Love brands. Love values.*

Max uses customer-centric tagline, i.e. *Look good. Feel good.*

HyperCITY uses store-centric tagline, i.e Big store. Big savings.

West Side uses store-centric tagline, i.e. Endless Possibilities

Reliance Digital uses store-centric tagline, i.e. Happiness in store

NEXT uses store-centric tagline, i.e. Best Brands. Best Bargains.

6.37 Location preference

Main street locations are most preferred locations by all the organised retailers except Big Megamart and HyperCITY, as they prefer inner city locations in order to open their stores. However, Max prefers both types of locations. All the organised retailers open their store in shopping malls/shopping centres and strip centres except HyperCITY and D▲Mart as HyperCITY prefers only shopping malls/shopping centres while D▲Mart prefers strip centres. Moreover, fashion-item superstores i.e. West Side and Max also prefer to open their stores in outlet centres.

6.38 Important factors while selecting retail store location

Sr. No.	Factors	Importance Scale*				K-S D value calculated
		4	3	2	1	
1.	Population size & characteristics	06	02	02	00	0.350
a.	Total size & density	09	01	00	00	0.650
b.	Age distribution	03	05	02	00	0.300
c.	Average educational level	00	07	03	00	0.250

d.	% of residents owning homes	00	01	08	01	0.300
e.	Total disposable income	08	02	00	00	0.550
f.	Per capita disposable income	03	07	00	00	0.500
g.	Occupation distribution	00	04	06	00	0.250
h.	Trends	10	00	00	00	0.750
2. Availability of labour		01	06	02	01	0.200
a.	Management	02	08	00	00	0.500
b.	Management trainee	01	08	01	00	0.400
c.	Clerical	02	06	02	00	0.300
d.	Labour	02	06	02	00	0.300
3. Closeness to source of supply		08	02	00	00	0.550
a.	Delivery cost	10	00	00	00	0.750
b.	Timeliness	09	01	00	00	0.650
c.	No of manufacturers & wholesalers	07	03	00	00	0.500
d.	Availability & reliability of merchandise lines	10	00	00	00	0.750
4. Promotion facilities		01	03	03	03	-0.050
a.	Availability & frequency of media	02	06	02	00	0.300
b.	Costs	05	03	02	00	0.300
c.	Waste	00	04	06	00	0.250
5. Economic base		04	03	03	00	0.250
a.	Dominant industry	06	03	01	00	0.400
b.	Extant of diversification	03	04	03	00	0.250
c.	Growth projections	08	02	00	00	0.550
d.	Freedom from economic & seasonal fluctuations	06	04	00	00	0.500
e.	Availability of credit & financial facilities	01	05	04	00	0.250
6. Competitive situation		05	03	02	00	0.300
a.	No & size of existing competitors	09	01	00	00	0.650
b.	Strength & weakness of competitors	05	05	00	00	0.500
c.	Short & long run outlook	01	08	01	00	0.400
d.	Level of saturation	02	06	02	00	0.300
7. Availability of store locations		03	06	01	00	0.400
a.	No & type of locations	10	00	00	00	0.750
b.	Cost of site	09	01	00	00	0.650
c.	Access to transportation	01	08	01	00	0.400
d.	Owning Vs leasing opportunities	01	01	08	00	0.250
e.	Leasing period & conditions	01	02	07	00	0.250
f.	Visibility of site	08	02	00	00	0.550
g.	Size & shape of trading area	05	05	00	00	0.500
h.	Zoning restrictions	00	02	07	01	0.150
i.	Parking facilities	09	01	00	00	0.650
j.	Size & shape of the building	01	08	01	00	0.40
8. Regulations		00	05	04	01	0.250
a.	Taxes	04	03	03	00	0.250
b.	Licensing	05	01	04	00	0.250
c.	Operations	01	06	03	00	0.250
d.	Minimum wages	00	03	07	00	0.250
e.	Zoning	00	02	08	00	0.250
* 4- extremely important, 3- important, 2- partially important, 1- not important						
Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) <i>D</i> value tabulated = 0.410; Level of significance (α) = 5 % (0.05)						

Closeness to the source of supply is extremely important for all the organised retailers except West Side and Max, as it is important to them while selecting the store location. Population size & characteristics are extremely important for all the organised retailers except Big Bazaar, West Side, Max and Reliance Digital as for West Side and Reliance Digital, it is important while, for Big Bazaar and Max, it is partially important while selecting the store location.

Competitive situation is extremely important for all the organised retailers except West Side, Reliance Digital, NEXT, Big Megamart and HyperCITY as it is important for West Side, Reliance Digital and NEXT while partially important for Big Megamart and HyperCITY while selecting the store location. The economic base is extremely important for organised retailers i.e. Big Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, West side and Reliance Digital; important for HyperCITY, Max and NEXT while partially important for Star Bazaar, Big Megamart and D▲Mart.

Availability of store locations is an important factor for all the organised retailers except West Side, Max, Reliance Digital and HyperCITY, as it is extremely important for West Side, Max and Reliance Digital while for HyperCITY, partially important while selecting a store location. Availability of labour is also an important factor for all the organised retailers except Big Megamart, Reliance Digital, NEXT and West Side, as it is partially important for Big Megamart and Reliance Digital while not important for NEXT; however, extremely important for West Side while selecting a store location.

Promotion facilities are important factors for fashion-item organised retailers i.e. Big Megamart, West Side and Max; partially important for some multi-format organised retailers i.e. HyperCITY, Big Bazaar and D▲Mart while not important for some organised retailers i.e. Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and NEXT; however, extremely important for Reliance Digital while selecting a store location. Regulations are important for all the organised retailers except HyperCITY, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar, D▲Mart and NEXT as it is partially important for some multi-format organised retailers i.e. HyperCITY, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar and D▲Mart while not important for NEXT while selecting store locations.

6.39 Store timings

There is no uniformity among organised retailers in store timings. HyperCITY and Big Megamart open their stores between 11.00 am to 9.30 pm on all the days of the week. Star Bazaar opens its stores for 14 hours from 8.30 am to 10.30 pm on all the days of the week. more.MEGASTore opens its stores for 13 hours from 09.30 am to 10.30 pm on all the days of the week. Big Bazaar opens its stores for 12 hours from 10.30 am to 10.30 pm on all the days of the week. While, D▲Mart also opens its stores for 12 hours from 10.00 am to 10.00 pm on all the days of the week. Max opens its stores for 11 hours from 11.00 am to 10.00 pm on all the days of the week. West Side opens its stores at 11.00 am to 10.30 pm on weekdays and 11.00 am to 10.00 pm on Sunday. Reliance Digital opens its stores between 11.00 am to 10.00 pm on all the days of the week, but on Wednesday for 12 hours from 10.00 am to 10.00 pm. NEXT opens its stores between 10.00 am to 09.30 pm on all the days of the week except Monday as it is closed.

6.40 Customer service strategy

All the organised retailers included in the study adopt *patronage solidifiers* (the low-cost little things that increase loyalty, like courtesy & suggestion selling) as a customer service strategy except more.MEGASTore, Reliance Digital and NEXT as they adopt *patronage builders* (high-cost activities like transaction speed & credit).

6.41 Service provided

All the organised retailers provide free as well as paid services to their customers.

Free services

Complaints and exchange / return handling (as per the exchange / return policy of the respective retailer), packaging & gift-wrapping, information, safety of personal things, acceptance of all international credit & debit cards, personal shoppers, well maintained washrooms (ladies and gents) & drinking water, air-condition environment, lighting, music, CCTV for security, fire safety, billing counters are some common customer services provided by all the organised retailers included in the study. Moreover, all the organised retailers provide some additional customer services.

Multi-format organised retailers (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar and D-Mart) provide following additional free services:

HyperCITY provides credit facility (finance on 0 % interest, EMI on electronics and furniture items), home delivery, alteration facilities, installations, parking, baby strollers, baby-sitting, fitting (trial) room, lift & staircase facility, after sale service, demonstrations, entertainment facilities, special facilities for physically handicapped, shopping carts, warranties, loud-speaker announcements, back office support, ATM terminal, customers care service (by toll free no. 18002097172 & 18001020468) and repairing services as free services. Star Bazaar provides home delivery, alteration facilities, installations, extended store hours, parking, fitting (trial) room, escalator & staircase facility, after sale service, demonstrations, entertainment facilities, shopping carts, warranties, back office support, weight counters of loose grocery, ATM terminal, customers service desk, customer loyalty desk, eye testing service and guarantee on Star brand merchandise as free services. More.MEGASStore provides credit (easy 0 % interest EMI & spot finance facility), home delivery, cash on delivery, alteration, installation, trial purchase, phone orders, parking, baby strollers, fitting rooms, fur storage, lift, escalator & staircase facility, after sales service & support, demonstrations, entertainment facilities, special facilities for physical handicapped, customers support service centre / desk, customer helpline number service centre (08652906676), back office, shopping carts, free testing of the merchandise, free recipes on a store website, SMS facility to find out the nearest store via SMS type more(space)<yourpincode> and sent to 56070, to give feedback SMS more<fdbk><yourcomment> to 56070 as free services. Big Bazaar provides credit (easy 0 % interest EMI & spot finance facility), home delivery, cash on delivery, alteration, installation, trial purchase, phone orders, parking, baby strollers, baby-sitting, fitting rooms, fur storage, lift, escalator & staircase facility, after sales service & support, demonstrations, entertainment facilities, medical facilities, special facility for physical handicapped, exchange counter, TV sets at different places in store, back office with

warehouse, weight counter for loose grocery, idli & dosa paste grinding, loudspeaker announcement, mirrors in fashion bazaar section, loan facility, customers service desk, loyalty card desk, foreign currency exchange counter, ATM terminal, customer helpline number service centre (18002002255), shopping carts, free testing of the merchandise, free talk time for TATA Docomo mobile number (shopping of worth ₹ 400 = ₹ 10 talk time free), acceptance of meal vouchers of Sadox & Accor as free services. D▲Mart provides parking, baby Strollers, fitting (trial) room, shopping carts, warranties, loudspeaker announcements as free services.

Fashion-item organised retailers (i.e. Big Megamart, West Side and Max) provide following additional free services. Big Megamart provides alteration facilities, parking, baby Strollers, baby-sitting, Fitting (trial) room, lift, escalator and stairs facility, after sale service, demonstrations, entertainment facilities, game zones, music zone (Karaoke, etc.), special facilities for physically handicapped, shopping carts, warranties, and loudspeaker announcements as free services. West side provides home delivery of altered garments, alteration facilities, installations, staff on late hours for members, extended store hours for members, baby-sitting, Fitting (trial) room, lift, escalator & staircase facility, demonstrations, entertainment facilities, pulling shopping carts, quality assurance, mirror on every floor, good back office & management office for support, Sensormatic system (tag) for merchandise, customers service desk and easy search option facility. While, Max provides home delivery, alteration facilities, parking, fitting (trial) room, lift, escalator & staircase facility, demonstrations, entertainment facilities, pulling shopping carts, mirrors in store, Sensormatic system (tag) for merchandise, customers service associate, easy search option facility, TV sets at billing counters, loudspeaker announcement, pass of different activities where Max is sponsor, and SMS service to know the store location & reward points (SMS 'TIC' to 56767).

Superstore based electronics-item organised retailers (i.e. Reliance Digital and NEXT) provide following free additional customer services. Reliance Digital provides credit (easy EMI & spot finance facility), home

delivery, installation through resQ, parking, restroom, baby-sitting, fur storage, staircase facility, after sales service & support through resQ, demonstrations, entertainment facilities, game zone, Sensormatic system (tag) for merchandise, customer service centre/desk, home theater experience zone, customer care service centre (02267276727), my finance desk, back office, online green room service, online reliance digital solution box, maintenance & repair, specialised customer training, one stop solution for repairs of all Reconnect brands as free services. While, NEXT provides credit (easy 0 % interest EMI & spot finance facility), home delivery, cash on delivery, installation, mail & phone orders with advance payment, parking, fur storage, staircase facility, after sales service & support, demonstrations, entertainment facilities, game zone, Sensormatic system (tag) for merchandise, customers service centre/desk, customer helpline number service centre (0124-4993500), back office, free gifts, online information regarding merchandise care, 30 days replacement guarantee, 30 days change of mind policy and shopping bags as free services.

Paid services

Multi-format organised retailers (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar and D▲Mart) provide following additional free services: HyperCITY provides gift certificate (of ₹ 50, 100, 250, 500, 1000, 2000), trial purchase, special sales for regular customers, bridal registry, restaurants (food planet within the store), beauty salon (Kapil's Salon), shopping bags (₹ 1, ₹ 3 and ₹ 4 respectively, for small, medium and large plastic bags), refreshment facilities, extended warranties on electronics and durables as paid services. Star Bazaar provides special sales for regular customers, restaurants (Live Bakery, Dali), fresh grinding service (Chakki), Sodexos, shopping bags (₹ 1, ₹ 2 and ₹ 5 respectively, for small, medium and large plastic bags), refreshment facilities (Coffee Café Day, Confectionary), Tata credit card as paid services. More.MEGASStore provides gift certificates, special sales for regular customers, restaurant & refreshment facility through the live bakery, shopping bags (₹ 1, ₹ 2 and ₹ 3 respectively for small, medium and large plastic bags) and repairing as paid services. Big Bazaar provides gift certificates, special sales for regular customers, restaurants &

refreshment facility (at Foodi counter), beauty salon (Javed Habib Hair Expresso), shopping bags (₹ 1, ₹ 2, ₹ 3 and ₹ 4 respectively, for small, medium, large and extra-large plastic bags) Mehndi corner, weight-checking machines, NAVRAS – jewellery bazaar, fixed deposit with guaranteed rebate as paid services. While, D-Mart provides alteration, shopping bags (₹ 1, ₹ 2 and ₹ 3 respectively, for small, medium and large plastic bags) and refreshment facilities as paid services.

Fashion-item organised retailers (i.e. Big Megamart, West Side and Max) provide following paid services. Big Megamart provides gift certificate, trial purchase, bridal registry, restaurants, beauty salon, shopping bags (₹ 1, ₹ 4 and ₹ 6 respectively, for small, medium and large plastic bags) and refreshment facilities as paid services. West Side provides gift certificate (of ₹ 50, 100, 500, 1000 in the denomination), trial purchase, special sales for regular customers, parking, restaurants (food café, Coffee parlour, Gourmet West – food section), Shopping bags (₹ 3, ₹ 5 and ₹ 7 respectively for small, medium and large plastic bags) and refreshment facilities as paid services. While Max provides gift certificate (of ₹ 100, 250, 500, 1000, 2000 and 5000 in the denomination), special sales for regular customers, restaurants, shopping bags (₹ 3 and ₹ 5 respectively for small and large plastic bags) and refreshment facilities as paid services.

Superstore based electronics-item organised retailers (i.e. Reliance Digital and NEXT) provide following free additional customer services. Reliance Digital provides gift certificate (of ₹ 500 to 10000 in the denomination), special sales for regular customers, shopping bags (₹ 3, ₹ 6 and ₹ 11 respectively, for small, medium and large plastic bags), health checkup plan – a preventive maintenance, enhanced utility through resQ accessories and extended warranty service as paid service. NEXT provides gift certificate (of ₹ 500 to 10000 in the denomination), special sales for regular customers, maintenance & repair, extended warranty, recharge your mobile phone and DTH & pay mobile & landline bills as paid services. (Organised retailers are charging for shopping bags after February 4, 2011, as per the notification of the Ministry of Environment & Forest, government of India).

6.42 Exchange / return policy

Multi-format organised retailers (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASTore, Big Bazaar and D-Mart) offer attractive exchange & return policy.

HyperCITY is pleased to offer exchange within 14 days of your purchase on merchandise of the original cash memo. The merchandise should be unused, undamaged, in the original packaging and in saleable condition. Mobile phones, MP3 players, innerwear, swimwear, jewellery, watches, cosmetics and any altered merchandise will not be exchanged. All appliances & electronics items will be exchanged subject to the warranty & guarantee terms of the manufacturer, with a valid receipt, while furniture is not exchanged or refunded in any situation unless the item has a manufacturing issue within the first year of purchase and if it is not repairable by us once the furniture has been assembled at the customer's address. They issue credit note/s valid for 1 month from the date of issue. All credit notes must be completely used in a single transaction. All cash transactions will be refunded in the form of a credit note. Credit card transactions will be refunded back to the credit card account or credit note as per customer convenience. Under no circumstances, they issue cash refunds. In the case of loss of credit note/s, no duplicate will be issued.

Star Bazaar offer exchange within 15 days of your purchase only if sales receipt is presented along with merchandise. An exchange will be done only if merchandise is in its original packaging and in resalable condition. The refund will be done only through the exchange vouchers. No exchange on Saturday & Sunday. Fresh merchandise of bakery, fruits, vegetables, non-vegetarian, undergarments, sale items will not be exchanged. Further, they take utmost care to ensure that only the best quality merchandise are made available to their customers. However, if there is any quality defect in any Star Branded merchandise the same will be replaced with the merchandise of same value within 15 days from the date of purchase if sales receipt is presented with merchandise.

more.MEGASTore offers hassle free return & exchange policy. In case, customers change their mind, more.MEGASTore would be pleased to exchange the

same within 14 days from the date of purchase - no questions are asked if the same is in original packaging and accompanied by its invoice. In case, an exchange is not required, customers can get issued a gift card of the full value of the bill, which can be utilised within 15 days at the store as per customer convenience.

Big Bazaar guaranteed the exchange of any merchandise that customers have bought from Big Bazaar & not satisfied. Return it along with a cash memo within 7 days of purchase. Merchandise like body care, cosmetics, crockery, jewellery, soft toys, undergarments, hair accessories, CDs, pharmaceuticals, toiletries etc. will not be exchanged.

D-Mart offers no exchange & return on frozen, dairy, deodorants and seasonal merchandise, no return of gift-wrapped merchandise, 2% deduction on the purchase through debit or credit card if returned, no return on undergarments, shoes, CDs, DVDs.

Fashion-item organised retailers (i.e. Big Megamart, West Side and Max) offer exchange & return policy. Big Megamart offers to exchange any merchandise within 15 days after purchasing, and get a credit note of the same value, which will be valid for next 15 days in the same store, but non-returnable unless defective like undergarments, including socks, shoe care and foot care merchandise. Altered, used, damaged and promotional merchandise, personal electronics items like mobile phones, cameras, etc. and sunglasses, watches and writing instruments are also not returnable. Big Megamart adopts no cash refund policy.

West side has the policy to satisfy their customers with the range, quality and value of the merchandise they offer. However, if customers are dissatisfied with the product that they have bought, they take required actions to assist them. West side expects that the customers should return unused merchandise within 30 days accompanied by a bill; they would exchange the returned items or give customers a complete refund. In the event that customers do not have the receipt, West side would offer them an exchange or offer a gift card to the selling price. West side has complete confidence in the quality of the products they do offer, however if customers have any complaint, they do address. They would exchange the returned items or give

customers a complete refund. In the event that customers do not have the receipt, West side would offer them an exchange or provide them a gift voucher for the current or last known selling price. No exchange or return on watches, jewellery, earrings, sunglasses, toys, cosmetics, disc, and lingerie and undergarments.

Max values their customers and guarantees the merchandise they trade. If a customer wants to change the merchandise bought or find it low in expectation, within 15 days of purchase, their customer relation associates will be happy to assist customers in finding a replacement. However, company policy expects the presentation of the original receipt for settlement. A credit voucher will be issued in value equivalent to a replacement for use in MAX stores in the whole country within 3 months of the date of issue. The above policy excludes the following: altered garments, used merchandise, undergarments including socks, discounted merchandise.

Superstore based electronics-item organised retailers (i.e. Reliance Digital and NEXT) offer a return & exchange policy. Reliance Digital offers that if customers are not satisfied with any of the merchandise, they will be happy to accept them for return and issue a credit note subject to the following: request for return should be made within seven days of purchase. The merchandise to be returned should be in saleable condition. Invoice copy and delivery Challan in the original will be required to be submitted at the time of the request. The Credit Note issued can be used for the purchase of any other merchandise within the store within the stipulated validity period. No return of mobile phones and computers. Music, gaming & computer software will be taken back only if its packaging/seal is not broken. No return of any merchandise purchased under a promotional scheme or discount or where invoice specifically mentions "no replacements".

NEXT offers its customers a 30 days change of mind policy. If for any reason, a customer wishes to return merchandise, the customer may do so within 30 days from the date of purchase, and may opt for a refund or store credit. Please note that the merchandise should be in factory-sealed condition. All merchandise sold at NEXT are covered under our 30-day replacement guarantee policy. Notify them of any manufacturing defect in the merchandise within 30 days from the date of delivery, and they will issue a replacement to you at no extra cost. In order to return merchandise,

fill the returns form that comes with the merchandise. Return will only be accepted if: item(s) are received with their original packaging, along with the original price tags, labels, and invoices. All free gifts, warranty card, booklets, accessory packaging materials, manuals, like remote controls, cords, cables, etc., and all other items originally included with the merchandise(s) delivered are returned with the merchandise. Returned items are in resalable conditions.

6.43 Use of Gap Model

All the organised retailers (included in the study) use gap model to understand knowledge gap, standard gap, delivery gap and communication gap in order to improve customer service quality except Star Bazaar, NEXT and D Δ Mart.

6.44 Customer relationship management (CRM)

All the organised retailers (included in the study) have much inclination towards CRM except D Δ Mart as it has partial CRM. HyperCITY has separate discovery club desk / cell dedicated to the customer relationship. Star Bazaar has also a separate cell dedicated to the customer relationship. more.MEGASStore is keen to maintain customer relationship through its dedicated customer support cell while Big Bazaar, through its dedicated customer service cell and loyalty programme cell.

Fashion-item organised retailers i.e. Big Megamart maintains customer relations through its dedicated CRM cell; West Side through its clubWest cell while Max through its separate customer service cell and customer relation associates. Superstore based electronics-item organised retailers i.e. Reliance Digital takes care of CRM activities through my assist – a customer service desk while NEXT through the customer care desk.

6.45 Database for CRM

All the multi-format hyper store organised retailers (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and Big Bazaar) collect information for database regarding *customer transactions* (purchase date, price paid, merchandise purchased, responses to promoted merchandise), *customer contacts* (record of customer interaction with store by websites, inquiries in-store kiosks, telephone calls), *customer preferences* (favourite colour, brands, fabrics, flavours, and apparel size), *descriptive information* (demographic & psychographic data of customers) and *customer responses to*

marketing activity (responsiveness to sales promotion & advertising). While, multi-format superstore organised retailer, i.e. D-Mart collects information for database regarding *customer transactions* (purchase date, the price paid, merchandise purchased, and responses to promoted merchandise) only.

Fashion-item organised retailers (i.e. Big Megamart, West Side and Max) collect information for database regarding *customer transactions* (purchase date, price paid, merchandise purchased, responses to promoted merchandise), *customer contacts* (record of customer interaction with the store by websites, inquiries in-store kiosks, telephone calls), *customer preferences* (favourite colour, brands, fabrics, flavours, and apparel size) and *descriptive information* (demographic & psychographic data of customers). However, West Side also collects the information regarding *customer responses to marketing activity* (responsiveness to sales promotion & advertising).

Electronics-item organised retailers (i.e. Reliance Digital and NEXT) collect information for database regarding *customer transactions* (purchase date, price paid, merchandise purchased, responses to promoted merchandise), *customer contacts* (record of customer interaction with the store by websites, inquiries in-store kiosks, telephone calls) and *descriptive information* (demographic & psychographic data of customers).

6.46 Methods of information collection for database

All the organised retailers collect the information for the database by keeping records of the customer transactions. All these organised retailers except D-Mart also conduct the in-store survey through printed questionnaire and collect information under membership programme. Moreover, some organised retailers (i.e. more.MEGASTore, Big Bazaar, Reliance Digital and NEXT) conduct an online survey in order to collect information; while Max and Big Bazaar also collect the information by taking customer feedback & suggestions. Big Bazaar also conducts a phone survey while Big Magamart does cross-selling in order to collect information for a database as a part of CRM.

6.47 CRM programmes

All the organised retailers use following CRM programmes in order to maintain a relationship and create loyal customers.

(a) Programmes for customer retention

All the organised retailers (included in the study) introduce membership as a part of its frequent shopper program that will help them to personalise their customers and they provide special customer services (free & paid) to retain their customers except, D▲Mart as it does not pay attention to retaining their customers and do not have any customer loyalty programs.

(b) Programmes to convert satisfied customers in high lifetime value customers

All the organised retailers (included in the study) do cross-selling and add on selling in order to convert satisfied customers in high lifetime value customers except, D▲Mart as it does not take efforts to convert satisfied customers in high lifetime value customers.

(c) Programmes to deal with unprofitable customers

No organised retailers have programmes to deal with unprofitable customers.

6.48 Separate cell to help customers in the store

All the organised retailers have a separate cell (customer support cell) to help customers in store and they all use listening and responding approach, respond to the customers with a courtesy, maintain speed and accuracy of service in order to help their customers

6.49 Key customers

All the organised retailers included in the study deals with retail clientele only except, Reliance Digital, as it deals with both retail as well as corporate clientele.

6.50 Challenges while dealing with key customers

Changing the landscape of Indian consumerism, changing retail trends, changing government role, stiff competition, cultural disparity, high demand for service standards, price war are some major challenges faced by all the organised

retailers while dealing with key customers. D▲Mart also faces the problems due to no membership, no special offers for members, no customised offers and partial CRM in order to deal with key customers.

6.51 Analysis of the profitability of customer retailing relationship

All the organised retailers included in the study regularly analyse the profitability of the customer retailing relationship at the account level through department analysis of their customer relationship and through periodic review by a professional cost accountant except D▲Mart and NEXT; as they do analyse the profitability of the customer retailing relationship at the account level only through periodic review by a professional cost accountant.

6.52 e-retailing

No organised retailers included in the study provide e-retailing service to their customers except, Big Bazaar, Reliance Digital and NEXT. Big Bazaar provides e-retailing service to their customers through the group website, i.e. www.futurebazaar.com; Reliance Digital through www.reliancedigitla.in while NEXT through www.next.co.in.

6.53 Layout while planning store design

All the multi-format hyper store organised retailers (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and Big Bazaar) use a mix of free form or boutique layout & grid layout to display the merchandise while planning store design while multi-format superstore organised retailer i.e. D▲Mart uses only grid layout to display the merchandise while planning store design.

Fashion-item organised retailers (i.e. Big Megamart, West Side and Max) use the free form or boutique layout to display the merchandise while planning store design. Superstore based electronics-item organised retailers (i.e. Reliance Digital and NEXT) use racetrack layout to display the merchandise while planning store design.

6.54 Signage to locate the merchandise category

All the organised retailers included in the study use category, promotional and point of sale signage in order to locate the merchandise category in their stores.

Moreover, some organised retailers (i.e. Big Megamart, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar and Reliance Digital) also use digital signage in order to locate the merchandise category in their stores.

6.55 Methods to display the merchandise in their stores

Freestanding displays, end caps, promotional aisles, wall displays and cash wrap displays (point of purchase counters or check out areas) are most preferred methods of displaying the merchandise in their stores among all the multi-format organised retailers included in the study. Moreover, some multi-format organised retailers (i.e. HyperCITY, more.MEGASStore and Big Bazaar) also use window display and entrance display methods of displaying the merchandise in their stores.

Fashion-item organised retailers (i.e. Big Megamart, West Side and Max) use window display, entrance display, free standing display, end caps, promotional aisles and wall display methods of displaying the merchandise in their stores. Moreover, Max also uses a dressing room display method to display the merchandise.

Superstore based electronics-item organised retailers (i.e. Reliance Digital and NEXT) use entrance display, freestanding display, promotional aisles and walls display methods of displaying the merchandise in their stores. Moreover, Reliance Digital also uses a cash wrap display method to display the merchandise.

6.56 Fixtures used to display merchandise

All the multi-format organised retailers (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar and D⁺Mart) use straight racks, rounder (capacity fixture), four-way fixture (feature fixture) and gondolas to display the merchandise in stores. Fashion-item organised retailers (i.e. Big Megamart, West Side and Max) use rounder (bulk fixture/capacity fixture), four-way fixture (feature fixture) and gondolas to display the merchandise in stores. Superstore based electronics-item organised retailers (i.e. Reliance Digital and NEXT) use only straight racks and rounder (bulk fixture/capacity fixture) to display the merchandise in the stores.

6.57 Presentation techniques to present the merchandise

All the organised retailers included in the study use item & size presentation, price lining, vertical merchandising, tonnage merchandising and frontal presentation techniques to present the merchandise in the store. Moreover, some organised retailers (i.e. Star Bazaar, Big Bazaar, West Side, Max, Reliance Digital and NEXT) also use an idea-oriented presentation technique.

6.58 Variables used to create an appealing store atmosphere

Some multi-format organised retailers (i.e. HyperCITY, more.MEGASStore and Big Bazaar) use lighting, colour, scent and music in order to create an appealing store atmosphere. While, Star Bazaar uses only lighting and music to create an appealing store atmosphere. Moreover, D▲Mart uses only music to create an appealing store atmosphere. Fashion-item organised retailers (i.e. Big Megamart, West Side and Max) use lighting, colour, scent and music for creating an appealing store atmosphere. Electronics-item organised retailers (i.e. Reliance Digital and NEXT) use lighting, colour, and music to create an appealing store atmosphere.

6.59 Store design

Visual merchandising is an extremely important component of store design for all the organised retailers included in the study. Store layout is also an extremely important component of store design for all the organised retailers except Star Bazaar and NEXT as it is important to them. Moreover, interior atmospherics is an extremely important component of store design for all the organised retailers except Star Bazaar as it is important. Exterior atmospherics is also an extremely important component of store design for some organised retailers i.e. HyperCITY, Big Bazaar, West Side, Max and Reliance Digital while for others, i.e. Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, D▲Mart, Big Megamart and NEXT, it is important.

S. N.	Measurement Variables	Importance Scale*				K-S D value calculated
		4	3	2	1	
1.	Exterior atmospherics	05	05	00	00	0.500
1	Store front	04	06	00	00	0.500
2	Store marquee/sign board	07	03	00	00	0.500
3	Frontage entrance	03	06	01	00	0.400
4	External display window/space	03	03	04	00	0.250
5	Building	04	05	01	00	0.400

6	Store architecture	05	04	00	01	0.400
7	Uniqueness of store	04	03	02	01	0.200
8	Visibility of store	09	01	00	00	0.650
9	Location/site of the store	07	03	00	00	0.500
10	Parking facilities	06	04	00	00	0.500
11	Exterior look of store	03	06	00	01	0.400
12	Ease of access	03	07	00	00	0.500
13	Store name plate	04	05	01	00	0.400
14	Health & safety standards	06	03	01	00	0.400
15	Surrounding area	01	03	05	01	0.150
2. Interior atmospherics		09	01	00	00	0.650
1	Flooring & ceiling	05	04	01	00	0.400
2	Lighting	09	01	00	00	0.650
3	Odour/smell/scent	05	05	00	00	0.500
4	Fixtures	02	06	02	00	0.300
5	Wall textures	01	07	02	00	0.300
6	Sounds	08	02	00	00	0.550
7	Colour	02	06	02	00	0.300
8	Temperature	08	02	00	00	0.550
9	Cleanliness	07	03	00	00	0.500
10	Aisles	03	05	02	00	0.300
11	Trial (experience) room/zone	09	00	01	00	0.650
12	Dead area	00	05	04	01	0.150
13	Merchandise	10	00	00	00	0.750
14	Graphics	01	06	02	01	0.200
15	Store size	09	01	00	00	0.650
3. Store layout		08	02	00	00	0.550
1	Space planning	09	01	00	00	0.650
2	Floor space allocation	06	04	00	00	0.500
3	E-display	00	01	09	00	0.250
4	Department location	06	03	01	00	0.400
5	Department size	02	08	00	00	0.500
6	Department compatibility	01	06	03	00	0.250
7	Location of various merchandise	07	03	00	00	0.500
8	Accessibility to cash counters	07	02	01	00	0.450
9	Signage	08	02	00	00	0.550
10	Space/merchandise category	07	03	00	00	0.500
4. Visual merchandising		10	00	00	00	0.750
1	Assortment	10	00	00	00	0.750
2	Theme	01	08	01	00	0.400
3	Racks & shelves	05	04	01	00	0.400
4	Ensemble	01	07	02	00	0.300
5	Payment counters	09	00	01	00	0.650
6	Merchandise display	07	03	00	00	0.500
7	The planogram	06	04	00	00	0.500
8	Props & mannequins	01	08	01	00	0.400
9	Point of sale sign	08	02	00	00	0.500
10	Methods of display	08	02	00	00	0.500

* 4- extremely important, 3- important, 2- partially important, 1- not important
Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) <i>D</i> value tabulated = 0.410; Level of significance (α) = 5 % (0.05)

Especially, HyperCITY has collaborated with JHP of London for in-store design. JHP is an excellent retail designing service provider with an experience in large format stores around the globe. HyperCITY deploys a good technology enabled infrastructure from JDA that is a leading global retail technology service provider firm. The JDA suite comprises the E3 Advanced Replenishment, Merchandise Management System, WinDSS point of sale and Intactix space planning modules. The system ensures that customers do not have to wait in long queues for billing, or transaction processing for enhancing the overall customer experience at HyperCITY. Johnson Diversey is a world class & trusted the source of cleaning and hygiene merchandise and services. Since food sanitation, store hygiene, safety, etc., are important in any store, Johnson Diversey assists in improving the customer shopping experience.

6.60 Future-plans

HyperCITY wants to provide the best merchandise from around the world, intuitive store design & adherence to international standards of service to make HyperCITY an unmatched experience. Star Bazaar looks forward to having the customer over at their stores to experience first-hand their promise and commitment to be the best for their customers at all times. more.MEGASTore's wants to consistently provide the Indian consumer a complete and differentiated shopping environment and a top retailer of the India by offering superior returns to all stakeholders. Big Bazaar wants to become most admired value retailers in all the sense of retaliating for all the stakeholders. D⁺Mart wants to offer more variety of the merchandise with a lesser price to their customers. Big Megamart wants to offer mega (international) brands at surprisingly low prices and offers a retail experience of a high-end. West Side hopes to expand rapidly with similar format stores that offer a fine balance between style & price retailing. Max hopes to be a market leader in the field of value retailing; wants to provide fashionable merchandise at affordable prices and wants to be innovative, cost effective and globally competitive in order to match with exceeding customer's expectations. The Reliance Digital hopes to become

sustainable value creator for all its stakeholders. The NEXT plans to build a chain of over 1000 showrooms throughout the country with an esteemed annual turnover of ₹ 500 crores in the next 3 years.

Chapter 7

Changing buying behaviour of customers in organised retail industry

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- Analysis of profile of customers in the organised retail industry
 - Analysis of buying behaviour of customers in the organised retail industry
 - Factors influencing buying behaviour of customers in the organised retail industry

CHAPTER 7

CHANGING BUYING BEHAVIOUR OF CUSTOMERS IN THE ORGANISED RETAIL INDUSTRY

Introduction

This chapter includes an analysis of the various data pertained to customers of organised retail industry, which have been collected through the individual questionnaire from the customers of the respective organised retailers / stores in a personal interaction. This chapter encompasses the analysis of profiles of customers, changing buying behaviour and factors affecting the buying behaviour. Further, results have been interpreted and discussed to reach on some inferences at the end of the different sections. This chapter has been divided into three sub-sections as follows:

7.1 Analysis of profile of customers in the organised retail industry

7.2 Analysis of buying behaviour of customers in the organised retail industry

7.3 Factors influencing buying behaviour of customers in the organised retail industry

ANALYSIS OF PROFILE OF CUSTOMERS IN THE ORGANISED RETAIL INDUSTRY

7.1.1 Residing area of customers

Table 7.1.1: Residing area of customers						
Retailers	Residing Areas					
	Urban		Semi-urban		Rural	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
HyperCITY	125	62.50	71	35.50	4	2.00
Star Bazaar	98	49.00	80	40.00	22	11.00
more.MEGASStore	92	46.00	78	39.00	30	15.00
Big Bazaar	124	62.00	68	34.00	8	4.00
D ⁺ Mart	88	44.00	65	32.50	47	23.50
Big Megamart	137	68.50	62	31.00	1	0.50
West Side	107	53.50	81	40.50	12	6.00
Max	123	61.50	62	31.00	15	7.50
Reliance Digital	89	44.50	78	39.00	33	16.50
NEXT	75	37.50	68	34.00	57	28.50
Mean	105.80	52.90	71.30	35.65	22.90	11.45
Standard Deviation	20.466	10.233	7.409	3.705	18.669	9.335

The organised retail industry has its majority of customers from urban areas and semi-urban areas. The organised retailers (included in the study) have the customers from all the areas i.e. urban, semi-urban and rural. But, the first majority of customers of all the retailers is from urban areas and the second majority of customers are from semi-urban areas, while some of the retailers are also able to tap an enough number of customers from rural areas, e.g. NEXT and Reliance Digital (electronics-item superstores), D⁺Mart, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore (multi-format organised retailers). However, there are also few organised retailers included in the study have a poor footfall of the customers from rural areas i.e. HyperCITY and Big Bazaar (multi-format organised retailers), Big Megamart (a fashion-item hyper store), West Side and Max (fashion-item superstores). The multi-format hyper stores organised retailers

(i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar) have a poor footfall from rural areas in comparison to multi-format super-stores organised retailer (i.e. D⁺Mart).

7.1.2 Gender of customers

Retailers	Genders			
	Male		Female	
	f	%	f	%
HyperCITY	91	45.50	109	54.50
Star Bazaar	111	55.50	89	44.50
more.MEGASStore	106	53.00	94	47.00
Big Bazaar	100	50.00	100	50.00
D ⁺ Mart	130	65.00	70	35.00
Big Megamart	76	38.00	124	62.00
West Side	85	42.50	115	57.50
Max	79	39.50	121	60.50
Reliance Digital	162	81.00	38	19.00
NEXT	165	82.50	35	17.50
Mean	110.50	55.25	89.50	44.75
Standard Deviation	32.226	16.113	32.226	16.113

Organised retail industry taps the male and female customers in equal proportion; however, the footfall of male customers is more in comparison to female customers. But, few retailers (i.e. HyperCITY- a multi-format hyper store; Big Megamart- a fashion-item hyper store, West Side & Max - fashion-item superstores) have more footfalls of female customers in comparison to male customers. All the fashion-item retailers are getting more footfalls from female customers; while, the electronics-item superstores (i.e. NEXT and Reliance Digital) are getting more footfalls from male customers. The multi-format superstore (i.e. D⁺Mart) has an equal footfall from both male and female customers.

7.1.3 Age of customers

The organised retail industry is flourishing with the footfall of youth customers in the stores. Its majority of customers' age ranges from 21 to 40 years.

Retailers	Age (in years)											
	Below 21		21-30		31-40		41-50		51-60		Above 60	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
HyperCITY	16	8.00	58	29.00	71	35.50	38	19.00	10	5.00	7	3.50
Star Bazaar	12	6.00	47	23.50	68	34.00	47	23.50	16	8.00	10	5.00
more.MEGASStore	13	6.50	43	21.50	67	33.50	46	23.00	19	9.50	12	6.00
Big Bazaar	19	9.50	50	25.00	62	31.00	40	20.00	21	10.50	8	4.00
D▲Mart	8	4.00	36	18.00	72	36.00	49	24.50	28	14.00	7	3.50
Big Megamart	30	15.00	66	33.00	58	29.00	30	15.00	14	7.00	2	1.00
West Side	22	11.00	67	33.50	62	31.00	31	15.50	12	6.00	6	3.00
Max	18	9.00	62	31.00	68	34.00	32	16.00	15	7.50	5	2.50
Reliance Digital	6	3.00	35	17.50	70	35.00	55	27.50	20	10.00	14	7.00
NEXT	4	2.00	24	12.00	72	36.00	60	30.00	25	12.50	15	7.50
Mean	14.80	7.40	48.80	24.40	67.00	33.50	42.80	21.40	18.00	9.00	8.60	4.30
Standard Deviation	7.913	3.957	14.505	7.253	4.807	2.404	10.337	5.168	5.696	2.848	4.115	2.058

However, the industry is getting the footfall from the customers of all the age groups. The industry is able to tap a greater number of customers from the age group of 41 to 50 years. Some organised retailers (i.e. Big Bazaar, Big Megamart, West Side and Max) included in the study are able to tap the customers from the age group of below 21 years in comparison to others; while a few others (i.e. more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar, D▲Mart, Reliance Digital, NEXT) are good enough to attract the footfalls from the age group of 51+ customers in comparison to others. The electronics-item superstores (i.e. NEXT and Reliance Digital) struggling the tap the customers from the age group of below 21 years; while fashion store organised retailers (i.e. Big Megamart, West Side, Max) are struggling the tap the customers from the age group of above 60 years.

7.1.4 Education of customers

Retailers	Education											
	Illiterate		Below HSC		HSC - SSC		Graduate		Postgraduate		Others	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
HyperCITY	0	0.00	14	7.00	28	14.00	67	33.50	86	43.00	5	2.50
Star Bazaar	5	2.50	18	9.00	36	18.00	58	29.00	75	37.50	8	4.00
more.MEGASStore	3	1.50	15	7.50	37	18.50	64	32.00	72	36.00	9	4.50
Big Bazaar	0	0.00	16	8.00	40	20.00	60	30.00	80	40.00	4	2.00
D ⁺ Mart	10	5.00	21	10.50	68	34.00	71	35.50	28	14.00	2	1.00
Big Megamart	0	0.00	10	5.00	15	7.50	70	35.00	98	49.00	7	3.50
West Side	0	0.00	12	6.00	16	8.00	72	36.00	95	47.50	5	2.50
Max	0	0.00	9	4.50	18	9.00	76	38.00	91	45.50	6	3.00
Reliance Digital	4	2.00	18	9.00	23	11.50	66	33.00	86	43.00	3	1.50
NEXT	6	3.00	17	8.50	39	19.50	57	28.50	75	37.50	6	3.00
Mean	2.80	1.40	15.00	7.50	32.00	16.00	66.10	33.05	78.60	39.30	5.50	2.75
Standard Deviation	3.458	1.729	3.801	1.900	15.944	7.972	6.350	3.175	19.834	9.917	2.173	1.087

The organised retail industry has well-educated customers in the Maharashtra state as the state has 82.34 literacy rate (according to the Census of 2011). Its majority of customers in the industry is graduates or post graduates. However, the industry is getting the footfall from the customers of all education groups. Few organised retailers (Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, D⁺Mart, Reliance Digital and NEXT) are also to attract illiterate customers in few numbers; while others (i.e. HyperCITY, Big Bazaar, Big Megamart, West Side, Max) are not having the illiterate customers.

7.1.5 Occupation of customers

Retailers	Occupations									
	Salaried		Self-employed		Homemaker		Student		Retired	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
HyperCITY	78	39.00	39	19.50	25	12.50	46	23.00	12	6.00
Star Bazaar	68	34.00	32	16.00	52	26.00	31	15.50	17	8.50
more.MEGASStore	70	35.00	28	14.00	42	21.00	50	25.00	10	5.00
Big Bazaar	81	40.50	34	17.00	36	18.00	38	19.00	11	5.50
D Mart	58	29.00	30	15.00	59	29.50	22	11.00	31	15.50
Big Megamart	79	39.50	46	23.00	20	10.00	45	22.50	10	5.00
West Side	80	40.00	42	21.00	16	8.00	50	25.00	12	6.00
Max	76	38.00	39	19.50	20	10.00	51	25.50	14	7.00
Reliance Digital	74	37.00	50	25.00	30	15.00	18	9.00	28	14.00
NEXT	73	36.50	49	24.50	29	14.50	20	10.00	29	14.50
Mean	73.70	36.85	38.90	19.45	32.90	16.45	37.10	18.55	17.40	8.70
Standard Deviation	6.977	3.488	7.852	3.926	14.310	7.155	13.295	6.648	8.514	4.257

The organised retail industry is getting the customers of all the occupational groups. Its majority of customers are salaried and self-employed. The second majority of customers are students and homemakers. D Mart is only retailer getting less footfalls of salaried customers in comparison to others and the industry mean value; while more.MEGASStore is getting less footfall of self-employed customers in comparison to others. The fashion store organised retailers (i.e. Big Megamart, West Side, Max) are getting less footfall from homemakers in comparison to the industry mean value; while, the electronics-item superstores (i.e. NEXT and Reliance Digital) are getting less footfall of student customers in comparison to the industry mean value. Some retailers (i.e. HyperCITY, Big Bazaar, Big Megamart, West Side, Max and Reliance Digital) have more salaried customers in comparison to the industry mean value. Reliance Digital and Big Magamart are able to tap more self-employed customers in comparison to the industry mean value. All the multi-format organised retailers included in the study (except HyperCITY) have more homemaker customers in comparison to the industry mean value. HyperCITY, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar, Big Megamart, West Side, and Max are getting more footfalls of student customers in comparison to others and the industry mean value. The electronics-item superstores (i.e. NEXT and Reliance Digital) and multi-format superstore (i.e. D Mart)

Mart) are getting more footfalls for retired customers in comparison to others and the industry mean value.

7.1.6 Family income (yearly) of customers

Table 7.1.6: Family income (yearly) of customers										
Retailers	Family income (in Lacs of ₹)									
	< 1		1 to 2		2 to 5		5 to 10		> 10	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
HyperCITY	1	0.50	15	7.50	68	34.00	78	39.00	38	19.00
Star Bazaar	12	6.00	22	11.00	78	39.00	62	31.00	26	13.00
more.MEGASStore	15	7.50	25	12.50	85	42.50	56	28.00	19	9.50
Big Bazaar	3	1.50	19	9.50	62	31.00	81	40.50	35	17.50
D ⁺ Mart	22	11.00	45	22.50	91	45.50	29	14.50	13	6.50
Big Megamart	0	0.00	12	6.00	65	32.50	90	45.00	33	16.50
West Side	2	1.00	14	7.00	70	35.00	87	43.50	27	13.50
Max	3	1.50	17	8.50	64	32.00	88	44.00	28	14.00
Reliance Digital	1	0.50	24	12.00	91	45.50	60	30.00	24	12.00
NEXT	2	1.00	29	14.50	90	45.00	59	29.50	20	10.00
Mean	6.10	3.05	22.20	11.10	76.40	38.20	69.00	34.50	26.30	13.15
Standard Deviation	7.520	3.760	9.647	4.824	11.974	5.987	19.293	9.647	7.718	3.859

The organised retail industry is getting the customers of all the income groups. However, its majority of customers are from two income groups, i.e. 2 to 5 LPA and 5 to 10 LPA family income. But, the industry is also attracting and getting the footfall of customers from the high-income group (i.e. more than 10 LPA) as well as low-income group (i.e. 1 to 2 LPA). Moreover, the industry has also customers from the lowest income group, i.e. less than 1 LPA. But, few organised retailers included in this study either do not have customers from less than 1 LPA family income group or having negligible customers from this income group, those are Big Megamart, HyperCITY, Big Bazaar, West Side, Max, Reliance Digital and NEXT. Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, D⁺Mart, Reliance Digital and NEXT have more customers from 1 to 2 LPA family income group in comparison to others (included in the study) and the industry mean value. more.MEGASStore and D⁺Mart are getting fewer customers from the 5+ 10 LPA family income group in comparison to others.

7.1.7 Marital status of customers

Table 7.1.7: Marital status of customers				
Retailers	Marital status			
	Single		Married	
	f	%	f	%
HyperCITY	74	37.00	126	63.00
Star Bazaar	62	31.00	138	69.00
more.MEGASStore	65	32.50	135	67.50
Big Bazaar	72	36.00	128	64.00
D▲Mart	48	24.00	152	76.00
Big Megamart	88	44.00	112	56.00
West Side	79	39.50	121	60.50
Max	77	38.50	123	61.50
Reliance Digital	52	26.00	148	74.00
NEXT	35	17.50	165	82.50
Mean	65.20	32.60	134.80	67.40
Standard Deviation	16.212	8.106	16.212	8.106

The organised retail industry is getting married as well as single customers. However, the industry has its more customers from the married marital status group in comparison to a single marital status group of customers.

The electronics-item superstores (i.e. NEXT and Reliance Digital) and D▲Mart are getting fewer customers from single marital status group of customers in comparison to others and the industry mean value; while the fashion-item retailers (i.e. Big Megamart, West Side, Max) as well as two multi-format hyper stores (i.e. HyperCITY and Big Bazaar) are tapping more customers from single marital status group of customers in comparison to others and the industry mean value.

But, the electronics-item superstores (i.e. NEXT and Reliance Digital) and D▲Mart are tapping more customers from a married marital status group of customers in comparison to others and the industry mean value. The fashion-item hyper store organised retailer (i.e. Big Megamart) is getting fewer customers from a married marital status group of customers as compared to others and the industry mean value.

7.1.8 Nature of family of customers

Table 7.1.8: Nature of family of customers				
Retailers	Nature of family			
	Nuclear		Joint	
	f	%	f	%
HyperCITY	136	68.00	64	32.00
Star Bazaar	103	51.50	97	48.50
more.MEGASStore	112	56.00	88	44.00
Big Bazaar	129	64.50	71	35.50
D ⁺ Mart	98	49.00	102	51.00
Big Megamart	146	73.00	54	27.00
West Side	123	61.50	77	38.50
Max	140	70.00	60	30.00
Reliance Digital	105	52.50	95	47.50
NEXT	103	51.50	97	48.50
Mean	119.50	59.75	80.50	40.25
Standard Deviation	17.545	8.773	17.545	8.773

The organised retail industry is getting both nuclear as well as joint families customers. However, the industry is tapping more customers from nuclear families in comparison to joint families.

Some retailers included in this study (i.e. Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, D⁺Mart, Reliance Digital and NEXT) are getting fewer footfalls from nuclear families in comparison to joint families and industry mean value; few others (i.e. HyperCITY, Big Bazaar, Big Megamart, West Side and Max) are getting fewer footfalls from joint families in comparison to nuclear families and industry mean value.

The multi-format superstore included in this study (i.e. D⁺Mart) is having highest customers from joint families in comparison to nuclear families and industry mean value; while the fashion-item hyper store (i.e. Big Megamart) is tapping highest customers from nuclear families in comparison to nuclear families and industry mean value.

7.1.9 Family size of customers

Table 7.1.9: Family size of customers
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Retailers	Family size (Number of Members)							
	< 4		4 to 5		6 to 8		> 8	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
HyperCITY	96	48.00	68	34.00	32	16.00	4	2.00
Star Bazaar	80	40.00	68	34.00	42	21.00	10	5.00
more.MEGAStore	76	38.00	70	35.00	40	20.00	14	7.00
Big Bazaar	92	46.00	65	32.50	35	17.50	8	4.00
D ⁺ Mart	61	30.50	72	36.00	45	22.50	22	11.00
Big Megamart	102	51.00	71	35.50	25	12.50	2	1.00
West Side	93	46.50	79	39.50	24	12.00	4	2.00
Max	98	49.00	75	37.50	20	10.00	7	3.50
Reliance Digital	72	36.00	80	40.00	36	18.00	12	6.00
NEXT	69	34.50	79	39.50	39	19.50	13	6.50
Mean	83.90	41.95	72.70	36.35	33.80	16.90	9.60	4.80
Standard Deviation	14.091	7.045	5.293	2.646	8.377	4.189	5.967	2.983

The organised retail industry is tapping the customers from all the family size groups of customers included in the study. But, the first majority of customers are from the family size of below 4 members and the second majority of customers are from 4 to 5 members' family size. However, the industry is also tapping enough footfalls from 6 to 8 members' family size. The fashion-item retailers (i.e. Big Megamart, West Side, Max) as well as two multi-format hyper stores (i.e. HyperCITY and Big Bazaar) are tapping more customers from the family size of below 4 members in comparison to others and industry mean value. The electronics-item superstores (i.e. NEXT and Reliance Digital) are getting more customers from the family size of 4 to 5 members in comparison to other retailers included in the study. The multi-format superstore included in this study (i.e. D⁺Mart) is having highest customers from the family size of more than 5 members in comparison others and industry mean value; while the fashion-item retailers (i.e. Big Megamart, West Side and Max) are getting minimum customers from the family size of more than 5 members in comparison to others and industry mean value.

7.1.10 Religion of customers

Table 7.1.10: Religion of customers												
Retailers	Religions											
	Hindu		Muslim		Buddhists		Christian		Sikh		Other	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
HyperCITY	155	77.50	26	13.00	12	6.00	4	2.00	1	0.50	2	1.00
Star Bazaar	150	75.00	40	20.00	7	3.50	1	0.50	0	0.00	2	1.00
more.MEGASStore	161	80.50	18	9.00	15	7.50	0	0.00	1	0.50	5	2.50
Big Bazaar	160	80.00	12	6.00	17	8.50	2	1.00	1	0.50	8	4.00
D ⁺ Mart	176	88.00	10	5.00	11	5.50	0	0.00	0	0.00	3	1.50
Big Megamart	136	68.00	38	19.00	15	7.50	6	3.00	1	0.50	4	2.00
West Side	135	67.50	48	24.00	10	5.00	4	2.00	0	0.00	3	1.50
Max	165	82.50	15	7.50	14	7.00	2	1.00	1	0.50	3	1.50
Reliance Digital	179	89.50	10	5.00	9	4.50	0	0.00	0	0.00	2	1.00
NEXT	178	89.00	10	5.00	9	4.50	0	0.00	0	0.00	3	1.50
Mean	159.50	79.75	22.70	11.35	11.90	5.95	1.90	0.95	0.50	0.25	3.50	1.75
Standard Deviation	15.953	7.977	14.392	7.196	3.247	1.624	2.132	1.066	0.527	0.264	1.841	0.920

The organised retail industry is getting the customers from all the religions. However, the majority of the customers are Hindus. The second majority is of Muslim customers. Not surprisingly, the third majority is of Buddhists customers, as the Maharashtra state has 73.4% of the total Buddhism followers in India. The retail industry is also tapping the customers from other religions, but they are very less in numbers.

ANALYSIS OF BUYING BEHAVIOUR OF CUSTOMERS IN THE ORGANISED RETAIL INDUSTRY

7.2.1 Purchase decision maker in the family

7.2.1: Purchase decision maker in the family of customers										
Retailers	Purchase decision makers									
	Self		Spouse		Children		Parent		Others	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
HyperCITY	82	41.00	65	32.50	10	5.00	38	19.00	5	2.50
Star Bazaar	85	42.50	78	39.00	12	6.00	23	11.50	2	1.00
more.MEGASStore	77	38.50	70	35.00	8	4.00	41	20.50	4	2.00
Big Bazaar	82	41.00	78	39.00	7	3.50	30	15.00	3	1.50
D Mart	96	48.00	66	33.00	20	10.00	16	8.00	2	1.00
Big Megamart	91	45.50	61	30.50	8	4.00	37	18.50	3	1.50
West Side	87	43.50	66	33.00	9	4.50	36	18.00	2	1.00
Max	90	45.00	65	32.50	5	2.50	38	19.00	2	1.00
Reliance Digital	120	60.00	44	22.00	19	9.50	16	8.00	1	0.50
NEXT	118	59.00	40	20.00	21	10.50	18	9.00	3	1.50
Mean	92.80	46.40	63.30	31.65	11.90	5.95	29.30	14.65	2.70	1.35
Standard Deviation	14.808	7.404	12.553	6.276	5.896	2.948	10.078	5.039	1.160	0.580

The majority of customers in the organised retail industry take the purchase making decision by self. The second majority of customers relies on their spouse; while the third majority relies on their parents to purchase making decision. Means, the majority of customers in the organised retail industry are either self-purchase decision maker in the family or rely on their spouse and parents.

The electronics-item superstores (i.e. NEXT and Reliance Digital) are getting more footfalls from the self-purchase decision-making customers in comparison to other retailers included in this study. The primary reason of the same is that both the stores have more than 80% of customers from the male group of customers.

All the multi-format hyper stores included in the study (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and Big Bazaar) along with fashion-item retailers (i.e. Big Megamart, West Side and Max) are getting more footfalls of the customers, whose purchase decision makers are their parents in comparison to other retailers. The reason of this more footfalls is that these stores have a good number of student customers, whose purchase decision makers are actually their parents.

7.2.1(a): Collection of information, while purchase decision making by customers				
Retailers	Collection of information for purchase decision-making			
	Yes		No	
	f	%	f	%
HyperCITY	187	93.50	13	6.50
Star Bazaar	176	88.00	24	12.00
more.MEGASStore	179	89.50	21	10.50
Big Bazaar	184	92.00	16	8.00
D ⁺ Mart	136	68.00	64	32.00
Big Megamart	190	95.00	10	5.00
West Side	188	94.00	12	6.00
Max	189	94.50	11	5.50
Reliance Digital	193	96.50	7	3.50
NEXT	192	96.00	8	4.00
Mean	181.40	90.70	18.60	9.30
Standard Deviation	16.854	8.427	16.854	8.427

The majority of customers in organised retail industry collects the information about merchandise and services before taking a purchase making decision. In comparison to other retailers included in this study, a large number of customers of a multi-format superstore (i.e. D⁺Mart) are least bothered about the information before taking a purchase making decision.

The preferred sources of customers in the organised retail industry for collecting the information before purchase decision making are (in order of most preferred to least preferred): advertising, internet, family members, neighbours / friends / relatives, package labels, in-store display, in-store information, salespersons, telemarketing and other sources.

7.2.2 Sources of information, while purchase decision-making

7.2.2: Sources of information, while purchase decision making by customers

Retailers	Sources of information																			
	Salespersons		Telemarketing		Advertising		In-store information		In-store display		Package labels		Family members		Neighbours / Friends / Relatives		Internet (www)		Others	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
HyperCITY	67	33.50	45	22.50	179	89.50	52	26.00	78	39.00	125	62.50	138	69.00	132	66.00	153	76.50	13	6.50
Star Bazaar	55	27.50	20	10.00	165	82.50	78	39.00	102	51.00	142	71.00	132	66.00	138	69.00	142	71.00	11	5.50
more.MEGASTore	76	38.00	12	6.00	171	85.50	82	41.00	98	49.00	137	68.50	143	71.50	142	71.00	136	68.00	10	5.00
Big Bazaar	72	36.00	13	6.50	175	87.50	90	45.00	89	44.50	150	75.00	146	73.00	139	69.50	150	75.00	15	7.50
D ⁺ Mart	88	44.00	4	2.00	119	59.50	76	38.00	65	32.50	105	52.50	123	61.50	130	65.00	98	49.00	9	4.50
Big Megamart	96	48.00	28	14.00	186	93.00	102	51.00	95	47.50	152	76.00	150	75.00	138	69.00	160	80.00	16	8.00
West Side	87	43.50	15	7.50	182	91.00	99	49.50	86	43.00	155	77.50	156	78.00	143	71.50	156	78.00	12	6.00
Max	92	46.00	14	7.00	178	89.00	91	45.50	90	45.00	143	71.50	149	74.50	135	67.50	161	80.50	17	8.50
Reliance Digital	104	52.00	23	11.50	180	90.00	103	51.50	98	49.00	89	44.50	167	83.50	169	84.50	178	89.00	13	6.50
NEXT	100	50.00	12	6.00	177	88.50	101	50.50	89	44.50	74	37.00	157	78.50	157	78.50	169	84.50	8	4.00
Mean	83.70	41.85	18.60	9.30	171.20	85.60	87.40	43.70	89.00	44.50	127.20	63.60	146.10	73.05	142.30	71.15	150.30	75.15	12.40	6.20
Standard Deviation	15.727	7.864	11.413	5.707	19.240	9.620	15.974	7.987	10.924	5.462	28.401	14.201	12.845	6.422	11.963	5.982	22.046	11.023	2.989	1.494

The customers of multi-format hyper store organised retailers rely on the advertising, internet sources, family members, neighbours / friends / relatives and package labels for collecting the information before the purchase decision making. Good news for the multi-format organised retailers is that there is a large number of their customers also prefer to collect the information from sources like in-store display, salespersons and in-store information. But, the customers of D⁺Mart (a multi-format super store) rely on neighbours / friends / relatives, family members, package labels, advertising and salespersons. The great number of customers from HyperCITY also prefers to collect the information from telemarketing sources before the purchase decision making. The customers of the electronics-item superstores (i.e. NEXT and Reliance Digital) collect massive information from all the sources before the purchase decision making.

7.2.3 Sources of information from advertising, while purchase decision-making

7.2.3: Sources of information from advertising, while purchase decision making by customers																				
Retailers	Sources of information from Advertising																			
	Television		Newspapers		Magazines		Hoardings		Pamphlets		Radio		Cinema		Celebrity endorsement		Websites		Others	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
HyperCITY	167	83.50	49	24.50	25	12.50	13	6.50	15	7.50	7	3.50	5	2.50	152	76.00	153	76.50	12	6.00
Star Bazaar	152	76.00	68	34.00	16	8.00	10	5.00	30	15.00	12	6.00	0	0.00	133	66.50	142	71.00	11	5.50
more.MEGAStore	148	74.00	75	37.50	28	14.00	19	9.50	36	18.00	14	7.00	2	1.00	142	71.00	136	68.00	13	6.50
Big Bazaar	161	80.50	51	25.50	19	9.50	26	13.00	40	20.00	18	9.00	1	0.50	150	75.00	150	75.00	16	8.00
D Mart	102	51.00	86	43.00	8	4.00	28	14.00	56	28.00	16	8.00	0	0.00	100	50.00	98	49.00	8	4.00
Big Megamart	175	87.50	52	26.00	35	17.50	11	5.50	16	8.00	11	5.50	2	1.00	161	80.50	160	80.00	14	7.00
West Side	169	84.50	66	33.00	25	12.50	19	9.50	35	17.50	13	6.50	0	0.00	152	76.00	156	78.00	9	4.50
Max	162	81.00	53	26.50	39	19.50	20	10.00	30	15.00	16	8.00	1	0.50	147	73.50	161	80.50	5	2.50
Reliance Digital	170	85.00	85	42.50	12	6.00	31	15.50	42	21.00	19	9.50	0	0.00	160	80.00	178	89.00	4	2.00
NEXT	166	83.00	90	45.00	10	5.00	39	19.50	48	24.00	20	10.00	0	0.00	157	78.50	169	84.50	2	1.00
Mean	157.20	78.60	67.50	33.75	21.70	10.85	21.60	10.80	34.80	17.40	14.60	7.30	1.10	0.55	145.40	72.70	150.30	75.15	9.40	4.70
Standard Deviation	21.054	10.527	15.911	7.956	10.520	5.260	9.359	4.680	12.891	6.445	4.006	2.003	1.595	0.798	18.038	9.019	22.046	11.023	4.624	2.312

The majority of customers in the organised retail industry, who collect the information from advertising, relies on the following sources (in order of most preferred to least preferred): television, websites, celebrity endorsement, newspapers, pamphlets, magazines, hoardings, radio, other sources and cinema.

7.2.4 Sources of influence for a customer, while purchase decision-making

7.2.4: Sources of influence for a customer, while purchase decision-making

Retailers	Sources of influence																									
	Self		Family members		Neighbors / Friends / Colleagues		Celebrity endorsement		Salesperson in a store		Direct-mail piece		Websites		TV commercials		Infomercials		Magazines ads		TV talk shows		Sales Promotion		Others	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
HyperCITY	79	39.50	135	67.50	129	64.50	147	73.50	60	30.00	23	11.50	142	71.00	152	76.00	159	79.50	20	10.00	79	39.50	143	71.50	11	5.50
Star Bazaar	82	41.00	129	64.50	135	67.50	128	64.00	48	24.00	26	13.00	131	65.50	137	68.50	146	73.00	13	6.50	72	36.00	151	75.50	9	4.50
more.MEGAStore	74	37.00	140	70.00	139	69.50	137	68.50	69	34.50	20	10.00	125	62.50	133	66.50	139	69.50	18	9.00	76	38.00	149	74.50	8	4.00
Big Bazaar	78	39.00	143	71.50	136	68.00	145	72.50	65	32.50	29	14.50	139	69.50	146	73.00	148	74.00	13	6.50	69	34.50	143	71.50	6	3.00
D Mart	63	31.50	120	60.00	127	63.50	95	47.50	81	40.50	9	4.50	87	43.50	87	43.50	103	51.50	5	2.50	39	19.50	168	84.00	9	4.50
Big Megamart	88	44.00	147	73.50	135	67.50	156	78.00	89	44.50	36	18.00	149	74.50	160	80.00	166	83.00	26	13.00	86	43.00	133	66.50	7	3.50
West Side	84	42.00	153	76.50	140	70.00	146	73.00	80	40.00	40	20.00	145	72.50	154	77.00	160	80.00	17	8.50	82	41.00	139	69.50	9	4.50
Max	87	43.50	146	73.00	132	66.00	142	71.00	85	42.50	35	17.50	160	80.00	147	73.50	159	79.50	30	15.00	80	40.00	140	70.00	8	4.00
Reliance Digital	117	58.50	164	82.00	166	83.00	155	77.50	97	48.50	12	6.00	167	83.50	155	77.50	168	84.00	6	3.00	89	44.50	132	66.00	10	5.00
NEXT	115	57.50	154	77.00	154	77.00	152	76.00	93	46.50	8	4.00	158	79.00	151	75.50	158	79.00	4	2.00	84	42.00	122	61.00	8	4.00
Mean	86.70	43.35	143.10	71.55	139.30	69.65	140.30	70.15	76.70	38.35	23.80	11.90	140.30	70.15	142.20	71.10	150.60	75.30	15.20	7.60	75.60	37.80	142.00	71.00	8.50	4.25
Standard Deviation	17.023	8.512	12.845	6.422	11.963	5.982	18.000	9.000	15.727	7.864	11.507	5.753	22.799	11.399	21.054	10.527	19.010	9.505	8.779	4.389	14.245	7.123	12.481	6.241	1.434	0.717

The majority of purchase decisions is influenced by different sources. The purchase decisions of customers in the organised retail industry are influenced by (in order of most influencing to least influencing sources): TV talk shows, infomercials, family members, websites, celebrity endorsement, TV commercials, sales promotion, neighbours / friends / colleagues, self, a salesperson in a store, direct-mail piece, magazine ads and others sources.

7.2.5 Purchaser (buyer) in the family

7.2.5: Purchaser (buyer) in the family of the customers										
Retailers	Purchaser (buyer) in the family									
	Self		Spouse		Children		Parent		Surrogate	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
HyperCITY	79	39.50	70	35.00	12	6.00	29	14.50	10	5.00
Star Bazaar	81	40.50	81	40.50	13	6.50	18	9.00	7	3.50
more.MEGASStore	73	36.50	74	37.00	10	5.00	34	17.00	9	4.50
Big Bazaar	78	39.00	80	40.00	9	4.50	26	13.00	7	3.50
D ⁺ Mart	91	45.50	79	39.50	16	8.00	12	6.00	2	1.00
Big Megamart	89	44.50	64	32.00	10	5.00	35	17.50	2	1.00
West Side	85	42.50	68	34.00	11	5.50	32	16.00	4	2.00
Max	88	44.00	70	35.00	8	4.00	31	15.50	3	1.50
Reliance Digital	119	59.50	50	25.00	15	7.50	16	8.00	0	0.00
NEXT	116	58.00	49	24.50	17	8.50	18	9.00	0	0.00
Mean	89.90	44.95	68.50	34.25	12.10	6.05	25.10	12.55	4.40	2.20
Standard Deviation	15.574	7.787	11.433	5.717	3.071	1.536	8.373	4.186	3.627	1.814

The majorities of customers in the organised retail industry are either self-purchase decision maker in the family or rely on their spouse and parents. Similarly, the majority of customers in the organised retail industry purchase the merchandise and services by self. The second majority of customers relies on their spouse; while the third majority relies on their parents to purchase the merchandise and services for them. Moreover, few customers also rely on their children and surrogate to purchase the merchandise and services for them. The electronics-item superstores (i.e. NEXT and Reliance Digital) are getting more footfalls from the self-purchaser in comparison to other retailers included in this study. The primary reason of the same is that both the stores have more than 80% of customers from the male group of customers. All the multi-format organised retailers included in the study are getting more footfalls from the customers, who rely on their spouse to purchase the merchandise and services for them in comparison to other retailers. The fashion store organised retailers included in the study (i.e. Big Megamart, West Side and Max) along with more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar and HyperCITY are getting more footfalls from the customers, who rely on their parents to purchase the merchandise and services for them in comparison to other retailers and industry mean value.

7.2.6 Duration of visiting the store of retailers

7.2.6: Duration of visiting the store by customers												
Retailers	Durations											
	First time		Last 3 months		Last 6 months		Last 1 year		Last 2 year		More than 2 years	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
HyperCITY	4	2.00	48	24.00	59	29.50	68	34.00	16	8.00	5	2.50
Star Bazaar	6	3.00	49	24.50	75	37.50	62	31.00	8	4.00	0	0.00
more.MEGASStore	7	3.50	52	26.00	71	35.50	59	29.50	11	5.50	0	0.00
Big Bazaar	3	1.50	28	14.00	72	36.00	56	28.00	29	14.50	12	6.00
D ⁺ Mart	5	2.50	50	25.00	70	35.00	67	33.50	7	3.50	1	0.50
Big Megamart	9	4.50	29	14.50	46	23.00	64	32.00	30	15.00	22	11.00
West Side	8	4.00	26	13.00	78	39.00	60	30.00	25	12.50	3	1.50
Max	8	4.00	31	15.50	72	36.00	61	30.50	28	14.00	0	0.00
Reliance Digital	12	6.00	44	22.00	79	39.50	65	32.50	0	0.00	0	0.00
NEXT	14	7.00	40	20.00	81	40.50	62	31.00	3	1.50	0	0.00
Mean	7.60	3.80	39.70	19.85	70.30	35.15	62.40	31.20	15.70	7.85	4.30	2.15
Standard Deviation	3.438	1.719	10.253	5.126	10.520	5.260	3.688	1.844	11.470	5.735	7.288	3.644

The majority of customers of HyperCITY (a multi-format hyper store) are visiting their store from last one year. HyperCITY is getting more footfalls of this category customers in comparison to others included in the study. The majority of customers of Star Bazaar (a multi-format hyper store) are visiting their store for last 6 months. Star Bazaar is getting more footfalls of this category customers in comparison to other multi-format organised retailers included in the study. The majority of customers of Big Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and D⁺Mart (all multi-format retailers) are also visiting their store for last 6 months. The majority of customers of the Big Megamart (a fashion-item hyper store) is visiting their store from last one year, while the majority of customers of fashion-item superstores (i.e. West Side and Max) is visiting their store for last 6 months. Moreover, the majority of customers of electronic superstores is also visiting the stores from last 6 months.

7.2.7 Visits to the store in a month

7.2.7: Visits of customers to the store in a month										
Retailers	Visits									
	1 Time		2 Times		3 Times		4 Times		More than 4 times	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
HyperCITY	19	9.50	40	20.00	59	29.50	67	33.50	15	7.50
Star Bazaar	14	7.00	35	17.50	63	31.50	78	39.00	10	5.00
more.MEGASStore	15	7.50	34	17.00	55	27.50	70	35.00	26	13.00
Big Bazaar	20	10.00	42	21.00	38	19.00	81	40.50	19	9.50
D ⁺ Mart	18	9.00	52	26.00	31	15.50	79	39.50	20	10.00
Big Megamart	89	44.50	68	34.00	24	12.00	14	7.00	5	2.50
West Side	81	40.50	75	37.50	26	13.00	10	5.00	8	4.00
Max	79	39.50	72	36.00	28	14.00	17	8.50	4	2.00
Reliance Digital	102	51.00	69	34.50	18	9.00	9	4.50	2	1.00
NEXT	107	53.50	63	31.50	19	9.50	8	4.00	3	1.50
Mean	54.40	27.20	55.00	27.50	36.10	18.05	43.30	21.65	11.20	5.60
Standard Deviation	40.123	20.061	16.200	8.100	16.895	8.447	33.757	16.879	8.337	4.169

The majority of customers of all the multi-format organised retailers (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar and D⁺Mart) visits the stores 3 or more times in a month. These retailers get a good footfall of customers from the 1 or 2-time visitors in the month. Moreover, they are also getting the footfalls from more than 4 times visitors in a month. The majority of customers of all the fashion stores organised retailers (i.e. Big Megamart, West Side and Max) as well as the electronics-item superstores (i.e. Reliance Digital and NEXT) visits the stores 1 or 2 times in a month. However, these retailers are also getting enough 3 and 4 times visitors in a month, but the number of more than 4-time visitors is very less and negligible.

7.2.8 Preferred days for visiting the stores

The majority of customers in the organised retail industry prefers to visit the stores on weekends. But, it does not mean that the industry is not getting footfall on weekdays. There are a great number of customers, who prefer to visit the stores on weekdays. Moreover, there are also a great number of customers, who actually visit the stores whenever they need to visit. Surprisingly, four multi-format organised retailers (i.e. Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar and D⁺Mart) are getting

fewer footfalls from the customers on weekends in comparison to others (included in the study) and the industry mean value. Big Bazaar is highest footfalls of customers on weekdays in comparison to others (included in the study) and the industry mean value. The reason for the same is its attractive schemes on weekdays.

7.2.8: Preferred days of customers for visiting the stores						
Retailers	Days					
	Weekdays		Weekends		Any day	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
HyperCITY	26	13.00	123	61.50	51	25.50
Star Bazaar	53	26.50	88	44.00	59	29.50
more.MEGASStore	38	19.00	98	49.00	64	32.00
Big Bazaar	68	34.00	79	39.50	53	26.50
D ⁺ Mart	40	20.00	99	49.50	61	30.50
Big Megamart	29	14.50	148	74.00	23	11.50
West Side	35	17.50	131	65.50	34	17.00
Max	41	20.50	128	64.00	31	15.50
Reliance Digital	30	15.00	132	66.00	38	19.00
NEXT	46	23.00	124	62.00	30	15.00
Mean	40.60	20.30	115.00	57.50	44.40	22.20
Standard Deviation	12.616	6.308	22.405	11.203	14.849	7.424

All multi-format organised retailers included in the study have a great number of customers, who visit the stores on all the days in comparison to others (included in the study) and the industry mean value.

7.2.9 Preferred time for visiting the stores

The majority of customers in the organised retail industry prefers to visit the stores in the evening time. But, it does not mean that the industry is not getting footfall in morning and afternoon. The industry has a good number of customers, who prefer to visit their stores in the morning. The industry is also getting the footfalls of the customers in the store in the afternoon, but it is less and negligible in the case of some retailers.

7.2.9: Preferred time for visiting the stores								
Retailers	Timings							
	Morning		Afternoon		Evening		Any time	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
HyperCITY	36	18.00	10	5.00	136	68.00	18	9.00
Star Bazaar	16	8.00	2	1.00	152	76.00	30	15.00
more.MEGASStore	28	14.00	16	8.00	128	64.00	28	14.00
Big Bazaar	35	17.50	8	4.00	125	62.50	32	16.00
D Mart	40	20.00	12	6.00	96	48.00	52	26.00
Big Megamart	12	6.00	6	3.00	143	71.50	39	19.50
West Side	18	9.00	5	2.50	137	68.50	40	20.00
Max	20	10.00	10	5.00	143	71.50	27	13.50
Reliance Digital	10	5.00	7	3.50	141	70.50	42	21.00
NEXT	15	7.50	12	6.00	121	60.50	52	26.00
Mean	23.00	11.50	8.80	4.40	132.20	66.10	36.00	18.00
Standard Deviation	10.873	5.437	4.050	2.025	15.796	7.898	11.025	5.513

Moreover, the industry also has a great number of customers, whose timing to visit the store is not fixed and they prefer to visit any point of time. All multi-format organised retailers included in the study except Star Bazaar are getting more footfalls in the morning time in comparison to others (included in the study) and the industry mean value.

7.2.10 Spending amount on purchasing from the stores

7.2.10: Spending amount of purchasing by customers from the stores								
Retailers	Spending amounts							
	< ₹ 1000		₹ 1000 - 2000		₹ 2001 - 5000		> ₹ 5000	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
HyperCITY	9	4.50	24	12.00	69	34.50	98	49.00
Star Bazaar	22	11.00	56	28.00	78	39.00	44	22.00
more.MEGASStore	20	10.00	60	30.00	82	41.00	38	19.00
Big Bazaar	16	8.00	36	18.00	75	37.50	73	36.50
D Mart	39	19.50	72	36.00	68	34.00	21	10.50
Big Megamart	8	4.00	30	15.00	65	32.50	97	48.50
West Side	12	6.00	33	16.50	72	36.00	83	41.50
Max	6	3.00	30	15.00	70	35.00	94	47.00
Reliance Digital	35	17.50	41	20.50	52	26.00	72	36.00
NEXT	30	15.00	45	22.50	65	32.50	60	30.00
Mean	19.70	9.85	42.70	21.35	69.60	34.80	68.00	34.00
Standard Deviation	11.691	5.845	15.471	7.735	8.262	4.131	26.733	13.367

The majority of customers of the fashion store retailers as well as electronics stores included in this study spends more than ₹ 5000 per month for purchasing from the stores, while the majority of customers of multi-format hyper store retailers except HyperCITY spend ₹ 2000 to ₹ 5000 per month. The HyperCITY is getting more footfalls of customers, who spend more than ₹ 5000 per month for purchasing from the store.

7.2.11 The categories of the products, from which customers purchase products

Retailers	Categories of the products							
	Basic (staples) merchandise		Fashion merchandise		Seasonal merchandise		Consumer durables merchandise	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
HyperCITY	139	69.5	104	52.0	46	23.0	98	49.0
Star Bazaar	140	70.0	130	65.0	36	18.0	79	39.5
more.MEGAStore	150	75.0	95	47.5	28	14.0	70	35.0
Big Bazaar	152	76.0	136	68.0	49	24.5	100	50.0
D ⁺ Mart	164	82.0	142	71.0	50	25.0	69	34.5
Big Megamart	5	2.5	200	100.0	98	49.0	48	24.0
West Side	4	2.0	200	100.0	75	37.5	52	26.0
Max	2	1.0	200	100.0	62	31.0	0	0.0
Reliance Digital	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	200	100.0
NEXT	4	2.0	12	6.0	0	0.0	200	100.0
Mean	76.0	38.0	121.9	61.0	44.4	22.2	91.6	45.8
Standard Deviation	77.260	38.630	72.226	36.113	30.653	15.326	63.778	31.889

The majority of customers of all the multi-format organised retailers purchases the products from all the categories of merchandise i.e. basic (staples) merchandise, fashion merchandise, seasonal merchandise and consumer durable. However, D⁺Mart is getting more footfalls of customers, who purchase the basic (staple) merchandise, fashion merchandise, seasonal merchandise category products in comparison to other multi-format stores. Big Bazaar and HyperCITY are getting more footfalls of customers, who purchase; the consumer durables merchandise category products in comparison to other multi-format stores. The majority of customers of fashion stores (i.e. Big Megamart, West Side and Max) purchase the products from fashion

merchandise category, as these are fashion stores; while the majority of customers of electronics-item superstores (i.e. Reliance Digital and NEXT) purchases the products from consumer durables merchandise category, as these store deals with the durables in large.

7.2.12 Types of products, the customers purchase from the stores

Figure 7.2.1

Figure 7.2.2

Figure 7.2.3

Figure 7.2.4

Figure 7.2.5

The customers of multi-format retailers (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar and D Mart) purchase all types of products from their stores, they offer. The majority of customers from HyperCITY purchases food & grocery, health & beauty, home & furniture, fashion products as well store level brands. The majority of customers of Star Bazaar purchase food & grocery, fashion & accessories, personal & home care, home & kitchen products as well as store level brands. The majority of customers of more.MEGASStore purchase grocery, home and personal care, apparels, footwear and electronic products. The majority of customers of Big Bazaar purchase grocery & staples, fashion, electronics, personal, kitchen & dining toys, sports, outdoors and home products. The majority of customers of D Mart purchase foods, garments, toiletries, beauty, kitchenware, footwear and home appliances. The food & grocery, fashion, home care, personal care, kitchen, electronics, products are some common types of the products purchased by customers of the organised retail industry.

Figure 7.2.6

Figure 7.2.7

Figure 7.2.8

The customers of fashion store retailers purchase all types of products from the stores, they offer. Women's wear, men's wear, kids wear, footwear and accessories are the most common products purchased by the customers of fashion store retailers. The majority of customers of all three fashion store retailers included in the study purchase Women's wear, men's wear, footwear and kids wear from the stores. Big Megamart and West Side are also getting a good sale of footwear, cosmetics, travel, toys and home products.

Figure 7.2.9

Figure 7.2.10

The customers of electronic store retailers purchase all types of products from the stores, they offer. TV, audio, home appliances, kitchen appliances, mobile phones, computer, cameras, gaming products and accessories are the most common products purchased by the customers of electronic store retailers. The majority of customers of both electronics stores retailers included in the study purchase entertainment items, home appliances, cameras, computers, phones, gaming products and accessories from the store.

7.2.13 Impulse buyers and types of products, the customers buy while impulse purchase

The majority of customers in the organised retail industry is impulse purchasers. The numbers of impulse buyers are high in case of all the multi-format hyper stores (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and Big Bazaar) in comparison to the industry mean value. But, D-Mart (multi-format superstore) is getting fewer footfalls from the impulse buyers in comparison to the industry mean value as well as multi-format hyper store included in the study.

Retailers	Impulse purchasing			
	Yes		No	
	f	%	f	%
	HyperCITY	184	92.00	16
Star Bazaar	190	95.00	10	5.00
more.MEGASStore	178	89.00	22	11.00
Big Bazaar	185	92.50	15	7.50
D Mart	159	79.50	41	20.50
Big Megamart	188	94.00	12	6.00
West Side	186	93.00	14	7.00
Max	179	89.50	21	10.50
Reliance Digital	128	64.00	72	36.00
NEXT	81	40.50	119	59.50
Mean	165.80	82.90	34.20	17.10
Standard Deviation	35.238	17.619	35.238	17.619

The numbers of impulse buyers are also high in case of all the fashion stores (i.e. Big Megamart, West Side and Max) in comparison to the industry mean value. However, the electronics retailers are not getting fewer footfalls of the impulse buyers in comparison to the industry mean value.

Figure 7.2.11

Figure 7.2.12

Figure 7.2.13

Figure 7.2.14

Figure 7.2.15

Food & grocery, beauty, electronics, fashion products are the most common type of products purchased by impulse buyers from the stores of the multi-format organised retailers (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar and D-Mart).

Figure 7.2.16

Figure 7.2.17

Figure 7.2.18

Women's wear, men's wear, kid's wear, foot wears and accessories are the most common type of products purchased by impulse buyers from the stores of fashion store retailers (i.e. Big Megamart, West Side and Max).

Figure 7.2.19

Figure 7.2.20

Accessories are the most common type of products purchased by impulse buyers from the stores of electronics store retailers (i.e. Reliance Digital and Next). However, the NEXT is also getting the impulse buyers in the categories of personal care, phones, games, and computer accessories.

7.2.14 Reasons of impulse purchase by customers

According to the customers of organised retail industry, the common and important reasons for impulse purchase are (in order of most important to least important): price reductions, multi-item discounts, the point of purchase display, demonstration and samples, salespeople, store atmosphere, store layout, coupons, packaging and shelving techniques. The majority of customers makes impulse purchases due to price reductions, multi-item discounts, the point of purchase display, demonstration and samples and salespeople.

In the case of customers of multi-format organised retailers (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar and D Mart) included in this study, two most important reasons for their impulse purchase are price reductions and multi-item discounts on products.

As per the customers of fashion store retailers (i.e. Big Megamart, West Side and Max), the most important reasons for their impulse purchase are multi-item discounts, the point of purchase display, price reductions, store atmosphere and salespeople. The customers of electronics stores prefer less impulse purchase in comparison to customers of multi-format and fashion store organised retailers. According to the customers of electronics store retailers (i.e. Reliance Digital and Next), the most important reasons for their impulse purchase are multi-item discounts, price reductions and salespeople.

Table 7.2.13: Reasons of impulse purchase by customers

Retailers	Reasons																			
	Point of purchase display		Price reductions		Store layout		Coupons		Shelving techniques		Demonstration and samples		Multi-item discounts		Packaging		Store atmosphere		Salespeople	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
HyperCITY	58	29.00	82	41.00	15	7.50	22	11.00	16	8.00	38	19.00	69	34.50	28	14.00	42	21.00	26	13.00
Star Bazaar	62	31.00	76	38.00	20	10.00	35	17.50	10	5.00	52	26.00	72	36.00	30	15.00	28	14.00	39	19.50
more.MEGAStore	43	21.50	71	35.50	28	14.00	12	6.00	20	10.00	48	24.00	65	32.50	22	11.00	38	19.00	33	16.50
Big Bazaar	68	34.00	80	40.00	33	16.50	40	20.00	28	14.00	56	28.00	76	38.00	32	16.00	45	22.50	40	20.00
D Mart	12	6.00	88	44.00	8	4.00	28	14.00	3	1.50	22	11.00	79	39.50	12	6.00	5	2.50	12	6.00
Big Megamart	70	35.00	68	34.00	49	24.50	18	9.00	32	16.00	45	22.50	80	40.00	24	12.00	58	29.00	48	24.00
West Side	75	37.50	70	35.00	42	21.00	32	16.00	29	14.50	48	24.00	82	41.00	22	11.00	62	31.00	53	26.50
Max	66	33.00	62	31.00	38	19.00	29	14.50	26	13.00	41	20.50	73	36.50	19	9.50	59	29.50	47	23.50
Reliance Digital	40	20.00	49	24.50	11	5.50	13	6.50	9	4.50	38	19.00	49	24.50	8	4.00	12	6.00	51	25.50
NEXT	32	16.00	38	19.00	5	2.50	7	3.50	3	1.50	17	8.50	39	19.50	9	4.50	9	4.50	43	21.50
Mean	52.60	26.30	68.40	34.20	24.90	12.45	23.60	11.80	17.60	8.80	40.50	20.25	68.40	34.20	20.60	10.30	35.80	17.90	39.20	19.60
Standard Deviation	20.173	10.086	15.320	7.660	15.337	7.668	10.926	5.463	10.967	5.483	12.528	6.264	14.049	7.025	8.553	4.277	21.447	10.723	12.630	6.315

7.2.15 The first preference of the customers while purchasing

The majority of customers' first preference is either quality or brand in the organised retail industry. However, the good news for the organised retailers is that there are also a great percentage of customers in the organised retail industry, whose first preference is discounts, schemes, price, quantity and other; while purchasing. The highest number of quality and brand conscious customers are from fashion store retailers (i.e. Big Megamart, West Side and Max). The highest number of price and quantity conscious customers are from multi-format organised retailers (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar and D▲Mart); while discounts and schemes conscious customers can be found from all organised retailers.

Table 7.2.14: The first preference of the customers while purchasing

Retailers	Variables for preference													
	Quality		Brand		Price		Quantity		Discounts		Schemes		Others	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
HyperCITY	52	26.00	41	20.50	26	13.00	22	11.00	28	14.00	26	13.00	5	2.50
Star Bazaar	37	18.50	30	15.00	32	16.00	29	14.50	34	17.00	32	16.00	6	3.00
more.MEGASStore	28	14.00	33	16.50	35	17.50	26	13.00	40	20.00	34	17.00	4	2.00
Big Bazaar	40	20.00	41	20.50	24	12.00	21	10.50	37	18.50	35	17.50	2	1.00
D▲Mart	23	11.50	21	10.50	31	15.50	31	15.50	45	22.50	44	22.00	5	2.50
Big Megamart	61	30.50	59	29.50	20	10.00	10	5.00	23	11.50	22	11.00	5	2.50
West Side	63	31.50	61	30.50	18	9.00	8	4.00	23	11.50	21	10.50	6	3.00
Max	60	30.00	57	28.50	21	10.50	9	4.50	24	12.00	25	12.50	4	2.00
Reliance Digital	50	25.00	47	23.50	26	13.00	20	10.00	26	13.00	28	14.00	3	1.50
NEXT	42	21.00	39	19.50	30	15.00	23	11.50	31	15.50	31	15.50	4	2.00
Mean	45.60	22.80	42.90	21.45	26.30	13.15	19.90	9.95	31.10	15.55	29.80	14.90	4.40	2.20
Standard Deviation	13.930	6.965	13.203	6.602	5.638	2.819	8.279	4.140	7.695	3.847	6.925	3.462	1.265	0.632

7.2.16 Reasons for visiting a particular store by customers

The customers in the organised retail industry, visit the particular organised retail stores due to several reasons, most notably, (in order of most important to least important as per the industry mean value calculated from the responses of customers): *merchandise* (merchandise assortment- variety of merchandise and brands, quality of assortment, in service situations, merchandise offered as part of service, styling or fashion guarantee, warranties and pricing, reasonable prices), *promotion* (advertising, displays, trading stamps, sales promotion- discount & special schemes, symbol and colours), *store atmosphere* (atmosphere of congeniality, customers' feeling of warmth, acceptance or ease, good & spacious ambience, and delighting store environment), *convenience* (general convenience, parking access, location convenience- proximity to home/office), *services* (service in general, salesclerk service, presence of self-service, ease of merchandise return, delivery service, phone ordering and credit policy), *physical facilities* (elevators, lighting, air conditioning, restrooms, store layout, shopping ease, aisle placement, carpeting and architecture), *post-transaction satisfaction* (merchandise in use, return & adjustment policy), *institutional factors* (projection of store- conservative or modern, reputation, reliability), *clientele* (social class appeal, store personnel, fit between self-image and store image- self-image congruence), *other* (friends suggested, no other store nearby, convenient store hours).

The merchandise (merchandise assortment- variety of merchandise and brands, quality of assortment, in service situations, merchandise offered as part of service, styling or fashion guarantee, warranties and pricing, reasonable prices) is the primary reason for visiting the stores among the customers of multi-format retailers (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar except D⁺Mart) as well as electronics-item superstores (i.e. Reliance Digital and NEXT) included in the study. As the promotion (advertising, displays, trading stamps, sales promotion- discount & special schemes, symbol and colours) is the primary reason for visiting the store by customers of D⁺Mart.

However, the store atmosphere (atmosphere of congeniality, customers' feeling of warmth, acceptance or ease, good & spacious ambience, and delighting

store environment) is the primary reason for visiting the stores among the customers of fashion store retailers (i.e. Big Megamart, West Side and Max).

The *convenience* (general convenience, parking access, location convenience-proximity to home/office) is a second reason for visiting the stores among the customers of multi-format retailers (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, D▲Mart except Big Bazaar). As the promotion (advertising, displays, trading stamps, sales promotion- discount & special schemes, symbol and colours) is a second reason for visiting the store by customers of Big Bazaar.

However, the merchandise (merchandise assortment- variety of merchandise and brands, quality of assortment, in service situations, merchandise offered as part of service, styling or fashion guarantee, warranties and pricing, reasonable prices) is a second reason for visiting the stores among the customers of fashion store retailers (i.e. Big Megamart, West Side and Max). Moreover, *services* (service in general, sales-clerk service, the presence of self-service, ease of merchandise return, delivery service, phone ordering and credit policy) is a second reason for visiting the stores among the customers of Reliance Digital and promotion is a second reason for visiting the store by customers of NEXT.

The promotion (advertising, displays, trading stamps, sales promotion-discount & special schemes, symbol and colours) is a third reason for visiting the stores among the customers of two multi-format retailers (i.e. Star Bazaar and more.MEGASStore); while, store atmosphere (atmosphere of congeniality, customers' feeling of warmth, acceptance or ease, good & spacious ambience, and delighting store environment) is a third reason for visiting the stores by customers of HyperCITY; *convenience* (general convenience, parking access, location convenience - proximity to home/office) is a third reason for visiting the stores by customers of Big Bazaar (a multi-format hyper store), two fashion-item superstores (i.e. West Side and Max) and Reliance Digital (an electronics superstore), and merchandise (merchandise assortment- variety of merchandise and brands, quality of assortment, in service situations, merchandise offered as part of service, styling or fashion guarantee, warranties and pricing, reasonable prices) is a third reason for visiting the stores by customers of D▲Mart.

Table 7.2.15: Reasons for visiting a particular store by customers

Retailers	Reasons for visiting																			
	Merchandise		Services		Clientele		Physical Facilities		Convenience		Promotion		Store Atmospheres		Institutional Factors		Post-transaction Satisfaction		Others	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
HyperCITY	120	60.00	98	49.00	65	32.50	90	45.00	107	53.50	98	49.00	105	52.50	63	31.50	69	34.50	53	26.50
Star Bazaar	119	59.50	97	48.50	61	30.50	88	44.00	101	50.50	97	48.50	95	47.50	55	27.50	65	32.50	59	29.50
more.MEGASStore	115	57.50	97	48.50	62	31.00	86	43.00	102	51.00	101	50.50	92	46.00	52	26.00	70	35.00	51	25.50
Big Bazaar	114	57.00	104	52.00	64	32.00	92	46.00	109	54.50	110	55.00	108	54.00	63	31.50	72	36.00	55	27.50
D Mart	90	45.00	70	35.00	40	20.00	61	30.50	88	44.00	119	59.50	47	23.50	32	16.00	32	16.00	50	25.00
Big Megamart	117	58.50	103	51.50	66	33.00	93	46.50	102	51.00	93	46.50	118	59.00	79	39.50	73	36.50	61	30.50
West Side	118	59.00	101	50.50	67	33.50	91	45.50	107	53.50	96	48.00	126	63.00	82	41.00	74	37.00	60	30.00
Max	106	53.00	98	49.00	63	31.50	87	43.50	103	51.50	91	45.50	112	56.00	73	36.50	68	34.00	52	26.00
Reliance Digital	114	57.00	105	52.50	68	34.00	79	39.50	101	50.50	96	48.00	92	46.00	69	34.50	66	33.00	53	26.50
NEXT	121	60.50	93	46.50	49	24.50	72	36.00	89	44.50	110	55.00	79	39.50	50	25.00	61	30.50	53	26.50
Mean	113.40	56.70	96.60	48.30	60.50	30.25	83.90	41.95	100.90	50.45	101.10	50.55	97.40	48.70	61.80	30.90	65.00	32.50	54.70	27.35
Standard Deviation	9.264	4.632	10.058	5.029	8.960	4.480	10.311	5.156	7.109	3.555	8.975	4.487	22.530	11.265	15.106	7.553	12.247	6.124	3.917	1.959

However, *services* (service in general, sales-clerk service, the presence of self-service, ease of merchandise return, delivery service, phone ordering and credit policy) is a third reason for visiting the stores by the customers of Big Megamart (a fashion-item hyper store) and NEXT (an electronics-item superstore).

7.2.17 Customers of organised retailers, visiting other stores / loyal customers of the organised retailers

Retailers	Customers visiting other stores			
	Yes		No	
	f	%	f	%
	HyperCITY	117	58.50	83
Star Bazaar	112	56.00	88	44.00
more.MEGASStore	109	54.50	91	45.50
Big Bazaar	106	53.00	94	47.00
D▲Mart	121	60.50	79	39.50
Big Megamart	131	65.50	69	34.50
West Side	125	62.50	75	37.50
Max	123	61.50	77	38.50
Reliance Digital	142	71.00	58	29.00
NEXT	146	73.00	54	27.00
Mean	123.20	61.60	76.80	38.40
Standard Deviation	13.348	6.674	13.348	6.674

The majority of customers in the organised retail industry visit more than one retail store. However, the industry has a great number of loyal customers. The multi-format organised retailers included in this study (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar, and D▲Mart) have more loyal customers in comparison to the others as well as industry mean value. However, among the multi-format organised retailers, the hyper stores (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and Big Bazaar) have also more loyal customers in comparison to a super store (i.e. D▲Mart).

The fashion store retailers (i.e. Big Megamart, West Side and Max) have less loyal customers and their majority of customers visiting other stores in comparison to the industry mean value. Moreover, the electronics store retailer's situation is poorer in having loyal customers. They have lesser loyal customers and their majority of customers visiting other stores in comparison to the industry mean value.

7.2.18 Type of stores visited by customers of organised retailers other than their stores

Retailers	Type of stores					
	Organised retail store		Unorganised retail store		Both	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
HyperCITY	46	39.32	20	17.09	51	43.59
Star Bazaar	36	32.14	27	24.11	49	43.75
more.MEGASStore	37	33.94	25	22.94	47	43.12
Big Bazaar	36	33.96	18	16.98	52	49.06
D ⁺ Mart	15	12.40	44	36.36	62	51.24
Big Megamart	40	30.53	24	18.32	67	51.15
West Side	36	28.80	21	16.80	68	54.40
Max	28	22.76	25	20.33	70	56.91
Reliance Digital	25	17.61	38	26.76	79	55.63
NEXT	19	13.01	42	28.77	85	58.22
Mean	31.80	26.45	28.40	22.85	63.00	50.71
Standard Deviation	9.750	9.443	9.419	6.373	13.115	5.702

In the organised retail industry, the majority of customers (among, who also visits other stores than the regular one) visit both organised as well as unorganised retail stores. However, there are also a great number of customers, who only visit other organised retail stores or unorganised retail stores. The customers of multi-format retail stores (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar), who visit both organised and unorganised retail stores (other than these stores) are less in comparison to others and especially D⁺Mart(a multi-format super store) & industry mean value.

The customers of electronics-item superstores (i.e. Reliance Digital and NEXT), who visit only unorganised retail stores (other than these stores) or more in the comparison industry mean value. The customers of some other retailers (i.e. Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and D⁺Mart) who visit only unorganised retail stores (other than these stores) are also more in comparison to the industry mean value and other retailers included in this study except customers of electronics-item superstores. The customers of multi-format retail stores (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar) and two fashion store retailers (i.e. Big Megamart and West Side), who visit only organised retail stores (other than these stores) are more in comparison others and the industry mean value.

7.2.19 Reasons for visiting other stores by customers

Retailers	Reasons																			
	Merchandise		Service		Clientele		Physical Facilities		Convenience		Promotion		Store Atmospheres		Institutional factors		Post-transaction satisfaction		Others	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
HyperCITY	70	59.829	72	61.538	21	17.949	38	32.479	48	41.026	46	39.316	39	33.333	28	23.932	12	10.256	23	19.658
Star Bazaar	68	60.714	69	61.607	15	13.393	33	29.464	50	44.643	41	36.607	35	31.250	24	21.429	14	12.500	26	23.214
more.MEGASStore	72	66.055	68	62.385	17	15.596	29	26.606	46	42.202	45	41.284	33	30.275	16	14.679	15	13.761	19	17.431
Big Bazaar	54	50.943	67	63.208	14	13.208	25	23.585	41	38.679	52	49.057	32	30.189	18	16.981	9	8.491	25	23.585
D Mart	88	72.727	91	75.207	10	8.264	42	34.711	38	31.405	65	53.719	42	34.711	12	9.917	17	14.050	20	16.529
Big Megamart	67	51.145	71	54.198	23	17.557	29	22.137	34	25.954	35	26.718	27	20.611	32	24.427	9	6.870	31	23.664
West Side	69	55.200	70	56.000	21	16.800	23	18.400	36	28.800	39	31.200	25	20.000	33	26.400	13	10.400	29	23.200
Max	76	61.789	78	63.415	19	15.447	26	21.138	28	22.764	42	34.146	29	23.577	31	25.203	10	8.130	26	21.138
Reliance Digital	75	52.817	81	57.042	18	12.676	49	34.507	48	33.803	62	43.662	56	39.437	46	32.394	28	19.718	23	16.197
NEXT	61	41.781	89	60.959	11	7.534	59	40.411	52	35.616	67	45.890	59	40.411	49	33.562	32	21.918	21	14.384
Mean	70.000	57.300	75.600	61.556	16.900	13.842	35.300	28.344	42.100	34.489	49.400	40.160	37.700	30.379	28.900	22.892	15.900	12.609	24.300	19.900
Standard Deviation	9.068	8.797	8.771	5.763	4.358	3.620	11.691	7.130	7.923	7.279	11.501	8.299	11.653	7.152	12.124	7.439	7.923	4.955	3.860	3.540

The customers in the organised retail industry, visit the other retail stores due to several reasons, most notably, (in order of most important to least important as per the industry mean value calculated from the responses of customers): *services* (service in general, salesclerk service, presence of self-service, ease of merchandise return, delivery service, phone ordering and credit policy), *merchandise* (merchandise assortment- variety of merchandise and brands, quality of assortment, in service situations, merchandise offered as part of service, styling or fashion guarantee, warranties and pricing, reasonable prices), *promotion* (advertising, displays, trading stamps, sales promotion- discount &

special schemes, symbol and colours), *convenience* (general convenience, parking access, location convenience- proximity to home/office), *store atmosphere* (atmosphere of congeniality, customers' feeling of warmth, acceptance or ease, good & spacious ambience, and delighting store environment), *physical facilities* (elevators, lighting, air conditioning, restrooms, store layout, shopping ease, aisle placement, carpeting and architecture), *institutional factors* (projection of store- conservative or modern, reputation, reliability), *other* (friends suggested, no other store nearby, convenient store hours), *clientele* (social class appeal, store personnel, fit between self-image and store image- self-image congruence), *post-transaction satisfaction* (merchandise in use, return & adjustment policy). The majority visits other stores in the search of better services, merchandise, promotional offers, convenience, store atmospheres and physical facilities.

FACTORS INFLUENCING BUYING BEHAVIOUR OF CUSTOMERS IN THE ORGANISED RETAIL INDUSTRY

7.3.1 The influence of sociological / environmental / external factors on buying behaviour of customers

Figure 7.3.1

The sociological / environmental / external factors [i.e. cultural, sub-cultural, society, status in society (social class), reference group, family life cycle and role in the family] significantly influence the buying behaviour of customers in the organised retail industry. The calculated weighted average scores (WAS) for the influence of sociological / environmental / external factors on buying behaviour of customers are supporting the statement.

The sociological / environmental / external factors have more influence on buying behaviour of customers of HyperCITY and D Mart in comparison to other multi-format organised retailers (i.e. Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and Big Bazaar).

Table 7.3.1: The influence of sociological / environmental / external factors on buying behaviour of customers

Retailers	Influence										Weighted Average Score (WAS)
	Extremely Influenced		Influenced		Neither Influenced Nor Uninfluenced		Uninfluenced		Not at all Influenced		
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
HyperCITY	60	30.00	86	43.00	34	17.00	13	6.50	7	3.50	0.895
Star Bazaar	58	29.00	78	39.00	39	19.50	15	7.50	10	5.00	0.795
more.MEGAStore	59	29.50	75	37.50	34	17.00	20	10.00	12	6.00	0.745
Big Bazaar	63	31.5	73	36.50	30	15.00	23	11.50	11	5.50	0.770
D Mart	66	33.00	76	38.00	32	16.00	18	9.00	8	4.00	0.870
Big Megamart	65	32.50	76	38.00	28	14.00	20	10.00	11	5.50	0.820
West Side	63	31.50	72	36.00	32	16.00	21	10.50	12	6.00	0.765
Max	63	31.50	71	35.50	32	16.00	22	11.00	12	6.00	0.755
Reliance Digital	62	31.00	69	34.50	33	16.50	24	12.00	12	6.00	0.725
NEXT	59	29.50	66	33.00	32	16.00	27	13.50	16	8.00	0.625
Mean	61.80	30.90	74.20	37.10	32.60	16.30	20.30	10.15	11.10	5.55	0.777
Standard Deviation	2.700	1.350	5.493	2.747	2.875	1.438	4.165	2.082	2.470	1.235	0.076

The sociological / environmental / external factors also have more influence on buying behaviour of customers of Big Megamart in comparison to other fashion store organised retailers (i.e. West Side and Max). However, the influence of sociological / environmental / external factors on buying behaviour of customers of electronics store retailers included in the study (i.e. Reliance Digital and NEXT) is less in comparison to other retailers and industry mean value.

7.3.2 The influence of psychological / individual / internal factors on buying behaviour of customers

Figure 7.3.2

The psychological / individual / internal factors (i.e. self-image, personality, personal values, lifestyle, memory, learning, perception, motivation, emotions, mood, involvement, information processing, beliefs, intention, attitude, communication, and persuasion) significantly influence the buying behaviour of customers in the organised retail industry. The calculated weighted average scores (WAS) for the influence of psychological / individual / internal factors on buying behaviour of customers are supporting the statement. The psychological / individual / internal factors significantly influence the buying behaviour of customers of all the multi-format hyper store organised retailers included in this study (HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and Big Bazaar) except D Mart (a multi-format superstore). The psychological / individual / internal factors have more influence on buying behaviour of customers of HyperCITY in comparison to other multi-format hyper store organised retailers (i.e. Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and Big Bazaar).

Table 7.3.2: The influence of psychological / individual / internal factors on buying behaviour of customers

Retailers	Influence										Weighted Average Score (WAS)
	Extremely Influenced		Influenced		Neither Influenced Nor Uninfluenced		Uninfluenced		Not at all Influenced		
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
HyperCITY	61	30.50	76	38.00	43	21.50	14	7.00	6	3.00	0.860
Star Bazaar	57	28.50	70	35.00	34	17.00	24	12.00	15	7.50	0.650
more.MEGASStore	56	28.00	68	34.00	30	15.00	29	14.50	17	8.50	0.585
Big Bazaar	58	29.00	66	33.00	28	14.00	30	15.00	18	9.00	0.580
D Mart	53	26.50	61	30.50	32	16.00	35	17.50	19	9.50	0.470
Big Megamart	61	30.50	69	34.50	28	14.00	27	13.50	15	7.50	0.670
West Side	57	28.50	65	32.50	25	12.50	31	15.50	22	11.00	0.520
Max	61	30.50	67	33.50	27	13.50	26	13.00	19	9.50	0.625
Reliance Digital	56	28.00	62	31.00	33	16.50	32	16.00	17	8.50	0.540
NEXT	51	25.50	58	29.00	32	16.00	37	18.50	22	11.00	0.395
Mean	57.10	28.55	670	33.10	31.20	15.60	28.50	14.25	17.00	8.50	0.590
Standard Deviation	3.381	1.691	5.116	2.558	5.051	2.525	6.451	3.225	4.570	2.285	0.127

The psychological / individual / internal factors have more influence on buying behaviour of customers of Big Megamart in comparison to other fashion store organised retailers (i.e. West Side and Max). However, the influence of psychological / individual / internal factors on buying behaviour of customers of Reliance Digital is significant and insignificant in case of NEXT.

7.3.3 The influence of store related factors on buying behaviour of customers

Figure 7.3.3

The store related factors (i.e. store image, store atmosphere, store brands, store location, sales personnel, discounts & schemes, and free services) significantly influence the buying behaviour of customers in the organised retail industry. The calculated weighted average scores (WAS) for the influence of store related factors on buying behaviour of customers are supporting the statement.

The store related factors significantly influence the buying behaviour of customers of all the multi-format hyper store organised retailers included in this study (HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and Big Bazaar) except D Mart (a multi-format superstore).

The store related factors have more influence on buying behaviour of customers of HyperCITY in comparison to other multi-format hyper store organised retailers (i.e. Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and Big Bazaar).

Table 7.3.3: The influence of store related factors on buying behaviour of customers

Retailers	Influence										Weighted Average Score (WAS)
	Extremely Influenced		Influenced		Neither Influenced Nor Uninfluenced		Uninfluenced		Not at all Influenced		
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
HyperCITY	57	28.50	74	37.00	40	20.00	19	9.50	10	5.00	0.745
Star Bazaar	55	27.50	68	34.00	26	13.00	32	16.00	19	9.50	0.540
more.MEGASStore	56	28.00	68	34.00	25	12.50	32	16.00	19	9.50	0.550
Big Bazaar	58	29.00	68	34.00	25	12.50	31	15.50	18	9.00	0.585
D ⁺ Mart	51	25.50	56	28.00	32	16.00	37	18.50	24	12.00	0.365
Big Megamart	61	30.50	68	34.00	27	13.50	25	12.50	19	9.50	0.635
West Side	62	31.00	69	34.50	28	14.00	24	12.00	17	8.50	0.675
Max	61	30.50	69	34.50	27	13.50	24	12.00	19	9.50	0.645
Reliance Digital	60	30.00	64	32.00	30	15.00	27	13.50	19	9.50	0.595
NEXT	59	29.50	61	30.50	30	15.00	31	15.50	19	9.50	0.550
Mean	58.00	29.00	66.50	33.25	29.00	14.50	28.20	14.10	18.30	9.15	0.589
Standard Deviation	3.367	1.683	4.994	2.497	4.497	2.249	5.308	2.654	3.434	1.717	0.102

The store related factors also have more influence on buying behaviour of customers of West Side in comparison to other fashion store organised retailers (i.e. Max and Big Megamart). However, the influence of store related factors on buying behaviour of customers of electronics store retailers included in the study (i.e. Reliance Digital and NEXT) is significant.

7.3.4 Factors influencing buying behaviour of customers of multi-format organised retailers

Figure 7.3.4

Figure 7.3.5

Figure 7.3.6

Figure 7.3.7

Figure 7.3.8

The sociological factors (i.e. cultural, sub-cultural, society, status in society (social class), reference group, family life cycle, and role in the family), psychological factors (i.e. self-image, personality, personal values, lifestyle, memory, learning, perception, motivation, emotions, mood, involvement, information processing, beliefs, intention, attitude, communication, and persuasion) and store related factors (i.e. store image, store atmosphere, store brands, store location, sales personnel, discounts & schemes, and free services) significantly influence buying behaviour of customers of multi-format organised retailers.

7.3.5 Factors influencing buying behaviour of customers of fashion store organised retailers

Figure 7.3.9

Figure 7.3.10

Figure 7.3.11

The sociological factors (i.e. cultural, sub-cultural, society, status in society (social class), reference group, family life cycle, and role in the family), psychological factors (i.e. self-image, personality, personal values, lifestyle, memory, learning, perception, motivation, emotions, mood, involvement, information processing, beliefs, intention, attitude, communication, and persuasion) and store related factors (i.e. store image, store atmosphere, store brands, store location, sales personnel, discounts & schemes, and free services) significantly influence buying behaviour of customers of fashion store organised retailers.

7.3.6 Factors influencing buying behaviour of customers of electronics store organised retailers

Figure 7.3.12

Figure 7.3.13

The sociological factors (i.e. cultural, sub-cultural, society, status in society (social class), reference group, family life cycle, and role in the family), psychological factors (i.e. self-image, personality, personal values, lifestyle, memory, learning, perception, motivation, emotions, mood, involvement, information processing, beliefs, intention, attitude, communication, and persuasion) and store related factors (i.e. store image, store atmosphere, store brands, store location, sales personnel, discounts & schemes, and free services) significantly influence buying behaviour of customers of electronics stores organised retailers.

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**Customer
satisfaction with
the merchandise
(products) and
services offered
by organised
retail industry**

-
- Customer satisfaction with merchandise (products) and services
 - Testing of hypotheses

CHAPTER 8

CUSTOMER SATISFACTION WITH MERCHANDISE (PRODUCTS) AND SERVICES OFFERED BY ORGANISED RETAIL INDUSTRY

Introduction

This chapter comprises the analysis of the various data pertained to customer satisfaction with merchandise and services offered by organised retail industry, which have been collected through the individual questionnaire from the customers of the respective stores in a personal interaction.

For a better analysis of the customer satisfaction, the customer expectations with merchandise and services have also been taken into the consideration for the study. And the responses pertained to the customer satisfaction have been collected on five point expectation cum satisfaction scale (basically an ordinal scale) ranging from greatly exceeding expectations and delighted (5), exceeding expectations and happy (4), matching expectations and satisfied (3), less than expectations and dissatisfied (2) and much less than expectations and disappointed (1).

The weighted average scores (WAS) for all the variables (included in the study for customer satisfaction) and / or all the organised retailers (included in the study) have been computed and presented in the line chart for a comparative analysis. Moreover, the statistics [i.e. frequency of responses (f), the percentage of responses (%), mean, standard deviation, weighted average scores (WAS)] of all the variables (included in the study for customer satisfaction) and / or all the organised retailers included in the study (i.e. multi-format (item) retailers, specialised fashion item retailers and specialised electronics item retailers) have also been presented in the tables for a better comparative analysis. Further, results have been interpreted and discussed to reach on some inferences at the end of the different sections.

Further, this chapter also comprises the testing of the hypotheses, which are supposed to be tested.

8.1. Customer satisfaction with merchandise assortment

Figure 8.1: Weighted average scores (WAS) for customer satisfaction with merchandise assortment

The mean WAS of all the organised retailers (included in this study) has been considered as the WAS of the industry for *customer satisfaction with merchandise assortment* and exhibited with the red line in *figure 8.1*. This WAS of the industry falls above the satisfied customer line in *figure 8.1*, which delineates that the organised retail industry satisfies a vast majority of customers with its *merchandise assortment*.

The WAS for customer satisfaction with *merchandise assortment* of some retailers (i.e. Big Bazaar, HyperCITY, Big Megamart and West Side) are greater than the WAS of the industry, which indicates that these retailers satisfy more customers with their *merchandise assortment* than others (included in this study) in the industry.

The most (i.e. 31.10%) customers are satisfied with *merchandise assortment* offered by the organised retailers (included in this study), as it matches with their expectations. The second largest group (i.e. 26.25%) of customers, who perceive that *merchandise assortment* is exceeding their expectations and they are

happy with it. The third major group (i.e. 21.65%) of customers is delighted with *merchandise assortment*, as it is greatly exceeding their expectations. However, there are also a massive number of customers, who are either dissatisfied (i.e. 13.10%) or disappointed (i.e. 7.90%) with *merchandise assortment*, because, the same is less than or much less than their expectations.

Table 8.1: Comparative statistics of customer satisfaction with merchandise assortment

Retailers	Responses on expectation cum satisfaction scale										Weighted Average Score (WAS)
	5		4		3		2		1		
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
HyperCITY	45	22.50	54	27.00	59	29.50	26	13.00	16	8.00	3.430
Star Bazaar	40	20.00	50	25.00	65	32.50	28	14.00	17	8.50	3.340
more.MEGAStore	39	19.50	48	24.00	64	32.00	31	15.50	18	9.00	3.295
Big Bazaar	49	24.50	59	29.50	66	33.00	17	8.50	9	4.50	3.610
D ⁺ Mart	38	19.00	48	24.00	60	30.00	33	16.50	21	10.50	3.245
Big Megamart	51	25.50	59	29.50	67	33.50	14	7.00	9	4.50	3.645
West Side	47	23.50	55	27.50	64	32.00	24	12.00	10	5.00	3.525
Max	41	20.50	49	24.50	62	31.00	29	14.50	19	9.50	3.320
Reliance Digital	39	19.50	51	25.50	57	28.50	31	15.50	22	11.00	3.270
NEXT	44	22.00	52	26.00	58	29.00	29	14.50	17	8.50	3.385
Mean	43.30	21.65	52.50	26.25	62.20	31.10	26.20	13.10	15.80	7.90	3.407
Standard Deviation	4.596	2.298	4.143	2.072	3.521	1.761	6.233	3.116	4.826	2.413	0.337

Big Bazaar leads in satisfying more customers with its *merchandise assortment* in comparison to its competitors or other multi-format retailers included in the study (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and D Mart), while, Big Megamart is a leader in satisfying more customers with its *merchandise assortment* in comparison to its competitors or other fashion item retailers included in the study (i.e. West Side and Max) and in the case of electronics item retailers included in this study, NEXT satisfies more customers with its *merchandise assortment* than its competitor included in the study (i.e. Reliance Digital).

8.2. Customer satisfaction with merchandise categories in the assortment

Figure 8.2: Weighted average scores (WAS) for customer satisfaction with merchandise categories in the assortment

The mean WAS of all the organised retailers (included in this study) has been perceived as the WAS of the industry for *customer satisfaction with merchandise categories in the assortment* and shown with the red line in *figure 8.2*. This WAS of the industry falls above the satisfied customer line in *figure 8.2*, which depicts that the organised retail industry satisfies a great majority of customers with its *merchandise categories (e.g. basic or staple, fashion, seasonal, consumer durable, etc.) in the assortment*.

The WAS for customer satisfaction with *merchandise categories in the assortment* of some retailers (i.e. Big Bazaar, West Side, Big Megamart, NEXT and HyperCITY) are greater than the WAS of the industry, which reveals that these retailers satisfy more customers with their *merchandise categories in the assortment* than others (included in this study) in the industry.

Table 8.2: Comparative statistics of customer satisfaction with merchandise categories in the assortment

Retailers	Responses on expectation cum satisfaction scale										Weighted Average Score (WAS)
	5		4		3		2		1		
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
HyperCITY	41	20.50	48	24.00	58	29.00	32	16.00	21	10.50	3.280
Star Bazaar	38	19.00	49	24.50	58	29.00	33	16.50	22	11.00	3.240
more.MEGASStore	36	18.00	48	24.00	55	27.50	37	18.50	24	12.00	3.175
Big Bazaar	45	22.50	53	26.50	63	31.50	26	13.00	13	6.50	3.455
D [▲] Mart	32	16.00	43	21.50	59	29.50	38	19.00	28	14.00	3.065
Big Megamart	43	21.50	51	25.50	60	30.00	31	15.50	15	7.50	3.380
West Side	41	20.50	52	26.00	59	29.50	32	16.00	16	8.00	3.350
Max	37	18.50	47	23.50	54	27.00	36	18.00	26	13.00	3.165
Reliance Digital	37	18.50	46	23.00	55	27.50	36	18.00	26	13.00	3.160
NEXT	42	21.00	50	25.00	53	26.50	33	16.50	22	11.00	3.285
Mean	39.20	19.60	48.70	24.35	57.40	28.70	33.40	16.70	21.30	10.65	3.256
Standard Deviation	3.882	1.941	2.983	1.492	3.098	1.549	3.534	1.767	5.100	2.550	0.264

The maximal (i.e. 28.70%) customers are satisfied with *merchandise categories in the assortment* offered by the organised retailers (included in this study), as those are matching with their expectations. The second verdant group (i.e. 24.35%) of customers, who deem that *merchandise categories in the assortment* are exceeding their expectations and they are happy. The industry also delights an ample number (i.e. 19.60%) of customers with *merchandise categories in the assortment* by greatly exceeding them than customers' expectations. The next gigantic group (i.e. 16.70%) of customers is dissatisfied with *merchandise categories in the assortment* because these are deficient to their expectations. Moreover, there is also a non-negligible number (i.e. 10.65%) of customers, those are disappointed with *merchandise categories in the assortment* as the same is much less than their expectations.

Big Bazaar satisfies more customers with its *merchandise categories in the assortment* in comparison to its competitors or other multi-format retailers included in the study (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and D▲Mart). While, Big Megamart leads in satisfying more customers with its *merchandise categories in the assortment* in comparison to its competitors or other fashion item retailers included in the study (i.e. West Side and Max) and in the case of electronics item retailers included in this study, NEXT satisfies more customers with its *merchandise categories in the assortment* than its competitor included in the study (i.e. Reliance Digital).

8.3. Customer satisfaction with the variety of merchandise in each category

The mean WAS of all the organised retailers (included in this study) has been comprehended as the WAS of the industry for *customer satisfaction with the variety of merchandise in each category* and displayed with the red line in *figure 8.3*. This WAS of the industry indulges above the satisfied customer line in *figure 8.3*, which explicates that the organised retail industry satisfies an umpteenth majority of customers with its *the variety of merchandise in each category as per different sizes, colours, designs, price, quality, quantity and brands*.

The WAS for customer satisfaction with *the variety of merchandise in each category* of some retailers (i.e. HyperCITY, Big Bazaar, Big Megamart and West Side) are more than the WAS of the industry, which evinces that these retailers satisfy

more customers with their *the variety of merchandise in each category* than others (included in this study) in the industry.

Figure 8.3: Weighted average scores (WAS) for customer satisfaction with the variety of merchandise in each category

The maximum (i.e. 28.50%) customers are satisfied with *the variety of merchandise in each category* offered by the organised retailers (included in this study), as it is matching with their expectations. The second giant group (i.e. 23.45%) of customers, who comprehend that *the variety of merchandise in each category* are exceeding their expectations and they are happy.

Moreover, the industry has also an excessive number (i.e. 20.85%) of delighted customers with *the variety of merchandise in each category* by greatly exceeding the same than their expectations. The next plenteous group (i.e. 16.00%) of customers is dissatisfied with *the variety of merchandise in each category* because these are lacking to their expectations. However, there is also a non-negligible disappointed (i.e. 11.20%) customers with *the variety of merchandise in each category*, as the same is much less than their expectations.

Retailers	Responses on expectation cum satisfaction scale										Weighted Average Score (WAS)
	5		4		3		2		1		
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
HyperCITY	43	21.50	46	23.00	57	28.50	35	17.50	19	9.50	3.295
Star Bazaar	40	20.00	46	23.00	58	29.00	33	16.50	23	11.50	3.235
more.MEGASStore	39	19.50	44	22.00	55	27.50	37	18.50	25	12.50	3.175
Big Bazaar	49	24.50	57	28.50	61	30.50	20	10.00	13	6.50	3.545
D ⁺ Mart	35	17.50	43	21.50	58	29.00	37	18.50	27	13.50	3.110
Big Megamart	48	24.00	49	24.50	56	28.00	29	14.50	18	9.00	3.400
West Side	43	21.50	52	26.00	60	30.00	28	14.00	17	8.50	3.380
Max	39	19.50	45	22.50	54	27.00	33	16.50	29	14.50	3.160
Reliance Digital	40	20.00	43	21.50	55	27.50	35	17.50	27	13.50	3.170
NEXT	41	20.50	44	22.00	56	28.00	33	16.50	26	13.00	3.205
Mean	41.70	20.85	46.90	23.45	57.00	28.50	32.00	16.00	22.40	11.20	3.268
Standard Deviation	4.244	2.122	4.533	2.266	2.261	1.130	5.164	2.582	5.317	2.658	0.309

Big Bazaar is also a leader in satisfying more customers with its *variety of merchandise in each category* in comparison to its competitors or other multi-format retailers included in the study (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and D⁺Mart). While, Big Megamart leads in satisfying more customers with its *variety of merchandise in each category* in comparison to its competitors or other fashion item retailers included in the study (i.e. West Side and Max) and in the case of electronics item retailers included in this study, NEXT satisfies more customers with its *variety of merchandise in each category* than its competitor included in the study (i.e. Reliance Digital).

8.4. Customer satisfaction with availability of newly launched merchandise, customised merchandise, unique merchandise and complementary merchandise

Figure 8.4: Weighted average scores (WAS) for customer satisfaction with availability of newly launched merchandise, customised merchandise, unique merchandise and complementary merchandise

The mean WAS of all the organised retailers (included in this study) has been perceived as the WAS of the industry for *customer satisfaction with availability of newly launched merchandise, customised merchandise, unique merchandise and complementary merchandise* and shown with the red line in *figure 8.4*. This WAS of the industry exists above the satisfied customer line in *figure 8.4*, which exhorts that the organised retail industry satisfies an adequate majority of customers by making available *newly launched merchandise, customised merchandise, unique merchandise and complementary merchandise* in each category.

The WAS for customer satisfaction with *the availability of newly launched merchandise, customised merchandise, unique merchandise and complementary merchandise* of some retailers (i.e. Big Bazaar, Big Megamart and West Side) are more than the WAS of the industry, which manifests that these retailers satisfy more customers with *the availability of newly launched merchandise, customised merchandise, unique merchandise and complementary merchandise* than others (included in this study) in the industry.

Table 8.4: Comparative statistics of customer satisfaction with the availability of newly launched merchandise, customised merchandise, unique merchandise and complementary merchandise											
Retailers	Responses on expectation cum satisfaction scale										Weighted Average Score (WAS)
	5		4		3		2		1		
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
HyperCITY	38	19.00	49	24.50	59	29.50	32	16.00	22	11.00	3.245
Star Bazaar	36	18.00	50	25.00	52	26.00	36	18.00	26	13.00	3.170
more.MEGAStore	37	18.50	52	26.00	61	30.50	29	14.50	21	10.50	3.275
Big Bazaar	43	21.50	48	24.00	66	33.00	28	14.00	15	7.50	3.380
D ⁺ Mart	33	16.50	44	22.00	55	27.50	40	20.00	28	14.00	3.070
Big Megamart	42	21.00	51	25.50	65	32.50	28	14.00	14	7.00	3.395
West Side	41	20.50	49	24.50	64	32.00	29	14.50	17	8.50	3.340
Max	40	20.00	48	24.00	59	29.50	32	16.00	21	10.50	3.270
Reliance Digital	38	19.00	49	24.50	62	31.00	30	15.00	21	10.50	3.265
NEXT	37	18.50	50	25.00	60	30.00	33	16.50	20	10.00	3.255
Mean	38.50	19.25	49.00	24.50	60.30	30.15	31.70	15.85	20.50	10.25	3.267
Standard Deviation	3.028	1.514	2.160	1.080	4.373	2.186	3.860	1.930	4.403	2.202	0.245

The most (i.e. 30.15%) customers are satisfied with *the availability of newly launched merchandise, customised merchandise, unique merchandise and complementary merchandise* by the organised retailers (included in this study). The second exuberant group (i.e. 24.50%) of customers, who understand that *the availability of newly launched merchandise, customised merchandise, unique merchandise and*

complementary merchandise is exceeding their expectations and they are happy. Moreover, the industry has also an intense number (i.e. 19.25%) of delighted customers with *the availability of newly launched merchandise, customised merchandise, unique merchandise and complementary merchandise*. The next enormous group (i.e. 20.85%) of customers is dissatisfied with *the availability of newly launched merchandise, customised merchandise, unique merchandise and complementary merchandise*. However, there is also a significant number (i.e. 10.25%) of disappointed customers with *the availability of newly launched merchandise, customised merchandise, unique merchandise and complementary merchandise*.

Big Bazaar performs better in satisfying more customers with *the availability of newly launched merchandise, customised merchandise, unique merchandise and complementary merchandise* in comparison to its competitors or other multi-format retailers included in the study (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and D Mart).

While, Big Megamart is also a better performer in satisfying more customers with *the availability of newly launched merchandise, customised merchandise, unique merchandise and complementary merchandise* as compared to its competitors or other fashion item retailers included in the study (i.e. West Side and Max) and in the case of electronics item retailers included in this study, Reliance Digital perform better in satisfying more customers with *the availability of newly launched merchandise, customised merchandise, unique merchandise and complementary merchandise* than its competitor included in the study (i.e. NEXT).

8.5. Customer satisfaction with brands in each merchandise category

The mean WAS of all the organised retailers (included in this study) has been deemed as the WAS of the industry for *customer satisfaction with brands in each merchandise category* and demonstrated by the red line in *figure 8.5*. This WAS of the industry exists above the satisfied customer line in *figure 8.5*, which addresses that the organised retail industry satisfies a substantial majority of customers with the availability of *the brands (i.e. local & regional, national, international, private / store, copycat, exclusive, generic brands) in each merchandise category*.

Figure 8.5: Weighted average scores (WAS) for customer satisfaction with brands in each merchandise category

The WAS for customer satisfaction with *brands in each merchandise category* of some retailers (i.e. Big Bazaar, Big Megamart and West Side) are more than the WAS of the industry, which discloses that these retailers satisfy more customers with *the brands in each merchandise category* than others (included in this study) in the industry.

The most (i.e. 29.40%) customers are satisfied with *brands in each merchandise category* offered by the organised retailers (included in this study). The second bounteous group (i.e. 24.75%) of customers, who ponder that *brands in each merchandise category* are exceeding their expectations and they are happy. The third flagrant group (i.e. 20.20%) of customers is delighted with *brands in each merchandise category* because the same is greatly exceeding their expectations. However, there are also a vast number of customers, who are either dissatisfied (i.e. 16.10%) or disappointed (i.e. 9.55%) with *brands in each merchandise category*, because, the same is less than or much less than their expectations.

Big Bazaar leads in satisfying more customers with *brands in each merchandise category* in comparison to its competitors or other multi-format retailers included in the study (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and D Mart).

Retailers	Responses on expectation cum satisfaction scale										Weighted Average Score (WAS)
	5		4		3		2		1		
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
HyperCITY	39	19.50	47	23.50	58	29.00	33	16.50	23	11.50	3.230
Star Bazaar	42	21.00	42	21.00	61	30.50	35	17.50	20	10.00	3.255
more.MEGASStore	33	16.50	52	26.00	54	27.00	38	19.00	23	11.50	3.170
Big Bazaar	44	22.00	47	23.50	60	30.00	34	17.00	15	7.50	3.355
D ⁺ Mart	33	16.50	52	26.00	53	26.50	39	19.50	23	11.50	3.165
Big Megamart	53	26.50	55	27.50	61	30.50	18	9.00	13	6.50	3.585
West Side	45	22.50	51	25.50	60	30.00	30	15.00	14	7.00	3.415
Max	41	20.50	46	23.00	59	29.50	35	17.50	19	9.50	3.275
Reliance Digital	38	19.00	49	24.50	60	30.00	31	15.50	22	11.00	3.250
NEXT	36	18.00	54	27.00	62	31.00	29	14.50	19	9.50	3.295
Mean	40.40	20.20	49.50	24.75	58.80	29.40	32.20	16.10	19.10	9.55	3.300
Standard Deviation	6.077	3.039	4.035	2.017	3.011	1.506	5.940	2.970	3.872	1.936	0.357

While, Big Megamart leads in satisfying more customers with *brands in each merchandise category* as compared to its competitors or other fashion item retailers included in the study (i.e. West Side and Max) and in the case of electronics item retailers included in this study, NEXT satisfies more customers with *brands in each merchandise category* than its competitor included in the study (i.e. Reliance Digital).

8.6 Customer satisfaction with quality assurance and quality of merchandise

Figure 8.6: Weighted average scores (WAS) for customer satisfaction with quality assurance and quality of merchandise

The mean WAS of all the organised retailers (included in this study) has acceded as the WAS of the industry for *customer satisfaction with quality assurance and quality of merchandise* and presented with the red line in *figure 8.6*. This WAS of the industry lies above the satisfied customer line in *figure 8.6*, which expresses that the organised retail industry satisfies a constitutive majority of customers with its *quality assurance and quality of merchandise*.

The WAS for customer satisfaction with *quality assurance and quality of merchandise* of some retailers (i.e. Big Bazaar, Big Megamart and West Side) are greater than the WAS of the industry, which unfolds that these retailers satisfy more customers with their *quality assurance and quality of merchandise* than others (included in this study) in the industry.

The majority (i.e. 31.10%) customers are satisfied with *quality assurance and quality of merchandise* offered by the organised retailers (included in this study), as the same matches with their expectations. The second plenteous group (i.e. 26.55%) of customers, who ponder that *quality assurance and quality of merchandise* are exceeding their expectations and they are happy. The third adjunct group (i.e.

19.50%) of customers is delighted with *quality assurance and quality of merchandise* because the same is greatly exceeding their expectations. However, there are also a pervasive number of customers, who are either dissatisfied (i.e. 14.50%) or disappointed (i.e. 8.35%) with *quality assurance and quality of merchandise*, because, the same is less than or much less than their expectations.

Table 8.6: Comparative statistics of customer satisfaction with quality assurance and quality of merchandise

Retailers	Responses on expectation cum satisfaction scale										Weighted Average Score (WAS)
	5		4		3		2		1		
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
HyperCITY	43	21.50	47	23.50	61	30.50	32	16.00	17	8.50	3.335
Star Bazaar	39	19.50	48	24.00	70	35.00	30	15.00	13	6.50	3.350
more.MEGAStore	36	18.00	55	27.50	61	30.50	31	15.50	17	8.50	3.310
Big Bazaar	45	22.50	54	27.00	67	33.50	23	11.50	11	5.50	3.495
D ⁺ Mart	33	16.50	65	32.50	58	29.00	27	13.50	17	8.50	3.350
Big Megamart	43	21.50	51	25.50	59	29.50	28	14.00	19	9.50	3.355
West Side	41	20.50	53	26.50	61	30.50	29	14.50	16	8.00	3.370
Max	38	19.00	49	24.50	62	31.00	33	16.50	18	9.00	3.280
Reliance Digital	37	18.50	52	26.00	62	31.00	29	14.50	20	10.00	3.285
NEXT	35	17.50	57	28.50	61	30.50	28	14.00	19	9.50	3.305
Mean	39.00	19.50	53.10	26.55	62.20	31.10	29.00	14.50	16.70	8.35	3.344
Standard Deviation	3.916	1.958	5.238	2.619	3.615	1.807	2.828	1.414	2.791	1.395	0.299

Big Bazaar is the champ in satisfying more customers with its *quality assurance and quality of merchandise* in comparison to its competitors or other multi-format retailers included in the study (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and D Mart). While, West Side leads in satisfying more customers with its *quality assurance and quality of merchandise* as compared to its competitors or other fashion item retailers included in the study (i.e. Big Megamart and Max) and in the case of electronics item retailers included in this study, NEXT leads in satisfying more customers with *quality assurance and quality of merchandise* than its competitor included in the study (i.e. Reliance Digital).

8.7 Customer satisfaction with the services

Figure 8.7: Weighted average scores (WAS) for customer satisfaction with the services

The mean WAS of all the organised retailers (included in this study) has been recognised as the WAS of the industry for *customer satisfaction with the services* and tendered with the red line in *figure 8.7*. This WAS of the industry aligns above the satisfied customer line in the *figure 8.7*, which describes that the organised retail industry satisfies a robust majority of customers with its *services* (e.g. *Credit, home delivery, alteration, installation, packaging (gift wrapping), complaints & returns handling, gift certificates, trial purchase, special sales for regular customers, staff on*

late hours, extended store hours, mail & phone orders, restrooms, restaurants, bridal registry, baby strollers, interior designers, personal shoppers, ticket outlets, parking, water fountains, pay phones, fitting rooms, beauty salon, fur storage, shopping bags, information, safety of personal things, lift & escalator facility, babysitting, after sale services, demonstrations, mobile and laptop charger points, entertainment facilities, refreshment facilities, medical facility, the internet billing facility, game zones, music zone (karaoke, etc.), special facilities for physically handicapped, other in-store services, other out-store services, other pre-purchase or post-purchase services, complementary or adjunct services - inventory support, installation, repair, etc.).

The WAS for customer satisfaction with *the services* of some retailers (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, Big Bazaar, Big Megamart and West Side) are greater than the WAS of the industry, which divulges that these retailers satisfy more customers with *their services* than others (included in this study) in the industry.

The dignified number (i.e. 30.65%) of customers are satisfied with *the services* offered by the organised retailers (included in this study), as the same matches with their expectations. The second signified group (i.e. 24.75%) of customers, who consider that *the services* are exceeding their expectations and they are happy.

The third coherent group (i.e. 20.40%) of customers is delighted with *the services* because the same is greatly exceeding their expectations. However, there are also an extensive number of customers, who are either dissatisfied (i.e. 15.65%) or disappointed (i.e. 8.55%) with *the services*, because, the same is less than or much less than their expectations.

Big Bazaar satisfies more customers with its *services* in comparison to its competitors or other multi-format retailers included in the study (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and D⁺Mart). While, West Side leads in satisfying more customers with its *services* in comparison to its competitors or other fashion item retailers included in the study (i.e. Big Megamart and Max) and in the case of electronics item retailers included in this study, Reliance Digital satisfies more customers with its *services* than its competitor included in the study (i.e. NEXT).

Table 8.7: Comparative statistics of customer satisfaction with the services

Retailers	Responses on expectation cum satisfaction scale										Weighted Average Score (WAS)
	5		4		3		2		1		
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
HyperCITY	48	24.00	59	29.50	61	30.50	21	10.50	11	5.50	3.560
Star Bazaar	42	21.00	51	25.50	67	33.50	24	12.00	16	8.00	3.395
more.MEGASStore	39	19.50	48	24.00	67	33.50	31	15.50	15	7.50	3.325
Big Bazaar	51	25.50	58	29.00	65	32.50	18	9.00	8	4.00	3.630
D Mart	27	13.50	43	21.50	60	30.00	46	23.00	24	12.00	3.015
Big Megamart	43	21.50	49	24.50	57	28.50	34	17.00	17	8.50	3.335
West Side	47	23.50	51	25.50	61	30.50	26	13.00	15	7.50	3.445
Max	31	15.50	43	21.50	58	29.00	45	22.50	23	11.50	3.070
Reliance Digital	41	20.50	47	23.50	59	29.50	33	16.50	20	10.00	3.280
NEXT	39	19.50	46	23.00	58	29.00	35	17.50	22	11.00	3.225
Mean	40.80	20.40	49.50	24.75	61.30	30.65	31.30	15.65	17.10	8.55	3.328
Standard Deviation	7.406	3.703	5.503	2.751	3.743	1.872	9.381	4.691	5.216	2.608	0.471

8.8 Customer satisfaction with the quality of the services

Figure 8.8: Weighted average scores (WAS) for customer satisfaction with the quality of the services

The mean WAS of all the organised retailers (included in this study) has been supposed as the WAS of the industry for *customer satisfaction with the quality of the services* and proposed with the red line in *figure 8.8*. This WAS of the industry rests above the satisfied customer line in the *figure 8.8*, which represents that the organised retail industry satisfies a sufficient majority of customers with their *quality of the services by managing service tangibles (tangibility), having consistency and dependability in service performance (reliability), committing to provide services in time (responsiveness), having competence, courtesy to its customers and security of service operations (assurance), and putting itself in its customers place (empathy)*.

The WAS for customer satisfaction with *the quality of the services* of some retailers (i.e. HyperCITY, Big Bazaar, Big Megamart and West Side) are greater than the WAS of the industry, which promulgates that these retailers satisfy more customers with their *quality of the services* than others (included in this study) in the industry.

The most (i.e. 29.10%) customers are satisfied with *the quality of the services* offered by the organised retailers (included in this study), as the same is as per their expectations. The second plenteous group (i.e. 23.70) of customers, who

think that *the quality of the services* is exceeding their expectations and they are happy. Moreover, the industry has also a thundering number (i.e. 19.90%) of delighted customers with *the quality of the services*. The next giant group (i.e. 17.45%) of customers is dissatisfied with *the quality of the services* because the same is lacking to their expectations. However, there is also a non-negligible disappointed (i.e. 9.85%) customers with *the quality of the services*.

Table 8.8: Comparative statistics of customer satisfaction with the quality of the services

Retailers	Responses on expectation cum satisfaction scale										Weighted Average Score (WAS)
	5		4		3		2		1		
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
HyperCITY	41	20.50	49	24.50	58	29.00	33	16.50	19	9.50	3.300
Star Bazaar	38	19.00	48	24.00	59	29.50	35	17.50	20	10.00	3.245
more.MEGASStore	39	19.50	46	23.00	57	28.50	37	18.50	21	10.50	3.225
Big Bazaar	48	24.00	52	26.00	63	31.50	24	12.00	13	6.50	3.490
D Mart	30	15.00	41	20.50	55	27.50	48	24.00	26	13.00	3.005
Big Megamart	47	23.50	51	25.50	58	29.00	29	14.50	15	7.50	3.430
West Side	46	23.00	53	26.50	60	30.00	27	13.50	14	7.00	3.450
Max	34	17.00	44	22.00	57	28.50	41	20.50	24	12.00	3.115
Reliance Digital	39	19.50	46	23.00	58	29.00	36	18.00	21	10.50	3.230
NEXT	36	18.00	44	22.00	57	28.50	39	19.50	24	12.00	3.145
Mean	39.80	19.90	47.40	23.70	58.20	29.10	34.90	17.45	19.70	9.85	3.264
Standard Deviation	5.846	2.923	3.893	1.947	2.150	1.075	7.078	3.539	4.473	2.237	0.349

Big Bazaar is also a champ in satisfying more customers with its *quality of the services* in comparison to its competitors or other multi-format retailers included in the study (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and D Δ Mart). While, West Side a champ in satisfying more customers with its *quality of the services* in comparison to its competitors or other fashion item retailers included in the study (i.e. Big Megamart and Max) and in the case of electronics item retailers included in this study, Reliance Digital leads in satisfying more customers with its *quality of the services* than its competitor included in the study (i.e. NEXT).

8.9 Customer satisfaction with the pricing of merchandise & services

Figure 8.9: Weighted average scores (WAS) for customer satisfaction with the pricing of merchandise & services

The mean WAS of all the organised retailers (included in this study) has been reckoned as the WAS of the industry for *customer satisfaction with the pricing of merchandise & services* and put forwarded with the red line in *figure 8.9*. This WAS of the industry reclines above the satisfied customer line in *figure 8.9*, which signifies that the organised retail industry satisfies an ample majority of customers with its customer expected *pricing of merchandise & services*.

The WAS for customer satisfaction with *the pricing of merchandise & services* of some retailers (i.e. Big Bazaar, D Δ Mart and NEXT) are more than the

WAS of the industry, which declares that these retailers satisfy more customers with their *pricing of merchandise & services* than others (included in this study) in the industry.

Table 8.9: Comparative statistics of customer satisfaction with the pricing of merchandise & services											
Retailers	Responses on expectation cum satisfaction scale										Weighted Average Score (WAS)
	5		4		3		2		1		
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
HyperCITY	40	20.00	44	22.00	59	29.50	34	17.00	23	11.50	3.220
Star Bazaar	39	19.50	47	23.50	61	30.50	32	16.00	21	10.50	3.255
more.MEGASStore	38	19.00	49	24.50	60	30.00	31	15.50	22	11.00	3.250
Big Bazaar	43	21.50	48	24.00	69	34.50	25	12.50	15	7.50	3.395
D▲Mart	46	23.00	53	26.50	59	29.50	24	12.00	18	9.00	3.425
Big Megamart	37	18.50	47	23.50	57	28.50	36	18.00	25	12.50	3.205
West Side	39	19.50	45	22.50	56	28.00	37	18.50	23	11.50	3.200
Max	41	20.50	44	22.00	58	29.00	35	17.50	22	11.00	3.235
Reliance Digital	36	18.00	52	26.00	58	29.00	34	17.00	20	10.00	3.250
NEXT	47	23.50	55	27.50	61	30.50	23	11.50	14	7.00	3.490
Mean	40.60	20.30	48.40	24.20	59.80	29.90	31.10	15.55	20.30	10.15	3.293
Standard Deviation	3.688	1.844	3.836	1.918	3.615	1.807	5.216	2.608	3.592	1.796	0.293

The maximum (i.e. 29.90%) customers are satisfied with *the pricing of merchandise & services* decided by the organised retailers (included in this study), as it matches with their expectations. The second exuberant group (i.e. 24.20%) of customers, who perceive that *the pricing of merchandise & services* is exceeding their expectations and they are happy.

Moreover, the industry also delights an adequate number (i.e. 20.30%) of customers with *the pricing of merchandise & services* by greatly exceeding the same than customers' expectations. The next enormous group (i.e. 15.55%) of customers is dissatisfied with *the pricing of merchandise & services* because it is deficient to their expectations. There is also a non-negligible number (i.e. 10.15%) of customers, those are disappointed with *the pricing of merchandise & services*, as the same is much less than their expectations.

D[▲]Mart leads in satisfying more customers with its *pricing of merchandise & services* in comparison to its competitors or other multi-format retailers included in the study (i.e. Big Bazaar, HyperCITY, Star Bazaar and more.MEGAStore). While, Max leads in satisfying more customers with its *pricing of merchandise & services* in comparison to its competitors or other fashion item retailers included in the study (i.e. Big Megamart and West Side) and in the case of electronics item retailers included in this study, NEXT leads in satisfying more customers with its *pricing of merchandise & services* than its competitor included in the study (i.e. Reliance Digital).

8.10 Customer satisfaction with the overall value Vs price of merchandise & services

The mean WAS of all the organised retailers (included in this study) has been presumed as the WAS of the industry for *customer satisfaction with the overall value Vs price of merchandise & services* and tendered with the red line in *figure 8.10*. This WAS of the industry slouches above the satisfied customer line in *figure 8.10*, which evinces that the organised retail industry satisfies a considerable majority of customers with its *overall value (i.e. product value, service value, personal value, image value) offered as compared to the price/cost (i.e. monetary cost, time cost, energy cost, psychic cost) of merchandise & services*.

Figure 8.10: Weighted average scores (WAS) for customer satisfaction with the overall value Vs price of merchandise & services

The WAS for customer satisfaction with *the overall value offered compared to the price/cost* of some retailers (i.e. Big Bazaar and HyperCITY) are greater than the WAS of the industry, which manifests that these retailers satisfy more customers with their *overall value offered compared to the price/cost* than others (included in this study) in the industry.

The utmost (i.e. 28.30%) customers are satisfied with *the overall value offered compared to the price/cost* by the organised retailers (included in this study), as it matches with their expectations. The second plenteous group (i.e. 23.15%) of customers, who comprehend that *the overall value offered compared to the price/cost* is exceeding their expectations and they are happy.

Moreover, the industry also delights a sufficient number (i.e. 20.25%) of customers with *the overall value offered compared to the price/cost* by greatly exceeding the value than customers' expectations. The next giant group (i.e. 16.80%) of customers is dissatisfied with *the overall value offered compared to the price/cost* because it is lacking to their expectations. There is also a non-negligible number (i.e. 11.50%) of customers, those are disappointed with *the overall value offered compared to the price/cost*, as the same is much less than their expectations.

Table 8.10: Comparative statistics of customer satisfaction with the overall value Vs price of merchandise & services											
Retailers	Responses on expectation cum satisfaction scale										Weighted Average Score (WAS)
	5		4		3		2		1		
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
HyperCITY	40	20.00	46	23.00	59	29.50	33	16.50	22	11.00	3.245
Star Bazaar	39	19.50	45	22.50	57	28.50	36	18.00	23	11.50	3.205
more.MEGASStore	37	18.50	52	26.00	53	26.50	33	16.50	25	12.50	3.215
Big Bazaar	46	23.00	53	26.50	61	30.50	25	12.50	15	7.50	3.450
D▲Mart	38	19.00	50	25.00	54	27.00	34	17.00	24	12.00	3.220
Big Megamart	39	19.50	46	23.00	57	28.50	34	17.00	24	12.00	3.210
West Side	40	20.00	44	22.00	58	29.00	35	17.50	23	11.50	3.215
Max	43	21.50	39	19.50	57	28.50	41	20.50	20	10.00	3.220
Reliance Digital	41	20.50	43	21.50	56	28.00	33	16.50	27	13.50	3.190
NEXT	42	21.00	45	22.50	54	27.00	32	16.00	27	13.50	3.215
Mean	40.50	20.25	46.30	23.15	56.60	28.30	33.60	16.80	23.00	11.50	3.239
Standard Deviation	2.635	1.318	4.270	2.135	2.459	1.229	3.950	1.975	3.528	1.764	0.245

Big Bazaar is a leader in satisfying more customers with its *overall value offered compared to the price/cost* in comparison to its competitors or other multi-format retailers included in the study (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and D▲Mart). While, Max

leads in satisfying more customers with its *overall value offered compared to the price/cost* in comparison to its competitors or other fashion item retailers included in the study (i.e. Big Megamart and West Side) and in the case of electronics item retailers included in this study, NEXT is a leader in satisfying more customers with its *overall value offered compared to the price/cost* than its competitor included in the study (i.e. Reliance Digital).

8.11 Customer satisfaction with the exterior atmospherics of the store

Figure 8.11: Weighted average scores (WAS) for customer satisfaction with the exterior atmospherics of the store

The mean WAS of all the organised retailers (included in this study) has been envisaged as the WAS of the industry for *customer satisfaction with the exterior atmospherics of the store* and furnished with the red line in *figure 8.11*. This WAS of the industry crouches above the satisfied customer line in *figure 8.11*, which connotes that the organised retail industry satisfies a cogitable majority of customers with *the exterior atmospherics (i.e. storefront, store marquee / sign board, frontage entrance, external display window / space, building, store architecture, uniqueness of the store, visibility of the store, location / site of store, parking facilities, exterior look of the store, ease of access, store nameplate, health & safety standards, surrounding area, etc.) of the stores.*

The WAS for customer satisfaction with *the exterior atmospherics of the store* of some retailers (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar, Big Megamart, West Side and Reliance Digital) are greater than the WAS of the industry, which unfolds that these retailers satisfy more customers with their *exterior atmospherics of the store* than others (included in this study) in the industry.

Table 8.11: Comparative statistics of customer satisfaction with the exterior atmospherics of the store

Retailers	Responses on expectation cum satisfaction scale										Weighted Average Score (WAS)
	5		4		3		2		1		
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
HyperCITY	41	20.50	46	23.00	67	33.50	29	14.50	17	8.50	3.325
Star Bazaar	43	21.50	47	23.50	63	31.50	31	15.50	16	8.00	3.350
more.MEGASStore	37	18.50	53	26.50	55	27.50	33	16.50	22	11.00	3.250
Big Bazaar	49	24.50	50	25.00	68	34.00	21	10.50	12	6.00	3.515
D ⁺ Mart	27	13.50	49	24.50	61	30.50	37	18.50	26	13.00	3.070
Big Megamart	52	26.00	49	24.50	61	30.50	24	12.00	14	7.00	3.505
West Side	43	21.50	48	24.00	65	32.50	26	13.00	18	9.00	3.360
Max	31	15.50	42	21.00	59	29.50	40	20.00	28	14.00	3.040
Reliance Digital	42	21.00	48	24.00	66	33.00	26	13.00	18	9.00	3.350
NEXT	23	11.50	48	24.00	65	32.50	37	18.50	27	13.50	3.015
Mean	38.80	19.40	48.00	24.00	63.00	31.50	30.40	15.20	19.80	9.90	3.278
Standard Deviation	9.319	4.660	2.828	1.414	4.028	2.014	6.293	3.146	5.633	2.817	0.441

The industry satisfies the utmost (i.e. 31.50%) customers with *the exterior atmospherics of the store* by matching the same with their expectations. The industry also has happy customers with *the exterior atmospherics of the store*, as a second major group (i.e. 24.00%), which feels that *the exterior atmospherics of the store* is exceeding their expectations.

Moreover, the industry also delights a substantial number (i.e. 19.40%) of customers with *the exterior atmospherics of the store* by greatly exceeding the same than customers' expectations. However, the industry carries the next major group (i.e. 15.20%) of dissatisfied customers with *the exterior atmospherics of the store*, as lacking to meet expectations of customers. At the same time, the industry hauls a non-negligible number (i.e. 9.90%) of disappointed customers with *the exterior atmospherics of the store*, as offers much less than expectations of customers.

Big Bazaar satisfies more customers with its *exterior atmospherics of the store* in comparison to its competitors or other multi-format retailers included in the study (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASTore and D-Mart). While, Big Megamart satisfies more customers with its *exterior atmospherics of the store* in comparison to its competitors or other fashion item retailers included in the study (i.e. Max and West Side) and in the case of electronics item retailers included in this study, Reliance Digital leads in satisfying more customers with its *exterior atmospherics of the store* than its competitor included in the study (i.e. NEXT).

8.12 Customer satisfaction with the interior atmospherics of the store

The mean WAS of all the organised retailers (included in this study) has been conceived as the WAS of the industry for *customer satisfaction with the interior atmospherics of the store* and decorated with the red line in *figure 8.12*.

This WAS of the industry inclines above the satisfied customer line in *figure 8.12*, which enlightens that the organised retail industry satisfies a volumetric majority of customers with *the interior atmospherics (i.e. flooring & ceiling, lighting, odour / smell / scent, fixtures, wall textures, sounds, colour, temperature, cleanliness, aisles, trial room, dead area, graphics, store size, etc.) of the stores*.

Figure 8.12: Weighted average scores (WAS) for customer satisfaction with the interior atmospherics of the store

The WAS for customer satisfaction with *the interior atmospherics of the store* of some retailers (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar, Big Megamart, West Side and Reliance Digital) are more than the WAS of the industry, which announces that these retailers satisfy more customers with *the interior atmospherics of the store* than others (included in this study) in the industry.

The industry satisfies the exhaustive (i.e. 30.85%) customers with *the interior atmospherics of the store* by matching the same with their expectations. The industry also has happy customers with *the interior atmospherics of the store*, as a second key group (i.e. 22.80%), which feels that *the interior atmospherics of the store* is exceeding their expectations.

Hereto, the industry also delights a competent number (i.e. 19.10%) of customers with *the interior atmospherics of the store* by greatly exceeding the same than customers' expectations. However, the industry totes the next large group (i.e. 16.90%) of dissatisfied customers with *the interior atmospherics of the store*, as imperfect to meet expectations. Moreover, the industry haulages a non-negligible number (i.e. 10.35%) of disappointed customers with *the interior atmospherics of the store*, as tender much less than expectations of customers.

Retailers	Responses on expectation cum satisfaction scale										Weighted Average Score (WAS)
	5		4		3		2		1		
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
HyperCITY	44	22.00	47	23.50	64	32.00	28	14.00	17	8.50	3.365
Star Bazaar	45	22.50	45	22.50	65	32.50	27	13.50	18	9.00	3.360
more.MEGASStore	39	19.50	47	23.50	62	31.00	31	15.50	21	10.50	3.260
Big Bazaar	48	24.00	53	26.50	67	33.50	21	10.50	11	5.50	3.530
D ⁺ Mart	19	9.50	34	17.00	61	30.50	57	28.50	29	14.50	2.785
Big Megamart	49	24.50	52	26.00	61	30.50	23	11.50	15	7.50	3.485
West Side	41	20.50	49	24.50	62	31.00	28	14.00	20	10.00	3.315
Max	38	19.00	46	23.00	55	27.50	37	18.50	24	12.00	3.185
Reliance Digital	41	20.50	48	24.00	58	29.00	31	15.50	22	11.00	3.275
NEXT	18	9.00	35	17.50	62	31.00	55	27.50	30	15.00	2.780
Mean	38.20	19.10	45.60	22.80	61.70	30.85	33.80	16.90	20.70	10.35	3.234
Standard Deviation	10.983	5.491	6.363	3.182	3.401	1.700	12.506	6.253	5.926	2.963	0.608

Big Bazaar also satisfies more customers with its *interior atmospherics of the store* in comparison to its competitors or other multi-format retailers included in the study (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and D⁺Mart). While, Big Megamart also satisfies more customers with its *interior atmospherics of the store* in comparison to its competitors or other fashion item retailers included in the study (i.e.

Max and West Side) and in the case of electronics item retailers included in this study, Reliance Digital also leads in satisfying more customers with its *interior atmospherics of the store* than its competitor included in the study (i.e. NEXT).

8.13 Customer satisfaction with the store layout

Figure 8.13: Weighted average scores (WAS) for customer satisfaction with the store layout

The mean WAS of all the organised retailers (included in this study) has been visualised as the WAS of the industry for *customer satisfaction with the store layout* and embellished with the red line in *figure 8.13*. This WAS of the industry bows above the satisfied customer line in *figure 8.13*, which communicates that the organised retail industry satisfies an illustrious majority of customers with *the store layout* (i.e. *space planning, floor space allocation, e-display, department location, department size, department compatibility, location of various products, accessibility to cash/billing counters, signage, etc.*).

The WAS for customer satisfaction with *the store layout* of some retailers (i.e. HyperCITY, Big Bazaar, Big Megamart, West Side, Max and Reliance Digital) are greater than the WAS of the industry, which divulges that these retailers satisfy more customers with their *store layout* than others (included in this study) in the industry.

Table 8.13: Comparative statistics of customer satisfaction with the store layout											
Retailers	Responses on expectation cum satisfaction scale										Weighted Average Score (WAS)
	5		4		3		2		1		
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
HyperCITY	38	19.00	48	24.00	59	29.50	35	17.50	20	10.00	3.245
Star Bazaar	36	18.00	46	23.00	57	28.50	34	17.00	27	13.50	3.150
more.MEGASStore	34	17.00	46	23.00	55	27.50	38	19.00	27	13.50	3.110
Big Bazaar	40	20.00	45	22.50	60	30.00	35	17.50	20	10.00	3.250
D Mart	18	9.00	36	18.00	59	29.50	56	28.00	31	15.50	2.770
Big Megamart	53	26.50	51	25.50	54	27.00	25	12.50	17	8.50	3.490
West Side	45	22.50	52	26.00	58	29.00	26	13.00	19	9.50	3.390
Max	38	19.00	49	24.50	57	28.50	34	17.00	22	11.00	3.235
Reliance Digital	37	18.50	45	22.50	57	28.50	33	16.50	28	14.00	3.150
NEXT	20	10.00	37	18.50	59	29.50	53	26.50	31	15.50	2.810
Mean	35.90	17.95	45.50	22.75	57.50	28.75	36.90	18.45	24.20	12.10	3.160
Standard Deviation	10.429	5.215	5.318	2.659	1.900	0.950	10.137	5.069	5.181	2.591	0.523

The industry satisfies the extensive group (i.e. 28.75%) of customers with *the store layout* by matching the same with their expectations. The industry also has happy customers with *the store layout*, as a second fundamental group (i.e. 22.75%), which feels that *the store layout* is exceeding their expectations. However, the industry bears the next large group (i.e. 18.45%) of dissatisfied customers with *the store layout*, as

immature to meet expectations. Herein, the industry also delights an effectual number (i.e. 17.95%) of customers with *the store layout* by greatly exceeding the same than customers' expectations. Moreover, the industry ferriages a non-negligible number (i.e. 12.10%) of disappointed customers with *the store layout*, as maintains much less than expectations of customers.

Big Bazaar also champs in satisfying more customers with its *store layout* in comparison to its competitors or other multi-format retailers included in the study (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and D Mart). While, Big Megamart champs in satisfying more customers with its *store layout* in comparison to its competitors or other fashion item retailers included in the study (i.e. Max and West Side) and in the case of electronics item retailers included in this study, Reliance Digital also champs in satisfying more customers with its *store layout* than its competitor included in the study (i.e. NEXT).

8.14 Customer satisfaction with the visual merchandising

Figure 8.14: Weighted average scores (WAS) for customer satisfaction with the visual merchandising

The mean WAS of all the organised retailers (included in this study) has been imagined as the WAS of the industry for *customer satisfaction with the visual merchandising* and adorned with the red line in *figure 8.14*. This WAS of the industry

reclines above the satisfied customer line in *figure 8.14*, which heralds that the organised retail industry satisfies an exuberant majority of customers with *the visual merchandising* (i.e. *theme, racks & shelves, ensemble, payment counters, merchandise display, the planogram, props & mannequins, point of sale sign, methods of display, etc.*).

The WAS for customer satisfaction with *the visual merchandising* of some retailers (i.e. HyperCITY, Big Bazaar, Big Megamart, West Side, Max and Reliance Digital) are greater than the WAS of the industry, which declares that these retailers satisfy more customers with their *visual merchandising* than others (included in this study) in the industry.

The industry satisfies the massive (i.e. 28.80%) customers with *the visual merchandising* by matching the same with their expectations. The industry also has happy customers with *the visual merchandising*, as a second basic group (i.e. 22.60%), which feels that *the visual merchandising* is exceeding their expectations.

Hereto, the industry also delights a great number (i.e. 19.45%) of customers with *the visual merchandising* by greatly exceeding the same than customers' expectations. However, the industry endures the next large group (i.e. 17.80%) of dissatisfied customers with *the visual merchandising*, as infantile to meet expectations. Moreover, the industry hauls a non-negligible number (i.e. 11.35%) of disappointed customers with *the visual merchandising*, as serve much less than expectations of customers.

Big Bazaar also leads in satisfying more customers with its *visual merchandising* in comparison to its competitors or other multi-format retailers included in the study (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and D[▲]Mart). While, Big Megamart also leads in satisfying more customers with its *visual merchandising* in comparison to its competitors or other fashion item retailers included in the study (i.e. Max and West Side) and in the case of electronics item retailers included in this study, Reliance Digital also champs in satisfying more customers with its *visual merchandising* than its competitor included in the study (i.e. NEXT).

Table 8.14: Comparative statistics of customer satisfaction with the visual merchandising

Retailers	Responses on expectation cum satisfaction scale										Weighted Average Score (WAS)
	5		4		3		2		1		
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
HyperCITY	41	20.50	47	23.50	59	29.50	31	15.50	22	11.00	3.270
Star Bazaar	40	20.00	42	21.00	56	28.00	37	18.50	25	12.50	3.175
more.MEGAStore	38	19.00	45	22.50	56	28.00	36	18.00	25	12.50	3.175
Big Bazaar	42	21.00	46	23.00	60	30.00	32	16.00	20	10.00	3.290
D Mart	25	12.50	39	19.50	59	29.50	46	23.00	31	15.50	2.905
Big Megamart	49	24.50	53	26.50	56	28.00	26	13.00	16	8.00	3.465
West Side	47	23.50	49	24.50	57	28.50	29	14.50	18	9.00	3.390
Max	41	20.50	47	23.50	58	29.00	35	17.50	19	9.50	3.280
Reliance Digital	40	20.00	44	22.00	57	28.50	37	18.50	22	11.00	3.215
NEXT	26	13.00	40	20.00	58	29.00	47	23.50	29	14.50	2.935
Mean	38.90	19.45	45.20	22.60	57.60	28.80	35.60	17.80	22.70	11.35	3.210
Standard Deviation	7.810	3.905	4.211	2.106	1.430	0.715	6.769	3.385	4.809	2.404	0.393

8.15 Customer satisfaction with the methods of promotion and communication

Figure 8.15: Weighted average scores (WAS) for customer satisfaction with the methods of promotion and communication

The mean WAS of all the organised retailers (included in this study) has been envisioned as the WAS of the industry for *customer satisfaction with the methods of promotion and communication* and shown with the red line in *figure 8.15*. This WAS of the industry crouches above the satisfied customer line in *figure 8.15*, which reports that the organised retail industry satisfies an affluent majority of customers with *the methods of promotion and communication* (i.e. *advertising, sales promotion, direct retailing, personal retailing, public relation / publicity and the internet / interactive retailing*).

The WAS for customer satisfaction with *the methods of promotion and communication* of some retailers (i.e. Big Bazaar, D Mart, Max and NEXT) are greater than the WAS of the industry, which publicises that these retailers satisfy more customers with their *methods of promotion and communication* than others (included in this study) in the industry.

The most (i.e. 29.40%) customers are satisfied with *the methods of promotion and communication* adopted by the organised retailers (included in this study), as those are matching with their expectations. The second largest group (i.e. 23.45%) of

customers, who perceive that *the methods of promotion and communication* are exceeding their expectations and they are happy. The third major group (i.e. 20.55%) of customers is delighted with *the methods of promotion and communication*, as the same are greatly exceeding their expectations. However, there are also a massive number of customers, who are either dissatisfied (i.e. 16.30%) or disappointed (i.e. 10.33%) with *the methods of promotion and communication*, because, those are less than or much less than their expectations.

Table 8.15: Comparative statistics of customer satisfaction with the methods of promotion and communication

Retailers	Responses on expectation cum satisfaction scale										Weighted Average Score (WAS)
	5		4		3		2		1		
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
HyperCITY	41	20.50	44	22.00	55	27.50	37	18.50	23	11.50	3.215
Star Bazaar	39	19.50	48	24.00	61	30.50	33	16.50	19	9.50	3.275
more.MEGAStore	41	20.50	44	22.00	59	29.50	35	17.50	21	10.50	3.245
Big Bazaar	47	23.50	51	25.50	62	31.00	25	12.50	15	7.50	3.450
D ⁺ Mart	40	20.00	47	23.50	66	33.00	27	13.50	20	10.00	3.300
Big Megamart	39	19.50	49	24.50	58	29.00	33	16.50	21	10.50	3.260
West Side	40	20.00	45	22.50	56	28.00	35	17.50	24	12.00	3.210
Max	43	21.50	50	25.00	57	28.50	31	15.50	19	9.50	3.335
Reliance Digital	39	19.50	45	22.50	56	28.00	36	18.00	24	12.00	3.195
NEXT	42	21.00	46	23.00	58	29.00	34	17.00	20	10.00	3.280
Mean	41.10	20.55	46.90	23.45	58.80	29.40	32.60	16.30	20.60	10.30	3.277
Standard Deviation	2.470	1.235	2.514	1.257	3.360	1.680	3.893	1.947	2.716	1.358	0.215

Big Bazaar is a leader in satisfying more customers with its *methods of promotion and communication* in comparison to its competitors or other multi-format retailers included in the study (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and D Mart). While, Max leads in satisfying more customers with its *methods of promotion and communication* in comparison to its competitors or other fashion item retailers included in the study (i.e. Big Megamart and West Side) and in the case of electronics item retailers included in this study, NEXT champs in satisfying more customers with its *methods of promotion and communication* than its competitor included in the study (i.e. Reliance Digital).

8.16 Customer satisfaction with the advertising methods

Figure 8.16: Weighted average scores (WAS) for customer satisfaction with the advertising methods

The mean WAS of all the organised retailers (included in this study) has been speculated as the WAS of the industry for *customer satisfaction with the advertising methods* and exhibited with the red line in *figure 8.16*. This WAS of the industry reclines above the satisfied customer line in *figure 8.16*, which apprises that the organised retail industry satisfies an immense majority of customers with its *advertising methods (i.e. in-store advertising methods and out-store advertising methods)*. The in-store advertising methods comprise the *visual display, signage, pamphlets, the point of purchase material, secondary packaging and cross*

promotions. And out-store advertising methods comprise the *television ads, radio ads, newspaper ads, journals & magazine ads, yellow pages, hoarding, wall paintings, pamphlets/propaganda, van advertising, online advertising, mobile billboard, LCD screening, cinema, fairs & exhibitions*. The WAS for customer satisfaction with *the advertising methods* of some retailers (i.e. HyperCITY, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar, Big Megamart, West Side and Reliance Digital) are more than the WAS of the industry, which annunciates that these retailers satisfy more customers with their *advertising methods* than others (included in this study) in the industry.

Table 8.16: Comparative statistics of customer satisfaction with the advertising methods

Retailers	Responses on expectation cum satisfaction scale										Weighted Average Score (WAS)
	5		4		3		2		1		
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
HyperCITY	40	20.00	47	23.50	56	28.00	36	18.00	21	21	3.245
Star Bazaar	38	19.00	42	21.00	58	29.00	39	19.50	29	23	3.195
more.MEGASStore	39	19.50	45	22.50	57	28.50	37	18.50	23	22	3.215
Big Bazaar	46	23.00	52	26.00	62	31.00	24	12.00	16	16	3.440
D▲Mart	32	16.00	40	20.00	56	28.00	44	22.00	30	28	3.030
Big Megamart	42	21.00	45	22.50	57	28.50	34	17.00	22	22	3.255
West Side	41	20.50	44	22.00	59	29.50	36	18.00	21	20	3.255
Max	40	20.00	44	22.00	57	28.50	35	17.50	25	24	3.210
Reliance Digital	40	20.00	46	23.00	63	31.50	30	15.00	21	21	3.270
NEXT	34	17.00	39	19.50	54	27.00	43	21.50	30	30	3.020
Mean	39.20	19.60	44.40	22.20	57.90	28.95	35.80	17.90	23.80	11.90	3.214
Standard Deviation	3.938	1.969	3.688	1.844	2.767	1.383	5.846	2.923	4.638	2.319	0.295

The industry satisfies the massive (i.e. 28.95%) customers with *the advertising methods* by matching the same with their expectations. The industry also has happy customers with *the visual merchandising*, as a second basic group (i.e. 22.20%), which feels that *the advertising methods* are exceeding their expectations. Hereto, the industry also delights a great number (i.e. 19.60%) of customers with *the advertising methods* by greatly exceeding the same than customers' expectations. However, the industry endures the next large group (i.e. 17.90%) of dissatisfied customers with *the advertising methods*, as infantile to meet expectations. Moreover, the industry hauls a non-negligible number (i.e. 11.90%) of disappointed customers with *the advertising methods*, as perform much less than expectations of customers.

Big Bazaar is also a leader in satisfying more customers with its *advertising methods* in comparison to its competitors or other multi-format retailers included in the study (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and D Mart). While, Big Megamart and West Side stand at an equal position to satisfy more customers with its *advertising methods* in comparison to its competitors or other fashion item retailers included in the study (i.e. Max) and in the case of electronics item retailers included in this study, Reliance Digital leads in satisfying more customers with its *advertising methods* than its competitor included in the study (i.e. NEXT).

8.17 Customer satisfaction with the sales promotion methods

Figure 8.17: Weighted average scores (WAS) for customer satisfaction with the sales promotion methods

The mean WAS of all the organised retailers (included in this study) has been figured as the WAS of the industry for *customer satisfaction with the sales promotion methods* and documented with the red line in *figure 8.17*.

This WAS of the industry inclines above the satisfied customer line in *figure 8.17*, which notifies that the organised retail industry satisfies a hulking majority of customers with its *sales promotion methods (i.e. schemes, free samples, gifts, rebates & discounts, contests and other activities, customer loyalty programs, premiums, prize & rewards)*.

The WAS for customer satisfaction with *the sales promotion methods* of some retailers (i.e. Big Bazaar and NEXT) are greater than the WAS of the industry, which pronounces that these retailers satisfy more customers with their *sales promotional methods* than others (included in this study) in the industry.

The maximal (i.e. 29.30%) customers are satisfied with *sales promotion methods* adopted by the organised retailers (included in this study), as those are matching with their expectations. The second verdant group (i.e. 23.80%) of customers, who deem that *sales promotion methods* are exceeding their expectations and they are happy.

The industry also delights an ample number (i.e. 20.85%) of customers with *sales promotion methods* by greatly exceeding them than customers' expectations. The next gigantic group (i.e. 16.15%) of customers is dissatisfied with *sales promotion methods* because those are deficient to their expectations.

Moreover, there is also a non-negligible number (i.e. 9.80%) of customers, those are disappointed with *sales promotion methods* as the same is much less than their expectations.

Big Bazaar also leads in satisfying more customers with its *sales promotion methods* in comparison to its competitors or other multi-format retailers included in the study (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and D▲Mart).

Table 8.17: Comparative statistics of customer satisfaction with the sales promotion methods											
Retailers	Responses on expectation cum satisfaction scale										Weighted Average Score (WAS)
	5		4		3		2		1		
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
HyperCITY	42	21.00	45	22.50	60	30.00	35	17.50	18	9.00	3.290
Star Bazaar	40	20.00	46	23.00	62	31.00	32	16.00	20	10.00	3.270
more.MEGAStore	42	21.00	47	23.50	58	29.00	34	17.00	19	9.50	3.295
Big Bazaar	49	24.50	56	28.00	63	31.50	20	10.00	12	6.00	3.550
D Δ Mart	42	21.00	48	24.00	58	29.00	30	15.00	22	11.00	3.290
Big Megamart	40	20.00	46	23.00	55	27.50	35	17.50	24	12.00	3.215
West Side	41	20.50	47	23.50	58	29.00	36	18.00	18	9.00	3.285
Max	39	19.50	47	23.50	59	29.50	35	17.50	20	10.00	3.250
Reliance Digital	39	19.50	46	23.00	57	28.50	36	18.00	22	11.00	3.220
NEXT	43	21.50	48	24.00	58	29.00	30	15.00	21	10.50	3.310
Mean	41.70	20.85	47.60	23.80	58.80	29.40	32.30	16.15	19.60	9.80	3.298
Standard Deviation	2.908	1.454	3.098	1.549	2.348	1.174	4.877	2.439	3.273	1.636	0.235

While, West Side leads in satisfying more customers with its *sales promotion methods* in comparison to its competitors or other fashion item retailers included in the study (i.e. Big Megamart and Max) and in the case of electronics item retailers included in this study, NEXT leads in satisfying more customers with its *sales promotion methods* than its competitor included in the study (i.e. Reliance Digital).

8.18 Customer satisfaction with the direct retailing methods

Figure 8.18: Weighted average scores (WAS) for customer satisfaction with the direct retailing methods

The mean WAS of all the organised retailers (included in this study) has been described as the WAS of the industry for *customer satisfaction with the direct retailing methods* and demonstrated by the red line in *figure 8.18*. This WAS of the industry curves underneath the satisfied customer line in *figure 8.18*, which denotes that the organised retail industry do not satisfy a giant majority of customers with its *direct retailing methods* (i.e. *direct mail, tele-retailing, direct response on TV/radio, mail order catalogues, SMS retailing and mobile retailing*).

The WAS for customer satisfaction with *the direct retailing methods* of some retailers (i.e. HyperCITY, Big Bazaar, West Side, Reliance Digital and NEXT) are more than the WAS of the industry, which notifies that these retailers satisfy more customers with their *direct retailing methods* than others (included in this study) in the industry.

The industry satisfies the extensive group (i.e. 27.15%) of customers with *the direct retailing methods* by matching the same with their expectations. However, the industry bears the next large group (i.e. 21.25%) of dissatisfied customers with *the direct retailing methods*, as immature to meet expectations. The industry also has

happy customers with *the direct retailing methods*, as a third fundamental group (i.e. 20.70%), which feels that *the direct retailing methods* are exceeding their expectations. Moreover, the industry ferriages a non-negligible number (i.e. 16.00%) of disappointed customers with *the direct retailing methods*, as maintains much less than expectations of customers. Herein, the industry also delights an effectual number (i.e. 14.90%) of customers with *the direct retailing methods* by greatly exceeding the same than customers' expectations.

Table 8.18: Comparative statistics of customer satisfaction with the direct retailing methods

Retailers	Responses on expectation cum satisfaction scale										Weighted Average Score (WAS)
	5		4		3		2		1		
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
HyperCITY	38	19.00	47	23.50	55	27.50	36	18.00	24	12.00	3.195
Star Bazaar	19	9.50	36	18.00	55	27.50	50	25.00	40	20.00	2.720
more.MEGAStore	20	10.00	34	17.00	53	26.50	51	25.50	42	21.00	2.695
Big Bazaar	40	20.00	46	23.00	60	30.00	33	16.50	21	10.50	3.255
D Mart	18	9.00	35	17.50	49	24.50	55	27.50	43	21.50	2.650
Big Megamart	27	13.50	45	22.50	50	25.00	46	23.00	32	16.00	2.945
West Side	40	20.00	44	22.00	58	29.00	36	18.00	22	11.00	3.220
Max	17	8.50	37	18.50	48	24.00	51	25.50	47	23.50	2.630
Reliance Digital	39	19.50	46	23.00	57	28.50	33	16.50	25	12.50	3.205
NEXT	40	20.00	44	22.00	58	29.00	34	17.00	24	12.00	3.210
Mean	29.80	14.90	41.40	20.70	54.30	27.15	42.50	21.25	32.00	16.00	2.973
Standard Deviation	10.475	5.238	5.211	2.606	4.165	2.082	8.860	4.430	10.044	5.022	0.567

Big Bazaar satisfies more customers with its *direct retailing methods* in comparison to its competitors or other multi-format retailers included in the study (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and D Mart). While, West Side also satisfies more customers with its *direct retailing methods* in comparison to its competitors or other fashion item retailers included in the study (i.e. Big Megamart and Max) and in the case of electronics item retailers included in this study, NEXT also satisfies more customers with its *direct retailing methods* than its competitor included in the study (i.e. Reliance Digital).

8.19 Customer satisfaction with the personal retailing methods

Figure 8.19: Weighted average scores (WAS) for customer satisfaction with the personal retailing methods

The mean WAS of all the organised retailers (included in this study) has been reckoned as the WAS of the industry for *customer satisfaction with the personal retailing methods* and scripted with the red line in *figure 8.19*. This WAS of the industry falls above the satisfied customer line in *figure 8.19*, which enlightens that the organised retail industry satisfies a gigantic majority of customers with its *personal retailing methods* (i.e. *face to face retailing in store, person to person telephonic conversation, etc.*).

The WAS for customer satisfaction with *the personal retailing methods* of some retailers (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar, Big Megamart, West Side and Reliance Digital) are greater than the WAS of the industry, which registers that these retailers satisfy more customers with their *personal retailing methods* than others (included in this study) in the industry.

Table 8.19: Comparative statistics of customer satisfaction with the personal retailing methods

Retailers	Responses on expectation cum satisfaction scale										Weighted Average Score (WAS)
	5		4		3		2		1		
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
HyperCITY	43	21.50	43	21.50	58	29.00	34	17.00	22	11.00	3.255
Star Bazaar	39	19.50	47	23.50	60	30.00	33	16.50	21	10.50	3.250
more.MEGASStore	38	19.00	46	23.00	54	27.00	38	19.00	24	12.00	3.180
Big Bazaar	44	22.00	46	23.00	57	28.50	31	15.50	22	11.00	3.295
D▲Mart	27	13.50	41	20.50	55	27.50	47	23.50	30	15.00	2.940
Big Megamart	41	20.50	46	23.00	53	26.50	35	17.50	25	12.50	3.215
West Side	43	21.50	48	24.00	55	27.50	33	16.50	21	10.50	3.295
Max	29	14.50	37	18.50	53	26.50	48	24.00	33	16.50	2.905
Reliance Digital	40	20.00	46	23.00	59	29.50	33	16.50	22	11.00	3.245
NEXT	29	14.50	39	19.50	59	29.50	43	21.50	30	15.00	2.970
Mean	37.30	18.65	43.90	21.95	56.30	28.15	37.50	18.75	25.00	12.50	3.155
Standard Deviation	6.482	3.241	3.725	1.863	2.627	1.313	6.258	3.129	4.397	2.198	0.361

The maximum (i.e. 28.15%) customers are satisfied with *the personal retailing methods* adopted by the organised retailers (included in this study), as those are matching with their expectations. The second giant group (i.e. 21.95%) of customers, who comprehend that *the personal retailing methods* are exceeding their expectations and they are happy. The next plenteous group (i.e. 18.75%) of customers is dissatisfied with *the personal retailing methods* because these are lacking to their expectations. Moreover, the industry has also an excessive number (i.e. 18.65%) of delighted customers with *the personal retailing methods* by greatly exceeding the same than their expectations. However, there is also a non-negligible disappointed (i.e. 12.50%) customers with *the personal retailing methods*, as those are much less than their expectations.

Big Bazaar also satisfies more customers with its *personal retailing methods* in comparison to its competitors or other multi-format retailers included in the study (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and D⁺Mart). While, West Side is also a better performer in satisfying more customers with its *personal retailing methods* in comparison to its competitors or other fashion item retailers included in the study (i.e. Big Megamart and Max) and in the case of electronics item retailers included in this study, Reliance Digital is a better performer in satisfying more customers with its *personal retailing methods* than its competitor included in the study (i.e. NEXT).

8.20 Customer satisfaction with the public relation/publicity methods

The mean WAS of all the organised retailers (included in this study) has been depicted as the WAS of the industry for *customer satisfaction with the public relation/publicity methods* and pointed by the red line in the *figure 8.20*.

This WAS of the industry furls beneath the satisfied customer line in the *figure 8.20*, which denotes that the organised retail industry do not satisfy a significant majority of customers with its *public relation / publicity methods (i.e. corporate brochures, posters, annual reports, press release, press conference, video press conference, internet release, store tours for media, meeting with customers, special events & sponsorships, social events, social development programs)*.

Figure 8.20: Weighted average scores (WAS) for customer satisfaction with the public relation/publicity methods

The WAS for customer satisfaction with *the public relation/publicity methods* of some retailers (i.e. HyperCITY, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar, Big Megamart, West Side, Max and Reliance Digital) are more than the WAS of the industry, which records that these retailers satisfy more customers with their *public relation/publicity methods* than others (included in this study) in the industry.

The industry satisfies the exhaustive (i.e. 26.35%) customers with *the public relation / publicity methods* by matching the same with their expectations. However, the industry totes the next large group (i.e. 21.00%) of dissatisfied customers with *public relation / publicity methods*, as imperfect to meet expectations. The industry also has happy customers with *the public relation / publicity methods*, as a third key group (i.e. 20.40%), which feels that *the public relation / publicity methods* are exceeding their expectations.

Hereto, the industry also delights a competent number (i.e. 16.25%) of customers with *the public relation / publicity methods* by greatly exceeding the same than customers' expectations. Moreover, the industry haulages a non-negligible high number (i.e. 16.00%) of disappointed customers with *public relation / publicity methods*, as tender much less than expectations of customers.

Table 8.20: Comparative statistics of customer satisfaction with the public relation/publicity methods

Retailers	Responses on expectation cum satisfaction scale										Weighted Average Score (WAS)
	5		4		3		2		1		
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
HyperCITY	38	19.00	48	24.00	57	28.50	35	17.50	22	11.00	3.225
Star Bazaar	22	11.00	33	16.50	59	29.50	47	23.50	39	19.50	2.760
more.MEGAStore	40	20.00	46	23.00	58	29.00	34	17.00	22	11.00	3.240
Big Bazaar	42	21.00	47	23.50	61	30.50	32	16.00	18	9.00	3.315
D ⁺ Mart	14	7.00	21	10.50	34	17.00	69	34.50	62	31.00	2.280
Big Megamart	39	19.50	47	23.50	54	27.00	36	18.00	24	12.00	3.205
West Side	38	19.00	48	24.00	55	27.50	33	16.50	26	13.00	3.195
Max	37	18.50	50	25.00	57	28.50	34	17.00	22	11.00	3.230
Reliance Digital	40	20.00	44	22.00	59	29.50	33	16.50	24	12.00	3.215
NEXT	15	7.50	24	12.00	33	16.50	67	33.50	61	30.50	2.325
Mean	32.50	16.25	40.80	20.40	52.70	26.35	42.00	21.00	32.00	16.00	2.999
Standard Deviation	10.977	5.489	10.737	5.369	10.318	5.159	14.353	7.176	16.499	8.250	0.870

Big Bazaar also leads in satisfying more customers with its *public relation / publicity methods* in comparison to its competitors or other multi-format retailers included in the study (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGAStore and D⁺Mart). While, Big Megamart is a better performer in satisfying more customers with its *public relation / publicity methods* in comparison to its competitors or other fashion item retailers included in the study (i.e. West Side and Max) and in the case of electronics item retailers included in this study, Reliance Digital is also a better performer in satisfying more customers with its *public relation / publicity methods* than its competitor included in the study (i.e. NEXT).

8.21 Customer satisfaction with the internet/interactive retailing methods

Figure 8.21: Weighted average scores (WAS) for customer satisfaction with the internet/interactive retailing methods

The mean WAS of all the organised retailers (included in this study) has been considered as the WAS of the industry for *customer satisfaction with the internet / interactive retailing methods* and graphed with the red line in *figure 8.21*. This WAS of the industry inclines beyond the satisfied customer line in *figure 8.21*, which intimates that the organised retail industry satisfies a large majority of customers with its *internet / interactive retailing methods* (i.e. e-mails, online discussion forums, weblogs, websites, e-pay, social networking sites).

The WAS for customer satisfaction with *the internet / interactive retailing methods* of some retailers (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar, Big Megamart, West Side, Max and Reliance Digital) are greater than the WAS of the industry, which inscribes that these retailers satisfy more customers with their *internet / interactive retailing methods* than others (included in this study) in the industry.

The utmost (i.e. 27.90%) customers are satisfied with *the internet / interactive retailing methods* adopted by the organised retailers (included in this study). The second exuberant group (i.e. 22.80%) of customers, who understand that *the*

internet / interactive retailing methods are exceeding their expectations and they are happy. Moreover, the industry has also an intense number (i.e. 19.90%) of delighted customers with *the internet / interactive retailing methods*. The next enormous group (i.e. 17.60%) of customers is dissatisfied with *the internet / interactive retailing methods*. However, there is also a significant number (i.e. 11.80%) of disappointed customers with *the internet / interactive retailing methods* adopted by industry.

Table 8.21: Comparative statistics of customer satisfaction with the internet/interactive retailing methods

Retailers	Responses on expectation cum satisfaction scale										Weighted Average Score (WAS)
	5		4		3		2		1		
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
HyperCITY	44	22.00	47	23.50	53	26.50	36	18.00	20	10.00	3.295
Star Bazaar	40	20.00	48	24.00	56	28.00	38	19.00	18	9.00	3.270
more.MEGASStore	39	19.50	48	24.00	59	29.50	34	17.00	20	10.00	3.260
Big Bazaar	46	23.00	48	24.00	62	31.00	28	14.00	16	8.00	3.400
D Mart	18	9.00	31	15.50	44	22.00	58	29.00	49	24.50	2.555
Big Megamart	44	22.00	45	22.50	53	26.50	35	17.50	23	11.50	3.260
West Side	40	20.00	47	23.50	53	26.50	36	18.00	24	12.00	3.215
Max	43	21.50	49	24.50	61	30.50	29	14.50	18	9.00	3.350
Reliance Digital	45	22.50	47	23.50	62	31.00	26	13.00	20	10.00	3.355
NEXT	39	19.50	46	23.00	55	27.50	32	16.00	28	14.00	3.180
Mean	39.80	19.90	45.60	22.80	55.80	27.90	35.20	17.60	23.60	11.80	3.214
Standard Deviation	8.080	4.040	5.254	2.627	5.554	2.777	8.917	4.458	9.571	4.785	0.527

Big Bazaar leads in satisfying more customers with its *internet / interactive retailing methods* in comparison to its competitors or other multi-format retailers included in the study (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and D Mart). While, Max is a better performer in satisfying more customers with its *internet / interactive retailing methods* in comparison to its competitors or other fashion item retailers included in the study (i.e. West Side and Big Megamart) and in the case of electronics item retailers included in this study, Reliance Digital is also a better performer in satisfying more customers with its *internet / interactive retailing methods* than its competitor included in the study (i.e. NEXT).

8.22 Customer satisfaction with the sales personnel

Figure 8.22: Weighted average scores (WAS) for customer satisfaction with the sales personnel

The mean WAS of all the organised retailers (included in this study) has been presumed as the WAS of the industry for *customer satisfaction with the sales personnel* and displayed with the red line in *figure 8.22*. This WAS of the industry leans heavily beyond the satisfied customer line in *figure 8.22*, which furnishes that the organised retail industry satisfies a great majority of customers with its *sales personnel (i.e. sales boys and sales girls)*.

The WAS for customer satisfaction with *the sales personnel* of some retailers (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, Big Bazaar, Big Megamart, West Side and Reliance Digital) are more than the WAS of the industry, which limns that these retailers satisfy more customers with their *sales personnel* than others (included in this study) in the industry.

Table 8.22: Comparative statistics of customer satisfaction with the sales personnel

Retailers	Responses on expectation cum satisfaction scale										Weighted Average Score (WAS)
	5		4		3		2		1		
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
HyperCITY	45	22.50	49	24.50	56	28.00	31	15.50	19	9.50	3.350
Star Bazaar	42	21.00	48	24.00	55	27.50	33	16.50	22	11.00	3.275
more.MEGAStore	40	20.00	45	22.50	57	28.50	36	18.00	22	11.00	3.225
Big Bazaar	48	24.00	52	26.00	61	30.50	26	13.00	13	6.50	3.480
D [▲] Mart	21	10.50	33	16.50	51	25.50	56	28.00	39	19.50	2.705
Big Megamart	44	22.00	50	25.00	58	29.00	28	14.00	20	10.00	3.350
West Side	42	21.00	52	26.00	60	30.00	29	14.50	17	8.50	3.365
Max	29	14.50	42	21.00	56	28.00	42	21.00	31	15.50	2.980
Reliance Digital	43	21.50	48	24.00	58	29.00	31	15.50	20	10.00	3.315
NEXT	40	20.00	46	23.00	54	27.00	36	18.00	24	12.00	3.210
Mean	39.40	19.70	46.50	23.25	56.60	28.30	34.80	17.40	22.70	11.35	3.226
Standard Deviation	8.168	4.084	5.662	2.831	2.914	1.457	8.779	4.389	7.394	3.697	0.486

The industry satisfies the utmost (i.e. 28.30%) customers with *the sales personnel* by matching the same with their expectations. The industry also has happy customers with *the sales personnel*, as a second major group (i.e. 23.25%), which feels that *the sales personnel* are exceeding their expectations. Moreover, the industry also delights a substantial number (i.e. 19.70%) of customers with *the sales personnel* by greatly exceeding the performance than customers' expectations. However, the industry carries the next major group (i.e. 17.40%) of dissatisfied customers with *the sales personnel*, as lacking to meet expectations of customers. At the same time, the industry hauls a non-negligible number (i.e. 11.35%) of disappointed customers with *the sales personnel*, as performed much less than expectations of customers.

Big Bazaar also leads in satisfying more customers with its *sales personnel* in comparison to its competitors or other multi-format retailers included in the study (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and D Mart). While, West Side is a better performer in satisfying more customers with its *sales personnel* in comparison to its competitors or other fashion item retailers included in the study (i.e. Max and Big Megamart) and in the case of electronics item retailers included in this study, Reliance Digital is also a better performer in satisfying more customers with its *sales personnel* than its competitor included in the study (i.e. NEXT).

8.23 Customer satisfaction with the contact personnel

Figure 8.23: Weighted average scores (WAS) for customer satisfaction with the sales personnel

The mean WAS of all the organised retailers (included in this study) has been recognised as the WAS of the industry for *customer satisfaction with the contact personnel* and demonstrated by the red line in *figure 8.23*. This WAS of the industry bows beyond the satisfied customer line in *figure 8.23*, which imparts that the organised retail industry satisfies a huge majority of customers with its *contact personnel* (i.e. *help desk people, service desk people, billing counter people, etc.*).

The WAS for customer satisfaction with *the contact personnel* of some retailers (i.e. HyperCITY, Big Bazaar, Big Megamart, West Side and Reliance Digital) are greater than the WAS of the industry, which pens that these retailers satisfy more customers with their *contact personnel* than others (included in this study) in the industry.

The majority (i.e. 28.30%) customers are satisfied with *the contact personnel* of the organised retailers (included in this study), as those are matching with their expectations. The second plenteous group (i.e. 23.45%) of customers, who ponder that *the contact personnel* are exceeding their expectations and they are happy.

The third adjunct group (i.e. 20.20%) of customers is delighted with *the contact personnel* because the performance of the same is greatly exceeding their expectations. However, there are also a pervasive number of customers, who are either dissatisfied (i.e. 16.70%) or disappointed (i.e. 11.35%) with *the contact personnel*, because, those are less than or much less than their expectations.

Big Bazaar also leads in satisfying more customers with its *contact personnel* in comparison to its competitors or other multi-format retailers included in the study (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and D▲Mart).

While, West Side is also a better performer in satisfying more customers with its *contact personnel* in comparison to its competitors or other fashion item retailers included in the study (i.e. Max and Big Megamart) and in the case of electronics item retailers included in this study, Reliance Digital also leads in satisfying more customers with its *contact personnel* than its competitor included in the study (i.e. NEXT).

Table 8.23: Comparative statistics of customer satisfaction with the contact personnel

Retailers	Responses on expectation cum satisfaction scale										Weighted Average Score (WAS)
	5		4		3		2		1		
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
HyperCITY	43	21.50	45	22.50	54	27.00	35	17.50	23	11.50	3.250
Star Bazaar	40	20.00	46	23.00	57	28.50	35	17.50	22	11.00	3.235
more.MEGAStore	37	18.50	44	22.00	57	28.50	37	18.50	25	12.50	3.155
Big Bazaar	46	23.00	53	26.50	60	30.00	27	13.50	14	7.00	3.450
D ⁺ Mart	31	15.50	42	21.00	54	27.00	40	20.00	33	16.50	2.990
Big Megamart	47	23.50	51	25.50	59	29.50	25	12.50	18	9.00	3.420
West Side	46	23.00	53	26.50	57	28.50	28	14.00	16	8.00	3.425
Max	40	20.00	46	23.00	58	29.00	33	16.50	23	11.50	3.235
Reliance Digital	42	21.00	49	24.50	57	28.50	30	15.00	22	11.00	3.295
NEXT	32	16.00	40	20.00	53	26.50	44	22.00	31	15.50	2.990
Mean	40.40	20.20	46.90	23.45	56.60	28.30	33.40	16.70	22.70	11.35	3.245
Standard Deviation	5.641	2.821	4.483	2.242	2.271	1.135	6.022	3.011	6.001	3.000	0.355

8.24 Customer satisfaction with the factors pertained to personnel

Figure 8.24: Weighted average scores (WAS) for customer satisfaction with the factors pertained to personnel

The mean WAS of all the organised retailers (included in this study) has been admitted as the WAS of the industry for *customer satisfaction with the factors pertained to personnel* and striated with the red line in *figure 8.24*. This WAS of the industry slouches beyond the satisfied customer line in the *figure 8.24*, which informs that the organised retail industry satisfies an enormous majority of customers with *factors pertained to personnel* (i.e. *mood, efforts, commitment, attitude, knowledge, skills, behaviour, approach to deliver the service, competence, courtesy, credibility, reliability, responsiveness, communication style, friendliness, helpfulness, discipline & punctuality, customer counselling ability*).

The WAS for customer satisfaction with *the factors pertained to personnel* of some retailers (i.e. HyperCITY, Big Bazaar, Big Megamart, West Side and Reliance Digital) are more than the WAS of the industry, which shapes that these retailers satisfy more customers with the *factors pertained to personnel* than others (included in this study) in the industry.

The maximum (i.e. 28.75%) customers are satisfied with *the factors pertained to personnel* of the organised retailers (included in this study), as those are matching

with their expectations. The second exuberant group (i.e. 23.55%) of customers, who perceive that *the factors pertained to personnel* are exceeding their expectations and they are happy.

Table 8.24: Comparative statistics of customer satisfaction with the factors pertained to personnel

Retailers	Responses on expectation cum satisfaction scale										Weighted Average Score (WAS)
	5		4		3		2		1		
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
HyperCITY	46	23.00	53	26.50	60	30.00	27	13.50	14	7.00	3.450
Star Bazaar	40	20.00	42	21.00	57	28.50	38	19.00	23	11.50	3.190
more.MEGAStore	39	19.50	43	21.50	56	28.00	37	18.50	25	12.50	3.170
Big Bazaar	48	24.00	55	27.50	61	30.50	25	12.50	11	5.50	3.520
D ⁺ Mart	29	14.50	42	21.00	56	28.00	42	21.00	31	15.50	2.980
Big Megamart	48	24.00	54	27.00	60	30.00	24	12.00	14	7.00	3.490
West Side	44	22.00	52	26.00	59	29.50	28	14.00	17	8.50	3.390
Max	31	15.50	41	20.50	51	25.50	45	22.50	32	16.00	2.970
Reliance Digital	40	20.00	47	23.50	61	30.50	31	15.50	21	10.50	3.270
NEXT	30	15.00	42	21.00	54	27.00	41	20.50	33	16.50	2.975
Mean	39.50	19.75	47.10	23.55	57.50	28.75	33.80	16.90	22.10	11.05	3.241
Standard Deviation	7.307	3.653	5.782	2.891	3.308	1.654	7.700	3.850	8.075	4.038	0.465

Moreover, the industry also delights an adequate number (i.e. 19.75%) of customers with *the factors pertained to personnel* by greatly exceeding the same than customers' expectations. The next enormous group (i.e. 16.90%) of customers are dissatisfied with *the factors pertained to personnel* because those are deficient to their expectations. There is also a non-negligible number (i.e. 11.05%) of customers, those are disappointed with *the factors pertained to personnel*, as those are much less than their expectations.

Big Bazaar champs in satisfying more customers with *the factors pertained to personnel* in comparison to its competitors or other multi-format retailers included in the study (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and D Mart). While, Big Megamart is a better performer in satisfying more customers with *the factors pertained to personnel* in comparison to its competitors or other fashion item retailers included in the study (i.e. Max and West Side) and in the case of electronics item retailers included in this study, Reliance Digital also champs in satisfying more customers with *the factors pertained to personnel* than its competitor included in the study (i.e. NEXT).

8.25 Customer satisfaction with the other tangible evidence

Figure 8.25: Weighted average scores (WAS) for customer satisfaction with the other tangible evidence

The mean WAS of all the organised retailers (included in this study) has been conceded as the WAS of the industry for *customer satisfaction with the other tangible evidence* and drawn with the red line in the *figure 8.25*. This WAS of the industry crouches beyond the satisfied customer line in the *figure 8.25*, which confabulates that the organised retail industry satisfies a giant majority of customers with *other tangible evidence* (i.e. *employee appearance, uniforms, billing statements, stationery, business cards, signage, exterior design, reports, brochures, the internet or web pages*).

The WAS for customer satisfaction with *the other tangible evidences* of some retailers (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, Big Bazaar, Big Megamart, West Side and Reliance Digital) are greater than the WAS of the industry, which indites that these retailers satisfy more customers with the *other tangible evidence* than others (included in this study) in the industry.

The industry satisfies the utmost (i.e. 28.90%) customers with *the other tangible evidence* by matching the same with their expectations. The industry also has happy customers with *the other tangible evidence*, as a second major group (i.e. 24.25%), which feels that *the other tangible evidence* are exceeding their expectations.

Moreover, the industry also delights a substantial number (i.e. 19.15%) of customers with *the other tangible evidence* by greatly exceeding the same than customers' expectations. However, the industry carries the next major group (i.e. 16.50%) of dissatisfied customers with *the other tangible evidence*, as lacking to meet expectations of customers.

At the same time, the industry hauls a non-negligible number (i.e. 11.20%) of disappointed customers with *the other tangible evidence*, as provided much less than expectations of customers.

Big Bazaar also champs in satisfying more customers with *the other tangible evidence* in comparison to its competitors or other multi-format retailers included in the study (i.e. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and D⁺Mart).

Retailers	Responses on expectation cum satisfaction scale										Weighted Average Score (WAS)
	5		4		3		2		1		
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
HyperCITY	41	20.50	52	26.00	57	28.50	30	15.00	20	10.00	3.320
Star Bazaar	42	21.00	53	26.50	55	27.50	31	15.50	19	9.50	3.340
more.MEGAStore	37	18.50	45	22.50	56	28.00	37	18.50	25	12.50	3.160
Big Bazaar	40	20.00	57	28.50	59	29.50	26	13.00	18	9.00	3.375
D ⁺ Mart	27	13.50	40	20.00	58	29.00	45	22.50	30	15.00	2.945
Big Megamart	45	22.50	55	27.50	59	29.50	26	13.00	15	7.50	3.445
West Side	40	20.00	54	27.00	61	30.50	26	13.00	19	9.50	3.350
Max	40	20.00	42	21.00	57	28.50	36	18.00	25	12.50	3.180
Reliance Digital	43	21.50	45	22.50	59	29.50	33	16.50	20	10.00	3.290
NEXT	28	14.00	42	21.00	57	28.50	40	20.00	33	16.50	2.960
Mean	38.30	19.15	48.50	24.25	57.80	28.90	33.00	16.50	22.40	11.20	3.237
Standard Deviation	6.075	3.037	6.311	3.156	1.751	0.876	6.481	3.240	5.700	2.850	0.398

While, Big Megamart is also a better performer in satisfying more customers with *the other tangible evidence* in comparison to its competitors or other fashion item retailers included in the study (i.e. Max and West Side) and in the case of electronics item retailers included in this study, Reliance Digital also leads in satisfying more customers with *the other tangible evidences* than its competitor included in the study (i.e. NEXT).

TESTING OF HYPOTHESES

Introduction

The mentioned below null hypotheses were formulated based on gaps in the literature review and objectives of the study. These hypotheses were formulated to study whether any significance exists of various strategies of organised retailers for significantly satisfying customers with various products & services.

H₀₁: Retailing strategies introduced by organised retailers are not significant to sustain in the hyper-competitive retail market.

H₀₂: Customers are not significantly satisfied with various products & services introduced by organised retailers.

For the purpose of statistical analyses, Kolmogorov-Smirnov one-sample test and one sample t-test have been identified to test the hypotheses.

Testing of hypothesis H₀₁

The conventional method for testing the hypothesis is to formulate the two hypotheses instead of one (Beri, 2000). The first is null hypothesis and second is an alternate hypothesis. Hence, the alternate hypothesis of **H₀₁** has also been formulated as mentioned below.

H_{A1}: Retailing strategies introduced by organised retailers are significant to sustain in the hyper-competitive retail market.

This hypothesis was formulated under certain assumptions for which no validation required as it is a common noticeable phenomenon that “retailing strategies introduced by organised retailers are significant to sustain in hyper-competitive retail market”. However, this statement is supported by product portfolio analysis (presented in chapter 5) where the significant majority of merchandise (products) of all the organised retailers (included in this study) belongs to Star category in the BCG matrix. Moreover, this alternate hypothesis (**H_{A1}**) is also supported by the customer satisfaction with various merchandise (products) and services offered by all the

organised retailers (included in this study). Therefore, the null hypothesis H_{01} i.e. retailing strategies introduced by organised retailers are not significant to sustain in the hyper-competitive retail market is rejected and the alternate hypothesis H_{A1} is accepted.

Testing of hypothesis H_{02}

The alternate hypothesis of H_{02} has also been formulated as mentioned below.

H_{A2} : Customers are significantly satisfied with various products & services introduced by organised retailers.

For testing this hypothesis, the data has been collected from the customers of 10 organised retailers (included in this study) through the question no. 30 of the individual questionnaire. This question no. 30 of the individual questionnaire comprises the 25 variables and some sub-variables of the organised retailers. The responses of customers pertained to the satisfaction have been collected on five point expectation cum satisfaction scale (basically an ordinal scale) ranging from greatly exceeding expectations and delighted (5), to much less than expectations and disappointed (1) with the middle of the scale identified by the response alternative matching expectations and satisfied (3). These responses of the customers about all 25 variables have been utilised to test this hypothesis (H_{02}) with the comprehension that if the customers are significantly satisfied with these 25 variables of organised retailers, therefore, they are significantly satisfied with various products & services introduced by organised retailers. Moreover, the means of the responses on all the 5 parameters of the scale have been considered as the representative responses of the industry for testing the hypothesis in the case of the overall industry.

For the purpose of statistical analyses, Kolmogorov-Smirnov one-sample test and one sample t-test have been identified to test the hypothesis. Kolmogorov-Smirnov one-sample test was used to study that whether there is a difference in the level of satisfaction of the respondents (i.e. customers of organised retailers). Therefore, Kolmogorov-Smirnov 'D' values (K-S 'D' Value) for all the 25 variables were calculated and compared with the critical values. The critical K-S 'D' value at

the 5% level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) is 0.096 and at the 10% level of significance ($\alpha = 0.10$) is 0.86.

And then, one sample t-test has been used to test the hypothesis H_{02} . The degree of freedom (DF) for each organised retailer will be 199 as the sample size is 200 customers of each organised retailers. The mean of the scale (μ) is 3, which is the test value. Only right-tailed values have been considered to test the hypothesis H_{02} . At the 5% level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$), the critical value of t is 1.645 and at the 10% level of significance ($\alpha = 0.10$), the critical value of t is 1.282. The results of both tests for all the 25 variables have been presented in the tables 8.26 to 8.50.

Retailers	Statistics of Kolmogorov-Smirnov one sample test			Statistics of one sample t-test			
	Calculated K-S 'D' Value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?	Calculated 't' value	p-value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?
HyperCITY	0.190	0.05	Yes	2.337	0.010	0.05	Yes
Star Bazaar	0.175	0.05	Yes	1.819	0.035	0.05	Yes
more.MEGASStore	0.155	0.05	Yes	1.699	0.045	0.05	Yes
Big Bazaar	0.270	0.05	Yes	2.389	0.009	0.05	Yes
D Mart	0.130	0.05	Yes	1.654	0.050	0.05	Yes
Big Megamart	0.285	0.05	Yes	2.417	0.008	0.05	Yes
West Side	0.230	0.05	Yes	2.344	0.010	0.05	Yes
Max	0.160	0.05	Yes	1.906	0.029	0.05	Yes
Reliance Digital	0.135	0.05	Yes	1.890	0.030	0.05	Yes
NEXT	0.170	0.05	Yes	2.287	0.012	0.05	Yes
Overall Industry	0.190	0.05	Yes	2.145	0.017	0.05	Yes

The calculated K-S 'D' values exceed the critical values (at the 5% level of significance) for *customer satisfaction with merchandise assortment* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well the overall industry, which signifies that there is a significant difference in the level of satisfaction of customers *with merchandise assortment* of all the organised retailers.

The calculated 't' values exceed the critical values (at the 5% level of significance) for *customer satisfaction with merchandise assortment* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry. Hence, the null hypothesis H_{02} i.e. "customers are not significantly satisfied with various products & services introduced by organised retailers" is rejected in case of *customer satisfaction with merchandise assortment* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry and the alternate hypothesis H_{A2} is accepted.

Retailers	Statistics of Kolmogorov-Smirnov one sample test			Statistics of one sample t-test			
	Calculated K-S 'D' Value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?	Calculated 't' value	p-value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?
HyperCITY	0.135	0.05	Yes	1.963	0.026	0.05	Yes
Star Bazaar	0.125	0.05	Yes	1.716	0.044	0.05	Yes
more.MEGASStore	0.095	0.10	Yes	1.466	0.072	0.10	Yes
Big Bazaar	0.205	0.05	Yes	2.242	0.013	0.05	Yes
Dmart	0.070	0.10	No	0.539	0.295	0.10	No
Big Megamart	0.170	0.05	Yes	2.162	0.016	0.05	Yes
West Side	0.160	0.05	Yes	2.068	0.020	0.05	Yes
Max	0.090	0.10	Yes	1.529	0.064	0.10	Yes
Reliance Digital	0.090	0.10	Yes	1.458	0.073	0.10	Yes
NEXT	0.125	0.05	Yes	2.243	0.013	0.05	Yes
Overall Industry	0.127	0.05	Yes	1.839	0.034	0.05	Yes

The computed K-S 'D' values exceed the critical values (at an α of 5% or 10%) for *customer satisfaction with merchandise categories in the assortment* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well the overall industry except Dmart, which evinces that there is a significant difference in the level of satisfaction of customers *with merchandise categories in the assortment* of all the organised retailers except Dmart.

The calculated 't' values also exceed the critical values (at an α of 5% or 10%) for *customer satisfaction with merchandise categories in the assortment* of all the

organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry except D⁺Mart. Hence, the null hypothesis H_{02} is rejected in case of *customer satisfaction with merchandise categories in the assortment* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry except D⁺Mart and the alternate hypothesis H_{A2} is accepted. But, the null hypothesis H_{02} is accepted in case of *merchandise categories in the assortment* of D⁺Mart. D⁺Mart is a superstore based retailer and offers limited *merchandise categories in the assortment* to its customers.

Retailers	Statistics of Kolmogorov-Smirnov one sample test			Statistics of one sample t-test			
	Calculated K-S 'D' Value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?	Calculated 't' value	p-value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?
HyperCITY	0.130	0.05	Yes	2.086	0.026	0.05	Yes
Star Bazaar	0.120	0.05	Yes	1.779	0.044	0.05	Yes
more.MEGASStore	0.090	0.10	Yes	1.604	0.072	0.10	Yes
Big Bazaar	0.235	0.05	Yes	2.475	0.013	0.05	Yes
D ⁺ Mart	0.080	0.10	No	0.950	0.295	0.10	No
Big Megamart	0.165	0.05	Yes	2.522	0.016	0.05	Yes
West Side	0.175	0.05	Yes	2.171	0.020	0.05	Yes
Max	0.090	0.10	Yes	1.616	0.064	0.10	Yes
Reliance Digital	0.090	0.10	Yes	1.643	0.073	0.10	Yes
NEXT	0.105	0.05	Yes	1.801	0.013	0.05	Yes
Overall Industry	0.128	0.05	Yes	2.003	0.034	0.05	Yes

The calculated K-S 'D' values exceed the critical values (at $\alpha = 0.05$ or 0.10) for *customer satisfaction with the variety of merchandise in each category* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well the overall industry except D⁺Mart, which evinces that there is a significant difference in the level of satisfaction of customers *with the variety of merchandise in each category* of all the organised retailers except D⁺Mart.

The computed 't' values also exceed the critical values (at an α of 5% or 10%) for *customer satisfaction with the variety of merchandise in each category* of all the

organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry except D⁺Mart. Hence, the null hypothesis H_{02} is rejected in case of *customer satisfaction with the variety of merchandise in each category* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry except D⁺Mart and the alternate hypothesis H_{A2} is accepted. But, the null hypothesis H_{02} is accepted in the case of *the variety of merchandise in each category* of D⁺Mart. D⁺Mart is a superstore based multi-item retailer and offers a limited *variety of merchandise in each category* for its customers.

Table 8.29: Statistics of Kolmogorov-Smirnov one-sample test and one sample t-test for customer satisfaction with the availability of newly launched merchandise, customised merchandise, unique merchandise and complementary merchandise

Retailers	Statistics of Kolmogorov-Smirnov one sample test			Statistics of one sample t-test			
	Calculated K-S 'D' Value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?	Calculated 't' value	p-value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?
HyperCITY	0.130	0.05	Yes	1.697	0.046	0.05	Yes
Star Bazaar	0.090	0.10	Yes	1.565	0.060	0.10	Yes
more.MEGASStore	0.150	0.05	Yes	1.677	0.048	0.05	Yes
Big Bazaar	0.185	0.05	Yes	1.951	0.026	0.05	Yes
D ⁺ Mart	0.060	0.10	No	0.672	0.251	0.10	No
Big Megamart	0.190	0.05	Yes	1.994	0.024	0.05	Yes
West Side	0.170	0.05	Yes	1.880	0.031	0.05	Yes
Max	0.135	0.05	Yes	1.852	0.033	0.05	Yes
Reliance Digital	0.145	0.05	Yes	1.651	0.050	0.05	Yes
NEXT	0.135	0.05	Yes	1.648	0.050	0.05	Yes
Overall Industry	0.139	0.05	Yes	1.734	0.042	0.05	Yes

The computed K-S 'D' values exceed the critical values (at an α of 5% or 10%) for *customer satisfaction with the availability of newly launched merchandise, customised merchandise, unique merchandise and complementary merchandise* by all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well the overall industry except D⁺Mart, which reveals that there is a significant difference in the level of satisfaction of customers *with the availability of newly launched merchandise, customised merchandise, unique merchandise and complementary merchandise* by all the organised retailers except D⁺Mart.

The calculated 't' values also exceed the critical values (at an α of 5% or 10%) for *customer satisfaction with the availability of newly launched merchandise, customised merchandise, unique merchandise and complementary merchandise* by all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry except D Mart. Hence, the null hypothesis H_{02} is rejected in case of *customer satisfaction with the availability of newly launched merchandise, customised merchandise, unique merchandise and complementary merchandise* from all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry except D Mart and the alternate hypothesis H_{A2} is accepted. But, the null hypothesis H_{02} is accepted in the case of *the availability of newly launched merchandise, customised merchandise, unique merchandise and complementary merchandise* by D Mart. D Mart is a superstore based multi-item retailer and makes sure the limited *availability of newly launched merchandise, customised merchandise, unique merchandise and complementary merchandise* to its customers.

Table 8.30: Statistics of Kolmogorov-Smirnov one-sample test and one sample t-test for customer satisfaction with the brands in each merchandise category

Retailers	Statistics of Kolmogorov-Smirnov one sample test			Statistics of one sample t-test			
	Calculated K-S 'D' Value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?	Calculated 't' value	p-value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?
HyperCITY	0.120	0.05	Yes	1.724	0.043	0.05	Yes
Star Bazaar	0.125	0.05	Yes	1.725	0.043	0.05	Yes
more.MEGASStore	0.095	0.10	Yes	1.302	0.097	0.10	Yes
Big Bazaar	0.155	0.05	Yes	2.116	0.018	0.05	Yes
D Mart	0.090	0.10	Yes	1.292	0.099	0.10	Yes
Big Megamart	0.245	0.05	Yes	2.585	0.005	0.05	Yes
West Side	0.180	0.05	Yes	2.283	0.012	0.05	Yes
Max	0.130	0.05	Yes	1.871	0.031	0.05	Yes
Reliance Digital	0.135	0.05	Yes	1.676	0.048	0.05	Yes
NEXT	0.160	0.05	Yes	1.663	0.049	0.05	Yes
Overall Industry	0.144	0.05	Yes	1.952	0.026	0.05	Yes

The calculated K-S ‘D’ values exceed the critical values (at $\alpha = 0.05$ or 0.10) for *customer satisfaction with the brands in each merchandise category* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well the overall industry, which manifests that there is a significant difference in the level of satisfaction of customers with the brands in each merchandise category of all the organised retailers.

The computed ‘t’ values also exceed the critical values (at an α of 5% or 10%) for *customer satisfaction with the brands in each merchandise category* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry. Hence, the null hypothesis H_{02} is rejected in case of *customer satisfaction with the brands in each merchandise category* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry and the alternate hypothesis H_{A2} is accepted.

Retailers	Statistics of Kolmogorov-Smirnov one sample test			Statistics of one sample t-test			
	Calculated K-S ‘D’ Value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?	Calculated ‘t’ value	p-value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?
HyperCITY	0.155	0.05	Yes	2.028	0.022	0.05	Yes
Star Bazaar	0.185	0.05	Yes	1.653	0.050	0.05	Yes
more.MEGASStore	0.160	0.05	Yes	1.725	0.043	0.05	Yes
Big Bazaar	0.230	0.05	Yes	2.171	0.016	0.05	Yes
D ⁺ Mart	0.180	0.05	Yes	1.700	0.045	0.05	Yes
Big Megamart	0.165	0.05	Yes	2.164	0.016	0.05	Yes
West Side	0.175	0.05	Yes	2.046	0.021	0.05	Yes
Max	0.145	0.05	Yes	1.687	0.047	0.05	Yes
Reliance Digital	0.155	0.05	Yes	1.675	0.048	0.05	Yes
NEXT	0.165	0.05	Yes	1.666	0.049	0.05	Yes
Overall Industry	0.172	0.05	Yes	1.884	0.031	0.05	Yes

The computed K-S ‘D’ values exceed the critical values (at the 5% level of significance) for *customer satisfaction with quality assurance and quality of merchandise* by all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well the overall

industry, which proves that there is a significant difference in the level of satisfaction of customers *with quality assurance and quality of merchandise* of all the organised retailers.

The calculated ‘t’ values also exceed the critical values (at the 5% level of significance) for *customer satisfaction with quality assurance and quality of merchandise* by all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry. Hence, the null hypothesis H_{02} is rejected in case of *customer satisfaction with quality assurance and quality of merchandise* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry and the alternate hypothesis H_{A2} is accepted.

Retailers	Statistics of Kolmogorov-Smirnov one sample test			Statistics of one sample t-test			
	Calculated K-S ‘D’ Value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?	Calculated ‘t’ value	p-value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?
HyperCITY	0.240	0.05	Yes	2.463	0.007	0.05	Yes
Star Bazaar	0.200	0.05	Yes	1.924	0.028	0.05	Yes
more.MEGASStore	0.170	0.05	Yes	1.678	0.047	0.05	Yes
Big Bazaar	0.270	0.05	Yes	2.482	0.007	0.05	Yes
D ⁺ Mart	0.080	0.10	No	0.102	0.459	0.10	No
Big Megamart	0.145	0.05	Yes	2.181	0.015	0.05	Yes
West Side	0.195	0.05	Yes	2.352	0.010	0.05	Yes
Max	0.085	0.10	No	0.519	0.302	0.10	No
Reliance Digital	0.135	0.05	Yes	1.910	0.029	0.05	Yes
NEXT	0.115	0.05	Yes	1.689	0.046	0.05	Yes
Overall Industry	0.158	0.05	Yes	1.939	0.027	0.05	Yes

The calculated K-S ‘D’ values exceed the critical values (at $\alpha = 0.05$) for *customer satisfaction with the services* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well the overall industry except D⁺Mart and Max, which endorses that there is a significant difference in the level of satisfaction of customers *with the services* of all the organised retailers except D⁺Mart and Max.

The computed ‘t’ values also exceed the critical values (at an α of 5%) for *customer satisfaction with the services* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry except D[▲]Mart and Max. Hence, the null hypothesis H_{02} is rejected in case of *customer satisfaction with the services* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry except D[▲]Mart and Max, and the alternate hypothesis H_{A2} is accepted. But, the null hypothesis H_{02} is accepted in the case of *the services* of D[▲]Mart and Max. D[▲]Mart is a superstore based multi-item retailer and Max is a superstore based fashion-item retailer. Both offer limited *services* to their customers in comparison to their competitors.

Retailers	Statistics of Kolmogorov-Smirnov one sample test			Statistics of one sample t-test			
	Calculated K-S ‘D’ Value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?	Calculated ‘t’ value	p-value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?
HyperCITY	0.140	0.05	Yes	2.004	0.023	0.05	Yes
Star Bazaar	0.125	0.05	Yes	1.677	0.048	0.05	Yes
more.MEGASStore	0.110	0.05	Yes	1.706	0.045	0.05	Yes
Big Bazaar	0.215	0.05	Yes	2.362	0.010	0.05	Yes
D [▲] Mart	0.070	0.10	No	0.041	0.484	0.10	No
Big Megamart	0.180	0.05	Yes	2.442	0.008	0.05	Yes
West Side	0.195	0.05	Yes	2.364	0.010	0.05	Yes
Max	0.080	0.10	No	0.941	0.174	0.10	No
Reliance Digital	0.115	0.05	Yes	1.693	0.046	0.05	Yes
NEXT	0.085	0.10	No	1.206	0.115	0.10	No
Overall Industry	0.127	0.05	Yes	1.836	0.034	0.05	Yes

The computed K-S ‘D’ values exceed the critical values (at an α of 5%) for *customer satisfaction with the quality of the services* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well the overall industry except D[▲]Mart, Max and NEXT, which substantiates that there is a significant difference in the level of satisfaction of customers *with the quality of the services* of all the organised retailers except D[▲]Mart, Max and NEXT.

The calculated ‘t’ values also exceed the critical values (at an α of 5%) for *customer satisfaction with the quality of the services* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry except D Δ Mart, Max and NEXT. Hence, the null hypothesis H_{02} is rejected in case of *customer satisfaction with the quality of the services* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry except D Δ Mart, Max and NEXT and the alternate hypothesis H_{A2} is accepted. But, the null hypothesis H_{02} is accepted in the case of *the quality of the services* of D Δ Mart, Max and NEXT. D Δ Mart is a superstore based multi-item retailer, Max is a superstore based fashion-item retailer and NEXT is a superstore based electronics-item retailer. According to their customers, *the quality of the services* of these three retailers falls short of their expectations.

Retailers	Statistics of Kolmogorov-Smirnov one sample test			Statistics of one sample t-test			
	Calculated K-S ‘D’ Value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?	Calculated ‘t’ value	p-value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?
HyperCITY	0.115	0.05	Yes	1.661	0.049	0.05	Yes
Star Bazaar	0.135	0.05	Yes	1.685	0.047	0.05	Yes
more.MEGASStore	0.135	0.05	Yes	1.676	0.048	0.05	Yes
Big Bazaar	0.200	0.05	Yes	1.881	0.031	0.05	Yes
D Δ Mart	0.190	0.05	Yes	2.352	0.010	0.05	Yes
Big Megamart	0.105	0.05	Yes	1.691	0.046	0.05	Yes
West Side	0.100	0.05	Yes	1.661	0.049	0.05	Yes
Max	0.115	0.05	Yes	1.789	0.038	0.05	Yes
Reliance Digital	0.130	0.05	Yes	1.648	0.050	0.05	Yes
NEXT	0.215	0.05	Yes	2.391	0.009	0.05	Yes
Overall Industry	0.144	0.05	Yes	1.918	0.028	0.05	Yes

The calculated K-S ‘D’ values exceed the critical values (at the 5% level of significance) for *customer satisfaction with the pricing of merchandise & services* of

all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well the overall industry, which reasserts that there is a significant difference in the level of satisfaction of customers *with the pricing of merchandise & services* of all the organised retailers.

The computed ‘t’ values also exceed the critical values (at the 5% level of significance) for *customer satisfaction with the pricing of merchandise & services* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry. Hence, the null hypothesis H_{02} is rejected in case of *customer satisfaction with the pricing of merchandise & services* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry and the alternate hypothesis H_{A2} is accepted.

Retailers	Statistics of Kolmogorov-Smirnov one sample test			Statistics of one sample t-test			
	Calculated K-S ‘D’ Value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?	Calculated ‘t’ value	p-value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?
HyperCITY	0.125	0.05	Yes	1.766	0.039	0.05	Yes
Star Bazaar	0.105	0.05	Yes	1.647	0.050	0.05	Yes
more.MEGASStore	0.110	0.05	Yes	1.761	0.040	0.05	Yes
Big Bazaar	0.200	0.05	Yes	2.327	0.010	0.05	Yes
D ⁺ Mart	0.110	0.05	Yes	1.808	0.036	0.05	Yes
Big Megamart	0.110	0.05	Yes	1.689	0.046	0.05	Yes
West Side	0.110	0.05	Yes	1.681	0.047	0.05	Yes
Max	0.100	0.05	Yes	1.663	0.049	0.05	Yes
Reliance Digital	0.100	0.05	Yes	1.727	0.043	0.05	Yes
NEXT	0.105	0.05	Yes	2.009	0.023	0.05	Yes
Overall Industry	0.117	0.05	Yes	1.878	0.031	0.05	Yes

The computed K-S ‘D’ values exceed the critical values (at $\alpha = 0.05$) for *customer satisfaction with the overall value V/S price of merchandise & services* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well the overall industry, which confirms that there is a significant difference in the level of satisfaction of customers *with the overall value V/S price of merchandise & services* of all the organised retailers.

The calculated 't' values also exceed the critical values (at $\alpha = 0.05$) for *customer satisfaction with the overall value V/S price of merchandise & services* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry. Hence, the null hypothesis H_{02} is rejected in case of *customer satisfaction with the overall value V/S price of merchandise & services* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry and the alternate hypothesis H_{A2} is accepted.

Retailers	Statistics of Kolmogorov-Smirnov one sample test			Statistics of one sample t-test			
	Calculated K-S 'D' Value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?	Calculated 't' value	p-value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?
HyperCITY	0.170	0.05	Yes	1.727	0.043	0.05	Yes
Star Bazaar	0.165	0.05	Yes	1.985	0.024	0.05	Yes
more.MEGASStore	0.125	0.05	Yes	1.795	0.037	0.05	Yes
Big Bazaar	0.235	0.05	Yes	2.242	0.013	0.05	Yes
D-Mart	0.085	0.10	No	0.468	0.320	0.10	No
Big Megamart	0.210	0.05	Yes	2.527	0.006	0.05	Yes
West Side	0.180	0.05	Yes	1.940	0.027	0.05	Yes
Max	0.060	0.10	No	0.329	0.371	0.10	No
Reliance Digital	0.180	0.05	Yes	1.855	0.033	0.05	Yes
NEXT	0.080	0.10	No	0.088	0.465	0.10	No
Overall Industry	0.149	0.05	Yes	1.681	0.047	0.05	Yes

The computed K-S 'D' values exceed the critical values (at an α of 5%) for *customer satisfaction with the exterior atmospherics of the store* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well the overall industry except D-Mart, Max and NEXT, which ratifies that there is a significant difference in the level of satisfaction of customers *with the exterior atmospherics of the store* of all the organised retailers except D-Mart, Max and NEXT.

The calculated 't' values also exceed the critical values (at an α of 5%) for *customer satisfaction with the exterior atmospherics of the store* of all the organised

retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry except D[▲]Mart, Max and NEXT. Hence, the null hypothesis H_{02} is rejected in case of *customer satisfaction with the exterior atmospherics of the store* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry except D[▲]Mart, Max and NEXT and the alternate hypothesis H_{A2} is accepted. But, the null hypothesis H_{02} is accepted in the case of *the exterior atmospherics of the store* of D[▲]Mart, Max and NEXT. D[▲]Mart is a superstore based multi-item retailer, Max is a superstore based fashion-item retailer and NEXT is a superstore based electronics-item retailer. As per their customers, *the exterior atmospherics of the store* of these three retailers are less than their expectations.

Retailers	Statistics of Kolmogorov-Smirnov one sample test			Statistics of one sample t-test			
	Calculated K-S 'D' Value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?	Calculated 't' value	p-value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?
HyperCITY	0.175	0.05	Yes	2.014	0.023	0.05	Yes
Star Bazaar	0.175	0.05	Yes	1.976	0.025	0.05	Yes
more.MEGASStore	0.140	0.05	Yes	1.664	0.049	0.05	Yes
Big Bazaar	0.240	0.05	Yes	2.279	0.012	0.05	Yes
D [▲] Mart	0.055	0.10	No	-1.180	0.120	0.10	No
Big Megamart	0.210	0.05	Yes	2.440	0.008	0.05	Yes
West Side	0.160	0.05	Yes	1.891	0.030	0.05	Yes
Max	0.095	0.10	Yes	1.607	0.055	0.10	Yes
Reliance Digital	0.135	0.05	Yes	1.952	0.026	0.05	Yes
NEXT	0.050	0.10	No	-1.212	0.113	0.10	No
Overall Industry	0.128	0.10	Yes	1.546	0.062	0.10	Yes

The calculated K-S 'D' values exceed the critical values (at an α of 5% or 10%) for *customer satisfaction with the interior atmospherics of the store* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well the overall industry except D[▲]Mart and NEXT, which establishes that there is a significant difference in the level of satisfaction of customers *with the interior atmospherics of the store* of all the organised retailers except D[▲]Mart and NEXT.

The computed 't' values also exceed the critical values (at an α of 5% or 10%) for *customer satisfaction with the interior atmospherics of the store* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry except D[▲]Mart and NEXT. Hence, the null hypothesis H_{02} is rejected in case of *customer satisfaction with the interior atmospherics of the store* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry except D[▲]Mart and NEXT and the alternate hypothesis H_{A2} is accepted. But, the null hypothesis H_{02} is accepted in the case of *the interior atmospherics of the store* of D[▲]Mart and NEXT. D[▲]Mart is a superstore based multi-item retailer and NEXT is a superstore based electronics-item retailer. As per their customers, *the interior atmospherics of the store* of these retailers are less than their expectations.

Retailers	Statistics of Kolmogorov-Smirnov one sample test			Statistics of one sample t-test			
	Calculated K-S 'D' Value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?	Calculated 't' value	p-value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?
HyperCITY	0.125	0.05	Yes	1.677	0.048	0.05	Yes
Star Bazaar	0.095	0.10	Yes	1.284	0.100	0.10	Yes
more.MEGASStore	0.075	0.10	No	1.015	0.156	0.10	No
Big Bazaar	0.125	0.05	Yes	1.715	0.044	0.05	Yes
D [▲] Mart	0.045	0.10	No	-1.329	0.093	0.10	No
Big Megamart	0.190	0.05	Yes	2.783	0.003	0.05	Yes
West Side	0.175	0.05	Yes	2.320	0.011	0.05	Yes
Max	0.120	0.05	Yes	1.735	0.042	0.05	Yes
Reliance Digital	0.095	0.10	Yes	1.321	0.094	0.10	Yes
NEXT	0.045	0.10	No	-1.190	0.118	0.10	No
Overall Industry	0.095	0.10	Yes	1.293	0.099	0.10	Yes

The computed K-S 'D' values exceed the critical values (at an α of 5% or 10%) for *customer satisfaction with the store layout* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well the overall industry except more.MEGASStore, D[▲]

Mart and NEXT, which ratifies that there is a significant difference in the level of satisfaction of customers *with the store layout* of all the organised retailers except more.MEGASStore, D[▲]Mart and NEXT.

The calculated ‘t’ values also exceed the critical values (at an α of 5% or 10%) for *customer satisfaction with the store layout* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry except more.MEGASStore, D[▲]Mart and NEXT. Hence, the null hypothesis H_{02} is rejected in case of *customer satisfaction with the store layout* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry except more.MEGASStore, D[▲]Mart and NEXT and the alternate hypothesis H_{A2} is accepted. But, the null hypothesis H_{02} is accepted in the case of *the store layout* of more.MEGASStore, D[▲]Mart and NEXT. more.MEGASStore is a hyper store-based retailer, D[▲]Mart is a superstore based multi-item retailer and NEXT is a superstore based electronics-item retailer. According to their customers, *the store layout* of these retailers is poorer than their expectations.

Retailers	Statistics of Kolmogorov-Smirnov one sample test			Statistics of one sample t-test			
	Calculated K-S ‘D’ Value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?	Calculated ‘t’ value	p-value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?
HyperCITY	0.135	0.05	Yes	1.890	0.026	0.05	Yes
Star Bazaar	0.090	0.10	Yes	1.575	0.044	0.10	Yes
more.MEGASStore	0.095	0.10	Yes	1.526	0.072	0.10	Yes
Big Bazaar	0.140	0.05	Yes	1.929	0.013	0.05	Yes
D [▲] Mart	0.045	0.10	No	-0.716	0.295	0.10	No
Big Megamart	0.190	0.05	Yes	2.601	0.016	0.05	Yes
West Side	0.165	0.05	Yes	2.438	0.020	0.05	Yes
Max	0.130	0.05	Yes	1.932	0.064	0.05	Yes
Reliance Digital	0.105	0.05	Yes	1.702	0.073	0.05	Yes
NEXT	0.055	0.10	No	-0.495	0.013	0.10	No
Overall Industry	0.109	0.05	Yes	1.639	0.034	0.10	Yes

The computed K-S ‘D’ values exceed the critical values (at an α of 5% or 10%) for *customer satisfaction with the visual merchandising* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well the overall industry except D[▲]Mart and

NEXT, which confirms that there is a significant difference in the level of satisfaction of customers *with the visual merchandising* of all the organised retailers except D[▲]Mart and NEXT.

The calculated 't' values also exceed the critical values (at an α of 5% or 10%) for *customer satisfaction with the visual merchandising* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry except D[▲]Mart and NEXT. Hence, the null hypothesis H_{02} is rejected in case of *customer satisfaction with the visual merchandising* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry except D[▲]Mart and NEXT and the alternate hypothesis H_{A2} is accepted. But, the null hypothesis H_{02} is accepted in the case of *the visual merchandising* of D[▲]Mart and NEXT. D[▲]Mart is a superstore based multi-item retailer and NEXT is a superstore based electronics-item retailer. According to their customers, *the visual merchandising* of these retailers is poorer than their expectations.

Retailers	Statistics of Kolmogorov-Smirnov one sample test			Statistics of one sample t-test			
	Calculated K-S 'D' Value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?	Calculated 't' value	p-value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?
HyperCITY	0.100	0.05	Yes	1.850	0.033	0.05	Yes
Star Bazaar	0.140	0.05	Yes	1.743	0.041	0.05	Yes
more.MEGAStore	0.120	0.05	Yes	1.773	0.039	0.05	Yes
Big Bazaar	0.200	0.05	Yes	2.321	0.011	0.05	Yes
D [▲] Mart	0.165	0.05	Yes	1.668	0.048	0.05	Yes
Big Megamart	0.130	0.05	Yes	1.820	0.035	0.05	Yes
West Side	0.105	0.05	Yes	1.772	0.039	0.05	Yes
Max	0.150	0.05	Yes	2.209	0.014	0.05	Yes
Reliance Digital	0.100	0.05	Yes	1.657	0.050	0.05	Yes
NEXT	0.130	0.05	Yes	1.980	0.025	0.05	Yes
Overall Industry	0.134	0.05	Yes	1.916	0.028	0.05	Yes

The calculated K-S 'D' values exceed the critical values (at the 5% level of significance) for *customer satisfaction with the methods of promotion and communication* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well the

overall industry, which establishes that there is a significant difference in the level of satisfaction of customers *with the methods of promotion and communication* of all the organised retailers.

The computed ‘t’ values also exceed the critical values (at the 5% level of significance) for *customer satisfaction with the methods of promotion and communication* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry. Hence, the null hypothesis H_{02} is rejected in case of *customer satisfaction with the methods of promotion and communication* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry and the alternate hypothesis H_{A2} is accepted.

Retailers	Statistics of Kolmogorov-Smirnov one sample test			Statistics of one sample t-test			
	Calculated K-S ‘D’ Value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?	Calculated ‘t’ value	p-value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?
HyperCITY	0.115	0.05	Yes	1.876	0.031	0.05	Yes
Star Bazaar	0.090	0.10	Yes	1.323	0.094	0.10	Yes
more.MEGASStore	0.105	0.05	Yes	1.650	0.050	0.05	Yes
Big Bazaar	0.200	0.05	Yes	2.275	0.012	0.05	Yes
D Δ Mart	0.060	0.10	No	0.183	0.427	0.10	No
Big Megamart	0.120	0.05	Yes	1.959	0.026	0.05	Yes
West Side	0.120	0.05	Yes	1.774	0.039	0.05	Yes
Max	0.105	0.05	Yes	1.694	0.046	0.05	Yes
Reliance Digital	0.145	0.05	Yes	1.686	0.047	0.05	Yes
NEXT	0.050	0.10	No	0.216	0.415	0.10	No
Overall Industry	0.108	0.05	Yes	1.623	0.053	0.10	Yes

The computed K-S ‘D’ values exceed the critical values (at an α of 5% or 10%) for *customer satisfaction with the advertising methods* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well the overall industry except D Δ Mart and NEXT, which confirms that there is a significant difference in the level of satisfaction of customers *with the advertising methods* of all the organised retailers except D Δ Mart and NEXT.

The calculated 't' values also exceed the critical values (at an α of 5% or 10%) for *customer satisfaction with the advertising methods* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry except D Δ Mart and NEXT. Hence, the null hypothesis H_{02} is rejected in case of *customer satisfaction with the advertising methods* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry except D Δ Mart and NEXT and the alternate hypothesis H_{A2} is accepted. But, the null hypothesis H_{02} is accepted in the case of *the advertising methods* of D Δ Mart and NEXT. D Δ Mart is a superstore based multi-item retailer and NEXT is a superstore based electronics-item retailer. According to their customers, *advertising methods* of these retailers are not as per the expectations of them.

Table 8.42: Statistics of Kolmogorov-Smirnov one-sample test and one sample t-test for customer satisfaction with the sales promotion methods							
Retailers	Statistics of Kolmogorov-Smirnov one sample test			Statistics of one sample t-test			
	Calculated K-S 'D' Value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?	Calculated 't' value	p-value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?
HyperCITY	0.135	0.05	Yes	1.894	0.030	0.05	Yes
Star Bazaar	0.140	0.05	Yes	1.721	0.043	0.05	Yes
more.MEGASStore	0.135	0.05	Yes	2.019	0.022	0.05	Yes
Big Bazaar	0.240	0.05	Yes	2.429	0.008	0.05	Yes
D Δ Mart	0.140	0.05	Yes	2.030	0.022	0.05	Yes
Big Megamart	0.105	0.05	Yes	1.847	0.033	0.05	Yes
West Side	0.130	0.05	Yes	1.928	0.028	0.05	Yes
Max	0.125	0.05	Yes	1.729	0.043	0.05	Yes
Reliance Digital	0.110	0.05	Yes	1.705	0.045	0.05	Yes
NEXT	0.145	0.05	Yes	2.117	0.018	0.05	Yes
Overall Industry	0.141	0.05	Yes	1.995	0.024	0.05	Yes

The calculated K-S 'D' values exceed the critical values (at $\alpha = 0.05$) for *customer satisfaction with the sales promotion methods* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well the overall industry, which homologates that there is a significant difference in the level of satisfaction of customers *with the sales promotion methods* of all the organised retailers.

The computed 't' values also exceed the critical values (at $\alpha = 0.05$) for *customer satisfaction with the sales promotion methods* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry. Hence, the null hypothesis H_{02} is rejected in case of *customer satisfaction with the sales promotion methods* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry and the alternate hypothesis H_{A2} is accepted.

Retailers	Statistics of Kolmogorov-Smirnov one sample test			Statistics of one sample t-test			
	Calculated K-S 'D' Value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?	Calculated 't' value	p-value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?
HyperCITY	0.100	0.05	Yes	1.663	0.049	0.05	Yes
Star Bazaar	0.000	0.10	No	-2.003	0.023	0.10	No
more.MEGASStore	0.000	0.10	No	-2.258	0.013	0.10	No
Big Bazaar	0.130	0.05	Yes	1.753	0.041	0.05	Yes
D-Mart	0.000	0.10	No	-2.439	0.008	0.10	No
Big Megamart	0.040	0.10	No	-0.554	0.290	0.10	No
West Side	0.110	0.05	Yes	1.687	0.047	0.05	Yes
Max	0.000	0.10	No	-2.663	0.004	0.10	No
Reliance Digital	0.110	0.05	Yes	1.674	0.048	0.05	Yes
NEXT	0.110	0.05	Yes	1.671	0.048	0.05	Yes
Overall Industry	0.040	0.10	No	-0.282	0.389	0.10	No

The calculated K-S 'D' values are less than the critical values (at $\alpha = 0.10$) for *customer satisfaction with the direct retailing methods* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well the overall industry except HyperCITY, Big Bazaar, D-Mart, West Side, Reliance Digital and NEXT, which establishes that there is no significant difference in the level of satisfaction of customers *with the direct retailing methods* of all the organised retailers except HyperCITY, Big Bazaar, D-Mart, West Side, Reliance Digital and NEXT.

The computed ‘t’ values are also less than the critical values (at $\alpha = 0.10$) for *customer satisfaction with the direct retailing methods* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry except HyperCITY, Big Bazaar, D⁺Mart, West Side, Reliance Digital and NEXT. Hence, the null hypothesis H_{02} is accepted in case of *customer satisfaction with the direct retailing methods* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry except HyperCITY, Big Bazaar, D⁺Mart, West Side, Reliance Digital and NEXT and the alternate hypothesis H_{A2} is rejected. But, the alternate hypothesis H_{A2} is accepted in the case of *the direct retailing methods* of HyperCITY, Big Bazaar, D⁺Mart, West Side, Reliance Digital and NEXT. HyperCITY and Big Bazaar are a hyper store-based multi-item retailers, D⁺Mart is a superstore based multi-item retailer, West Side is a superstore based fashion-item retailers and NEXT is a superstore based electronics-item retailer. According to their customers, *the direct retailing methods* adopted by these retailers are as per the expectations of them.

Retailers	Statistics of Kolmogorov-Smirnov one sample test			Statistics of one sample t-test			
	Calculated K-S ‘D’ Value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?	Calculated ‘t’ value	p-value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?
HyperCITY	0.120	0.05	Yes	1.925	0.028	0.05	Yes
Star Bazaar	0.130	0.05	Yes	1.705	0.045	0.05	Yes
more.MEGASStore	0.090	0.10	Yes	1.616	0.054	0.10	Yes
Big Bazaar	0.135	0.05	Yes	2.160	0.016	0.05	Yes
D ⁺ Mart	0.050	0.10	No	-0.514	0.304	0.10	No
Big Megamart	0.100	0.05	Yes	2.014	0.023	0.05	Yes
West Side	0.130	0.05	Yes	2.217	0.014	0.05	Yes
Max	0.035	0.10	No	-0.936	0.175	0.10	No
Reliance Digital	0.125	0.05	Yes	1.766	0.039	0.05	Yes
NEXT	0.050	0.10	No	-0.247	0.403	0.10	No
Overall Industry	0.088	0.10	Yes	1.360	0.088	0.10	Yes

The computed K-S ‘D’ values exceed the critical values (at an α of 5% or 10%) for *customer satisfaction with the personal retailing methods* of all the

organised retailers (included in this study) as well the overall industry except D[▲]Mart, Max and NEXT, which indicates that there is a significant difference in the level of satisfaction of customers *with the personal retailing methods* of all the organised retailers except D[▲]Mart, Max and NEXT.

The calculated ‘t’ values also exceed the critical values (at an α of 5% or 10%) for *customer satisfaction with the personal retailing methods* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry except D[▲]Mart, Max and NEXT. Hence, the null hypothesis H_{02} is rejected in case of *customer satisfaction with personal retailing methods* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry except D[▲]Mart, Max and NEXT and the alternate hypothesis H_{A2} is accepted. But, the null hypothesis H_{02} is accepted in the case of *the personal retailing methods* of D[▲]Mart, Max and NEXT. D[▲]Mart is a superstore based multi-item retailer, Max is a superstore based fashion-item retailer and NEXT is a superstore based electronics-item retailer. According to their customers, *the personal retailing methods* adopted by these retailers are not as per the expectations of them.

Retailers	Statistics of Kolmogorov-Smirnov one sample test			Statistics of one sample t-test			
	Calculated K-S ‘D’ Value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?	Calculated ‘t’ value	p-value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?
HyperCITY	0.115	0.05	Yes	1.694	0.046	0.05	Yes
Star Bazaar	0.005	0.10	No	-1.714	0.044	0.10	No
more.MEGASStore	0.120	0.05	Yes	1.789	0.038	0.05	Yes
Big Bazaar	0.150	0.05	Yes	1.952	0.026	0.05	Yes
D [▲] Mart	0.000	0.10	No	-2.941	0.002	0.10	No
Big Megamart	0.100	0.05	Yes	1.801	0.037	0.05	Yes
West Side	0.105	0.05	Yes	1.681	0.047	0.05	Yes
Max	0.120	0.05	Yes	1.671	0.048	0.05	Yes
Reliance Digital	0.115	0.05	Yes	1.647	0.050	0.05	Yes
NEXT	0.000	0.10	No	-2.946	0.002	0.10	No
Overall Industry	0.040	0.10	No	-0.012	0.495	0.10	No

The computed K-S ‘D’ values exceed the critical values (at an α of 5%) for *customer satisfaction with the public relation/publicity methods* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) except Star Bazaar, D Δ Mart, NEXT and the overall industry, which evinces that there is a significant difference in the level of satisfaction of customers *with the public relation/publicity methods* of all the organised retailers except Star Bazaar, D Δ Mart, NEXT.

The calculated ‘t’ values also exceed the critical values (at an α of 5%) for *customer satisfaction with the public relation/publicity methods* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) except Star Bazaar, D Δ Mart, NEXT and the overall industry. Hence, the null hypothesis H_{02} is rejected in case of *customer satisfaction with the public relation/publicity methods* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) except Star Bazaar, D Δ Mart, NEXT and the overall industry and the alternate hypothesis H_{A2} is accepted. But, the null hypothesis H_{02} is accepted in the case of *the public relation/publicity methods* of Star Bazaar, D Δ Mart, NEXT and the overall industry. Star Bazaar is a hyper store based multi-item retailer, D Δ Mart is a superstore based multi-item retailer and NEXT is a superstore based electronics-item retailer. According to their customers, *the public relation/publicity methods* adopted by these retailers are not as per the expectations of them.

Retailers	Statistics of Kolmogorov-Smirnov one sample test			Statistics of one sample t-test			
	Calculated K-S ‘D’ Value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?	Calculated ‘t’ value	p-value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?
HyperCITY	0.120	0.05	Yes	2.314	0.011	0.05	Yes
Star Bazaar	0.120	0.05	Yes	1.900	0.029	0.05	Yes
more.MEGASStore	0.130	0.05	Yes	1.771	0.039	0.05	Yes
Big Bazaar	0.180	0.05	Yes	2.215	0.014	0.05	Yes
D Δ Mart	0.000	0.10	No	-2.834	0.003	0.10	No
Big Megamart	0.110	0.05	Yes	2.272	0.012	0.05	Yes
West Side	0.100	0.05	Yes	1.943	0.027	0.05	Yes

Max	0.165	0.05	Yes	2.077	0.020	0.05	Yes
Reliance Digital	0.170	0.05	Yes	2.090	0.019	0.05	Yes
NEXT	0.100	0.05	Yes	1.661	0.049	0.05	Yes
Overall Industry	0.106	0.05	Yes	1.788	0.038	0.05	Yes

The calculated K-S ‘D’ values exceed the critical values (at $\alpha = 0.05$) for *customer satisfaction with the internet/interactive retailing methods* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well the overall industry except D Δ Mart, which evinces that there is a significant difference in the level of satisfaction of customers *with the internet/interactive retailing methods* of all the organised retailers except D Δ Mart.

The computed ‘t’ values also exceed the critical values (at an α of 5%) for *customer satisfaction with the internet/interactive retailing methods* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry except D Δ Mart. Hence, the null hypothesis H_{02} is rejected in case of *customer satisfaction with the internet/interactive retailing methods* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry except D Δ Mart and the alternate hypothesis H_{A2} is accepted. But, the null hypothesis H_{02} is accepted in the case of *the internet/interactive retailing methods* of D Δ Mart. D Δ Mart is a superstore based multi-item retailer and not good at meeting the expectations of today's generation, as poor at *the internet/interactive retailing*.

Retailers	Statistics of Kolmogorov-Smirnov one sample test			Statistics of one sample t-test			
	Calculated K-S ‘D’ Value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?	Calculated ‘t’ value	p-value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?
HyperCITY	0.150	0.05	Yes	2.354	0.010	0.05	Yes
Star Bazaar	0.125	0.05	Yes	2.131	0.017	0.05	Yes
more.MEGASStore	0.110	0.05	Yes	1.760	0.040	0.05	Yes
Big Bazaar	0.205	0.05	Yes	2.420	0.008	0.05	Yes
D Δ Mart	0.005	0.10	No	-2.102	0.018	0.10	No
Big Megamart	0.160	0.05	Yes	2.232	0.013	0.05	Yes

West Side	0.170	0.05	Yes	2.109	0.018	0.05	Yes
Max	0.045	0.10	No	-0.185	0.427	0.10	No
Reliance Digital	0.145	0.05	Yes	2.126	0.017	0.05	Yes
NEXT	0.100	0.05	Yes	1.871	0.031	0.05	Yes
Overall Industry	0.113	0.05	Yes	1.776	0.039	0.05	Yes

The calculated K-S ‘D’ values exceed the critical values (at $\alpha = 0.05$) for *customer satisfaction with the sales personnel* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well the overall industry except D⁺Mart and Max, which reasserts that there is a significant difference in the level of satisfaction of customers *with the sales personnel* of all the organised retailers except D⁺Mart and Max.

The computed ‘t’ values also exceed the critical values (at an α of 5%) for *customer satisfaction with the sales personnel* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry except D⁺Mart and Max. Hence, the null hypothesis H_{02} is rejected in case of *customer satisfaction with the sales personnel* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry except D⁺Mart and Max and the alternate hypothesis H_{A2} is accepted. But, the null hypothesis H_{02} is accepted in the case of *the sales personnel* of D⁺Mart and Max. D⁺Mart is a superstore based multi-item retailer and Max is a superstore based fashion-item retailer. According to their customers, *the sales personnel* of these retailers perform below the expectations of them.

Retailers	Statistics of Kolmogorov-Smirnov one sample test			Statistics of one sample t-test			
	Calculated K-S ‘D’ Value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?	Calculated ‘t’ value	p-value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?
HyperCITY	0.110	0.05	Yes	2.144	0.017	0.05	Yes
Star Bazaar	0.115	0.05	Yes	1.810	0.036	0.05	Yes
more.MEGASStore	0.090	0.10	Yes	1.324	0.094	0.10	Yes
Big Bazaar	0.195	0.05	Yes	2.364	0.010	0.05	Yes
D ⁺ Mart	0.035	0.10	No	-0.110	0.456	0.10	No
Big Megamart	0.185	0.05	Yes	2.385	0.009	0.05	Yes

West Side	0.180	0.05	Yes	2.440	0.008	0.05	Yes
Max	0.120	0.05	Yes	1.779	0.038	0.05	Yes
Reliance Digital	0.140	0.10	Yes	2.089	0.019	0.10	Yes
NEXT	0.045	0.10	No	-0.110	0.456	0.10	No
Overall Industry	0.120	0.05	Yes	1.895	0.030	0.05	Yes

The calculated K-S ‘D’ values exceed the critical values (at an α of 5% or 10%) for *customer satisfaction with the contact personnel* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well the overall industry except D Δ Mart and NEXT, which reasserts that there is a significant difference in the level of satisfaction of customers *with the contact personnel* of all the organised retailers except D Δ Mart and NEXT.

The computed ‘t’ values also exceed the critical values (at an α of 5% or 10%) for *customer satisfaction with the contact personnel* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry except D Δ Mart and NEXT. Hence, the null hypothesis H_{02} is rejected in case of *customer satisfaction with the contact personnel* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry except D Δ Mart and NEXT and the alternate hypothesis H_{A2} is accepted. But, the null hypothesis H_{02} is accepted in the case of *the contact personnel* of D Δ Mart and NEXT. D Δ Mart is a superstore based multi-item retailer and NEXT is a superstore based electronics-item retailer. According to their customers, *the contact personnel* of these retailers perform below the expectations of them.

Table 8.49: Statistics of Kolmogorov-Smirnov one-sample test and one sample t-test for customer satisfaction with the factors pertained to personnel							
Retailers	Statistics of Kolmogorov-Smirnov one sample test			Statistics of one sample t-test			
	Calculated K-S ‘D’ Value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?	Calculated ‘t’ value	p-value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?
HyperCITY	0.195	0.05	Yes	2.364	0.010	0.05	Yes
Star Bazaar	0.095	0.10	Yes	1.570	0.059	0.10	Yes
more.MEGASStore	0.090	0.10	Yes	1.521	0.065	0.10	Yes
Big Bazaar	0.220	0.05	Yes	2.454	0.007	0.05	Yes
D Δ Mart	0.045	0.10	No	-0.185	0.427	0.10	No
Big Megamart	0.210	0.05	Yes	2.456	0.007	0.05	Yes

West Side	0.175	0.05	Yes	2.257	0.013	0.05	Yes
Max	0.040	0.10	No	-0.351	0.363	0.10	No
Reliance Digital	0.140	0.05	Yes	1.769	0.039	0.05	Yes
NEXT	0.035	0.10	No	-0.267	0.395	0.10	No
Overall Industry	0.121	0.05	Yes	1.798	0.037	0.05	Yes

The computed K-S ‘D’ values exceed the critical values (at an α of 5% or 10%) for *customer satisfaction with the factors pertained to personnel* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well the overall industry except D \blacktriangle Mart, Max and NEXT, which proves that there is a significant difference in the level of satisfaction of customers *with the factors pertained to personnel* of all the organised retailers except D \blacktriangle Mart, Max and NEXT.

The calculated ‘t’ values also exceed the critical values (at an α of 5% or 10%) for *customer satisfaction with the factors pertained to personnel* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry except D \blacktriangle Mart, Max and NEXT. Hence, the null hypothesis H_{02} is rejected in case of *customer satisfaction with the factors pertained to personnel* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry except D \blacktriangle Mart, Max and NEXT and the alternate hypothesis H_{A2} is accepted. But, the null hypothesis H_{02} is accepted in the case of *the factors pertained to personnel* of D \blacktriangle Mart, Max and NEXT. D \blacktriangle Mart is a superstore based multi-item retailer, Max is a superstore based fashion-item retailer and NEXT is a superstore based electronics-item retailer. According to their customers, *personnel* of these retailers perform below the expectations of them pertained to mood, efforts, commitment, attitude, knowledge, skills, behaviour, approach to delivering the service, competence, courtesy, credibility, reliability, responsiveness, communication style, friendliness, helpfulness, discipline & punctuality, customer counselling ability of personnel.

Table 8.50: Statistics of Kolmogorov-Smirnov one-sample test and one sample t-test for customer satisfaction with the other tangible evidence							
Retailers	Statistics of Kolmogorov-Smirnov one sample test			Statistics of one sample t-test			
	Calculated K-S ‘D’ Value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?	Calculated ‘t’ value	p-value	α	Calculated value exceeds critical value?

HyperCITY	0.150	0.05	Yes	2.094	0.019	0.05	Yes
Star Bazaar	0.150	0.05	Yes	2.242	0.013	0.05	Yes
more.MEGASStore	0.090	0.10	Yes	1.398	0.082	0.10	Yes
Big Bazaar	0.180	0.05	Yes	2.057	0.020	0.05	Yes
DMart	0.050	0.05	No	-0.442	0.329	0.05	No
Big Megamart	0.195	0.05	Yes	2.352	0.010	0.05	Yes
West Side	0.175	0.05	Yes	1.961	0.026	0.05	Yes
Max	0.095	0.10	Yes	1.558	0.060	0.10	Yes
Reliance Digital	0.135	0.05	Yes	1.996	0.024	0.05	Yes
NEXT	0.035	0.05	No	-0.363	0.358	0.05	No
Overall Industry	0.123	0.05	Yes	1.726	0.043	0.05	Yes

The computed K-S ‘D’ values exceed the critical values (at an α of 5% or 10%) for *customer satisfaction with the other tangible evidences* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well the overall industry except DMart and NEXT, which confirms that there is a significant difference in the level of satisfaction of customers *with the other tangible evidence* of all the organised retailers except DMart and NEXT.

The calculated ‘t’ values also exceed the critical values (at an α of 5% or 10%) for *customer satisfaction with the other tangible evidence* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry except DMart and NEXT. Hence, the null hypothesis H_{02} is rejected in case of *customer satisfaction with the other tangible evidence* of all the organised retailers (included in this study) as well as the overall industry except DMart and NEXT and the alternate hypothesis H_{A2} is accepted. But, the null hypothesis H_{02} is accepted in the case of *the other tangible evidence* of DMart and NEXT. DMart is a superstore based multi-item retailer and NEXT is a superstore based electronics-item retailer. According to their customers, these retailers do not match the expectations of them pertained to *the other tangible evidence*.

Chapter 9

Conclusion and recommendations

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- Introduction
 - Conclusions
 - Recommendations
 - Areas for further research

CHAPTER 9

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Introduction

The retail industry of India is one among the most contributing sectors to the GDP and employment in the country, considered as a vibrant industry and a pillar of the Indian economy. The growth estimations of the industry are quite lucrative and estimated that the Indian retail market will be one of the top five markets (in terms of economic value) in the world. The business in the retail sector is divided between the organised and unorganised retailers. The major share in the retailing business is with unorganised retailers. However, the organised retail business is growing considerably and estimated to grow with much faster rate in the future. The organised retail sector is passing through the transformation from the last one decade due to the entry of corporate groups like Tata Group, Reliance Group, Bharti Enterprises, Aditya Birla Group, Future Group, RPG Enterprises, Piramal Group, Vishal Group, K Raheja Group, Vivek Group, etc. The organised retail sector is shifting towards the adoption of modern retailing concepts due to these new entrants, who are keen to revolutionise the industry. The retailing sector is witnessing the drastic changes in the introduction of the different formats of retailing e.g. shopping malls, supermarkets, hypermarkets, department stores, convenience store, etc. The organised retailers are not only revolutionising the sector in the urban areas but also moving towards smaller cities and even rural areas of the country. The organised retailers offer the world-class assortment of merchandise and services, affordable pricing and an appealing shopping environment to meet the expectations of customers.

It is a known fact that the customer is the king. Mahatma Gandhi also told the importance of the customer to a business and said that the customer is the most important visitor in the business premises. The customer is not dependent on your business. The business is dependent on him. The customer is not an interruption in the business. The customer is the purpose of the business. The customer is not an outsider in the business. The customer is part of the business. Businesses are not doing a favour by serving the customer. The customer is doing a favour by giving an opportunity to do

so. By taking the inspiration from this great thought, this current study has been pursued to analyse the products (merchandise) & services and retailing strategies by considering the point of views of both the organised retailers as well as customers. This chapter comprises the conclusions driven from the analyses of the data collected (which have been presented in chapter 5, 6, 7 and 8) from the organised retailers and customers of them. This chapter also comprises the recommendations based on the analyses of the data collected from the organised retailers and customers of them and areas of future research. This chapter has been segregated into the sections as follows:

9.1 Conclusions

- Conclusions drawn from the analysis of merchandise (products) & customer services in the organised retail industry
- Conclusions drawn from the analysis of retailing strategies introduced by organised retail industry
- Conclusions drawn from the analysis of profile of customers in the organised retail industry
- Conclusions drawn from the analysis of buying behaviour of customers in the organised retail industry
- Conclusions drawn from the analysis factors influencing buying behaviour of customers in the organised retail industry
- Conclusions drawn from the analysis of customer satisfaction with the merchandise (products) and services offered by organised retail industry
- Conclusions drawn from testing of hypotheses

9.2 Recommendations

9.3 Areas for further research

9.1 CONCLUSIONS

9.1.1 Conclusions drawn from the analysis of merchandise (products) & customer services in the organised retail industry

The merchandise lines of the organised retailers were considered in the analysis of merchandise in the organised retail industry, as it was not possible to include all the merchandise offered by some multi-format retailers, offering more than 30000 merchandise to their customers. The players in the organised retail industry offer very much similar merchandise lines to their customers. However, the variety of merchandise under different merchandise lines slightly differs with each other.

The multi-format (item) organised retailers (e.g. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar and D⁺Mart) offer very much similar merchandise lines to each other and the most common merchandise lines are food & grocery, health, beauty / personal care, home care, furniture, fashion, electronics, toys, sports, accessories, private / store levels. However, D⁺Mart does not offer the private / store levels to its customers. Some multi-item organised retailers (e.g. Star Bazaar and Big Bazaar) offer more merchandise lines as compared to their competitors. Star Bazaar offers some international brand under the special merchandise line International zone and Big Bazaar offers some gift items (e.g. cakes & chocolates, gift vouchers, gift sets, valentine's day, Diwali, charity, flowers, greeting cards, seasonal gifts, sweets & dry fruits) for special occasions under the gift merchandise line.

The multi-format (item) organised retailers offer a wide variety of merchandise in each category as per different sizes, colours, designs, price, quality, quantity and brands, which differs slightly as compared to each other. However, the hyper-store based organised retailers (e.g. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more. MEGASStore and Big Bazaar) offer more variety of merchandise as compared to the super - store based organised retailers (e.g. D⁺Mart).

The fashion item organised retailers offer a very much similar merchandise line with each other and the most common merchandise line are women's wear, men's wear, youth wear, kid's wear, footwear and fashion accessories. However, few (e.g. Big Magamart and West Side) offers more merchandise line, i.e. home items and travel

items. Moreover, Big Magamart also offers toys to its customers as compared to its other for differentiating itself.

The hyper store based fashion-item organised retailers (e.g. Big Megamart) offer a wide variety of merchandise in each category as per different sizes, colours, designs, price, quality, quantity and brands while superstore based fashion-item organised retailers (e.g. West Side and Max) offer a narrow variety of merchandise in each category.

The electronics-item organised retailers (e.g. Reliance Digital and NEXT) also offer a very much similar merchandise lines to each other and the most common merchandise lines are phones, computers, TVs & audio, cameras, home appliances, kitchen appliances, gaming and accessories. However, some retailers (e.g. NEXT) offers few more merchandise lines (e.g. writing instruments and fragrances) to its customers. The electronics-item organised retailers also offer a narrow variety of merchandise as per different sizes, colours, designs, price, quality, quantity and brands.

In conclusion, food & grocery, beauty / personal care, home care and fashion are the most contributing merchandise lines in the growth of the multi-format (item) organised retailers, while women's wear, men's wear and kid's wear are the most contributing merchandise lines in the growth of the fashion item organised retailers and kitchen appliances and home appliances are the most contributing merchandise lines in the growth of the electronics item organised retailers

The players in the organised retail industry also offer a very much similar services to their customers and the most common services are home delivery, alteration facilities (in case of apparel), packaging / gift wrapping, installations in case of electronics item, complaints & exchange handling, personal shoppers, parking, fitting / trial rooms, information, safety of personal things, lift / escalator & staircase facility, after sale service for electronics and durables, demonstrations of merchandise, entertainment facilities, acceptance of all international credit & debit cards, shopping carts, warranties on merchandise, washrooms & drinking water facilities, air-condition environment, music, enough billing-counters, CCTV for security, fire safety arrangement, back office for support, customers care service, repairing services in case

of durable, gift certificates, special sales for regular customers, restaurants, shopping bags, refreshment facilities etc. However, the hyper store based organised retailers (e.g. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar and Big Megamart) provide more services to their customers as compared to superstore based organised retailers (e.g. D▲Mart, West Side, Max, Reliance Digital and NEXT).

9.1.2 Conclusions drawn from the analysis of retailing strategies introduced by organised retail industry

The organised retailers use similar retailing strategies with little difference in the execution. However, organised retailers employ different retailing strategies in a different retailing format, e.g. retailing strategies of hyper store retailers differ from superstore retailers. Nevertheless, it does not mean that hyper store or superstore retailers are not adopting the successful strategies of each other.

Moreover, organised retailers also employ different retailing strategies in the different areas of operations, e.g. retailing strategies of multi-item organised retailers differ from the fashion item organised retailers and electronics item organised retailers. Despite, there is also similarity among the strategies of multi-item organised retailers, fashion-item organised retailers and electronics-item organised retailers.

The organised retailers use demographic, psychographic and behavioural variables for segmenting the retail market. Age, family life cycle, gender, income, occupation and education are most the common variables for demographic segmentation while lifestyle and personality are most common variables for psychographic segmentation and usage rate, loyalty status, occasions, benefits and innovativeness are the most common variables for behavioural segmentation of the retail market. The multi-format organised retailers (e.g. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar and D▲Mart) adopt full market coverage segmentation strategy while the fashion item organised retailers (e.g. Big Megamart, West Side and Max) prefer selective specialisation segmentation strategy and the electronics item organised retailers (e.g. Reliance Digital and NEXT) adopt market specialisation segmentation strategy for segmenting the retail market.

The multi-format organised retailers (e.g. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar and D▲Mart) adopt an undifferentiating targeting

strategy or mass retailing to target the retail market. The concentrated targeting strategy is mostly adopted strategy among superstore organised retailers (e.g. West Side, Max and NEXT) while other organised retailers (e.g. Big Megamart and Reliance Digital) prefers differentiating targeting strategy or selective retailing.

More for less is most popular positioning strategy among both hyper & superstore based organised retailers (e.g. HyperCITY, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar, D▲Mart, Max and Reliance Digital) for positioning their offerings among the targeted customers. However, some organised retailers (e.g. Star Bazaar and NEXT) adopt same for less positioning strategy while others (Big Megamart and West Side) more for same positioning strategy.

Both hyper & superstores / multi-format & specialised organised retailers (e.g. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, Big Bazaar, Max, Reliance Digital and NEXT) adopt a retail market penetration strategy in order to grab the growth opportunities, while some other organised retailers (e.g. more.MEGASStore, D▲Mart and West Side) adopt a retail market expansion strategy and others (e.g. Big Megamart) adopt a retail format development strategy by offering merchandise & services with the new retail format.

The most favourable defensive choice is a preemptive defence strategy among both hyper and superstore organised retailers (e.g. Big Megamart, HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, Big Bazaar, Max and Reliance Digital). All these retailers attack competitors more aggressively by launching a wide range of merchandise and brands in different categories.

The mobile defence strategy is second most favourable defensive choice among superstores organised retailers (e.g. D▲Mart, West Side and NEXT) and they hope to expand rapidly by stretching its domain to new territories with the similar format store. However, some (e.g. more.MEGASStore – a multi-format hyper store organised retailer) uses contraction defence strategy by giving up from the weaker territories from where the company is not getting sufficient ROI.

Cost leadership strategy is a common choice as a business level strategy at store-level among the multi-format organised retailers (e.g. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar,

more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar and D▲Mart). However, hyper store based fashion-item organised retailers (e.g. Big Megamart) follow differentiation strategy at store-level while some super store fashion-item organised retailers (e.g. West Side) follow differentiation focus strategy at store-level and other specialised superstore organised retailers (e.g. Max, Reliance Digital and NEXT) prefer cost focus strategy at store-level.

The organised retailers face some common problems in framing overall retailing strategies are the high price of real estate, lack of preferred locations and retail space, high cost of space and location, trained workforce, multiple & a complex taxation system of India, many entrants as online retailers, high demand for service standards as consumerism is shifting in India.

The organised retailers consider the product (merchandise) as an extremely important element of their retail marketing mix. Price is also an extremely important element of RMM for the organised retailers except few (e.g. Big Megamart and West Side). However, these organised retailers consider it as an important element of RMM. The organised retailers also consider promotion as an extremely important element of RMM except few (e.g. Big Megamart); however, it is important for Big Megamart.

The premises / place is an extremely important element of RMM for the organised retailers except few (e.g. D▲Mart, Max and NEXT), however, it is an important element for D▲Mart and Max, while partially important for NEXT. Personnel / people are considered as an extremely important element of RMM by the organised retailers, except few (e.g. D▲Mart and Max). For them, it is an important element. The presentation is an extremely important element of RMM for all the organised retailers, except few (e.g. more.MEGASStore, D▲Mart and NEXT) as it is important for more.MEGASStore and partially important for D▲Mart and NEXT. Physical evidence is an important element of RMM for the organised retailers except few (e.g. NEXT), as it is partially important.

A heterogeneous mix of brands is the first choice among the multi-format organised retailers (e.g. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar and D▲Mart), however, a hyper store based fashion store organised retailers (e.g. Big

Megamart) also offer a heterogeneous mix of brands to targeted customers. The offering basket of all these retailers contains generic, local, regional, national, copycat, international and private/store brands, while fashion-item superstores (e.g. West Side and Max) choose a blend of private label & other brands to offer and their offering basket contains private (store level) in all categories offered, exclusive, national (manufacturers) and international brands. Moreover, electronics item superstores (e.g. Reliance Digital and NEXT) offer multi-brands in different categories of the merchandise and their offering basket contains all the leading (world's most popular brands) national and international brands.

The target market, goods & service growth potential, trends (fashion), image of retailer, customer segments and responsiveness to customers are some important factors for organised retailers, while planning merchandise and target market, retailer's image, manufactures Vs private brands, the customer service offered and perceived goods/service benefits are some important factors for organised retailers while planning merchandise quality.

The hyper store organised retailers (e.g. Big Megamart, HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and Big Bazaar) adopt wide variety & a deep assortment strategy as a retail assortment strategy, which is characterised by many goods/service categories & a large assortment in each category, while, some super store organised retailers (e.g. D-Mart and NEXT) opt narrow variety & a shallow assortment strategy characterised by few goods/service categories & a limited assortment in each category and a few others (e.g. West Side, Max and Reliance Digital) adopt narrow variety & a deep assortment strategy characterised by few goods/service categories & a large assortment in each category.

Multi-format organised retailers (e.g. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar and D-Mart) offer staples (basic), fashion, consumer durable and seasonal merchandise category to their customers. Size, price, quality, brand, customer segments, discounts and schemes are the most common base to categorise the merchandise while displaying in the store. Fashion-item organised retailers (e.g. Big Megamart, West Side and Max) offer fashion merchandise category

to their customers and use size, colour, design, price, quality, brand, customer needs, discounts and schemes as a base to categorise the merchandise while displaying in the store. And electronics-item superstores (e.g. Reliance Digital and NEXT) offer consumer durables merchandise category and categorise the merchandise based on size, design, price, quality, brand, customer segments, customer needs, discounts and schemes to display in the store.

The organised retailers make sure the availability of newly launched merchandise/brands as soon as possible if falls in the category of the merchandise they offer. Moreover, the retailers (e.g. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more. MEGASStore, Big Bazaar, Big Megamart, West Side, Max and Reliance Digital) also offer customised, unique and complementary merchandise in a few categories.

As a management of unprofitable merchandise, some organised retailers (e.g. Big Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, West Side, Max and Reliance Digital) try to find the way to convert unprofitable merchandise into profitable merchandise and then determine that whether unprofitable merchandise relates to profitable business relationships or not; if not then they drop them from the assortment. While, other organised retailers (e.g. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, D▲Mart and NEXT) do not try to find the way to make them profitable, but directly determine that whether unprofitable merchandise relates to profitable business relationships or not; if not then they drop them from the assortment. However, some other (e.g. Big Megamart) usually drops unprofitable merchandise from the assortment.

Manufacturers are first major suppliers of all the organised retailers while wholesalers are second major suppliers of all the organised retailers except few (e.g. West Side, Max and Reliance Digital) and merchandise brokers are third major suppliers of the organised retailers except few (e.g. Big Megamart, Star Bazaar and D▲Mart). However, most of the organised retailers also rely on commission agents to supply international brands except few (e.g. Star Bazaar, Big Bazaar and D▲Mart). Moreover, few other (e.g. Star Bazaar) also gets supplies for some cooperatively & individually owned offices. All the organised retailers get a trade, quantity and seasonal discounts from their suppliers. Moreover, most of the organised retailers also get

promotional discounts except few (e.g. HyperCITY, Big Megamart and D▲Mart). The organised retailers consider reliability, price-quality, order-processing time, guarantee, long-term relationship, reorders and innovativeness as the most important characteristics for selecting a vendor for the supply of the items of their assortment. Both hyper and superstore organised retailers show a keen interest in the partner relationship management. They maintain the long-lasting relationship with all their partners, especially suppliers / vendors. The organised retailers prefer weekly and monthly stock planning of merchandise. However, multi-format organised retailers (e.g. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar and D▲Mart) also do the daily planning in case of perishable merchandise, frozen, vegetables, fruits, other farm merchandise, non-vegetables, etc.

Most of the organised retailers (e.g. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, D▲Mart, Max, Reliance Digital and NEXT) adopt maximising market share as pricing objective, while, other organised retailers (e.g. more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar, Big Megamart and West Side) adopt merchandise quality leadership as a pricing objective. Most of the organised retailers (HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar, Max, and Reliance Digital) adopt leadership-oriented pricing approach and others (e.g. Big Megamart, D▲Mart, West Side and NEXT) adopt cost-oriented pricing approach in order to price the merchandise.

High-low pricing strategy (a form of value pricing strategy) is the most popular pricing strategy among organised retailers (e.g. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, D▲Mart, Big Megamart and NEXT) while other retailers (e.g. more.MEGASStore and Big Bazaar) adopt another form of value pricing strategy, i.e. everyday low pricing strategy. However, perceived value-pricing strategy is also popular among superstore organised retailers (e.g. West Side, Max and Reliance Digital) in order to keep a promise to provide customers well-difference value & experience in their stores. Discount & allowance pricing (i.e. reducing the prices to reward customer responses), psychological pricing (i.e. adjusting prices for psychological effects) and promotional pricing (i.e. temporarily reducing the prices) are most common price-adjustment strategies among both hyper and superstore organised retailers to adjust or reduce the price of the merchandise and services. Value added retailing is most preferred tactics by

all the organised retailers except few (e.g. D▲Mart and NEXT) as they follow to maintain and grow tactics to fight a price war. No organised retailers take concern of customer before changing the price of merchandise & services, but all these retailers take the response of customers through feedback and consider for the future course of action except few (e.g. D▲Mart and NEXT). The organised retailers (e.g. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar, Max and Reliance Digital) always charge less than the MRP of most of the merchandise due to leadership-oriented approach, however, some merchandise is still sold at MRP. While some other organised retailers (e.g. Big Megamart, D▲Mart, West Side and NEXT) charge less than the MRP on most of the merchandise, but due to cost-oriented approach, they charge equal to MRP to recover the margin on the merchandise.

The organised retailers (e.g. HyperCITY, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar and Reliance Digital) appeal to reason; some others (e.g. Star Bazaar, D▲Mart, Max and NEXT) appeal to emotion while others (e.g. Big Megamart and West Side) appeal to sense in order to create a brand image among targeted customers. All the organised retailers use advertising, sales promotion, direct retailing, personal retailing, public relation / publicity and internet / interactive retailing methods for developing brand image and customer loyalty among existing and potential customers.

The organised retailers do both indoor (in-store) as well as outdoors (out-store) advertising to communicate and promote their offerings and include visual display, signage, the point of purchase material, secondary packaging and cross promotion methods of in-store advertising. However, some retailers (e.g. Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar and Reliance Digital) also use pamphlets, while some others (e.g. Big Megamart, HyperCITY, Big Bazaar and Max) do loud speaker announcement about various discounts & schemes for the day in order to advertise. Moreover, others (e.g. Big Megamart, Big Bazaar and Reliance Digital) also use electronic signage to advertise within the store. Yellow page advertising, the newspaper and hoardings advertising are most preferred modes of outdoor advertising among the organised retailers. Moreover, online advertising is also a common method adopted by organised retailers except a few. However, some retailers (e.g. Big Megamart, Big Bazaar, D▲Mart, West Side, Max and Reliance Digital) also advertise in magazines &

journals. Some other methods of outdoor advertising are also used by organised retailers i.e. television ads by few (e.g. Big Bazaar, West Side, Max and Reliance Digital); radio ads by few (e.g. Big Bazaar, D-Mart and Reliance Digital). The organised retailers spend less on advertising in comparison to any other industry especially outdoor advertising.

Schemes, gifts, rebates, discounts, loyalty programmes, premiums, prizes, rewards and contests are some popular tools opted by the organised retailers for sales promotion. However, some organised retailers (e.g. Big Megamart, HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and Big Bazaar) also provide a free sample as an integral part of the sales promotion. Buy & get free, bulk purchase discount, value / combo pack (offer) discount / deal, percentage off (discount) on MRP, up to percentage price off, flat percentage off / discount, price (₹) off / discounts, buy more and pay less (get more), flat price, starting at ₹, only / just for ₹, save ₹, ₹ onward / approx, fixed price scheme, ₹ to ₹, limited offer, offer / deal of the day or today's offer, store (our) price and special offer schemes are some common sales promotion schemes introduced by the organised retailers. Moreover, organised retailers also introduced a membership scheme and exclusive schemes for customers who wish to enrol for membership except few (e.g. D-Mart) in order to create some loyal customer base. The organised retailers give free gifts on the purchase of specific items, assured gifts and premiums to their customers while promotion. Moreover, some organised retailers (e.g. Big Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, Reliance Digital and NEXT) also offer the EMI facility to their customers in order to promote sales. The organised retailers think that the sales promotion influence customer purchase intention, therefore they do adequate sales promotional activities in the store to influence the customer purchase intention.

Direct emails and mail order catalogues and SMS retailing are most common direct retailing techniques adopted by the organised retailers except a few. However, some organised retailers (e.g. HyperCITY, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar, Reliance Digital and NEXT) are also involved in tele-retailing / mobile retailing form of direct retailing. The organised retailers adopt the face-to-face retailing technique of personal retailing within the store. Corporate brochures, annual reports, press release, press conferences, video press conferences are some most common medium to maintain relationships with the public. However, some organised retailers (e.g. HyperCITY,

more.MEGAStore, Big Bazaar, West Side, Max and Reliance Digital) organise and sponsor special events. Moreover, some multi-format organised retailers (e.g. HyperCITY, Big Bazaar, more.MEGAStore) and fashion item organised retailers (e.g. Big Megamart, West Side, Max) conduct social events & social development programmes for publicity.

The organised retailers use e-mails and websites as interactive retailing tools in order to create a brand image among the internet users. The organised retailers also utilise the social media platforms to interact with their techno savvy customers except few (e.g. D-Mart) to create a brand image. Online feedback is also a popular tool of interactive retailing among the organised retailers except few (e.g. Big Megamart and West Side). Moreover, electronics super store organised retailers (e.g. Reliance Digital and NEXT) take online feedback on Facebook. However, some other organised retailers (e.g. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar and Max) use the online discussion forum as interactive retailing tools to create a brand image among customers.

Use of celebrity services is not so popular among organised retailers to create a brand image. However, some organised retailers (e.g. Big Bazaar, Big Megamart, West Side and Max) use celebrity services for promotions. The organised retailers use the tagline and logo for creating a unique brand image among the customers. The most of the organised retailers use customer-centric tagline except few (e.g. HyperCITY, West Side, Reliance Digital and NEXT) as these others use the store-centric tagline.

The organised retailers prefer main street locations to open their stores except few (e.g. Big Megamart and HyperCITY), as these others prefer inner city locations. However, some others (e.g. Max) prefer both types of locations. The organised retailers open their store in shopping malls / shopping centres and / or strip centres. However, some fashion item superstores (e.g. West Side and Max) also prefer to open their stores in outlet centres. Total size & density of population, total disposable income of the population, per capita disposable income of the population, trends among the population, delivery cost of the supply, timeliness for supply, number of manufacturers & wholesalers in the area, availability & reliability of merchandise lines, the growth projections in the area, freedom from economic & seasonal fluctuations, number and size of existing competitors in the area, strength & weakness of competitors, number and type of

locations in the area, cost of site, visibility of site, size & shape of trading area and parking facilities are some important factors for selecting a retail store location by the organised retailers.

There is no uniformity among organised retailers in store timings. Some organised retailers (e.g. HyperCITY and Big Megamart) keep open their stores 10.30 hours, some others (e.g. Star Bazaar) keep open stores for 14 hours, few others (e.g. more.MEGASStore) keep open stores for 13 hours, some retailers (e.g. Big Bazaar, D⁺Mart) keep open stores for 12 hours, other retailers (e.g. Max, Reliance Digital) keep open stores for 11 hours on all the days of the week, while others (e.g. West Side) keep open stores at 11.30 hours on weekdays and 11.00 hours on Sunday, moreover, few others (e.g. NEXT) keep open stores for 11.30 hours on all the days of the week except Monday as it is closed.

The most of the organised retailers adopts patronage solidifiers customers service strategy and involved in the low-cost little things that increase loyalty, like courtesy & suggestion selling) except some (e.g. more.MEGASStore, Reliance Digital and NEXT) as these others adopt patronage builders customers service strategy and involved in high-cost activities like transaction speed & credit. The organised retailers (whether multi-format, fashion item or electronics item organised retailers) offer attractive exchange & a return policy to protect their customers and gain their confidence. The organised retailers use gap model to understand knowledge, standard, delivery and communication gaps to improve customer service quality except few retailers (e.g. Star Bazaar, NEXT and D⁺Mart).

The organised retailers interested to have a CRM and maintain the same through the customer service desk or customer loyalty desk at the store level. The multi-format hyper store organised retailers (e.g. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and Big Bazaar) and fashion item organised retailers (e.g. Big Megamart, West Side and Max) collect information for database regarding customer transactions (purchase date, price paid, merchandise purchased, responses to promoted merchandise), customer contacts (record of customer interaction with store by websites, inquiries in-store kiosks, telephone calls), customer preferences (favourite colour, brands, fabrics, flavours, and apparel size), descriptive information (demographic &

psychographic data of customers) and customer responses to marketing activity (responsiveness to sales promotion & advertising), while electronics-item organised retailers (e.g. Reliance Digital and NEXT) collect information for database regarding customer transactions, customer contacts and descriptive information only and multi-format superstore organised retailers (e.g. D-Mart) collect information for database regarding customer transactions only.

The organised retailers collect the information for the database by keeping records of the customer transactions. These organised retailers also conduct the in-store survey through printed questionnaire and collect information under a membership programme except few (e.g. D-Mart). Moreover, some organised retailers (e.g. more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar, Reliance Digital and NEXT) also conduct an online survey in order to collect information; while some others (e.g. Max and Big Bazaar) collect the information by taking customer feedback & suggestions.

The organised retailers use CRM programmes in order to maintain a relationship and create loyal customers, except few (e.g. D-Mart). The organised retailers also have a separate cell (customer support cell) to help customers in store and they all use listening and responding approach, respond to the customers with a courtesy, maintain speed and accuracy of service in order to help their customers

The most of the organised retailers deals with retail clientele only except few (e.g. Reliance Digital), who deal with both retail as well as corporate clientele. The organised retailers face the problems like changing the landscape of Indian consumerism, changing retail trends, changing government role, stiff competition, cultural disparity, high demand for service standards, the price war while dealing with key customers. Some of the store based organised retailers (e.g. Big Bazaar, Reliance Digital and NEXT) also provide e-retailing service to their customers.

The multi-format hyper store organised retailers (e.g. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and Big Bazaar) use a mix of free form or boutique layout and grid layout to display the merchandise while planning store design, while multi-format superstore organised retailers (e.g. D-Mart) use only grid layout to display the merchandise while planning store design. Fashion-item organised retailers (e.g. Big Megamart, West Side and Max) use the free form or boutique layout to display the

merchandise while planning store design and superstore based electronics-item organised retailers (e.g. Reliance Digital and NEXT) use racetrack layout to display the merchandise while planning store design. The organised retailers use category, promotional and point of sale signage for locating the merchandise category in their stores. Moreover, some organised retailers (e.g. Big Megamart, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar and Reliance Digital) also use digital signage.

Freestanding displays, end caps, promotional aisles, wall displays and cash wrap displays (point of purchase counters or check out areas) are most preferred methods of displaying the merchandise in the stores among the multi-format organised retailers. However, some multi-format organised retailers (e.g. HyperCITY, more.MEGASStore and Big Bazaar) also use window display and entrance display methods of displaying the merchandise in their stores. Fashion-item organised retailers (e.g. Big Megamart, West Side and Max) use window display, entrance display, free standing display, end caps, promotional aisles and wall display methods of displaying the merchandise in their stores. However, some fashion item organised retailers (e.g. Max) also use a dressing room display method. Superstore based electronics-item organised retailers (e.g. Reliance Digital and NEXT) use entrance display, freestanding display, promotional aisles and walls display methods of displaying the merchandise in their stores. However, some other (e.g. Reliance Digital) also uses a cash wrap display method.

The multi-format organised retailers (e.g. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar and D▲Mart) use straight racks, rounder (capacity fixture), four-way fixture (feature fixture) and gondolas, while fashion-item organised retailers (e.g. Big Megamart, West Side and Max) use rounder (bulk fixture/capacity fixture), four-way fixture (feature fixture) and gondolas and superstore based electronics-item organised retailers (e.g. Reliance Digital and NEXT) use only straight racks and rounder (bulk fixture/capacity fixture) to display the merchandise in the stores. The organised retailers use item & size presentation, price lining, vertical merchandising, tonnage merchandising and frontal presentation techniques, however, some organised retailers (e.g. Star Bazaar, Big Bazaar, West Side, Max, Reliance

Digital and NEXT) also use an idea-oriented presentation technique to present the merchandise in the store.

Some hyper store based multi-format organised retailers (e.g. HyperCITY, more.MEGASStore and Big Bazaar) and fashion item organised retailers (e.g. Big Megamart, West Side and Max) use lighting, colour, scent and music, while some other hyper store based multi-format organised retailers (e.g. Star Bazaar) use only lighting and music for creating an appealing store atmosphere. Moreover, multi-format superstore organised retailers (e.g. D-Mart) use only music to create an appealing store atmosphere and electronics items organised retailers (i.e. Reliance Digital and NEXT) use lighting, colour, and music to create an appealing store atmosphere.

Visual merchandising, store layout, interior atmospherics and exterior atmospherics are important components of the store design for the organised retailers. Storefront, store marquee/sign board, visibility of the store, location/site of the store, parking facilities and ease of access are some important component of the exterior atmospherics of the store. Lighting, odour/smell/scent, sounds, temperature, cleanliness, trial (experience) room/zone, merchandise and store size are the important component of the interior atmospherics of the store. Space planning, floor space allocation, department size, the location of various merchandise, signage and space/merchandise categories are the important component of the store layout. Assortment, payment counters, merchandise display, the planogram, point of sale sign and methods of display are the important component of visual merchandising.

9.1.3 Conclusions drawn from the analysis of profile of customers in the organised retail industry

Data pertained to residing area, gender, age, education, occupation, family income (yearly), marital status, nature of family, family size and religion of customers was accumulated for analysis of the profile of customers in the organised retail industry. The analysis of the data concludes the following:

The organised retail industry is getting the customers from all the areas i.e. urban, semi-urban and rural areas. However, the majority of customers of organised retailers is from urban areas and semi-urban areas. Nevertheless, some retailers (e.g.

NEXT and Reliance Digital, D-Mart, Star Bazaar, more.MEGAStore), locating their stores near to the rural areas are also able to tap an enough number of customers from rural areas.

The organised retail industry is attracting the male and female customers in equal proportion with its offerings. However, the footfall of male customers is more in comparison to female customers. It is the fact the females are more fashion conscious in India. Not surprising, the fashion item retailers (e.g. Big Megamart, West Side & Max) attract more female customers; while, the electronics item retailers (e.g. NEXT and Reliance Digital) attract more male customers, which reflects that the purchase of an expensive item is still in the hand of males.

The organised retail industry has something to offer to all the age groups. But, it is flourishing with the footfall of youth customers, whose age ranges from 21 to 40 years. The organised retailers are also attracting a great number of customers from the age group of 41 to 50 years with their offerings. However, the electronics item retailers (e.g. NEXT and Reliance Digital) are getting their majority of customers from the age group of 31 to 60 years.

The industry is attracting the customers of all education groups and has well-educated customers in the Maharashtra state as the state has 82.34 literacy rate. And, the majority of customers in the industry are graduates or post graduates.

The organised retailers are attracting the customers from all the occupational groups. However, the majority of customers are salaried and self-employed and another majority is of students and homemakers.

The organised retailers have something to offer to the customers of all the income groups. However, the majority of customers are from two income groups, i.e. 2 to 5 LPA and 5 to 10 LPA. Nevertheless, the retailers are also attracting the customers from the high-income group (i.e. more than 10 LPA) as well as low-income group (i.e. 1 to 2 LPA).

The organised retail industry is attracting both married as well as single customers. However, the industry has its more customers from the married marital status group. Nevertheless, the electronics item superstores (e.g. NEXT and Reliance Digital) and multi-format superstores (e.g. D-Mart) are getting more customers from a married marital status group, while the fashion item retailers (e.g. Big Megamart, West Side, Max) as well as some multi-format hyper stores (e.g. HyperCITY and Big Bazaar) are attracting more customers from single marital status group.

The offering basket of organised retailers has something for both nuclear as well as joint families customers. However, the industry is getting more customers from nuclear families. Nevertheless, some retailers (e.g. Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, D-Mart, Reliance Digital and NEXT) are getting fewer footfalls from nuclear families. The retailers are also attracting the customers from all the family size groups of customers. However, the majority of customers are from the family size of below 5 members' family size.

The organised retailers are getting the customers from all the religions due to the diversity of the country. However, the majority of the customers are Hindus. The second majority is of Muslim customers, nevertheless, not surprisingly, the third majority is of Buddhists customers, as the Maharashtra state has 73.4% of the total Buddhism followers in India.

9.1.4 Conclusions drawn from the analysis of buying behaviour of customers in the organised retail industry

Data pertained to various factors / elements of customer behaviour were accumulated for analysis of the buying behaviour of customers in the organised retail industry. The analysis of the data concludes the following:

The majority of customers in the organised retail industry is either self-purchase decision maker in the family or relies on their spouse and parents. The electronics-item superstores (e.g. NEXT and Reliance Digital) are getting more footfalls from the self-purchase decision-making customers. The primary reason of the same is that such retailers have more than 80% of customers are male.

The customers in organised retail industry collect the information about merchandise and services before taking a purchase making decision and their preferred sources for collecting the information are advertising, the internet, family members, neighbours / friends / relatives, package labels, in-store display, in-store information, salespersons and telemarketing. Good news for the retailers is that the customers also prefer to collect the information from sources like in-store display, salespersons and in-store information. The customers, who collect the information from advertising, rely on the television, websites, celebrity endorsement, newspapers, pamphlets, magazines, hoardings, radio and cinema and the purchase decisions TV talk shows, infomercials, family members, websites, celebrity endorsement, TV commercials, sales promotion, neighbours / friends / colleagues, self, a salesperson in a store, direct-mail piece and magazine ads.

The customers of the organised retailers prefer to purchase the merchandise and service, either by self or rely on their spouse and parents. The customers of the multi-format retailers (e.g. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar and D-Mart) visit the stores 3 or more times in a month, while customers of the fashion stores organised retailers (e.g. Big Megamart, West Side and Max) as well as the electronics item superstores (e.g. Reliance Digital and NEXT) visit the stores 1 or 2 times in a month.

The reason for more visits in the multi-format stores is that all these offer staples categories merchandise to their customers. The customers prefer to visit the stores on weekends. But, it does not mean that the industry is not getting footfall on weekdays. The multi-format organised retailers get great footfalls of customers on all the seven days. Usually, customers prefer to visit the stores in the evening time. But, it does not mean that the industry is not getting footfall in morning and afternoon.

The customers of the fashion store retailers as well as electronics stores spend more than ₹ 5000 per month for purchasing from the stores while the customers of multi-format retailers spend ₹ 2000 to ₹ 5000 per month. The customers of the multi-format organised retailers purchases the products from all the categories of merchandise i.e. basic (staples) merchandise, fashion merchandise, seasonal merchandise and consumer durable, while customers of fashion stores (e.g. Big Megamart, West Side and Max) purchase the products from fashion merchandise

categories and customers of electronics item superstores (e.g. Reliance Digital and NEXT) purchases the products from consumer durables merchandise category.

The good news for the industry is that the customers in the organised retail industry are impulse buyers. The multi-format hyper stores (e.g. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASTore and Big Bazaar) and fashion stores (e.g. Big Megamart, West Side and Max) are attracting a great number of impulse buyers. Food & grocery, beauty, electronics, fashion products are the most common type of products purchased by impulse buyers from the stores of the multi-format organised retailers, while women's wear, men's wear, kid's wear, footwear and accessories are the most common type of products purchased by impulse buyers from the stores of fashion store retailers and accessories are the most common type of products purchased by impulse buyers from the stores of electronics item retailers. The common reasons for impulse purchase are price reductions, multi-item discounts, the point of purchase display, demonstration and samples, salespeople, store atmosphere, store layout, coupons, packaging and shelving techniques.

The customers' first preference is either quality or brand while purchasing merchandise. However, the good news for the organised retailers is that there are also a great percentage of customers in industry, whose first preference is discounts, schemes, price, quantity and other while purchasing.

The customers of organised retailers visit their stores due to several reasons, most notably merchandise (merchandise assortment- variety of merchandise and brands, quality of assortment, in service situations, merchandise offered as part of service, styling or fashion guarantee, warranties and pricing, reasonable prices), promotion (advertising, displays, trading stamps, sales promotion- discount & special schemes, symbol and colours), store atmospheres (atmosphere of congeniality, customers' feeling of warmth, acceptance or ease, good & spacious ambience, and delighting store environment), convenience (general convenience, parking access, location convenience- proximity to home/office), services (service in general, salesclerk service, presence of self-service, ease of merchandise return, delivery service, phone ordering and credit policy), physical facilities (elevators, lighting, air conditioning, restrooms, store layout, shopping ease, aisle placement, carpeting and

architecture), post-transaction satisfaction (merchandise in use, return & adjustment policy), institutional factors (projection of store- conservative or modern, reputation, reliability), clientele (social class appeal, store personnel, fit between self-image and store image- self-image congruence), other (friends suggested, no other store nearby, convenient store hours).

The merchandise is the primary reason for visiting the stores among the customers of multi-format hyper store retailers (e.g. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar) as well as electronics-item superstores (e.g. Reliance Digital and NEXT). The promotion is the primary reason for visiting the store by customers of multi-format superstore retailers (e.g. D⁺Mart). However, the store atmosphere is the primary reason for visiting the stores among the customers of fashion store retailers (e.g. Big Megamart, West Side and Max). The majority of customers in the organised retail industry, visit more than one retail store. However, the industry has a great number of loyal customers, who do not visit any other stores. The multi-format organised retailers (e.g. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, Big Bazaar, and D⁺Mart) have more loyal customers. However, among the multi-format organised retailers, the hyper stores (e.g. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and Big Bazaar) have more loyal customers in comparison to a superstore (e.g. D⁺Mart). The customers, who visit more than the regular one store, visit both organised as well as unorganised retail stores. However, those customers first preference is both organised as well as unorganised retail stores. The customers visit the other retail stores due to several reasons, most notably for better services, finding the merchandise of their choice, better promotional offers, convenience, better store atmospheres and physical facilities, due to institutional factors like projection of store, reputation, reliability etc., due to other reasons like friends suggested, no other store nearby, convenient store hours etc., better post-transaction satisfaction like merchandise in use, return & adjustment policy.

9.1.5 Conclusions drawn from the analysis factors influencing buying behaviour of customers in the organised retail industry

Data pertained to various factors influencing the buying behaviour of customers was accumulated for analysis of factors influencing the buying behaviour of customers in the organised retail industry. The analysis of the data concludes the following:

The sociological / environmental / external factors (e.g. cultural, sub-cultural, society, status in society, reference group, family life cycle and role in the family) have a significant influence on the buying behaviour of customers in the organised retail industry. However, the influence of sociological / environmental / external factors on buying behaviour of customers of electronics store retailers is less in comparison to customers of other retailer formats. This depicts that the buying decisions pertained to the consumer durables particularly electronics item and other technological items are less influenced by sociological factors. Nevertheless, the buying decisions pertained to the staples (basic) and fashion merchandise are more influenced by the sociological factors.

The psychological / individual / internal factors (e.g. self-image, personality, personal values, lifestyle, memory, learning, perception, motivation, emotions, mood, involvement, information processing, beliefs, intention, attitude, communication, and persuasion) also have significant influence on the buying behaviour of customers in the organised retail industry and these factors influence the buying behaviour of customers of different formats (superstores or hyper stores) and type of retailers (e.g. multi-item, fashion item or electronics item).

The store related factors (e.g. store image, store atmosphere, store brands, store location, sales personnel, discounts & schemes and free services) also significantly influence the buying behaviour of customers in the organised retail industry and these factors also influence the buying behaviour of customers of different formats (superstores or hyper stores) and type of retailers (e.g. multi-item, fashion item or electronics item).

9.1.6 Conclusions drawn from the analysis of customer satisfaction with the merchandise (products) and services offered by organised retail industry

Data pertained to customer satisfaction with various merchandise and services was accumulated for analysis of customer satisfaction with the merchandise (products)

and services offered by organised retail industry. The analysis of the data concludes the following:

The organised retail industry satisfies the customers with its customer expected merchandise assortment; merchandise categories (e.g. basic or staple, fashion, seasonal, consumer durable, etc.) in the assortment; the variety of merchandise in each category as per different sizes, colours, designs, price, quality, quantity and brands; availability of newly launched merchandise, customised merchandise, unique merchandise and complementary merchandise in each category; availability of the brands (i.e. local & regional, national, international, private / store, copycat, exclusive, generic brands) in each merchandise category; quality assurance and quality of merchandise; services and quality of the services; pricing of merchandise & services; overall value offered as compared to the price/cost of merchandise & services; exterior atmospherics, the interior atmospherics of the stores; store layout and visual merchandising; methods of promotion and communication (e.g. advertising, sales promotion, personal retailing and the internet or interactive retailing); sales personnel, contact personnel and factors pertained to personnel; and other tangible evidence (e.g. employee appearance, uniforms, billing statement, internet or web pages etc.).

The hyper-stores based organised retailers leads in satisfying the customers as compared superstore based organised retailers. However, superstore retailers also perform better than hyper-stores in satisfying customers in some areas. The superstore retailers (e.g. D⁺Mart, West Side and Max) satisfy more customers with their pricing of merchandise & services as compared to their hyper store counterparts. The fashion item superstore based retailers (e.g. West Side and Max) performs better in satisfying customers with their sales promotion methods, public relation/publicity methods, internet/interactive retailing methods as compared to their hyper store counterparts (e.g. Big Megamart). The electronics-item superstore retailers (e.g. Reliance Digital and NEXT) also perform better than the hyper store similar item retailers (e.g. HyperCITY, Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore and Big Bazaar) in satisfying customer with the availability of newly launched merchandise, customised merchandise, unique merchandise and complimentary merchandise, brands in each category, pricing of merchandise & services and direct retailing.

Some superstore retailers (e.g. D-Mart, Max, Reliance Digital and Next) are lacking to match the industry standards in satisfying their customers in an area like the quality of services, exterior and interior atmospherics of the store, store layout, personal retailing methods, factors pertained to personnel, other tangible evidence, etc.. Moreover, even some hyper store retailers (e.g. Star Bazaar and more.MEGASStore) are also not matching the industry standards in satisfying their customers in an area like store layout, visual merchandising, factors pertained to personnel, etc.

Therewith, adequate individual customers of different retail stores are dissatisfied or disappointed with the merchandise and services offered. Those products & services have been discussed in the recommendation section for better understanding and recommendation to the concerns.

9.1.6 Conclusions drawn from testing of hypotheses

The first null hypothesis stated that “retailing strategies introduced by organised retailers are not significant to sustain in the hyper-competitive retail market”. This hypothesis was framed under certain assumptions for which no validation required as it is a common noticeable phenomenon that “retailing strategies introduced by organised retailers are significant to sustain in hyper-competitive retail market”. However, this statement is supported by product portfolio analysis (presented in chapter 5) where the significant majority of merchandise (products) of all the organised retailers belongs to Star category in the BCG matrix. Moreover, this statement is also supported by the customer satisfaction with various merchandise (products) and services offered by all the organised retailers. Therefore, the first null hypothesis is rejected and the alternate hypothesis, i.e. “retailing strategies introduced by organised retailers are significant to sustain in hyper-competitive retail market” is accepted. However, the retailers have to travel a long distance to meet the international standards in organised retailing.

The second null hypothesis stated that “customers are not significantly satisfied with various products & services introduced by organised retailers”. The results of hypothesis testing depict that customers are significantly satisfied with various products & services introduced by organised retailers except direct retailing methods and public relation/publicity methods. Therefore, the second null hypothesis is also rejected, which

signifies that the organised retailers offer various products and services as per the expectation of their targeted customers.

Therewith, it would be better to mention that the customers of some retailers (e.g. D⁺Mart, Max, Reliance Digital, NEXT, Star Bazaar and more.MEGAS⁺Store) are not significantly satisfied with some products & services introduced by them. Those products & services have been discussed in the recommendation section for better understanding and recommendation to the concerns.

9.2 RECOMMENDATIONS

This sub-section comprises the recommendations based on the analyses of the data collected from the organised retailers and customers of them for the betterment of the industry and to improve the level of customer satisfaction.

- 1) Some merchandise lines of the organised retailers fall in the category of Question Mark in the BCG matrix, e.g. HyperCITY's electronics and toys;

more.MEGASStore's general merchandise, mobile phones & accessories and computers & accessories; Big Bazaar's bed & bath bazaar, home bazaar, mobile bazaar and furniture bazaar; D-Mart's home appliances and bags & trolleys; Big Megamart's home mart and travel mart; West Side's home & gift; Max's children's wear and footwear, Reliance Digital's mobile phones and computers; and NEXT's computers & tablets and personal care. The concern retailer should select few types of merchandise to convert them into the Star category, or they may also divest them from the assortment.

- 2) Few more merchandise lines of the organised retailers also fall in the category of Dog in the BCG matrix, e.g. HyperCITY's sports; Star Bazaar's international zone; more.MEGASStore's fruits & vegetables and sports; Big Bazaar's farm fresh and books, magazines & stationery bazaar; D-Mart's frozen, toys & games and stationery; Big Megamart's toys; West Side's luggage; Reliance Digital's gaming; and NEXT's fragrances and writing Instruments. The concern retailer should liquidate these merchandise lines from the assortment. This action will assist them to introduce new merchandise lines on the place of the existing one, which are not attracting the enough customers. In this way, the retailers can increase the sales and the satisfaction of the customers.
- 3) The industry is not getting an adequate number of the customers from rural areas. The retailers should offer the product and service needed by the rural area people. E.g. the organised retailer can introduce the farm and agriculture merchandise line for the rural area farm background customers, under this line can offer the merchandise like seeds, insecticides, pesticides, fertilisers, small farm equipment, etc. to attract the rural area customers. Similarly, retailers can also offer the merchandise line for pet animals of rural area people.
- 4) The organised retail industry is also getting fewer customers from the age group of below 21. The retailers should update their assortment by adding books, study materials; other items needed by that group, etc. to attract this age group customer. The organised retail industry is also getting fewer customers from the family income group of less than 2 LPA. The retailers should communicate and

promote their merchandise and service among them for winning their confidence and attracting them to the stores.

- 5) The customers in the organised retail industry collect the information about the merchandise and services from various sources, e.g. advertising, internet, family members, neighbours / friends / relatives, package labels, in-store display, in-store information, salespersons, telemarketing, etc. The retailers need to make sure the availability of the adequate information through all the sources. The customers in the organised retail industry prefer to visit the stores on weekends. The retailers need to entice them on weekdays too by offering better promotional schemes, eat, play and shop environment.
- 6) The customers are also impulse buyers. The retailers need to cash their impulse buying habits by offering better services, sales promotion, visual merchandising and employing helping sales people. The customers in the organised retail industry also visit more than one store for better merchandise and services. The retailers should make them loyal by matching their expectation.
- 7) The sociological, psychological and store related factors significantly influence the buying behaviour of the customers. The retailers should offer something unique for every customer according to their expectations to in cash the influence of the various factors on buying behaviour.
- 8) The industry needs to ensure the full support to their customers and customers should realise the same. It will help the industry to gain the confidence of the customers and they will not only be loyal but also spread positive word of mouth.
- 9) The industry needs to reward good customers through the special promotional schemes e.g. deposit schemes with guaranteed rebates, special discounts to loyal customers, the gift for special occasions, etc. This will also assist the retailers to create a great number of loyal customers.

- 10) The problems of the customers need to be handled efficiently. The contact and sales personnel should be capable enough to understand the questions and concerns of the customers as well able to answer questions.
- 11) Today's customers want a quick response to their problems and issues through all the mediums. The retailers should ensure the same through all the mediums like phone, email, social media, etc. The stores must be reachable through all the mediums.
- 12) The industry is revolutionising the organised retail sector of India. But, many players in the industry adopt only some traditional promotional methods for communication with their customers. For better promotion and communication, the industry should integrate the retail communication mix and need to include the various tools from advertising, sales promotion, personal retailing, direct retailing, internet retailing and public relation methods.
- 13) Although organised retailers consider the customer relationship as the prime goal to attract the customers and maintain good customer relationship. However, many players, especially superstore based retailers (e.g. D⁺Mart and NEXT) lack to maintain the customer relation (CR). These players need to maintain a customer relationship management department for analysing and applying customer relationship at the individual level.
- 14) The most organised retailers in the industry concentrate only on the retail clientele. These retailers can also target of the corporate / business clientele to grow their business in this segment.
- 15) The retail marketing mix is the key element or vital role player for satisfying customers. Many players in the industry (e.g. D⁺Mart and NEXT) not giving equal importance to every element of the mix. The retailers need to give equal importance to every element of mix whether it is merchandise or price, promotion, premises, presentation, personnel.

- 16) Store level planning is the important decision to increase the efficiency of the particular store of an organised retailer. Many small players (e.g. D[▲]Mart, Max and NEXT) do not do much planning at store-level. The retailers need to use the different and diversified tools available for store-level planning to increase the efficiency and effectiveness of the store. The BCG matrix should be used for merchandise portfolio analysis. ETOP and PEST analysis for better understanding of the internal as well as external environmental factors should be used while five force analysis for understanding the competition and its intensity.
- 17) Although, the organised retailers offer good merchandise categories to their customers, but the customers of some retailers (e.g. more.MEGASStore, D[▲] Mart, Max and NEXT) are not happy with the merchandise categories and a variety of merchandise in each category offered by them. Therefore, these retailers first need to revise their merchandise categories as per the expectations of the customers and then should offer the variety of merchandise in each category as per different sizes, colours, designs, price, quality, quantity and brands.
- 18) The industry also makes sure availability of the newly launched merchandise, customised merchandise, unique merchandise and complementary merchandise in each category. However, few retailers (e.g. Star Bazaar and D[▲]Mart) lack to match the industry standards, hence need to improve the availability of the newly launched merchandise, customised merchandise, unique merchandise and complementary merchandise in each category offered by them to enhance the customer satisfaction level.
- 19) Although, the organised retailers offer a wide range of brands in each category, but the few (e.g. more.MEGASStore and D[▲]Mart) are lacking to satisfy the customers with their brand offerings. These retailers strongly need to re-shuffle their brand offerings from local & regional brands, national brands, international brands, private (store) brands and others, i.e. copycat, exclusive, generic brands.

- 20) Although, the organised retailers offer a wide variety of services (e.g. credit, home delivery, alteration, installation, packaging, complaints & returns handling and may more) to their customers. But, the customers are not happy with some services of the few retailers (e.g. D⁺Mart and Max). These retailers should re-check their services and the quality of their services. The retailers must ensure the standards of the services and make sure that their personnel are able to manage tangibility of the services, the reliability of services, responsiveness in the services, able to assure the quality and empathy while providing the services.
- 21) The organised retail industry is trying very hard to enhance the shopping experience of the customers and also getting the success in the same. However, few retailers (e.g. D⁺Mart, Max and NEXT) are inefficient to satisfy their customers with the exterior and interior environment of the stores. The need of the hour is to provide an appealing store environment to keep enticing the customers. Therefore, these retailers need to rethink and recreate the exterior and interior environment of their stores. First, retailers should create an appealing exterior environment through an attracting storefront, sign board, store nameplate, frontage entrance and external display window. The uniqueness, visibility and location of the store also play an important role in creating an appealing exterior environment. Then, retailers should make sure an appealing interior environment through an attracting lighting, odour / smell / scent, sounds, colour, temperature, fixtures, wall textures, flooring & ceiling, cleanliness, aisles, trial room, and store size.
- 22) The store layout and visual merchandising play an important role in attracting the customers; easily locate merchandise, space management and presentation of the merchandise. Although, the industry inclined to match the international standards in visual merchandising, but some retailers (e.g. Star Bazaar, more.MEGASStore, D⁺Mart, Max and NEXT) still least bother about layouts and visual merchandising planning, as their customers are not much satisfied. Therefore, these retailers need to improve their store layout planning by doing proper space planning, floor space allocation, e-display, managing a department

location, department size, department compatibility, the location of various products, accessibility to cash/billing counters and signage. The visual merchandising needs to comprise the attractive themes, racks & shelves, ensemble, merchandise display, the point of sale sign and methods of display.

- 23) Although, the organised retailers are satisfying their customers through the adoption of promotional and communication methods. Nevertheless, retailers need to improve the some communication and promotional methods. E.g. the advertising is not considered much important in this industry as compared to other. But, the retailers should not forget the power of the communication through the advertising methods and should adopt some in store as well as out-store methods of communication. The in-store methods are visual display, signage, pamphlets, point of purchase material, secondary packaging and cross-promotion, while out-store methods can be selected from television, radio, newspapers, journals & magazine, yellow pages, hoardings, wall paintings, pamphlets/propaganda, van advertising, online advertising, mobile billboard, LCD screening, cinema, fairs & exhibitions.
- 24) The many customers are dissatisfied with the direct retailing and public relation methods of communication adopted by the industry. The retailers need to adopt some new methods of direct retailing (e.g. direct mail, tele-retailing, direct response on TV/radio, mail order catalogues, SMS retailing and mobile retailing) and public relations (e.g. corporate brochures, posters, annual reports, press release, press conference, video press conference, internet release, store tours for media, meeting with customers, special events & sponsorships, social events, social development programs).
- 25) Today, the people spend much time on the world wide webs. The organised retailers also understand the fact and making their presence on the internet through the website, social media platforms, weblogs, discussion forums and emails. Nevertheless, some retailers (e.g. D_{Mar}) are poor in making their effective presence on the world wide webs and social media platforms like

Facebook, Twitter, Youtube, etc. These retailers need to match their steps with the need of the hours to be successful in the long-run.

- 26) The people are an integral part of any business and play an important role in satisfying customers. In the retail business, the two categories of people have direct contact with the customers, i.e. sales people and contact people (e.g. help desk people, service desk people, billing counter people etc.). These people's mood, efforts, commitment, attitude, knowledge, skills, behaviour, approach to delivering the service, competence, courtesy, credibility, reliability, responsiveness, communication style, friendliness, helpfulness, discipline & punctuality, counselling ability has the direct relation with the satisfaction of the customers. Although, the retailers employ capable and trained the people to deal with the customers. But, some retailers (e.g. Star Bazaar, more.MEGASore, D Mart, Max and NEXT) lack to so and need to improve this area.
- 27) Some organised retailers (e.g. Star Bazaar, more.MEGASore, D Mart, Max and NEXT) also need to improve the management of other tangible evidence like employee appearance, uniforms, billing statements, the internet or web pages, etc.
- 28) The customers suggested some facilities required to introduce by retailers like deposit schemes with guaranteed rebate, mail & phone orders, internet facility (wifi), mobile and laptop charger points, product on demand, information about discounts & schemes through SMS and Whatsapp, internet billing facility, medical facility and insurance facility.
- 29) The customers also think that there is an urgent need to improve the following services: parking facility is very poor in case of some retailers, especially superstore retailers, and even it is also paid service. The retailers charge an amount for shopping bags after February 4, 2011, as per the notification of the Ministry of Environment & Forest, Government of India, however, the customer are not happy with it. The customers also face the problems at baggage counters for the safety of personal things due to large queues. The after sale services on durable purchased from the retailers are provided by the

manufacturers. The customers complain that they do not get adequate mediator support from the retailers. The customers also face long queues at cash/billing counters, which really annoy them sometimes and expect less than five minutes waiting time in the queue. The female customers are not happy with the trial rooms' management. Where, they are allowed to carry only a few items to try at a time. The customers also found that the attrition rate of the sale and contact personnel is high in the industry. Therefore, the customers have to listen from the personnel that they are new and recently joined the store and not aware about the different policies of the retailers.

- 30) Organised retailers face the closest competition from the unorganised retailers of the Industry. To beat the competitions effectively, organised retailers need to offer the unmatched merchandise assortment at an unmatched price and continue to improve the shopping experience of the customers through the adoption of international standards in retailing.
- 31) Online retailing is the biggest threat for the store based organised retailers. To face this threat, the retailers need to continue with their shop, eat and play concept of retailing. The organised retailers need to continuously improve the refreshment and entertainment facilities in their stores along with the merchandise and services. Moreover, organised retailers should also introduce and improve (those already introduced) phone, email and web order facility for their customers. The organised retailer should also launch their free mobile app, through which the customers can not only place their orders, but also get the information about the latest promotional schemes and discounts.
- 32) The organised retailers face many problems like the high price of real estate, lack of preferred locations and retail space, high cost of space and location, trained workforce, multiple & a complex taxation system, many entrants as online retailers, high demand for service standards, inefficiency of the supply chains, lack of adequate infrastructure and demand for higher wages by the workforce, etc. The stakeholders in the industry like Government, real state suppliers, workforce suppliers, other supply chains and others should understand the issues of the organised retailers because the support of all the

stockholders will lead to a solid foundation towards the growth of the organised retail sector.

9.3 AREAS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

Future research should consider this study for other sectors like banking, insurance, telecom, automobile, etc. The researchers can study the marketing / retailing strategies for products and services in these suggested areas. Another area of research would be a cross-comparison of retailing strategies of unorganised retailers and organised retailers.

This is the study of store-based retailers. The future research should carry this study with the e-retailers. The comparative study of store-based and e-retailers would also be carried. In this study, only two format retailers (i.e. hyper store and superstore) have been selected, in future research another formats (e.g. convenience store, discount stores, speciality stores, department stores) can be considered.

In this study, three different item retailers (multi-item, fashion item and electronics item) were taken into the consideration, in future research another kind of item retailers can be taken into the consideration.

Section 3

Supportive Information

- Bibliography
- Appendix

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Admin (2011), "PEST analysis", Crackmba, available at: <http://crackmba.com/pest-analysis>.
2. Altintas, Murat Hakan; Kiliç, Serkan; Senol, Gokhan and Isin, Feride Bahar (2010), "Strategic objectives and competitive advantages of private label products: Manufacturers' perspective", *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, Vol. 38 Iss: 10, pp. 773-788.
3. Arbuckle, Dani (2015), "Defensive Strategies in Strategic Management", *Demand Media*, available at: <http://yourbusiness.azcentral.com/defensive-strategies-strategic-management-4676.html>.
4. Asikhia, Olalekan (2010), "Customer Orientation and Firm Performance among Nigerian Small and Medium Scale Businesses", *International Journal of Marketing Studies*, Vol. 2 No. 1, pp. 197-212.
5. Auh, Seigyoung; Menguc, Bulent; Fisher, Michelle and Haddad, Abeer (2011), "The perceived autonomy–perceived service climate relationship: The contingency effect of store-level tenure diversity", *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Vol. 18 Iss: 6, pp. 509-520.
6. Avlonitis, George J. and Indounas, Kostis A. (2007), "Service pricing: An empirical investigation", *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Vol. 14 Iss: 1, pp. 83-94.
7. Bajaj, Chetan; Tuli, Rajnish and Srivastava, Nidhi Varma (2010), *Retail Management*, Oxford.
8. Barber, Clifford S and Tietje, Brian C (2004), "A distribution services approach for developing effective competitive strategies against "big box" retailers", *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Vol. 11 Iss: 2, pp. 95-107.
9. Barone, Michael J.; Norman, Andrew T. and Miyazaki, Anthony D. (2007), "Consumer response to retailer use of cause-related marketing: Is more fit better?", *Journal of Retailing*, Vol. 83 Iss: 4, pp. 437-445.
10. Barry, B. J. and Jill, A. S. (2000), "Atmospheric affect as a tool for creating value and gaining share of customer", *Journal of Business Research*, 49, pp. 91-101.
11. Baskaran, Kamaladevi (2011), "Success of retail in India: the customer experience management scenario" *International Journal of Electronic Marketing and Retailing*, Vol. 4 No. 2/3, pp. 206-223.

12. Batra, S. K. and Kazmi S. H. H. (2004), *Consumer Behaviour – Text and Cases*, Excel Books, India, 1st Ed.
13. Beard, Ross (2014), “Why Customer Satisfaction is important”, Client Heartbeat, available at: <http://blog.clientheartbeat.com/why-customer-satisfaction-is-important/>.
14. Beri, G. C. (2000), *Marketing Research*, Tata McGraw-Hill Education Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi, India.
15. Bodet, Guillaume (2008), “Customer satisfaction and loyalty in service: Two concepts, four constructs, several relationships”, *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Vol. 15 Iss: 3, pp. 156-162.
16. Brown, Steven P. and Lam, Son K. (2008), “A Meta-Analysis of Relationships Linking Employee Satisfaction to Customer Responses”, *Journal of Retailing*, Vol. 84 Iss: 3, pp. 243-255.
17. Burt, Steve; Johansson, Ulf and Thelander, Åsa (2011), “Standardised marketing strategies in retailing? IKEA’s marketing strategies in Sweden, the UK and China”, *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Vol. 18 Iss: 3, pp. 183-193.
18. Cacho-Elizondo, Silvia and Loussaïef, Leila (2010), “The Influence of Sustainable Development on Retail Store Image”, *International Business Research*, Vol. 3 No. 3, pp. 100-110.
19. Campo, Katia and Gijbrecchts, Els (2004) “Should retailers adjust their micro-marketing strategies to the type of outlet? An application to location-based store space allocation in limited and full-service grocery stores”, *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Vol. 11 Iss: 6, pp. 369-383.
20. Cassab, Harold (2009), “Investigating the dynamics of service attributes in multi-channel environments”, *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Vol. 16 Iss: 1, pp. 25-30.
21. Chakraborty, Anasua (2013), “Retail Industry”, available at: <http://info.shine.com/industry/retail/7.html>.
22. Chen, Shih-Mei and Huddleston, Patricia (2009), “A comparison of four strategies to promote fair trade products”, *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, Vol. 37 Iss: 4, pp. 336-345.
23. Ciotti, Gregory (2013), “15 Customer Service Skills that Every Employee needs”, February, available at: <http://www.helpscout.net/blog/customer-service-skills/>.

24. Coca-Stefaniak, J. Andres; Parker, Cathy and Rees, Patricia (2010), "Localisation as a marketing strategy for small retailers", *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, Vol. 38 Iss: 9, pp. 677-697.
25. Cohen, Heidi (2011), "30 Branding Definitions", Branding, available at: <http://heidicohen.com/30-branding-definitions/>.
26. Copper, D. and Schindler, P. S. (2006), *Marketing Research: Concept & Case*, Tata McGraw Hill Publishing Co. Ltd., Delhi.
27. Corporate Catalyst India (2012), "A report on Indian Retail Industry", available at http://www.rasci.in/downloads/2012/Retail_Industry_India_2012.pdf, pp. 13-14
28. Cronbach, L. (1951), "Coefficient alpha and the internal structure of tests", *Psychometrika*, 16, pp. 297-334
29. D&B (2014), "Indian Retail Industry: Challenges, Opportunities & Outlook", available at <https://www.dnb.co.in/IndianRetailIndustry/overview.asp>.
30. Darley, William K.; Luethge, Denise J. and Thatte, Ashish (2008), "Exploring the relationship of perceived automotive salesperson attributes, customer satisfaction and intentions to automotive service department patronage: The moderating role of customer gender", *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Vol. 15 Iss: 6, pp. 469-479.
31. Datta, Palto Ranjan; Akwensivie, Divine Mawuli and Akwensivie, Gad (2008), "Store design: the effect of Iceland's refit strategy on food consumers", *Journal of Business & Retail Management Research*, Vol.1 Issue1, October.
32. Davidson, William R.; Sweeney, Daniel J. and Stampfl, Ronald W. (1988), *Retailing Management*, John Wiley & Sons.
33. Demoulin, Nathalie T. M. and Zidda, Pietro (2009), "Drivers of Customers' Adoption and Adoption Timing of a New Loyalty Card in the Grocery Retail Market", *Journal of Retailing*, Vol. 85 Iss: 3, pp. 391-405.
34. Demoulin, Nathalie T.M. and Zidda, Pietro (2008), "On the impact of loyalty cards on store loyalty: Does the customers' satisfaction with the reward scheme matter?", *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Vol. 15 Iss: 5, pp 386-398.
35. Dharni, Khushdeep and Chawla, Madhur (2012), "Antecedents of IT effectiveness in Indian retail sector", *International Journal of Electronic Marketing and Retailing*, Vol. 5, No.1, pp. 32-47.

36. Dhillon, Jaskaran Singh; Joshi, Madhur and Verma, Ramita (2012), "Emergence of Retailing Sector in India: Challenges and Opportunities", *IJMBS*, Vol. 2, Issue 4, pp. 02-03.
37. Dhume, Sudheer (2012), "Service Quality Dimensions In Retail Settings: An Empirical Study at Selected Apparel Specialty Stores of Mumbai", *International Journal of Research in Commerce, Economics & Management*, Vol. 2 Iss: 2, pp. 01-05.
38. Diallo, Mbaye Fall (2012), "Effects of store image and store brand price-image on store brand purchase intention: Application to an emerging market", *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Vol. 19 Iss: 3, pp. 360-367.
39. Dikshit, Anand (2011), "The Uneasy Compromise - Indian Retail", *The Wall Street Journal*, August, 12, pp. 05-22.
40. Diona, Delphine and Arnould, Eric (2011), "Retail Luxury Strategy: Assembling Charisma through Art and Magic", *Journal of Retailing*, Vol. 87 Iss: 4, pp. 502-520.
41. Esbjerg, Lars; Jensen, Birger Boutrup; Bech-Larsen, Tino; Barcellos, Marcia Dutra de; Boztug, Yasemin and Grunert, Klaus G. (2012), "An integrative conceptual framework for analysing customer satisfaction with shopping trip experiences in grocery retailing", *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Vol. 19 Iss: 4, pp. 445-456.
42. Etgar, Michael and Rachman-Moore, Dalia (2011), "The relationship between national cultural dimensions and retail format strategies", *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Vol. 18 Iss: 5, pp. 397-404.
43. Evans, Jody; Bridson, Kerrie; Byrom, John and Medway, Dominic (2008), "Revisiting retail internationalisation: Drivers, impediments and business strategy", *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, Vol. 36 Iss: 4, pp. 260- 280.
44. FICCI (2011), "Sector Profile", Federation of Indian Chambers of Commerce and Industry, available at http://www.ficci.com/sector/33/Project_docs/Sector-prof.pdf.
45. Fonseca, Jaime R. S. (2009), "Customer satisfaction study via a latent segment model", *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Vol. 16 Iss: 5, pp. 352-359.
46. Fornell, C. (1992), "A national customer satisfaction barometer: the Swedish experience", *Journal of Marketing*, Vol. 56, No. 1, pp. 6-21.

47. Fullerton, Gordon (2005), "The service quality–loyalty relationship in retail services: does commitment matter?", *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Vol. 12 Iss: 2, pp. 99-111.
48. Gauri, Dinesh Kumar; Trivedi, Minakshi and Grewal, Dhruv (2008), "Understanding the Determinants of Retail Strategy: An Empirical Analysis", *Journal of Retailing*, Vol. 84 Iss: 3, pp. 256-267.
49. Glueck, W. F. and Lauch, L. R. (1984), *Business Policy and Strategic Management*, McGraw-Hill, New York.
50. González-Benito, Óscar and Martos-Partal, Mercedes (2012), "Role of Retailer Positioning and Product Category on the Relationship between Store Brand Consumption and Store Loyalty", *Journal of Retailing*, Vol. 88 Iss: 2, pp. 236-249.
51. Goodrich, Kendall and Ramsey, Rosemary (2012), "Are consumers with disabilities receiving the services they need?", *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Vol. 19 Iss: 1, pp. 88-97.
52. Grewal, Dhruv; Roggeveen, Anne L. and Tsiros, Michael (2008), "The Effect of Compensation on Repurchase Intentions in Service Recovery", *Journal of Retailing*, Vol. 84 Iss: 4, pp. 424-434.
53. Haemoun, Oh (1999), "Service quality, customer satisfaction and customer value: A holistic perspective", *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, Vol. 18 Iss: 1, pp. 67-82.
54. Hamburg, C. and Koschate, N. (2004), "How do consumers react to price increases", *International Journal of Research in Marketing*, Vol. 26 No. 4.
55. Handa, Vidushi and Grover, Navneet (2012), "Retail Sector in India: Issues & Challenges" *ZENITH International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, Vol. 2, Issue 5, pp. 6.
56. Hansen, Torben; Jensen, Jan Møller and Solgaard, Hans Stubbe (2011), "When supermarket consumers get stocked in the middle", *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, Vol. 39 Iss: 11, pp. 836-850.
57. Harper, Douglas (2015), "Retail", *Online Etymology Dictionary*, available at: <http://www.etymonline.com/index.php?term=retail>.
58. Hoffman, K. Douglas and Bateson, John E. G. (2007), *Services Marketing: Concepts, Strategies, & Cases*, Thomson South-Western, India, 3rd Ed.

59. Huddleston, Patricia; Whipple, Judith; Mattick, Rachel Nye and Lee, So Jung (2009), "Customer satisfaction in food retailing: comparing specialty and conventional grocery stores", *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, Vol. 37 Iss: 1, pp. 63-80.
60. Humphrey, Albert (2005), "SWOT Analysis for Management Consulting", *SRI Alumni Newsletter*, December.
61. Hyper One Center (2011), *Hyper Market*, Malls Guide, available at http://www.mallsguide.com/ShoppingCenter.aspx?sc_id=1572&title=Hyper%20One%20Center.
62. IBEF (2015), "Retail Industry in India", India Brand Equity Foundation, available at: <http://www.ibef.org/industry/retail-india.aspx>.
63. Ilonen, Laura; Wren, Jody; Gabrielsson, Mika and Salimäki, Markku (2011), "The role of branded retail in manufacturers' international strategy", *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, Vol. 39 Iss: 6, pp. 414-433.
64. Jayawardhena, Chanaka and Farrell, Andrew M. (2011), "Effects of retail employees' behaviours on customers' service evaluation", *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, Vol. 39 Iss: 3, pp. 203-217.
65. Jhureley, Ashutosh (2011), "6P's of Retail leading to 7th P – Profit", *Multi-channel Retail & Supply Chain*, available at: <http://ashutoshjhureley.blogspot.in/2010/09/6ps-of-retail-leading-to-7th-p-profit.html>.
66. Joo, Mingyu; Mazumdar, Tridib and Raj, S. P. (2012) "Bidding Strategies and Consumer Savings in NYOP Auctions", *Journal of Retailing*, Vol. 88 Iss: 1, pp. 180-188.
67. Kantabutra, Sooksan (2011), "Examining store manager effects in consumer and staff satisfaction: Evidence from Thailand", *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Vol. 18 Iss: 1, pp. 46-57.
68. Kazmi, A. (2007), *Business Policy and Strategic Management*, Tata McGraw Hill Publishing Company Limited, New Delhi.
69. Khraim, Hamza Salim; Khraim, Aymen Salim; Al-Kaidah, FirasMuslam and AL-Qurash, Daher (2011), "Jordanian Consumer's Evaluation of Retail Store Attributes: The Influence of Consumer Religiosity", *International Journal of Marketing Studies*, Vol. 3 No. 4, pp. 105-116.

70. Kleijnen, Mirella; Ruyter, Ko de and Wetzels, Martin (2007), "An assessment of value creation in mobile service delivery and the moderating role of time consciousness", *Journal of Retailing*, Vol. 83 Iss: 1, pp. 33-46.
71. Kohijoki, Anna-Maija (2011), "The effect of aging on consumer disadvantage in grocery retail services among the Finnish elderly", *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Vol. 18 Iss: 4, pp. 370-377.
72. Koistinen, Katri and Järvinen, Raija (2009), "Consumer observations on channel choices—Competitive strategies in Finnish grocery retailing", *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Vol. 16 Iss: 4, pp. 260-270.
73. Kukar-Kinney, Monika; Ridgwaya, Nancy M. and Monroe, Kent B. (2012), "The Role of Price in the Behaviour and Purchase Decisions of Compulsive Buyers", *Journal of Retailing*, Vol. 88 Iss: 1, pp. 63-71.
74. Kukar-Kinney, Monika; Xia, Lan and Monroe, Kent B. (2007), "Consumers' perceptions of the fairness of price-matching refund policies", *Journal of Retailing*, Vol. 83, Iss: 3, pp. 325-337.
75. Levy, M.; Weitz, B. and Pandit, A. (2012), *Retailing Management*, Tata McGraw Hill Education Private Limited, New Delhi.
76. Likert, R. (1970), "A Technique for the Measurement of Attitude", In Gene F. summer ed., *Attitude Measurement*, Chicago: Rand McNally.
77. Lindquist, Jay D. and Sirgy, M. Joseph (2003), *Shopper, Buyer and Consumer Behaviour – Theory and Marketing Applications*, Atomic Dog Publishing, USA, 2nd Edition.
78. Lonarkar, Pramod Pandurangrao and Gore, Parmeshwar (2012), "Change in Retail Shopping Behaviour: Why and for Whom?", *International Journal of Research in Commerce, Economics & Management*, Vol. 2 Iss: 1, pp. 108-111.
79. Loundon, David L. and Della Bitta, Albert J. (2002), *Consumer Behaviour*, Tata McGraw-Hill Publishing Company Limited, New Delhi, 4th Ed.
80. Lu, Yan and Seock, Yoo-Kyoung (2008), "The influence of grey consumers' service quality perception on satisfaction and store loyalty behaviour", *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, Vol. 36 Iss: 11, pp. 901-918.
81. Madaan, KVS (2011), *Fundamental of Retailing*, Tata McGraw Hill Education Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi.

82. Mahajan, A. C. (2015), "Retail eCommerce Sales in India 2014 – 2018", *Dazeinfo*, January 7.
83. Mai, Enping (Shirley); Yang, Jun and Chen, Haozhe (2011), "Primary product network size on complementary product sales: Moderating effects of customer characteristics", *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, Vol. 39 Iss: 11, pp. 851-866.
84. Majumder, Sanjoy (2011), "Changing the way Indians shop", *BBC News*, November, 25,
85. Manning, Kenneth C. and Sprott, David E. (2007) "Multiple unit price promotions and their effects on quantity purchase intentions", *Journal of Retailing*, Vol. 83 Iss: 4, pp. 411-421.
86. Martenson, Rita (2007), "Corporate brand image, satisfaction and store loyalty: A study of the store as a brand, store brands and manufacturer brands", *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, Vol. 35 Iss: 7, pp. 544-555.
87. Martínez-Ruiz, María Pilar; Jiménez-Zarco, Ana Isabel and Cascio, Robert (2011), "Assessing the maximum level of customer satisfaction in grocery stores: A comparison between Spain and the USA", *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, Vol. 39 Iss: 7, pp. 504-521.
88. Mazaheri, Ebrahim; Basil, Debra Z.; Yanamandram, Venkata and Daroczi, Zoltan (2011), "The impact of pre-existing attitude and conflict management style on customer satisfaction with service recovery", *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Vol. 18 Iss: 3, pp. 235-245.
89. McDaniel, C. D. and Gates, R. H. (2001), *Marketing Research Essential*, Thomson South-Western.
90. Medina, Cayetano and Rufin, Ramón (2009), "The mediating effect of innovation in the relationship between retailers' strategic orientations and performance", *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, Vol. 37 Iss: 7, pp. 629- 655.
91. Meyer-Waarden, Lars (2007), "The effects of loyalty programs on customer lifetime duration and share of wallet", *Journal of Retailing*, Vol. 83, Iss: 2, pp. 223-236.
92. Mohan, Geetha; Sivakumaran, Bharadhwaj and Sharma, Piyush (2012), "Store environment's impact on variety seeking behaviour" *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Vol. 19 Iss: 4, pp. 419-428.

93. Moriarty, Mike; Peng, Althea; Rhim, Helen and Salman, Fabiola (2013), "Global Retailers: Cautiously Aggressive or Aggressively Cautious?", *The 2014 Global Retail Development Index*, A.T. Kearney Consultants, USA.
94. Moriarty, Mike; Rhim, Helen; Salman, Fabiola and Ben-Shabat, Hana (2014), "Full Steam Ahead for Global Retailers", *The 2014 Global Retail Development Index*, A.T. Kearney Consultants, USA.
95. MSEDCL (2015) "MSEDCL locations", available at: http://www.mahadiscom.in/maps/map_index.shtm.
96. Murthi, B.P.S. and Rao, Ram C. (2012), "Price Awareness and Consumers' Use of Deals in Brand Choice", *Journal of Retailing*, Vol. 88 Iss: 1, pp. 34-46.
97. Muzondo, Noeland and Mutandwa, Edward (2011), "The Seven Ps of Marketing and Choice of main Grocery Store in a Hyperinflationary Economy", *Contemporary Marketing Review*, Vol. 1 (9), pp. 01-18.
98. Nair, Suja R. (2011), *Retailing Management*, Himalaya Publishing House, India.
99. Nath, Rachna and Gupt, Akash (2012), "Winds of change Retail reforms in India", PWC, available at [https://www.pwc.in/en_IN/in/assets/pdfs/industries/retail-andconsumer/Winds_of_change_Retail_Reforms_in_India_final_Sept_2012_\(with_RM\).pdf](https://www.pwc.in/en_IN/in/assets/pdfs/industries/retail-andconsumer/Winds_of_change_Retail_Reforms_in_India_final_Sept_2012_(with_RM).pdf).
100. Neelankavil, J. P. (2007), *International Business Research*, M. E. Sharpe Inc., New York.
101. Netemeyer, Richard G. and Maxham III, James G. (2007), "Employee versus supervisor ratings of performance in the retail customer service sector: Differences in predictive validity for customer outcomes", *Journal of Retailing*, Vol. 83 Iss: 1, pp. 131-145.
102. Ngobo, Paul-Valentin (2011), "Private label share, branding strategy and store loyalty", *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Vol. 18 Iss: 4, pp. 259-270.
103. Ogden, James R. and Ogden, Denise T. (2004), *Retailing: Integrated Retail Management*, Houghton Mifflin.
104. Omar, Ogenyi and Abisoye, Kareem O. (2008), "The Role of Price as a Determining Factor in Grocery Retail Store Patronage", *Journal of Business & Retail Management Research*, Vol. 2, Issue 2.
105. Omholt, Tore (2002), "Strategic Reconfiguration and Management of Retail Centers Creating Competitive Advantage through Communicative Competence", *Asian Academy of Management Journal*, Vol. 7 No. 2, pp. 87-101.

106. Orth, Ulrich R. and Green, Mark T. (2009), "Consumer loyalty to family versus non-family business: The roles of store image, trust and satisfaction", *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Vol. 16 Iss: 4, pp. 248-259.
107. Padilla, Charlette and Eastlick, Mary Ann (2009), "Exploring urban retailing and CBD revitalisation strategies", *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, Vol. 37 Iss: 1, pp. 7-23.
108. Parasuraman, A., Grewal, D. and Krishnan, R. (2007), *Marketing Research*, Biztantra, New Delhi, India.
109. Perner, Lars (2008), "Consumer Behaviour", Department of Marketing, Marshall School of Business, University of Southern California, USA.
110. Phillips, B S (1966), *Social Research Strategy & Tactics*, McMillan Publishing Company Inc., US.
111. Phulia, Anita Bindal and Sharma, Monika (2014), "Role of Retail sector in India", *International Journal of Research*, Vol. 1, Issue 8, pp. 152-158.
112. Porter, M. E. (1985), *Competitive Advantage: Creating and Sustaining Superior Performance*, Free Press, New York.
113. Pradhan, S. (2009), *Retailing Management – Text & Cases*, Tata McGraw Hill Education Private Limited, New Delhi.
114. Pradhan, Swapna (2011), *Retail Merchandising*, Tata Mcgraw Hill Education Private Ltd., New Delhi, India.
115. Prasad, B. V. S. (2013), "E-tailing in India", *Abhinav- National Monthly Refereed Journal of Research in Commerce & Management*, Vol. 2, Issue 7, pp. 20-28.
116. Prasad, Cherukuri Jayasankara and Aryasri, Ankiseti Ramachandra (2011) "Effect of shopper attributes on retail format choice behaviour for food and grocery retailing in India", *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, Vol. 39 Iss: 1, pp. 68-86.
117. Prasad, Priya and Harikumar, P. N. (2013), "Indian Retail Sector reforms since liberation", *Caarmal Journal of Management Research*, Vol. 1, Issue 2, pp. 94.
118. PTI (2014), "Indian retail market to reach 47 lakh crore by 2016-17: study", *The Economic Times*, 11, February.
119. Rahman, Tazyn (2012), "Organised Retail Industry in India – Opportunities and Challenges", *International Journal of Research in Finance & Marketing*, Volume 2, Issue 2, pp. 82-94.

120. Rahman, Tazyn (2012), "Organised Retail Industry in India – Opportunities and Challenges", *International Journal of Research in Finance & Marketing*, Vol. 2, Iss: 2, pp. 82-94.
121. Rai, Manish and Gopal, R. (2014), "A study on the feasibility of retail store location for TATA Tesco convenience store in Navi Mumbai", *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, International Business Research Conference, IES Management College and Research Centre, Mumbai, India, Special Issue, pp. 35-39.
122. Rajagopal (2011), "Impact of radio advertisements on buying behaviour of urban commuters", *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, Vol. 39 Iss: 7, pp. 480-503.
123. Ranganath, N. Santosh; Kama, Raju T. and Rao, P. Trinadha (2011), "Emerging Role of Technology in Retail Sector", *International Journal of Research in Computer Application & Management*, Vol. 1 Iss. 5, pp. 71-75.
124. Rani, A. Sandhya (2012), "Retailing Strategies for Customer Satisfaction: Comparative Study of More and Food World", *International Journal of Research in Commerce & Management*, Vol. 3 Iss: 5, pp. 135-136.
125. Rao, K. Rama Mohana and Manikyam, K. Ratna (2012), "Customers' Experience with Small Scale Retail Stores - An Empirical Study", *International Journal of Research in Commerce & Management*, Vol. 3 Iss. 5, pp. 86-89.
126. Richards, Timothy J.; Gómez, Miguel I. and Pofahl Geoffrey (2012), "A Multiple-discrete/Continuous Model of Price Promotion", *Journal of Retailing*, Vol. 88 Iss: 2, pp. 206–225.
127. Ripley, Louise M. (2015), "Selecting an Overall Positioning Strategy", *Introductory Marketing*, available at: <http://www.yorku.ca/lripley/imUsegment.htm>.
128. Ruiz, María Pilar Martínez and Descals, Alejandro Mollá (2008), "Retail price promotion influences for product varieties in grocery stores: evidence from Spain", *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, Vol. 36 Iss: 6, pp. 494-517.
129. Sánchez-Fernández, Raquel and Iniesta-Bonillo, M. Ángeles (2009), "Efficiency and quality as economic dimensions of perceived value: Conceptualisation, measurement, and effect on satisfaction", *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Vol. 16 Iss: 6, pp. 425-433.

130. Sayed, Md Abu (2015), "Merchandising: The magic word", *Textile Apex*, available at: <http://textileapex.blogspot.in/2014/09/merchandising-magic-word.html>.
131. Schau, Hope Jensen; Dellande, Stephanie and Gilly, Mary C. (2007), "The impact of code switching on service encounters", *Journal of Retailing*, Vol. 83 Iss: 1, pp. 65-78.
132. Sekaran, U. (2003), *Research Methods for Business: A Skill Building Approach*, John Wiley & Sons Inc., New York.
133. Shaikh, Anwar; Alvi, Sajid and Jagtap, Manisha (2012), "A Study of the Factors Influencing the Buyer's Decision to Buy a Particular Product with reference to selected Supermarkets in Pune City", *Indian Journal of Commerce & Management Studies*, Special Issue, Jan., pp. 7-15.
134. Shankar, Venkatesh; Inman, J. Jeffrey; Mantrala, Murali; Kelley, Eileen and Rizley, Ross (2011), "Innovations in Shopper Marketing: Current Insights and Future Research Issues", *Journal of Retailing*, Vol. 87, Supplement 1, pp. S29-S42.
135. Sheng, Shibin and Pan, Yue (2009), "Bundling as a new product introduction strategy: The role of brand image and bundle features", *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Vol. 16 Iss: 5, pp. 367-376.
136. Sikri, Sunita and Wadhwa, Dipti (2012), "Growth and Challenges of Retail Industry in India: An Analysis", *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Management Review*, Vol. 1, Issue 1, pp. 01-14.
137. Singh, Harvinder; Chadha, S.K. and Rishi, Bikramjit (2010), "Service quality measurement and its implications: a case study of Vishal Mega Mart", *International Journal of Services and Standards*, Vol. 6 No. 2, pp. 150-169.
138. Smith, Rhonda L. (2006), "The Australian grocery industry: a competition perspective", *The Australian Journal of Agricultural and Resource Economics*, Vol. 50, pp. 33-50.
139. Söderlund, Magnus and Julander, Claes-Robert (2009), "Physical attractiveness of the service worker in the moment of truth and its effects on customer satisfaction", *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Vol. 16 Iss: 3, pp. 216-226.
140. Söderlund, Magnus and Rosengren, Sara (2007), "Receiving word-of-mouth from the service customer: An emotion-based effectiveness assessment", *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Vol. 14 Iss: 2, pp. 123-136.

141. Söderlund, Magnus and Rosengren, Sara (2010), "The happy versus unhappy service worker in the service encounter: Assessing the impact on customer satisfaction", *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Vol. 17 Iss: 2, pp. 161-169.
142. Standop, Dirk and Grunwald, Guido (2009), "How to solve product-harm crises in retailing?: Empirical insights from service recovery and negative publicity research", *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, Vol. 37 Iss: 11, pp. 915-932.
143. Stanton, A. (2015), "Store Design Layout", available at: http://www.radford.edu/~astanton/mktg343/store_design_layout_visual_merchandising.ppt&usd=2&usg=AFQjCNHbo1zz4IPbL3qzykLjaXvPVeUbBw.
144. Sun, Jing and Ma, Jingting (2009), "The Study of China Retail Business Development Strategy", *International Journal of Marketing Studies*, Vol. 1 No. 1, pp. 19-22.
145. Suwelack, Thomas; Hogleve, Jens and Hoyer, Wayne D. (2011), "Understanding Money-Back Guarantees: Cognitive, Affective, and Behavioural Outcomes", *Journal of Retailing*, Vol. 87 Iss: 4, pp. 462-478.
146. Swinyard, William R (2003), "The effects of salesperson mood, shopper behaviour, and store type on customer service", *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Vol. 10 Iss: 6, pp. 323-333.
147. Tanabe, Mario; Angelo, Claudio Felisoni De and Alexander, Nicholas (2004), "The effectiveness of strategic planning: competitiveness in the Brazilian supermarket sector", *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Vol. 11 Iss: 1, pp. 51-59.
148. Thakor, Mrugank V.; Suri, Rajneesh and Saleh, Katayoun (2008), "Effects of service setting and other consumers' age on the service perceptions of young consumers", *Journal of Retailing*, Vol. 84 Iss: 2, pp. 137-149.
149. *The Hindu* (2014), "Indian retail market to reach 47 lakh crore by 2016-17: study", 11, February.
150. *The Hindu Business Line* (2014), "Indian retail market set to touch \$865 billion by 2023", 27 February.
151. The planning Factory Limited (2014) "What is Merchandise Planning?", available at: http://www.planfact.co.uk/what_is_merchandise_planning.htm.

152. Thiruvankadam, T. and Panchanatham, N. (2011), "Influence Of Demography on Store Patronage Behaviour of Chennai Shoppers", *International Journal of Research in Computer Application & Management*, Vol. 1 Iss. 5, pp. 39-42.
153. Torres-Moraga, Eduardo; Jara-Sarrua, Luis and Moneva, Jose M. (2008) "Measuring supermarket service quality: proposal for a scale", *International Journal of Services and Standards*, Vol. 4 No. 1, pp. 81-96.
154. Tyagi, Rahul (2008), "Supply Chain Implications of Customer-Centric Merchandising Strategy", *Journal of Business & Retail Management Research*, Vol. 2 Issue. 2.
155. Vázquez-Carrasco, Rosario and Foxall, Gordon R. (2006), "Influence of personality traits on satisfaction, the perception of relational benefits, and loyalty in a personal service context", *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Vol. 13 Iss: 3, pp. 205-219.
156. Vesel, Patrick and Zabkar, Vesna (2009), "Managing customer loyalty through the mediating role of satisfaction in the DIY retail loyalty program", *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Vol.16 Iss: 5, pp. 396-406.
157. Vetrivel, T. (2011), "Customer Relationship Management in Retailing with Special Reference to Fast Moving Consumer Goods In Erode District, Tamilnadu, India", *International Journal of Research in Computer Application & Management*, Vol. 1 Iss. 2, pp. 47-52.
158. Walker, James L. (1995), "Service encounter satisfaction: conceptualised", *Journal of Services Marketing*, Vol. 9 No.1, pp. 5-14.
159. Watchravesringkan, Kittichai (Tu) and Punyapiroje, Chompunuch (2011), "A comparative investigation of consumers' attitudes toward marketing practices of hypermarket retailers in Thailand", *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, Vol. 39 Iss: 9, pp. 702-720.
160. Waters, Shari (2015), "Retailing", *About Money*, available at: <http://retail.about.com/od/glossary/g/retailing.htm>.
161. Watson, Stevie (2012), "Consumer responses to service situations: Tests for main and interaction effects", *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Vol. 19 Iss: 3, pp. 287-296.
162. White, Allyn; Breazeale, Michael and Collier, Joel E. (2012), "The Effects of Perceived Fairness on Customer Responses to Retailer SST Push Policies", *Journal of Retailing*, Vol. 88 Iss: 2, pp. 250-261.

163. Wiles, Michael A. (2007), "The effect of customer service on retailers' shareholder wealth: The role of availability and reputation cues", *Journal of Retailing*, Vol. 83, Iss: 1, pp. 19-31.
164. Yan, Ruiliang and Pei, Zhi (2009), "Retail services and firm profit in a dual-channel market", *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Vol. 16 Iss: 4, pp. 306-314.
165. Yi, Y. (1991), "A critical review of customer satisfaction", *Review of Marketing*, American Marketing Association, Chicago II, pp. 68-123.
166. Zielke, Stephan (2008), "Exploring asymmetric effects in the formation of retail price satisfaction", *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Vol. 15 Iss: 5, pp. 335-347.
167. Zolfagharian, Mohammad Ali and Paswan, Audhesh (2009), "Perceived service innovativeness, consumer trait innovativeness and patronage intention", *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Vol. 16 Iss: 2, pp. 155-162.

APPENDIX

INSTITUTIONAL QUESTIONNAIRE

Name _____
Designation _____
Name of Store _____
Place of Store _____

1. What are your variables to segment the market?

- Geographic Segmentation
- Demographic Segmentation
- Psychographic Segmentation
- Behavioural Segmentation

If Geographic-

- **Region-** North, West, South, East, Central
- **Area-** Urban, Suburban, Rural

If Demographic-

- **Age-** infants, below 5 years, 5-10, 11-20, 21-34, 35-49, 50-60, 60+
- **Family Life Cycle-** young, single; young, married, no children; young, married, child.....
- **Gender-** male and female
- **Income-** low, lower middle, middle, upper middle, and high
- **Occupation-** unskilled worker, skilled worker, students, self-employed, homemaker, retired
- **Education-** illiterate, school SSC/HSC, non-graduate, graduate / postgraduate (general/professional)
- **Religion-** Hinduism, Islam, Catholic, Sikh

If Psychographic-

- **Life Style-** culture oriented, sport oriented, outdoor oriented
- **Personality-** compulsive, gregarious, authoritarian, ambitious, aggressive, shy, emotional

If Behavioural-

- **User Status-** non-user, ex-user, potential user, first time user, regular user
- **Usage Rate-** light, medium, heavy
- **Loyalty Status-** none, medium, strong, absolute
- **Readiness Stage-** unaware, aware, informed, interested, desirous, intending to buy
- **Attitude towards Product-** enthusiastic, positive, indifferent, negative, hostile
- **Occasions-** regular, special
- **Benefits-** quality, service, economy, speed
- **Perceived Risk-** high, medium, low
- **Innovativeness-** innovator, early adopter, early majority, late majority, laggard

2. Which segmentation strategy do you use & why?

- Single Segment Concentration Strategy
- Product Specialisation Strategy
- Selective Specialisation Strategy
- Market Specialisation Strategy
- Full Market Coverage Strategy

3. Which targeting strategy do you use & why?

- Undifferentiating targeting strategy or mass retailing (no specific mix)
- Differentiated targeting strategy or selective retailing (specific mix)
- Concentrated targeting strategy or niche retailing (small but profitable)
- Micro (local or individual) targeting strategy or customised retailing
- Multi-segment targeting strategy

4. Which Positioning Strategy do you use & why?

- More for more
- Less for much less
- More for the same
- More for less
- The same for less

5. What kind of retail marketing strategy do you adopt?

- Market penetration
- Retail format development
- Market expansion
- Diversification

6. Which defensive strategy do you use?

- Preemptive defense (more aggressive launch an attack on enemy)
- Counteroffensive defense (provides an opportunity to attacker to attack frontally)
- Flanking defense (serve as a defensive corner for weak front)
- Position defense (strategy to retain position)
- Mobile defense (stretches its domain to new territories)
- Contraction defense (giving up weaker territories or activities)

7. With which tool you perform Store-Level Planning.

- SWOT analysis
- PEST analysis
- Five force analysis
- ETOP analysis

Is SWOT analysis the tool? Yes/No

If 'Yes' please, specify SWOT Analysis-
Strengths_____

Weaknesses_____

Opportunities_____

Threats_____

Is PEST analysis the tool? Yes/No

If 'Yes' please, specify PEST Analysis-
Political & Legal Forces_____

EconomicForces_____

Socio-culturalForces_____

TechnologicalForces_____

Is Five Forces analysis the tool? Yes/No

If 'Yes' please, specify Five Force Analysis-
Forces of Competition created by Rivalry _____

Potential Threats from New Entrants _____

Potential Threats from the Firms, which provide Substitute Products & Services _____

Supplier's Bargaining Powers _____

Buyer's Bargaining Powers _____

Is ETOP analysis the tool? Yes/No

If 'Yes' please, specify-
Market _____

Technological _____

Suppliers _____

Economic _____

Regulatory _____

Political _____

Socio-cultural _____

International _____

–

8. With the Boston Matrix where you see your retail store at present?

- Star (i.e. high market share, high rate of market growth)
- Cash Cow (i.e. high market share, low rate of market growth)
- Dog (i.e. low market share, low rate of market growth)
- Question Mark (i.e. low market share, high rate of market growth)

9. Which Generic Strategy do you follow at the retail store level?

- Cost Leadership (i.e. broadly target with lower cost)
- Differentiation (i.e. broadly target with differentiation)
- Cost Focus (i.e. narrowly target with lower cost)
- Differentiation Focus (i.e. narrowly target with differentiation)

10. What problems do you face in framing overall retailing strategy-

11. What are your core advantages?

- Low cost
- Efficient operations
- Strong private brands
- Fashion reputation
- Category dominance
- Image

12. Please rate the following variables of the retail marketing mix on the importance scale.

Sr. No.	Variables	Importance Scale*			
		4	3	2	1
1.	Product (Merchandise)				
2.	Price				
3.	Promotion				
4.	Premises / Place				
5.	Personnel / People				
6.	Presentation				
7.	Physical Evidence				
* 4- extremely important, 3- important, 2- partially important, 1- not important					

13. How do you manage your retail marketing-mix?

14. Which types of brands are available in your store?

- Multi-brands
- Exclusive brands
- Heterogeneous mix of brands
- Mix of private label & other brands

15. Which of the following brands are offered by your store?

- Generic brands
- Local brands
- National (manufacturer) brands
- International brands
- Private (store) brands
- Exclusive brands
- Copycat brands

16. What are the factors important when planning merchandise?

- Target market
- Goods & service growth potential
- Fashion trends
- Your image
- Competition
- Customer segments
- Responsiveness to customers
- Amount of investment
- Profitability
- Risk

Please rate the factors on the importance scale.

Sr. No.	Factors	Importance Scale*			
		4	3	2	1
1.	Target market				
2.	Goods & service growth potential				
3.	Trends (fashion)				
4.	Your image				
5.	Competition				
6.	Customer segments				
7.	Responsiveness to customers				
8.	Amount of investment				
9.	Profitability				
10.	Risk				

* 4- extremely important, 3- important, 2- partially important, 1- not important

17. What are the factors important to you when planning merchandise quality?

- Target market
- Competition
- Your image
- Store location
- Stock turnover
- Profitability
- The customer service offered
- Personnel
- Perceived goods/service benefits
- Manufactures vs. private brands

Rate the factors on the importance scale.

Sr. No.	Factors	Importance Scale*			
		4	3	2	1
1.	Target market				
2.	Competition				
3.	Your image				
4.	Store location				
5.	Stock turnover				
6.	Profitability				
7.	Manufacturers Vs private brands				
8.	The customer service offered				
9.	Personnel				
10.	Perceived goods/service benefits				
* 4- extremely important, 3- important, 2- partially important, 1- not important					

18. Which of the following product assortment (retail assortment strategy) is adopted by your store?

- **A narrow variety & a shallow assortment** (few goods/service categories & a limited assortment in each category)
- **A wide variety & a shallow assortment** (many goods/service categories & a limited assortment in each category)
- **A narrow variety & a deep assortment** (few goods/service categories & a large assortment in each category)
- **A wide variety & a deep assortment** (many goods/service categories & a large assortment in each category)

19. How do you categorise the products/brands?

- Size
- Quality
- Discounts
- Colour
- Brand
- Schemes
- Design
- Customer Segment
- Price
- Customer Needs

20. Which categories of merchandise does your store offer?

- Basic (Staples)
- Consumer Durable
- Fashion
- Seasonal

21. Do you provide a wide range of products (merchandise) in each category?

Yes/No

If 'Yes' please, specify-

22. Do you provide different product (merchandise) lines in each category? Yes/No

If 'Yes' please, specify-

23. Do you provide different brands in each category of merchandise? Yes/No

If 'Yes' please, specify-

24. Do you provide customised products (merchandise) to customers? Yes/No

If 'Yes' please, specify-

25. Do you provide newly launched products/brands? Yes/No

If 'Yes' please, specify-

26. Do you provide unique products (merchandise) to the customers? Yes/No

If 'Yes' please, specify-

27. Do you provide complementary products (merchandise) / items? Yes/No

If 'Yes' please, specify-

28. How do you handle unprofitable products & services-

- Find a way to make them profitable
- Determine if they are related to profitable business retailing relationships
- Drop them from the assortment
- Others
- None

29. Who are your main suppliers?

- Manufacturers
- Wholesalers

- Merchant Brokers
- Commission Agents
- Trade Shows
- The Cooperatively Owned Offices
- The Independent Owned Offices
- The Individually Owned Offices

30. What type of discounts your stores get from suppliers?

- Trade
- Quantity
- Promotional
- Promotional
- Cash

31. Which characteristics are important for you while selecting a vendor?

- Reliability
- Price-quality
- Order processing time
- Exclusive rights
- Functions provided
- Information
- Ethics
- Guarantee
- Credit
- Long-term relationship
- Reorders
- Markup
- Innovativeness
- Local advertising
- Investment
- Risk

Please rate the characteristics on the importance scale.

Sr. No.	Characteristics	Importance Scale*			
		4	3	2	1
1.	Reliability				
2.	Price-quality				
3.	Order processing time				
4.	Exclusive rights				
5.	Functions provided				
6.	Information				
7.	Ethics				
8.	Guarantee				
9.	Credit				
10.	Long-term relationship				
11.	Reorders				
12.	Markup				
13.	Innovativeness				
14.	Local advertising				
15.	Investment				
16.	Risk				
* 4- extremely important, 3- important, 2- partially important, 1- not important					

32. Do you make stock planning?

Yes/No

If 'Yes', for how much time-

- Weekly planning
- Monthly planning
- Yearly planning
- Long term planning

33. Do you work on partner relationship with your suppliers/vendors? Yes/No

34. What is your main objective of Pricing?

- Survival
- Maximising current profit
- Maximising market share
- Maximising market skimming
- Product quality leadership

35. Which pricing approach do you follow to set the price?

- Demand-oriented pricing
- Cost-oriented pricing
- Competition-oriented pricing
- Leadership-oriented pricing

36. Which pricing strategy do you use?

- Market-skimming pricing
- Market-penetration pricing
- Variable (zone) pricing
- Markup pricing
- Target return pricing
- Perceived value pricing
- Going rate pricing
- Value pricing
- Everyday low pricing (EDLP)
- High-low pricing

37. Which price-adjustment strategy do you use?

- **Discount & allowance pricing-** reducing prices to reward customer responses such as paying early or promoting the product.
- **Segmented pricing-** adjusting the price to allow for differences in customers, products, or locations.
- **Psychological pricing-** adjusting prices for psychological effect.
- **Promotional pricing-** temporarily reducing prices to increase short-run sales.
- **Geographical pricing-** adjusting prices to account for the geographic location of the customer.
- **Dynamic pricing-** adjusting prices continually to meet the characteristics and needs of individual customers and situations.
- **International pricing-** adjusting prices for the international market.

38. Which tactics do you follow to fight with price war?

- Value added retailing
- Customer education
- Maintain & grow
- Quit

39. Do you ask the customers before price change? **Yes/No**

40. Do you charge always less than MRP? **Yes/No**

41. How do you create Brand Image?

- Appeal to reason
- Appeal to emotion
- Appeal to senses

42. Do you use any method to develop a brand image & customer loyalty- **Yes/No**

If yes, please specify which promotional tools are you using to entice customers?

- Advertising
- Personal retailing
- Sales promotion
- Public relation/publicity
- Direct retailing
- Internet/interactive retailing

If advertising,

a) In-store

1. Visual display
2. Signage
3. Pamphlets
4. Point of purchase material
5. Secondary packaging
6. Cross promotion
7. Others, please specify _____

b) Out-Store

1. Television
2. Radio
3. Newspapers
4. Journals & magazine
5. Yellow pages
6. Hoardings, wall paintings
7. Pamphlets/propaganda
8. Van advertising
9. Online advertising
10. Mobile billboard
11. LCD screening
12. Cinema
13. Fairs & exhibitions
14. Others, please specify _____

If, sales promotions

a) Schemes

1. Membership
2. Monthly shopping
3. Limited offers
4. Best buys of the month
5. Buy & get free
6. Discount on bulk purchase
7. Combo packs discount
8. Exclusive schemes for members
9. Others, please specify_____

b) Free samples: please specify_____

c) Gifts

1. Free gift with purchase of specific items
2. Gift hampers for special occasions
3. Assured gift & premiums
4. Others, please specify_____

d) Rebates & discounts

1. Discounts on purchase of specific items
2. Discount on bulk purchase
3. Combo-pack discounts
4. EMI
5. Vouchers & coupons
6. Others, please specify_____

e) Customer loyalty programs, prizes & rewards:

Please specify_____

f) Contest

1. Lucky draws, sweepstakes
2. Holiday activities
3. Fashion shows, art exhibits
4. Others, please specify_____

Please rate the following statements on agreement scale.

Statements	Agreement Scale*			
	4	3	2	1
Sales promotions influence customer purchase intention.				

Sales promotions increase customer satisfaction level.				
Sales promotions affect the frequency to visit the store.				
Sales promotions play a vital role to spend more.				
Sales promotions entice to repurchase.				
Customers purchase more quantity due to sales promotion.				
Your store does adequate sales promotion activities.				
Your store justifies its punch line.				
* 4- extremely agree, 3- agree, 2- partially agree, 1- not agree				

If, direct retailing

- | | |
|--------------------------------|---------------------------|
| a) Direct mail | f) Mobile retailing |
| b) Tele-retailing | g) Others, please specify |
| c) Direct response on TV/radio | _____ |
| d) Mail order catalogues | _____ |
| e) SMS retailing | |

If, personal retailing

- | | |
|--------------------------------------|---|
| a) Face to Face Retailing | d) Person to person telephonic conversation |
| b) Personal online chats | e) Others, please specify |
| c) Person to person video conference | _____ |

If, internet / interactive retailing

- | | |
|-----------------------------|----------------------------|
| a) E-mails | f) Social networking sites |
| b) Online discussion forums | g) Others, please specify |
| c) Weblogs | _____ |
| d) Web sites | _____ |
| e) e-pay | |

If, public relation / publicity retailing

- | | |
|---------------------------|----------------------------------|
| a) Corporate Brochures | g) Internet release |
| b) Posters | h) Stores tours for media |
| c) Annual Reports | i) Meeting with customers |
| d) Press Release | j) Special events & sponsorships |
| e) Press conference | k) Social events |
| f) Video press conference | l) Social development programs |

m) Others, please specify

43. How much is spent on advertising-

44. Are you using celebrity services for adverting?

Yes/No

If Yes, Please Specify the Name-

45. Do you use a tag line and logo?

Yes/No

If Yes, Please Specify-

If yes, which of the following category of tagline do you use?

- Business-Centric
- Relationship-Centric
- Customer-Centric
- Store-Centric
- Other, specify

46. Which location do you prefer to open the stores?

- Downtown location
- Inner city location
- Main street location

47. Generally, where do you prefer to open your stores?

- Shopping malls/centres
- Strip centres
- Unplanned centres
- Community centres
- Neighbourhood centres
- Regional centres
- Outlet centres
- Theme/festival centres
- Power centres
- Lifestyle centres

48. Which are the important factors, you consider while selecting a retail location.

- Population size & characteristics
- Availability of labour
- Closeness to source of supply
- Promotion facilities
- Economic base

- Competitive situation
- Availability of store locations
- Regulations

Please rate the following factors on the importance scale.

Sr. No.	Factors	Importance Scale*			
		4	3	2	1
1. Population size & characteristics					
a.	Total size & density				
b.	Age distribution				
c.	Average educational level				
d.	% of residents owning homes				
e.	Total disposable income				
f.	Per capita disposable income				
g.	Occupation distribution				
h.	Trends				
2. Availability of labour					
a.	Management				
b.	Management trainee				
c.	Clerical				
d.	Labour				
3. Closeness to source of supply					
a.	Delivery cost				
b.	Timeliness				
c.	No of manufacturers & wholesalers				
d.	Availability & reliability of merchandise lines				
4. Promotion facilities					
a.	Availability & frequency of media				
b.	Costs				
c.	Waste				
5. Economic base					
a.	Dominant industry				
b.	Extent of diversification				
c.	Growth projections				
d.	Freedom from economic & seasonal fluctuations				
e.	Availability of credit & financial facilities				
6. Competitive situation					
a.	Number & size of existing competitors				
b.	Strength & weakness of competitors				
c.	Short & long run outlook				
d.	Level of saturation				
7. Availability of store locations					
a.	Number & type of locations				
b.	Cost of site				
c.	Access to transportation				
d.	Owning V/S leasing opportunities				
e.	Leasing period & conditions				

f.	Visibility of site				
g.	Size & shape of trading area				
h.	Zoning restrictions				
i.	Parking facilities				
j.	Size & shape of the building				
8. Regulations					
a.	Taxes				
b.	Licencing				
c.	Operations				
d.	Minimum wages				
e.	Zoning				
* 4- extremely important, 3- important, 2- partially important, 1- not important					

49. What are the timings of your store?

Please. Specify- _____

50. What customer services are provided by your store?

- Credit
- Delivery
- Alterations
- Installations
- Packaging (gift wrapping)
- Complaints & returns handling
- Gift certificates
- Trial purchase
- Special sales for regular customers
- Staff on late hours
- Extended store hours
- Mail & phone orders
- Bridal registry
- Interior designers
- Personal shoppers
- Ticket outlets
- Parking
- Water fountains
- Payphones
- Baby strollers
- Restrooms
- Restaurants
- Babysitting
- Fitting rooms
- Beauty salon
- Fur storage
- Shopping bags
- Information
- Safety of personal things
- Lift & escalator facility
- After sale services
- Demonstrations
- Mobile and laptop charger points
- Entertainment facilities
- Refreshment facilities
- Insurance cover
- Medical facility
- The internet billing facility

- Internet facility (Wi-Fi)
- Game zones
- Music zone (karaoke, etc.)
- Special facilities for physically handicapped
- Others, please specify _____

51. Which customer service strategy do you adopt?

- **Patronage builders** (high-cost activities that are the primary factors behind customer loyalties, like transaction speed & credit)
- **Patronage solidifiers** (the “low-cost little things” that increase loyalty, like courtesy & suggestion selling)
- **Disappointers** (expensive activities that do no real good, like weekday deliveries for two-earner families)
- **Basics** (low-cost activities that are “naturally expected”. They don’t build patronage, but their absence could reduce patronage, like free parking, in-store directories)

52. Does your store use GAP model for improving retail customer services?

If, yes

- Knowledge gap
- Standard gap
- Delivery gap
- Communication gap

53. Does your retail store have a CRM?

- Yes
- No
- Partial

54. What information do you collect in the customer database?

- **Customer Transactions-** Purchase date, price paid, product purchased, Responses to the promoted products
- **Customer contacts-** A record of customer interaction with the store by websites, inquiries in-store kiosks, telephone calls
- **Customer Preference-** Favourite colour, brands, fabrics, flavours, apparel size
- **Descriptive information-**Demographic & psychographic data of customers
- **Customer Responses to Marketing Activity-**Responsiveness to sales promotion, advertising

55. What CRM programs do you use?

- Programs for Customer Retention
 - Frequent Shoppers Programs
 - Special Customer Services
 - Personalisation of Customers
 - To develop the sense of community among customers
- Programs to Convert Satisfied Customers in High Life Time Value Customers
 - Cross Selling
 - Add on Selling
- Programs to Deal with Unprofitable Customers

56. Is there a separate cell, to help the customers in your store- Yes/No

If yes, how do you solve the problems of the customers?

57. On what basis and by what method do you receive information about your customers-

58. What do you consider your weak spots with key customers-

59. With which customer from following category you deal most-

- Retail clientele
- Corporate clientele
- Correspondent clientele

60. Does your store regularly analyse the profitability of consumer retailing relationship- Yes/No

If yes, how do you analyse them?

- At household level
- At the individual level
- At the account level

How do you perform the analysis?

- Vendor provided CRM software
- Departmental analysis of their CR
- “Homegrown” CRM software
- Periodic review by a professional cost accountant
- Other

61. Are you providing e-retailing service to customers-

- Yes
- No

62. Which layout does your store adopt while planning store design?

- Free flow layout
- Grid layout
- Free form or boutique layout
- Loop layout
- Spine layout
- Racetrack layout

63. Which types of Signage are used by your store to locate the product category?

- Category
- Promotional
- Point of sale
- Digital signage

64. Which methods does your store adopt to display the products?

- Window displays
- Entrance display
- Free standing display
- End caps
- Promotional aisles
- Walls display
- Dressing room display
- Cash wraps display

65. Which type of fixtures does your store use to display products?

- Straight racks
- Rounder (bulk fixture/capacity fixture)
- Four-way fixture (feature fixture)
- Gondolas

66. Which presentation techniques are used by your store to present the products?

- Idea-oriented presentation
- Item & size presentation
- Colour presentation
- Price lining
- Vertical merchandising
- Tonnage merchandising
- Frontal presentation

67. Which variables are used by your store to create an appealing store atmosphere?

- Lighting
- Colour
- Scent
- Music

68. Please rate the following variables of store atmospherics on the importance scale, which entice the customers.

S. N.	Measurement Variables	Importance Scale*			
		4	3	2	1
1. Exterior atmospherics					
1	Storefront				
2	Store marquee/sign board				
3	Frontage entrance				
4	External display window/space				
5	Building				
6	Store architecture				
7	Uniqueness of store				
8	Visibility of store				
9	Location/site of the store				
10	Parking facilities				
11	Exterior look of store				
12	Ease of access				
13	Store nameplate				
14	Health & safety standards				
15	Surrounding area				
2. Interior atmospherics					
1	Flooring & ceiling				
2	Lighting				
3	Odour/smell/scent				
4	Fixtures				
5	Wall textures				
6	Sounds				
7	Colour				
8	Temperature				
9	Cleanliness				
10	Aisles				
11	Trial (experience) room/zone				
12	Dead area				
13	Merchandise				
14	Graphics				
15	Store size				
3. Store layout					
1	Space planning				
2	Floor space allocation				
3	E-display				
4	Department location				
5	Department size				

6	Department compatibility				
7	Location of various merchandise				
8	Accessibility to cash counters				
9	Signage				
10	Space/merchandise category				
4. Visual merchandising					
1	Assortment				
2	Theme				
3	Racks & shelves				
4	Ensemble				
5	Payment counters				
6	Merchandise display				
7	The planogram				
8	Props & mannequins				
9	Point of sale sign				
10	Methods of display				
* 4- extremely important, 3- important, 2- partially important, 1- not important					

69. What are your plans in the new future at store-level?

Thank you so much.

INDIVIDUAL QUESTIONNAIRE

Name of the city: _____ Name of the Store: _____

CUSTOMER PROFILE

1. Name: _____

2. Address: _____

3. Contact Number & Email: _____

4. Residing area:

🏡 Urban

🏡 Semi-urban

🏡 Rural

5. Gender:

• Male

• Female

6. Age (in years):

• Below 21

• 31-40

• 51-60

• 21-30

• 41-50

• Above 60

7. Education:

• Illiterate

• 10th -12th (HSC - SSC)

• Other Plz.,

• Below 10th
(HSC)

• Graduate

Specify

• Postgraduate

8. Occupation:

• Salaried

• Homemaker

• Retired

• Self-employed

• Student

9. Family Income (Yearly):

• Less than 1 Lakh

• 2 to 5 Lakhs

• More than 10 Lakhs

• 1 to 2 Lakhs

• 5 to 10 Lakhs

10. Marital Status:

• Single

• Married

11. Nature of Family:

• Nuclear

• Joint

12. Family Size

• Less than 4 Members

• 6-8 Members

• 4-5 Members

• More than 8 Members

13. Religion:

• Hindu

• Muslim

• Buddhists

- Sikh
- Christian
- Other plz., specify

BUYING BEHAVIOUR

14. Generally, who take the purchase making decisions in your family?

- Self
- Children
- Others
- Spouse
- Parents

15. Do you collect the information, while purchase decision making?

- Yes
- No

If yes, from where you collect information regarding the products & services?

- Salespersons
- Family members
- Telemarketing
- Neighbours/Friends/Relatives
- Advertising
- Through Internet (www)
- In-store information
- Others, please specify
- In-store display
- _____
- Package labels

-If advertising, by which source?

- Television
- Radio
- Newspapers
- Cinema
- Magazines
- Celebrity endorsement
- Hoardings
- Websites
- Pamphlets
- Others

16. How are you influenced to buy a product?

- Self
- TV commercials
- Family members
- Infomercials
- Neighbours / Friends / Colleagues
- Magazines ads
- Celebrity endorsement
- TV talk shows
- Salesperson in a store
- News
- Direct-mail piece
- Sales Promotion
- Websites
- Others

17. Generally, who do the purchasing in your family?

- Self
- Children
- Surrogate
- Spouse
- Parents

18. For how long, you have been visiting this retail store.

- First time
- Last 6 months
- Last 2 year
- Last 3 months
- Last 1 year
- More than 2 years

19. How many times do you visit the store in a month?

- 1 Time
- 3 Times
- More than 4 times
- 2 Times
- 4 Times

20. On which day of the week, you prefer to visit this store.

- Weekdays (Monday to Friday)
- Any day
- Weekends (Saturday & Sunday)

21. When you prefer to visit this store?

- Morning
- Evening
- Afternoon
- Any time

22. How much do you spend for purchasing from this store in a month?

- Less than ₹ 1000
- ₹ 2001-5000
- ₹ 1000-2000
- More than ₹ 5000

23. Which category of the products do you usually purchase?

- Basic (staples) merchandise
- Seasonal merchandise
- Fashion merchandise
- Consumer durable merchandise

24. What type of products do you usually purchase?

- Food & Grocery
- Electronics
- Health & Beauty
- Toys
- Home & Furniture
- Sports
- Fashion
- Other, please specify

25. Do you make unplanned purchasing from this store?

- Yes
- No

If yes, what type of products _____?

Reason for unplanned purchase

- Point of purchase display
- Price reductions
- Store layout
- Coupons
- Shelving techniques
- Demonstration and samples
- Multi-item discounts
- Packaging
- Store atmosphere
- Salespeople
- Any other, please specify _____

26. While purchasing, you give the preference to-

(Put number 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 & 7 in order of preference)

- Brand
- Price
- Others
- Quality
- Quantity
- Discounts
- Schemes

27. Why do you visit this store?

a) Merchandise

Merchandise assortment (variety of merchandise and brands), quality of assortment, in service situations, merchandise offered as part of service, styling or fashion guarantee, warranties and pricing, reasonable prices

b) Service

Service in general, ease of merchandise return, delivery service, salesclerk service, phone ordering, presence of self-service, and credit policy

c) Clientele

Social class appeal, store personnel, Fit between self-image and store image (self-image congruence)

d) Physical Facilities

Elevators, lighting, air conditioning, restrooms, store layout, shopping ease, aisle placement, carpeting and architecture.

e) Convenience

General convenience, parking access, location convenience (proximity to home/office)

f) Promotion

Advertising, displays, trading stamps, sales promotion (discount & special schemes), symbol and colours

g) Store Atmospheres

Atmosphere of congeniality, customers' feeling of warmth, acceptance or ease, good & spacious ambience, and delighting store environment

h) Institutional factors

Projection of store (conservative or modern), reputation, reliability

i) Post-transaction satisfaction

Merchandise in use and return & adjustment policy

j) Others

Friends suggested, no other store nearby, convenient store hours

28. Do you visit any other store apart from this?

- Yes
- No

If yes,

- Organised retail store
- Unorganised retail store
- Both

Reasons for visiting this other store

a) Merchandise

Merchandise assortment (variety of merchandise and brands), quality of assortment, in service situations, merchandise offered as part of service, styling or fashion guarantee, warranties and pricing, reasonable prices

b) Service

Service in general, ease of merchandise return, delivery service, salesclerk service, phone ordering, presence of self-service, and credit policy

c) Clientele

Social class appeal, store personnel, Fit between self-image and store image (self-image congruence)

d) Physical Facilities

Elevators, lighting, air conditioning, restrooms, store layout, shopping ease, aisle placement, carpeting and architecture.

e) Convenience

General convenience, parking access, location convenience (proximity to home/office)

f) Promotion

Advertising, displays, trading stamps, sales promotion (discount & special schemes), symbol and colours

g) Store Atmospheres

Atmosphere of congeniality, customers' feeling of warmth, acceptance or ease, good & spacious ambience, and delighting store environment

h) Institutional factors

Projection of store (conservative or modern), reputation, reliability

i) Post-transaction satisfaction

Merchandise in use and return & adjustment policy

j) Others

Friends suggested, no other store nearby, convenient store hours

FACTORS INFLUENCING BUYING BEHAVIOUR

29. How is your buying behaviour influenced by following Factors? Please rate them on a scale ranging from +2 to -2 (by Tick Mark).

S. N.	Factors	2	1	0	-1	-2
1	Sociological / Environmental / External factors					
	Cultural, sub-cultural, society, status in society (social class), reference group, family life cycle, and role in the family					
2	Psychological / Individual / Internal factors					
	Self-image, personality, personal values, lifestyle, memory, learning, perception, motivation, emotions, mood, involvement, information processing, beliefs, intention, attitude, communication, and persuasion					
3	Store related factors					
	Store image, store atmosphere, store brands, store location, sales personnel, discounts & schemes, and free services.					
*2 = Extremely Influenced, 1 = Influenced, 0 = Neither Influenced nor uninfluenced, -1 = Uninfluenced, -2 = Not at all influenced						

CUSTOMER SATISFACTION

30. How do you rate the variables of the store or retailers mentioned below describing the products (merchandise) & services, prices, promotion, premises / place, presentation, personnel / people, physical evidence on the expectation cum satisfaction scale? Please rate these variables on a five-point scale (by tick mark). The scales are ranging like following-

Expectation cum satisfaction scale-

- A rating of 5 indicates that the variable is greatly exceeding your expectations and you are delighted.
- A rating of 4 indicates that the variable is exceeding your expectations and you are happy.
- A rating of 3 indicates that the variable is matching your expectations and you are satisfied.
- A rating of 2 indicates that the variable is less than your expectations you are dissatisfied.
- A rating of 1 indicates that the variable is much less than your expectations and you are disappointed.

Sr. No.	Variables	Expectation cum satisfaction scale				
		5	4	3	2	1
	Ratings*					
Products (Merchandise) offered						
1	<i>Merchandise assortment</i>					

2	<i>Merchandise categories in the assortment</i>					
	Basic or staple, fashion, seasonal, consumer durable etc.					
3	<i>Variety of merchandise in each category</i>					
	As per different sizes, colours, designs, price, quality, quantity and brands					
4	<i>Availability of newly launched merchandise, customised merchandise, unique merchandise and complementary merchandise</i>					
5	<i>Brands in each merchandise category</i>					
	Local & regional brands, national brands, international brands, private (store) brands and others, i.e. copycat, exclusive, generic brands					
6	<i>Quality assurance and quality of merchandise</i>					
Services offered						
7	<i>Services</i>					
	Credit, home delivery, alteration, installation, packaging (gift wrapping), complaints & returns handling, gift certificates, trial purchase, special sales for regular customers, staff on late hours, extended store hours, mail & phone orders, bridal registry, babysitting, interior designers, personal shoppers, baby strollers, ticket outlets, parking, water fountains, pay phones, restaurants, fitting rooms, beauty salon, fur storage, shopping bags, restrooms, information, safety of personal things, lift & escalator facility, after sale services, demonstrations, mobile and laptop charger points, entertainment facilities, refreshment facilities, the internet billing facility, game zones, music zone (karaoke, etc.), special facilities for physically handicapped, other in-store services, other out-store services, other pre-purchase or post-purchase services, complementary (adjunct) services (i.e. inventory support, installation, repair)					
8	<i>Quality of services</i>					
	As per the ability to manage its tangibles (tangibility), consistency and dependability in service performance (reliability), commitment to providing services in time (responsiveness), competence, courtesy to its customers and the security of its operations (assurance), ability to put itself in its customers place (empathy)					
Price						
9	<i>The pricing of merchandise & services</i>					
10	<i>The overall value (product value, service value, personal value, image value) Vs price (overall cost- monetary cost, time cost, energy cost, psychic cost) of merchandise & services</i>					
Premises / Place						
11	<i>Exterior atmospherics of the store</i>					

	Storefront, store marquee / sign board, frontage entrance, external display window / space, building, store architecture, uniqueness of the store, visibility of the store, location / site of store, parking facilities, exterior look of the store, ease of access, store nameplate, health & safety standards, surrounding area						
12	<i>Interior atmospherics of the store</i>						
	Flooring & ceiling, lighting, odour / smell / scent, fixtures, wall textures, sounds, colour, temperature, cleanliness, aisles, trial room, dead area, graphics, store size						
Presentation							
13	<i>Store layout</i>						
	Space planning, floor space allocation, e-display, department location, department size, department compatibility, location of various products, accessibility to cash/billing counters, signage						
14	<i>Visual merchandising</i>						
	Theme, racks & shelves, ensemble, payment counters, merchandise display, the planogram, props & mannequins, point of sale sign, methods of display						
Promotion							
15	<i>Methods of promotion and communication</i>						
16	<i>Advertising methods</i>						
	In-store methods (i.e. visual display, signage, pamphlets, point of purchase material, secondary packaging, cross-promotion) and out-store methods (television, radio, newspapers, journals & magazine, yellow pages, hoardings, wall paintings, pamphlets/propaganda, van advertising, online advertising, mobile billboard, LCD screening, cinema, fairs & exhibitions)						
17	<i>Sales promotion methods</i>						
	Schemes, free samples, gifts, rebates & discounts, contests and other activities, customer loyalty programs, premiums, prize & rewards						
18	<i>Direct retailing methods</i>						
	Direct mail, tele-retailing, direct response on TV/radio, mail order catalogues, SMS retailing, mobile retailing						
19	<i>Personal retailing methods</i>						
	Face to face retailing in store, person to person telephonic conversation						
20	<i>Public relation / publicity methods</i>						
	Corporate brochures, posters, annual reports, press release, press conference, video press conference, internet release, store tours for media, meeting with customers, special events & sponsorships, social events, social development programs						
21	<i>Internet / interactive retailing methods</i>						
	E-mails, online discussion forums, weblogs, websites, e-pay, social networking sites						
Personnel / people							
22	<i>Sales personnel</i>						

	Sales boys and sales girls					
23	<i>Contact personnel</i>					
	Help desk people, service desk people, billing counter people, etc.					
24	<i>Factors pertained to personnel</i>					
	Mood, efforts, commitment, attitude, knowledge, skills, behaviour, approach to delivering the service, competence, courtesy, credibility, reliability, responsiveness, communication style, friendliness, helpfulness, discipline & punctuality, customer counselling ability					
Physical (tangible) evidence						
25	<i>Other tangible evidence</i>					
	Employee appearance, uniforms, billing statements, stationery, business cards, signage, exterior design, reports, brochures, internet or web pages					

CUSTOMER SUGGESTIONS

31. If, any variable or sub-variable (mentioned in question 30) falls short of your expectation and you want an improvement in it. Please mention here.

S. N.	Variable	S. N.	Variable
1		2	
3		4	
5		6	
7		8	
9		10	
11		12	
13		14	
15		16	
17		18	
19		20	
21		22	
23		24	
25		26	
27		28	
29		30	
31		32	
33		34	
35		36	
37		38	

39		40	
41		42	
43		44	
45		46	
47		48	
49		50	

32. Any other facility, which you want from your store, please mention here.

1		6	
2		7	
3		8	
4		9	
5		10	

33. Any other suggestion, please.

Thank you so much.

MAP OF MAHARASHTRA STATE IN INDIA

Source: (MSEDCL, 2015)
ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Participation in seminars / conferences and papers presented

- Participated in international conference on “Recontouring Business”, organised by Sadhu Vaswani Institute of Management Studies For Girls, Pune on January 22-23, 2016.
- Participated in international conference on “Ongoing Research in the fields of Management Studies and Information Technology”, organised by Audyogik Shikshan Mandal, Pune on January 8-9, 2016.
- Presented a paper titled “NGO Management through Efficacious Human Resources” at a national conference organised by Siddhant Institute of Business Management, Pune on March 13 & 14, 2015.
- Presented a paper titled “Assessing the Demographic Orientation towards Store Design” at a national conference on “Emerging Trends in Information Technology and Business Management” organised by Dr D. Y. Patil Institute of Management, Pune, on March 9, 2012.
- Presented a paper titled “Corporate Social Responsibility Practices in India” at a national conference on “Recent Amendments in Corporate Laws inclusive of Direct & Indirect Laws” organised by Indrayani Mahavidyalaya, Talegaon on February 16 to 18, 2012.
- Presented a paper titled “Islamic Banking: Strategic Issues and Challenges in India” at a national conference on “Strategic Management for Today’s Business” organised by Dept. of Business Management, Siddhant College of Engineering, Pune on October 7, 2011.
- Presented a paper titled “Store Image - A Critical Success Factor in Dynamic Retailing Environment”, at a national seminar on “Economic Environment of Business” organised by Sir M Visvesvaraya Institute of Management Studies & Research, Mumbai on September 24, 2011.

Publications

- Atul Kumar and Vinaydeep, “Intrinsic Reward System & Motivation: A Study of Management Teachers Perspective” in *International Journal of Human Resource Management and Research (IJHRMR)*, Vol. 2, Issue 4, December 2012, pp. 33-44, ISSN: 2249-6874 (Print) & 2249-6874 (Online), Impact Factor (JCC): 2.9966.

- Atul Kumar and Vinaydeep Brar, “Measurement of the Demographic Inclination towards Store Image” in *Vishwakarma Business Review*, Vol. 2, Issue 2, July 2012, pp. 88-93, ISSN: 2229-6514 (Print) & 2230-8237 (Online).
- Atul Kumar, “Store Image - A Critical Success Factor in Dynamic Retailing Environment: An Investigation” in *Asian Journal of Management*, Vol. 3, Issue 1, January-March 2012, pp. 01-05, ISSN 0976- 495X (Print).
- Atul Kumar, “The Changing Buying Behaviour of Customers in Organised Retail Sector of Pune City” in *International Journal of Research in Social Sciences*, Vol. 2, Issue 1, February 2012, pp. 242-263, ISSN: 2249-2496 (Online).
- Atul Kumar, “Measuring the Women’s Involvement in Purchase Making Decisions” in *International Journal of Marketing and Technology*, Vol. 2, Issue 2, February 2012, pp. 255-276, ISSN: 2249-1058 (Online), IC Value: 5.9.
- Atul Kumar and Vinaydeep, “Purchase Decisions: An Empirical Study of Women’s Role in Family” in *KBSCMR’s Journal of Management Research*, Vol. 2, December 2011, pp. 43-54, ISSN 0973-1513 (Print).
- Atul Kumar, “Demographic & Geographic Inclination towards Store Design: a Study of Shopping Mall Customers in Maharashtra-State, India” in *Asian Journal of Management*, Vol. 2, Issue 3, July-Sept. 2011, pp. 87-93, ISSN 0976-495X (Print).
- Atul Kumar, “Islamic Banking: Strategic Issues and Challenges in India” in *proceedings of a national conference on Strategic Management for Today’s Business* organised by Siddhant College of Engineering, Pune, ISBN 978-81-8465-811-8.
- Vinaydeep and Atul Kumar, “Talent Management for Effective Customer Relationship Management” in *proceedings of a national conference on Strategic Management for Today’s Business* organised by Siddhant College of Engineering, ISBN 978-81-8465-811-8.